

**PRAGMATICS OF NEUROLOGIST-PATIENT INTERACTION
IN SELECTED UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITALS
IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA**

BY

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Abstract

Neurologist-patient interaction, an important hospital situation that focuses on the care for people with language-related disorders or impairments, has attracted interest from various disciplinary standpoints. Global attention to neurologist-patient interaction is growing, with focus on communication models, patterns, applications, and various indices in the interactional contexts. Similar attention remains scanty within the Nigerian context. This study, therefore, investigated communication model in neurologist-patient interaction in selected university teaching hospitals (UTHs) in southwestern Nigeria, in order to identify the communication goals and patterns, discourse strategies, pragmatic acts, and contexts that shape the interaction.

Jacob Mey's Pragmatic Acts, complemented by Emanuel and Emanuel's model of doctor-patient relationship, served as the theoretical framework. Data comprising 40 audio-recorded neurologist-patient interactions were collected from the UTHs of Olabisi Onabanjo University, Sagamu (nine); Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti (eight) and Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Osogbo (six) and University College Hospital, Ibadan (17). These were supplemented with patients' case notes and interviews conducted with neurologists. The data were transcribed following modified Arminen's notations of conversation analysis and subjected to pragmatic analysis.

Four models of communication, namely paternalistic, informative, interpretive, and deliberative, exhibited through varying discourse strategies were identified in the neurologist-patient interaction with the diagnostic and therapeutic communication as goals. The paternalistic model reflected slightly casual conversational conventions and registers. These were achieved through the *pragmemic* activities of situated speech acts, psychological and physical acts, via patients' quarrel-induced acts, controlled and managed through neurologists' shared situation knowledge. All these produced empathising, pacifying, promising and instructing practs. The patients' practs were explaining, provoking, associating and greeting in the paternalistic model. The informative model reveals the use of adjacency pairs, formal turn-taking, precise detailing, institutional talks and dialogic strategies. Through the activities of the speech, prosody and physical acts, the practs of declaring, alerting and informing were utilised by neurologists, while the patients exploited adapting, requesting and selecting practs. Monologic contribution was the norm in the interpretive model. It involves the confirmatory and routine opening-and-closing discourse strategies. The communicative activities through the speech, prosody and physical acts showed the utilisation of deducing, predicting, prioritising and interpreting practs by neurologists; while patients adopted conforming, inquiring, requesting and deciding practs. The negotiating conversational strategy of the deliberative model featured in the speech, prosody and physical acts. In this model, practs of suggesting, teaching, persuading and convincing were utilised by the neurologists. The patients deployed the practs of questioning, demanding, considering and deciding. The contextual variables revealed that the four models often coalesced in the selected UTHs within the situational and psychological contexts. However, the paternalistic model was predominantly employed by neurologists with over six years in practice, while the interpretive, informative and deliberative models were found among neurologists below six years in practice in the selected UTHs.

Neurologist-patient interaction in university teaching hospitals in southwestern Nigeria is shaped by neurologists' experience, patients' peculiarities and shared knowledge. All these reinforce the paternalistic as an invaluable model for enhanced and effective communication.

Keywords: Medical pragmatics, Communication model, Neurologist-patient interaction, University teaching hospitals in Southwestern Nigeria

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Dedication

The One who led me where mere strength and brains could not,
Immortal, Invisible, Only Wise God;

Mama (Pastor) Akinkunmi

for freely giving me the much-needed balance for the SSCE form when all other hopes were lost;

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Certification

I certify that this work was carried out by Ayodele James AKINOLA
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LIST OF NOTATIONS

[] simultaneous speech and voices, its start and end

= immediately continuous talk, no interval

(0.2) pause and its length in seconds

(.) micropause, shorter than 0.2 seconds

: stretch

WORD loud

_ : falling intonation

↑ marked rise in pitch

↓ marked fall in pitch

da- production of word is cut off

word< abruptly finished, but not cut off

>< pronounced faster than the surrounding speech

<> pronounced slower than the surrounding speech

\$ laughter in the voice

£ smile as talk continues *

° ° diminishing voice

shivering voice

() unclearly heard

(()) researcher's comment

^ expression of anger

P^SP: Name of individual mentioned in the interaction which is veiled in line with research ethics by the researcher. It signifies the Protection of Subject's Privacy *

P^LP: Name of specific study location mentioned in the interaction which is ethically veiled by the researcher for the Protection of specific Location's Privacy *

(Main notation source: Arminen, 2005)

* Notations included by the researcher

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

Neurologist-patient interaction, which is an important aspect of medical discourse, has attracted interest from various disciplinary standpoints. Global attention to neurologist-patient interaction is growing, where communication model and various indices in the communicative contexts were considered. This study investigates neurologist-patient interaction, a sub-genre of doctor-patient interaction, which is a genre of medical communication. Remarkably, doctor-patient discourse has been approached in a multi-dimensional way ranging from medical practitioners, anthropologists, sociolinguists, applied linguists, discourse analysts to pragmaticians and many others, (see Ennis, 2004; Kalitzkus, Matthiessen, 2009; Kleinman, and Benson, 2006; Adegbite and Odebunmi 2006; Odebunmi, 2006; etc). Many of these have contributed towards establishing a basis for hospital interactions for discourse studies.

Central to doctor-patient interaction as a viable medical research is communication between various stakeholders within and around the hospital domain (Ennis, 2004). Korsch and Negrete (1972), whose research provides a basis for doctor-patient interaction, observe that most of the existing research on the subject, have concentrated on investigating the problem of doctor-patient communication. This is without recourse to the crucial but neglected aspect of medical care. However, since the ability to communicate efficiently and effectively is key towards the success or failure of any communicative event, the study of various communication variables in doctor-patient interaction from diverse disciplines has continued to enjoy scholarly attention.

More so, scholars such as Clever, Jin, Levinson, Meltzer, (2008); Frostholm, Fink, Oernboel, Christensen, Toft, et al (2005); Frederiksen, Kragstrup and Dehlholm-Lambertsen, (2010) and Rathnakar et al. (2013) are in unison with regards to communication behaviours of interactants as an important factor through which satisfaction is achieved. In fact, satisfaction is believed to be attained through the communication behaviours of doctors; their dominance, concern about the psycho-social issues of the patient, illness perceptions, concordance between the doctor's

communication style, the patient's need for attachment, and the patient's attitude (Ellis, 2013).

Some scholars outside the shore of Africa, such as Coulthand and Ashby (1976), Labov and Fanshel (1977), Mishler (1984), van Naerssen (1985), Drennan et al. (1991), Myerscough (1992), Wodak (1997), Davidson (2001), Valero-Garces (2002), Briggs and Briggs (2003) and Wilce (2004) have approached doctor-patient communication from the traditions of discourse analysis and conversation analysis (Odebunmi, 2006). Works on medical discourse in Nigeria is centred around issues such as the register, linguistics, content and function of communication between doctors and their patients among others (see Ogunbode, 1991; Oloruntoba-Oju, 1996; Alabi, 1996; Odebunmi, 2003; Adegbite and Odebunmi, 2003, 2006, 2012 and 2016). While some of these studies have explored communicative situations involving patients and various health care professionals, there is limited documentation on neurologist-patient interaction.

Neurologists are medical doctors who are specially trained in diagnosing, treating and managing disorders of the brain and nerves. Their roles during consultation include the diagnosis and treatment of neurological disorder. In some cases, they advise the primary care doctor managing the diagnosed person's overall health system (American Academy of Neurology, 2017). Due to the nature of the patients that are diagnosed and treated by neurologists, their mode of communication may be different from other professionals. It has been observed that models of communication have a remarkable influence on the achievement or otherwise of the diagnostic and therapeutic goals of doctor-patient interaction (Agarwal, and Murinson, 2012; Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992; and Pawlikowska, Leach, Lavallee, Charlton, Piercy, 2007). Naska corroborated this by affirming that there are strong positive relationships between a medical practitioner's communication skills and a patient's capacity to follow through with medical recommendations, self-manage a chronic medical condition, and adopt preventive health behaviours (Naska, 2017).

Bonvicini (2011) observes that findings of previous studies show that the clinician's ability to explain, listen and empathise can have a profound effect on biological and functional health outcomes as well as patient satisfaction and experience of care. An account after World War II given by Kennedy and Fasolino (2014) confirms that physicians were highly regarded at the time of the war. As a result, their communication

mode was paternalistic and patients trusted them to behave in their best interests and were disease-oriented physician-centred (Kennedy and Fasolino, 2014).

In medical communication, there are various models of communication. The suitability of one model or the other has often been the subject of criticism among stakeholders in medical practice and medical discourse alike. Some scholars, especially in the developed nations of the world, advocate the dominant use of particular communication mode or models for “all” cases of doctor-patient interaction against the use of some others, (see Emanuel and Emanuel 1992; Pellegrino, 2006; and Oprea, 2009) One major deficiency identifiable with this call is its lack of consideration for the place of context in interactions. In a particular hospital situation and geographical location, for example, certain communicative events may be possible. Whereas governed by certain conditions, which may include, culture, education, nature of the illness of patients, and even location, certain communicative behaviours might be impossible.

Pragmatics, a field of linguistic investigation which makes necessary reference to the aspects of context (Levinson, 1983), is a veritable tool to the understanding of communication in medical discourse such as the neurologist-patient interaction. Since the understanding of context is key to the description of neurologist-patient interaction, pragmatics is a relevant theory that can be adopted by scholars who are interested in the identification of communication goal, how such goal is arrived at, roles of participants, model of communication, and other contributing factors in the discourse.

Consequently, this study examines models of communication in neurologist-patient interaction, especially in the context of Southwestern Nigeria university teaching hospitals within the confine of pragmatics. Study on models of communication in these hospitals was selected because of the peculiarity of neurologist-patient interaction as a sub-genre of doctor-patient interaction. This will advance existing researches and provide information on the various communicative models, features, linguistic peculiarity and their potentialities for human interactions in other communicative domains.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Across the world, attention to doctor-patient interaction is increasing. Some of the areas of focus include communication models, patterns, applications, and various indices in the interactional contexts. Previous studies in Nigeria on doctor-patient interactions with regards to pragmatics have been focused on the linguistic activities and contexts that determine what constitute communication, shape and patterns of such communication among doctors, patients, and other relevant individuals within the scope of the discourse. Significant contributions have been made by Odebunmi (2003, 2008, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2015, 2016), Faleke (2005), Adegbite and Odebunmi (2006), Salami (2006), Akinola (2013), Nwabueze and Nwankwo (2016) and many others.

Odebunmi (2003) investigates diagnostic news delivery from the purview of general pragmatics. Odebunmi treats diagnosing as one of the institutional acts performed in the hospital. Faleke (2005) considers aspects of pragmatics in nurse-patient interactions. Her focus was on the discourses by doctors and nurses in Southwestern Nigerian hospitals.

Similarly, Odebunmi (2006) selects examples from oral discourses of doctors that relate to diagnosis. These, he used to explain locutions that are and are not meant to be understood by patients. The interest of Salami (2006) is the doctor-pregnant women interactions. The study examines the speech acts performed in the interactions. Some of the other contributions to hospital-related studies in Nigeria came from the angle of psycholinguistics, while others, such as Sunday (2008), employ a phonological view. Akinola (2013) approaches medical discourse in a holistic investigation of the interactions between doctors and aphasics. He concentrates on the situated meanings of the uttered expressions of the patients using the tools of pragmatics. Odebunmi (2016) explores how doctors and patients track response responsibility discursively, for patients' poor health after treatment recommendations have been delivered. The scope was limited to hospitals in the Southwestern part of Nigeria. The study establishes that doctors' simplified language which facilitates consultative exchanges is useful in negotiating responsibility in poor health discourses, and as a result institutes a more effective medical procedure on patients among others. Nwabueze and Nwankwo (2016) investigate ethnicity in the interpersonal communication between doctors and patients. They argue that the doctors' ethnic background affects the level of information and level of communication patients have with the doctors. Also, it was posited that gender was a

factor in information disclosure on serious illnesses with a recourse to doctors' ethnic background.

Beyond the shore of Nigeria, Pikor-Niedzialek (2001) provides an insight into medical discourse through a study of doctor-patient interactions. In the study, he takes a contrastive view of a pragmatic approach to doctor-patient communication. Emphasis was on Gricean pragmatics. Moreover, in Heritage and Maynard's (2006) study on doctor-patient interactions, physicians were invited to use the study's coding framework to evaluate their own conduct and to modify their conduct in a more patient-centred direction. As a result of the findings in the study, there was a documented overwhelming prevalence of doctor-centred behaviour which was also conceived as an intervention. Through this, they added to the claim that doctor-patient interaction is a viable research domain. Other scholars whose studies are notable in the field of medical discourse include Byrne and Long (1976), Labov and Fanshel (1977), Wodak (1997), Coulthand and Ashby (1976), Korsch and Negrete (1972), Johnova (2008).

Furthermore, in a recent study, Bank, Gage, Kenney, Korardy, Mckinley, Obetz, *et al* (2013) focus on the use of Scribes in the emergency department with a bid to improving physician productivity and patient interaction. In the study, the scholars aver that use of scribes produces improvement in physician-patient interaction and also results in large increases in physician productivity and system cardiovascular revenue. Montague, Chen, Xu, Chewing and Barrett (2013) investigate the relationship between nonverbal communication behaviours such as eye contact and social touch to patient assessments of clinician empathy, connectedness, and liking. It was discovered that length of visit and eye contact between clinician and patient were positively related to the patient's assessment of the clinician's empathy. Also, the scholars aver that eye contact was significantly related to patient perceptions of clinician attributes, such as connectedness and liking. More so, eye contact and social touch were significantly related to patient perceptions of clinician empathy. To Singo (2014), code-switching in doctor-patient communication is an important area of study. As a result, he elucidates and builds on the notion of code-switching as an 'everyday' phenomenon in multilingual society with a focus on Harare city.

The focus of some of the existing studies on what constitutes communication, its shape and patterns from various contexts are laudable. However, the description of the

communication goals and patterns, discourse strategies, pragmatics, and contexts that shape the interactions from the purview of available models of communication in doctor-patient interaction remain scarce. It is also notable from the studies that there is silence on neurologist-patient interaction as a specific aspect of doctor-patient relationship, unlike efforts put into research involving other specialists in medical practice and the peculiarity of their conversations with specific patients. More so, information on communication models in neurologist-patient relationship remained diminutive. This is particularly so in sub-Saharan African, especially the Southwestern region of Nigeria.

Going by these observations, this study is concerned with communication in neurologist-patients' relationship and how the participants involved "act" within the context of this relationship based on the models adopted by neurologists in the interaction. Due to the hiatus in the previous studies, this study identifies the communication goals and patterns, discourse strategies, pragmatic acts, and contexts that shape the neurologist-patient interaction. It is an attempt to explore the peculiar indices through which diagnostic and therapeutic communication are deployed through the information provided by patients, and also how this information is processed by neurologists in various contexts of the adopted communication models.

1.3 Aim and objectives

The aim of this study is to investigate the contextual communication model in neurologist-patient interactions in university teaching hospitals, Southwestern Nigeria, using the tool of pragmatics. In line with this, the objectives of the study are to:

1. identify the communication goals and patterns of neurologist-patient interaction in university teaching hospitals in the Southwestern region of Nigeria;
2. examine the discourse strategies employed by the interactants in the interactions;
3. describe the pragmatic acts that characterise the interaction;
4. pinpoint the predominant communication model(s) and contexts that determine the selection of such model(s); and
5. make generalisable deductions that are capable of improving neurologist-patient interactions and other doctor-patient relationship.

1.4 Purpose of the study

Research efforts into language disorder as an aspect of discourse analysis in other parts of the world have gained some recognition. Also, communication model in doctor-patient relationship has attracted diverse views and advocacy. This cannot be said to have attracted appreciable attention, especially, among discourse analysts and pragmatics in Nigeria and other parts of sub-Saharan Africa. Although many investigations have been carried out by discourse analysts and others to unveil the peculiarity of doctor-patient interaction. Even at that, most of the works have concentrated on the broader view of doctors' interactions with their patients. Many have not considered the peculiarity of communication model employed in hospitals interaction, and also area of doctor's specialisation, as important determinants of the kind of interactions that take place. The success or otherwise of this has also not been fully explored. However, in the academic, there is a consensus that every specialist in medical practice possesses a unique way of handling their patients, especially in the aspect of language choice and patterns of communication. Language itself is a creative ability of man. Hence, the way a neurologist will use language in his interaction with patients, in specific contexts is worthy of being investigated. This study is, therefore, tailored towards investigating the communication models of the interactions between neurologists and their patients. In doing this, the study unravels what pragmatic choices the neurologists employed in the interaction, and what or which communication model informed these choices. Also, how interactants achieve pragmatic success or otherwise in the situated communication is explored. In the study, the conceptual communication structures in the interactions are also investigated. All these help in providing generalizable deductions that are capable of improving neurologist-patient interactions in Nigeria and other places.

According to Sunday (2008:4), "culture affects attitudes and attitudes control behaviour". Since diverse kinds of patients seek a cure to language impairment and related nervous disorder, the attitudes of both the neurologists and patients stemming from socio-cultural worldview are expected to impact on their interaction. Pragmatics makes possible the understanding of the role played by culture and attitudes in the context of neurologist-patient interaction. In this study, the pragmatic imports of this unique meeting are, therefore, explored so as to provide insight into how the understanding of a discourse situation contributes to right perception and attitude among

interactants and also sheds light on the recognition of the linguistic choice available to the participants in a communicative domain.

1.5 Scope and delimitation of the study

This study is a partial reflection of communication model(s) in neurologist-patient interactions in Nigeria, in that, its findings involved only neurological departments of university teaching hospitals in the southwestern states of Nigeria. These are Oyo, Osun, Ogun, and Ekiti states respectively. The data were those of conversations between neurologists and their patients which occur at the level of consultations in the consulting rooms.

In a bid to carry out the study's objective, the natural conversations between neurologists and patients, including non-verbal communication, were observed and considered in the analysis. Other non-situated interactions involving other individuals that were present, except the relatives of patients, were excluded from the analysis and presentation of results. This is done to ensure that only participants whose consents were secured were the actual ones that were recorded and analysed for the study.

1.6 Significance of the study

The study advances efforts of pragmaticians in medical discourse. By investigating communication model in neurologist-patient interaction from the perspective of pragmatics, it will be easier for neurologists to apply the appropriate knowledge in the aspect of the communication choice with their patients, as a result, help in the treatment and care of the patients in a much more productive way and engender improved doctor-patient relationship. Similarly, the patients are also provided information on the available choices in their interactions with the physicians. Other experts and professionals in language-related disciplines can gain insight from the interactions in the study; and also, learn from how each participant contributed towards the achievement of the communicative goals so as to apply relevant communication models into familiar or corresponding situations of human interactions.

This study is significant for its peculiar focus on the description of communication model and the linguistic choices in the interactions that take place between neurologists and their patients. It, therefore, provides insights into neurologist-patient communication, especially, those who are non-native speakers of the English language but use the English

language alongside some indigenous languages in hospital interactions. The deductions from the study can help to ascertain idealising what should determine communication, and the models to be employed in hospital interactions.

1.7 The concept of neurolinguistics

Neurolinguistics is a fusion of neurology and language or linguistics. While a neurologist deals with the functioning of the nervous system, in order to treat disease, a linguist, undertakes a scientific study of language, looking at its structure and its use (Whitaker 1975). Regarding the relationship that exists between neurology and linguistics, Whitaker (1975) draws inferences from the personnel involved in the two disciplines thus:

The duo is mutually reinforcing. Often times, modern neurologists ask stroke patients whether they suffered language impairment after the stroke; they even use the present linguistic status of the patient in their diagnosis. Similarly, linguists now seek neurological insights in assessing language disorder. Therefore, neurolinguistics is a discipline that deals with how language is represented in the nervous system, focusing attention on both the static (structural) and dynamic (process) aspects of language and brain.

Neurolinguistics is, therefore, the study of how language is processed and represented in the brain. The major concern of neurolinguists is to identify the parts of the brain involved with the production and understanding of language and to determine where the components of language (phonemes, morphemes, and structure or syntax) are stored. In doing so, they make use of techniques for analysing the structure of the brain and the effects of brain damage on language (Eastman and Longyear, 2008). To Parker (1986) the nature of neurolinguistics is “basically a correlational and statistical enterprise”. From the “correlational” point of view, the scholar explains that the preoccupation of the linguist is to try to “find correspondences between particular language function and particular parts of the brain...” Neurolinguistics, as a “statistical enterprise” is explained from the assumption that the linguist has some limitation. Parker opines that “the linguists cannot draw absolute correlations between a particular part of the brain and a particular language dysfunction for all human beings...” He, therefore, sees neurolinguists as the rescuer of linguists in that, “neurologists essentially make statistical

correlations between localised brain damage and particular language processing deficits”.

Often times, people tend to confuse neurolinguistics with psycholinguistics. While it is true that these disciplines have many things in common; for example, both are language-focused; they are distinctively different from each other. Psycholinguistics on its own merges the fields of psychology and linguistics to study how people process language and how language use is related to underlying mental processes (Eastman and Longyear, 2008). The focal point in psycholinguistics is mind in relation to language and other issues, while neurolinguistics concentrates on the brain and other components of the nervous system. Studies of children’s language acquisition and of second-language acquisition are psycholinguistic in nature. Psycholinguists work to develop models for how language is processed and understood, using evidence from studies of what happens when these processes go awry. They also study language disorders such as aphasia among others.

1.8 Evolution of human communication

Hurford (2008) asserts that human languages are far more complex than any animal communication system. Supporting a generally accepted perspective, He says that communication through language by human “are learned, rather than innate, a fact which partially accounts for their great diversity. Human languages are semantically compositional, generating new meaningful combinations as functions of the meanings of their elementary parts (words). This is unlike any known animal communication system (except the limited waggle dance of honeybees)”. The human’s ability to use language in describing and referring to objects and events in the far distant past and the far distant future is considered as another feature which distinguishes language from animal communication systems. The complexity of languages arises partly from self-organisation through cultural transmission over many generations of users. The human willingness altruistically to impart information is also unique (Hurford, 2008).

Scholars such as Harrub, Thompson and Miller (2003) agree that most humans have developed an ability to communicate through oral language and can comprehend, as well as express, written thoughts. Lieberman’s (1998) use of biblical terminology “in the beginning was the word” finds comfort within Harrub, Thompson and Miller’s postulations on the evolution of language.

Harrub, Thompson and Miller further assert that at creation, the first creations possessed the ability to understand verbal communication, and to speak themselves. Accordingly, they assert that the depiction of the origin of languages coincides with the present status of the world languages today and that the available linguistic evidence does not support the model postulated by evolutionary sources for the origin of languages. Harrub, *et al* (2003) also observes that “many evolutionary linguists believe that all human languages have descended from a single, primitive language, which itself evolved from the grunts and noises of the lower animals”. The scholars support Chomsky’s allusion that “the innate ability of children to acquire the grammar necessary for a language can be explained only if one assumes that all grammars are variations of a single, generic “universal grammar” and that all human brains come “with a built-in language organ that contains this language blueprint”.

1.8.1 Components of language processing

The human brain generally exhibits a slightly enlarged area in the left hemisphere called the planum temporal (PT) (Pott, 2008). The PT is a structure apparently involved in the processing of visual symbols and speech. Since the 1960s scientists have argued that the PT was necessary for language and may even constitute a uniquely human evolutionary adaptation. The new study is the first to demonstrate that the structure exists in another species, that is, the chimpanzee (Milligan, Astington and Dack, 2007).

In order to establish how language is processed in human, Milligan, Astington and Dack (2007) measured the right and left hemispheres of eighteen chimpanzee brains and found the enlarged area to be present in seventeen of the specimens. In contrast, studies of human brains have shown that seven out of ten humans display an enlarged PT. The existence of the PT in both humans and chimpanzees provides strong evidence that the structure existed in a common ancestor of both species some eight million years ago (Pinker, 1994).

Pott (2008) says that since chimpanzees do not appear to have developed language, the study suggested three distinct things. First, the PT in the common ancestor may have been unrelated to language functions but later evolved to fulfil those tasks in humans alone. (Second, the ancestral PT may have evolved to serve language functions, but followed separate trajectories in humans and chimpanzees. Humans developed spoken and sign languages. This raises the possibility that chimpanzees may have developed a

form of gestural-visual communication that is yet to be understood, the researchers said. Finally, it is possible that the PT is tangentially, but not directly, related to language functions in either humans or chimpanzees. Instead, the structure may be involved in unknown functions that are common to both species.

1.8.2 Structure of the human brain

The human brain has a number of physiological and structural characteristics that must be understood before beginning a discussion of the brain as language organ. The brain is described as a portion of the central nervous system contained within the skull. It is the control centre for movement, sleep, hunger, thirst, and virtually every other vital activity necessary to survival (Toga, 2009). Further, Toga says “all human emotions, including love, hate, fear, anger, elation, and sadness are controlled by the brain”. This implies that the brain also receives and interprets the countless signals that are sent to it from other parts of the body and from the external environment. The brain is, therefore, responsible for making human to be conscious, emotional and intelligent. The structure of the human brain is illustrated below.

Fig. 1.1: The human brain

Source: <http://www.brainwaves.com/>

The human brain has three major structural components: the large dome-shaped cerebrum at the top, the smaller somewhat spherical cerebellum which is at the lower right, and the brainstem located at the centre. The brainstem is continuous with the spinal

cord. Both the brain and the spinal cord are surrounded by three membranes called the meninges. Inflammation of the meninges is known as meningitis (Toga, 2009).

In Bookheimer's (2002) account of the structure of the brain which is corroborated by Pandora (2012). The structure is said to be described first, from the cerebrum, which consists of a cortex, that is, the outer layer and a subcortex which is also divided into two hemispheres and joined by a membrane called the corpus callosum. Pandora observes that in all humans, the right hemisphere controls the left side of the body; the left hemisphere controls the right side of the body. "This arrangement called contralateral neural control is not limited to humans but is also present in all vertebrates--fish, frogs, lizards, birds and mammals".

Offering more insights, Bookheimer (2002) opines that another crucial feature of brain physiology is that each hemisphere has somewhat unique functions (unlike other paired organs such as the lungs, kidneys, breasts or testicles which have identical functions). In other words, hemisphere function is asymmetrical. This is most strikingly the case in humans, where the right hemisphere, in addition to controlling the left side of the body also controls spatial acuity, while the left hemisphere, in addition to controlling the right side of the body controls abstract reasoning and physical tasks which require a step-by-step progression. In adults, the left hemisphere also controls language; even in most left-handed patients, lateralisation of language skills in the left hemisphere is completed by the age of puberty (Pandora, 2012).

In explaining how scholars know that the left hemisphere controls language in most adults, Ciaramidaro, Adenzato, Enrici, Erk, Pia, et al (2007) aver that there is a great deal of physical evidence for the left hemisphere as the language centre in the majority of healthy adults. Ciaramidaro et al (2007) say that tests have demonstrated increased neural activity in parts of the left hemisphere when subjects are using language. The same type of tests has demonstrated that artistic endeavour draws normally more heavily on the neurones of the right hemispheric cortex. A person with a stroke in the right hemisphere loses control over parts of the left side of the body, sometimes also suffers a diminution of artistic abilities. But language skills are not impaired even if the left side of the mouth is crippled, the brain can handle language as before. A person with a stroke in the left hemisphere loses control of the right side of the body; also, seventy percent of adult patients with damage to the left hemisphere will experience at least some language

loss which is not due only to the lack of control of the muscles on the right side of the mouth. In this, verbal communication of any sort is disrupted in a variety of ways that are not connected with the voluntary muscles of the vocal apparatus (Pandora, 2012).

1.8.3 Language and the brain

In comprehending certain issues relating to language and the brain, the contributions of Noam Chomsky are significant. To Chomsky and many other linguists, the human ability to acquire language is innate. They opine that there are universal principles of how human language is structured. In the line of this, there are language-specific factors known as parameters, which are the choices that govern specific languages based on the convention of that language (Chomsky, 1981).

The ability of the human beings to use language depends on the enormous amount of brain resources (Lamb, Cheng, Harrison, Farh and Shipman, 2011). These resources have to manage information of many thousands of words and many syntactic constructions and their interconnections and relate them to meanings and meaningful structures. Lamb et al (2011) aver that this complex combination of brain structures can be called “the brain’s linguistic system”. This implies that the physical basis of language transcends the use of the lips, tongue, or the ear, else, deaf and dumb people would have been exempted from the class of language users. Through the brain, human sign language, which is based on visible gesture rather than the creation of sound waves is possible for human interaction and recognised as the equally creative system just like the spoken and written forms of language. In sign language, the basis is not the hand, just as spoken language is not based on the lips or tongue. In neurology clinics, there are many patients who have lost both the ability to write as well as to express themselves using sign language, yet they never lose manual dexterity in other tasks such as sitting, standing and even decoding when a remark is made.

The implication of the situation above is that language is mainly dependent on the brains rather than the other parts involved in human interaction. This emphasises the importance of neurolinguistics to the understanding of language and use. Since the concern of neurolinguists is to study the physical structure of the brain as it relates to language, language production and comprehension (Willems and Varley, 2010); a pragmatic study of neurologist-patient interaction is invaluable to language study in

specific contexts and can aid the identification of ailment and proffering of solutions where there are problems.

1.8.4 Causes of speech and language disorders

There are various causes of speech and language disorders. Saint Elizabeth Regional Medical Centre (2014) views these from the perspective of children's use of language. The institution provides some insights into some of these causes which include: congenital syndromes; disorders of the prenatal environment, syndromes acquired after birth and factors that may contribute to a speech-language disorder. The institution says that congenital syndromes are present at birth; and that some of these syndromes that can cause language disorders include genetic syndromes, chromosomal syndromes, or metabolic disorders.

Genetic syndromes are explained to be those transmitted through genes and can be passed along from a parent to their child. Some genetic syndromes that may affect speech-language development include Fragile X Syndrome and congenital deafness. David and Moncrieff (2008) aver that chromosomal syndromes occur when there is an abnormality within a person's genetic composition. They posit that some chromosomal syndromes that may affect speech-language development include Turner Syndrome, Pierre Robin, Cri du Chat Syndrome, Klinefelter Syndrome, and DiGeorge Syndrome. The Metabolic disorder is said to affect a person's growth, development, and subsequent learning.

A research carried out by the Saint Elizabeth Regional Medical Centre (SERMC) in 2014 shows that disorders of the prenatal environment can be caused by a mother's contraction of, or exposure to, a particular disease or toxin. Rubella is identified as the most common virus that results in language impairment in the child. Other possible diseases that can affect language development include HIV/AIDS, herpes simplex, and chicken pox. Toxins, such as radiation (X-rays), alcohol, tobacco, and drugs can also affect the unborn child and result in language impairment. Fetal Alcohol Syndrome (FAS) may occur when a woman consumes alcohol during her pregnancy. FAS can cause a variety of difficulties, including speech and language disorders.

In the same report by SERMC, it is observed that syndromes acquired after birth can be caused by oxygen deprivation to the brain, infections, toxins, and traumatic brain injuries. Respiratory disorders or lack of oxygen to the brain during or shortly after birth

can cause brain damage, leading to language impairment. Infections, such as measles, mumps, and meningitis, and toxins, such as lead and poisons, can cause language impairment. Traumatic brain injuries from falls or accidents may also cause language impairments. Another cause of traumatic brain injury in infants is Shaken Baby Syndrome.

David and Moncrieff (2008), Morales (2009); ASHA. (2009); Mettler (2009) and Lamb et al (2011) corroborated the findings of SERMC that there are many factors that may contribute to a speech-language disorder. For instance, when speech-language disorders are not associated with any other syndrome or disability, they are known as “Specific Language Impairments” (Lamb et al 2011). Mettler (2009) says that the definite cause of specific language impairment is usually unknown, but there are a variety of factors that may or may not have influenced the speech and language development of that child. These, according to Mettler (2009), include:

Familial tendency: Specific-Language Impairment tends to run in families. However, there is not a known genetic link at this time. Currently, studies are being conducted to learn more about a possible genetic link.

Middle ear infections: Middle ear infections are extremely common among young children. A middle ear infection may cause a temporary hearing loss. When a child has frequent ear infections, at a young age during critical periods, they can miss out on sounds and language in their environment, causing a delay in their development.

Environment: Children need a lot of language stimulation in their environment and exposure to language in a variety of ways. When children are deprived of language stimulation early in their development they may not learn the sounds and rules of language. When caregivers respond to their child's pointing and grunting, the child does not perceive the need to use words to control his/her environment. Sometimes, an older sibling may "talk" for the child, also decreasing the need for the child to develop his/her speech and language. Environments that are not rich in language and new experiences can decrease the child's exposure to language and delay their development.

Some speech-language disorders have no known cause. Specific Language Impairment, Specific Learning Disability, and Autism are among those that still have an unknown aetiology (Mettler, 2009).

1.8.5 Language disorders related to the brain and effects

The notion that language is an important means of self-identification is an undeniable fact. It is through the language we speak that our sense of identity is bound up. Language is one of the principal markers of social identity and it serves as an important means of creating a sense of (ethnic) community. It is an indicator not only of a common present but also of a common past (Tonkin, 2003).

Caplan (1995) construes “language as an object of beauty in its own right...” He avers that language is vital to individual success. It is the natural human endowment. Chomsky (1968) agrees that every human being is capable of acquiring and utilising language. This is conveyed through his notion of competence and performance. However, certain factors can deprive human beings the right to the effective use of language. This is called language disorder or impairment. Such factors do not only affect one’s competence, but also performance. Diseases affecting language can cripple a person in his or her family or social group. Ongoing researches are making progress in understanding language, its neural basis, and how to successfully intervene in the course of language disorders.

Crystal (1997) defines language disorder as “...any systematic deficiency in the way people speak, listen, read, write, or sign that interferes with their ability to communicate with their peers”. Sunday (2008:10) says “language disorder may be attributed to a physical cause in some cases. In some people, it may be due to brain damage”. These have been given various names such as aphasia, dyslexia, schizophasia and so on.

Effects of language disorder have been identified as capable of seriously impairing the linguistic skills of affected people (Healey, 1997:474). Other effects of language disorder on communication include stigmatisation in the society, depression as a result of loneliness, perpetual incommunicativeness and dejection, lack of respect from others, inability to perform social functions, inability to make ends meet thus tending towards poverty, imbecility among others.

As a result, language disorder can be described as an impairment of humans, and their ability to utilise the creative power of communication in some or many forms. Crystal (1987) sees it as any systematic deficiency in the way people speak, listen, read, write, or sign that interferes with their ability to communicate with their peers. He observes that at one extreme, the handicap may be quite mild, such as a minor impediment of

pronunciation; while at the other, there may be an almost total breakdown of all modes of communication, as in severe forms of brain damage.

Some of the widely recognised disorders relating to language are discussed.

1.8.6.1 Aphasia

Aphasia is a coinage from the Greek words *a*, “not”; *phanai*, “to speak” (Mettler, 2009). The term was introduced by the French physician Armand Trousseau to denote an inability to express thoughts by means of speech, as a consequence of certain brain disorders (Geschwind, 1972). The meaning has since been extended to cover the loss of the faculty of interchanging thought, so that it may even denote a temporary but complete loss of memory (Buckingham, 1981). According to Sunday (2008), “the word aphasia is used only for cases of brain damage involving language dysfunction, not general brain damage”. Parker (1986) opines that it is also an acquired language disorder (which) only applies to a person who has already developed a linguistic system. He explains that somebody who has brain damage present at birth or who has it immediately after birth is not aphasic, in the strict sense of the term.

In an account of Mettler (2009) on aphasia, there are many types of this ailment. For instance, motor aphasia involves a loss of memory of the coordinated movements necessary for the formation of symbols. This usually includes gestures, speech, and writing. (The inability to write is commonly termed *agraphia*.) Victims of this disorder are unable to name any object shown to them, although they know what it is. Neither can they reply to any question although they may understand it.

In sensory aphasia, a loss of memory of the meaning of symbols occurs. This may affect the recollection of spoken language. The victim can hear every sound but cannot understand a single spoken word (Parker, 1986). Other identified types of the ailment are Broca aphasia, Wernicke aphasia, Transcortical aphasia, global aphasia, anomic aphasia and so on.

1.8.6.2 Dysfluencies

Dysfluency is one of the features of aphasia. Edwards (2002) describes it as a type of disorder of fluency related to stammering or stuttering. Dysfluency is regarded as a neurological damage while stammering and stuttering have often been categorised as genetic language disorders which have no known cause.

McNeil (1979:217) observes that speech dysfluencies are of different types. He identifies these as hesitation; breakdown and anti-utterance. He posits that hesitation is any interruptions in the flow of the speech output, such as unfilled pauses, filled pauses, glottal clicks and audible inhalations. McNeil observes that breakdowns in speech dysfluencies occur when there are collapses of structure followed by new structure build-ups, which are like breakdowns, but they involve no change of direction. The anti-utterance is referred to as the encoding a portion of an utterance prematurely; and errors of articulation.

Research in computational linguistics has revealed a correlation between native language and patterns of disfluencies in spontaneously uttered speech. Recent linguistic research has suggested that non-pathological disfluencies may contain a variety of meaning; the frequency of "uh" and "um" in English is often reflective of a speaker's alertness or emotional state. Some have hypothesised that the time of an "uh" or "um" is used for the planning of future words; other researchers have suggested that they are actually to be understood as full-fledged function words rather than accidents, indicating a delay of variable time in which the speaker wishes to pause without voluntarily yielding control of the dialogue. There is some debate as to whether to consider them a form of white noise or as a meaning-filled part of language (Snyder and Anderson 2008). Speech disfluencies are however not regarded a serious language impairment.

1.8.6.4 Expressive language disorder

Expressive language disorder refers to a situation where a person has difficulty conveying or expressing information in speech, writing, sign language or gesture. For pre-school children, the impairment is not evident in the written form, since they have not started formal education. Some children are late in reaching typical language milestones in the first three years, but eventually, catch up to their peers. These children are commonly referred to as "late-talkers". Children who continue to have difficulty with verbal expression may be diagnosed with expressive language disorder or another language impairment (Benner, 2005).

Children with expressive language disorder have difficulties with the grammatical aspects of spoken language such as using the correct verb tense (they might say "I go" when they mean "I went") and combining words to form accurate phrases and sentences. They typically produce much shorter phrases and sentences than other children of the

same age, and their vocabulary is smaller and more basic (Garvey, 1975). Children with expressive language disorder are usually below the average level for their age in putting words and sentences together to express thoughts; recalling the names of words, and using language appropriately in a variety of settings with different people (Cicci, 1980).

For many children, the cause of expressive language disorder is not known. Children who experience difficulties in language development alone are typically diagnosed with specific language impairment. For other children, expressive language disorder is associated with known developmental difficulties or impairments, (for example, Down syndrome, autism or hearing loss). Many children with expressive language disorder will have an accompanying “receptive” language disorder, meaning that they have difficulty in understanding language. Expressive language disorder can be a developmental (from birth) or acquired impairment. An acquired impairment occurs after a period of normal development (Benner, 2005).

1.8.6.5 Language comprehension deficit

Language comprehension deficit implies that the child has difficulties with understanding what is said to them. The symptoms vary between children but, generally, problems with language comprehension usually begin before the age of four years. Children need to understand spoken language before they can use language effectively. In most cases, the child with a receptive language problem also has an expressive language disorder, which means they have trouble using spoken language. It is estimated that between three and five percent of children have a receptive or expressive language disorder, or a mixture of both (Cicci, 1980). Another name for language comprehension deficit, according to Cicci, is “receptive language disorder”. With respect to this disorder and others, treatment options may include speech-language therapy among others.

A report by the State Government of Victoria (2015) agrees that there is no standard set of symptoms that indicate language comprehension deficit since it varies from one child to the next. The document, however, assumes that symptoms relating to language comprehension deficit may include not seeming to listen when they (the children) are spoken to; appearing to lack interest when storybooks are read to them; inability to understand complicated sentences; inability to follow verbal instructions; parroting words or phrases of things that are said to them (echolalia); language skills below the expected level for their age.

This language impairment is often associated with developmental disorders such as autism or Down syndrome. In other cases, language comprehension deficit is caused by brain injuries such as trauma, tumour or disease. For some children, difficulty with language is the only developmental problem they experience.

1.9 Diagnoses and treatment of language-related disorder

The nervous system refers to “those elements within the animal organism that are concerned with the reception of stimuli, the transmission of nerve impulses, or the activation of muscle mechanisms” (Kording, 2007; Mettler, 2009). In the discipline of neurology, consideration of disorders of the nervous system is the core issue. It varies from psychiatry, which deals with behavioural disturbances of a functional nature. However, scholars have not been able to clearly define the division between these two medical specialities, because neurological disorders often manifest both organic and mental symptoms. Efforts at diagnosing and treating the emanating disorder of the nervous system have been major concerns of neurologists, how these are carried out is discussed.

Diagnoses of language-related disorder sometimes vary depending on the nature of speech or language impairment of various patients in need of treatment. Scholars in related disciplines to speech treatment such as Thonssen and Gilkinson (1955); Ulman, and Sutherland (1979); O'Brian and Onslow (2011) are of the opinion that the initial investigation of events leading the patients to the clinic is also an important factor that determines type or method of diagnosis. Some of the methods of diagnoses identified by Roth and Worthington (2015) include:

- a) hearing tests by an audiologist to make sure the language problems are not caused by hearing loss and to establish whether or not the patient is able to pay attention to sound and language (auditory processing assessment)
- b) testing the patient's comprehension (by a speech pathologist) and comparing the results to the expected skill level for the patient's age. If the patient is from a non-English speaking home, assessment of comprehension should be performed in their first language, as well as in English, using culturally appropriate materials
- c) close observation of the patient in a variety of different settings while they interact with a range of people
- d) assessment by a neurologist to help identify any associated cognitive problems

- e) vision tests to check for vision loss.

Treatment options depend on the severity of the impairment. Roth and Worthington (2015) summarise steps in the selection and programming of treatment targets and provide sample case profiles for early intervention through adolescence. They also identify a number of basic principles of effective intervention regardless of the age of the or disorder. Some of the treatment options enumerated are:

- a) Group sessions with a speech pathologist;
- b) Individual therapy sessions with a speech pathologist;
- c) School-based language intervention programmes;
- d) Assistance from special education teachers;
- e) Teacher's aid support for children with severe language impairment; and
- f) Speech pathology sessions combined with home programmes that parents can use with their child.

There are, however, other descriptions of general and specific treatments for addressing language disorders. American Speech-Language-Hearing Association' (ASHA) Report has, for example, made some attempts at organising treatment options into broader categories, with the recognition that intervention approaches do not always fit neatly into one particular category. It should, therefore, be borne in mind that some of the approaches listed above are most often associated with treatment for social communication disorder and autism spectrum disorder. The listed treatment options are included because they are also used with a broader population of children and adults with language disorders (ASHA Report, 2015). The list is, however, not exhaustive.

1.10 General models of human communication

In the general context, models of communication vary based on the areas of specialisation of individual proponents. A few of the existing communication models are discussed.

1.10.1 Shannon-Weaver mathematical model

Human communication occurs in a variety of ways. Claude Elwood Shannon and Warren Weaver (1949) have been identified as the first major model for communication. They were engineers and mathematicians working for Bell Telephone Laboratories in the

United States. The original communication model was designed to mirror the functioning of radio and telephone technologies (International Association of Communication Activist, n. d). Their initial model consisted of three primary parts: sender (the part of a telephone a person spoke into), channel (the telephone itself), and receiver (the part of the phone where one could hear the other person). This model is called the mathematical, or early linear or “transmission” model of communication. (Broadhurst and Darnell, 1965).

To Broadhurst and Darnell, there is often a static that interferes with one listening to a telephone conversation. They identify this as noise which could also mean the absence of signal. As a result, communication is perceived as a means of sending and receiving information. This model gains its strengths from the notions of simplicity, generality, and quantifiability. The linear or “transmission” model of communication were structured based on five elements namely: a specific information source, which produces a message; a transmitter, which encodes the message into signals; a channel, to which signals are adapted for transmission; a receiver, which decodes the message from the signal; and a destination, where the message arrives. Shannon and Weaver assume that there were three levels of problems for communication within this model, these are: the technical problem which probes how accurately can the message be transmitted; the semantic problem, which requires how precisely is the meaning “conveyed”; and the effectiveness problem, which queries how effectively does the received meaning affect behaviour (shkaminski.com, n.d.).

Chandler (1994) disagrees on the suitability of the transmission model to human communication. He avers that the transmission model is purely a technical one that describes the functionality of telephone technology, especially with regards to the “noise factor”. He opines that the model “is not merely a gross over-simplification but a dangerously misleading misrepresentation of the nature of human communication”. Chandler reasons that such model assumes that communicators are isolated individuals. And as such (like the telephone), gives no allowance for differing purposes; no allowance for differing interpretations; no allowance for unequal power relations; and no allowance for situational contexts. (see Chandler, 1994)

1.10.2 David Berlo SMCR model

Berlo's (1960) model of communication, an advancement of Shannon and Weaver's (1949) model sees communication from the perspective of the Sender-Message-Channel-Receiver (SMCR). The relevance of the model becomes significant after the World War II because of the flexibility of the "source" idea which includes oral, written, electronic, or any other kind of "symbolic" generator-of-messages. Also, the M of the "Message" was made the central element, stressing the transmission of ideas (Management Study Guide, 2015; Oyero, 2010). The model recognised that receivers were important to communication, for they were the targets. Moreover, the notions of "encoding" and "decoding" emphasised the problems experienced by humans (psycho-linguistically) in translating own thoughts into words or other symbols and in deciphering the words or symbols of others into terms they can understand. The SMCR model of communication separated the model into clear parts and has been expanded upon by other scholars.

1.10.3 Wilbur Schramm two-way interchange model

Wilbur Schramm (1954) was one of the first to alter the mathematical model of Shannon and Weaver (Businessstopia, 2017). According to Businessstopia, Schramm conceived of decoding and encoding as activities maintained simultaneously by sender and receiver; he also made provisions for a two-way interchange of messages. In this, he made an inclusion of an "interpreter" as an abstract representation of the problem of meaning. In his assumptions, communication is described along a few major dimensions: Message (what type of things are communicated), source / emisor / sender / encoder (by whom), form (in which form), channel (through which medium), destination / receiver / target /decoder (to whom), and Receiver (see Schramm, 1963).

Schramm also indicated that humans must examine the impact that a message has (both desired and undesired) on the target of the message. For example, between parties, communication includes acts that confer knowledge and experiences, give advice and commands, and ask questions. These acts may take many forms, in one of the various manners of communication. The form depends on the abilities of the group communicating. Together, communication content and form make messages that are sent towards a destination. The target can be oneself, another person or being, another entity (such as a corporation or group of beings).

In relation to language studies, Schramm's model sees communication as processes of information transmission governed by three levels of semiotic rules: Syntactic (formal

properties of signs and symbols), Pragmatic (concerned with the relations between signs/expressions and their users) and Semantic (study of relationships between signs and symbols and what they represent). Therefore, communication is the social interaction where at least two interacting agents share a common set of signs and a common set of semiotic rules. This commonly held rule in some sense ignores auto-communication, including intrapersonal communication via diaries or self-talk, both secondary phenomena that followed the primary acquisition of communicative competencies within social interactions.

1.10.4 Barnlund transactional model

Barnlund (1968) proposed a transactional model of communication. The basic premise of the transactional model of communication is that individuals are simultaneously engaging in the sending and receiving of messages. In a slightly more complex form, a sender and a receiver are linked reciprocally. This second attitude of communication referred to as the constitutive model or constructionist view, focuses on how an individual communicates as the determining factor of the way the message will be interpreted. Communication is viewed as a conduit; a passage in which information travels from one individual to another and this information becomes separate from the communication itself. A particular instance of communication is called a speech act (See Grice, 1975). The sender's personal filters and the receiver's personal filters may vary depending upon different regional traditions, cultures, or gender; which may alter the intended meaning of message contents. In the presence of "communication noise" on the transmission channel (air, in this case), reception and decoding of content may be faulty, and thus the speech act may not achieve the desired effect.

1.10.5 Westley and MacLean's conceptual model

Westley and MacLean, (1957) conceptual model was proposed to argue that communication does not begin when one person starts to talk, instead the beginning of communication is when a person responds selectively to his immediate physical surroundings (Shoemaker and Reese 1996). This model accounts for feedback, it also recognises "objects of co-orientation" (Mortensen, 1972; Petersons and Khalimzoda 2016). It accounts for non-binary interactions, a situation where more than just two people are communicating directly, and as well as gives recognition to the other different models such as interpersonal against mass-mediated communication (Communicationtheory.org, 2010). This model is deficient in that, it accounts for many

more variables in the typical communication interaction. However, it is still two-dimensional. Another challenge is that it cannot account for the multiple dimensions of the typical communication event involving a broad context and multiple messages.

1.10.6 Ruesch and Bateson functional model

Ruesch and Bateson (1951) conceived of communication as functioning simultaneously at four levels of analysis. At level one is the basic intrapersonal process. The next is interpersonal and focuses on the overlapping fields of experience of two interactants. At the third level, which comprises many people is the group interaction. Finally, the cultural level, which is the fourth, links large groups of people. Moreover, each level of activity consists of four communicative functions. These are: evaluating, sending, receiving, and channelling. This model focuses less on the structural attributes of communication, that is, the source, message, receiver, etc, instead, the emphasis is placed more on the actual determinants of the process.

1.11 Deductions from the existing models

Going by some of the models discussed, it can be deduced that communication models are either linear, transactional, interactive and so on. This is buttressed.

- The Linear model is a one-way model to communicate with others. It consists of the sender encoding a message and channelling it to the receiver in the presence of noise. In this, there is a clear-cut beginning and end to communication. However, it displays no feedback from the receiver. For example; a letter, email, text message, lecture. Shannon and Weaver's mathematical model is an example of this.
- The transactional model assumes that people are connected through communication; they engage in transaction. There is the recognition that each individual is a sender-receiver, not merely a sender or a receiver. Secondly, it recognises that communication affects all parties involved. Therefore, communication is fluid/simultaneous. This is how most conversations are patterned. The transactional model also contains ellipses that symbolise the communication environment, that is, how one interprets the data that is given, and so on. An example of the model in this category is Barnlund's (1968).
- Interactive is two linear models stacked on top of each other. The sender channels a message to the receiver and the receiver then becomes the sender and channels a message to the original sender. This model has added feedback, indicates that

communication is not a one-way but a two-way process. It also has “field of experience” which includes humans’ cultural background, ethnicity geographic location, the extent of travel, and general personal experiences accumulated over the course of a lifetime. The none simultaneous feedback can be a disadvantage in this model. For example, in the use of Short Message Service (SMS). A user (sender) sends a message to another user (the receiver), then the original sender has to wait for the message from the original receiver to react. This waiting is conceived as a drawback of this model. In this category is the Westley and MacLean’s conceptual model

1.11.1 Communication noise

In any communication model, noise is the interference with the decoding of messages sent over a channel by an encoder. (Watzlawick, Beavin, and Jackson, 1967:112). There are many examples of noise. These include environmental noise, physiological-impairment noise, semantic noise (different interpretations of the meanings of certain words). For example, the word "weed" can be interpreted as an undesirable plant in a yard, or as a euphemism for marijuana. Others are syntactical noise, (mistakes in grammar like abrupt changes in verb tense during a sentence), organisational noise, psychological noise, and cultural noise (stereotypical assumptions such as calling a certain person, certain names they regard offensive despite its original meaning (Nettleton, Orriols-Puig and Fornells, 2010).

1.12 Communication/consultation models in hospitals

Communication model in the hospital is an important aspect of institutional interaction (see Arminen, 2005). Among some medical professionals, the term “consultation” is preferred. Medical consultation connotes an encounter between a medical practitioner and a patient. This may be initiated by a patient when there is a need for such as a result of (suspected) illness or at the instance of the doctor when preventive medicine or screening is being instituted (Pawlikowska, Leach, Lavalley, Charlton and Piercy, 2007). Researchers in medicine and related disciplines have explored various consultation models in hospital interactions. Some of these are summarised.

According to Pawlikowska et al (2007), there are some consultation models referred to as “individual consultation models”. This refers to models of consultation that were

developed by “people who bring to their analysis their own experience and vision, (psychologists or anthropologists) and so the emphasis of each model differs.

Further, the categorisations range from being overarching approaches (Maslow, 1954) and Berne (1964); consultation dynamics (Balint, 1957); doctor-centred (Bryne and Long, 1976); doctor-patient dialogic’s sharing of responsibilities (Pendleton, Schofield, Tate and Havelock, 1984); contemporary models such as Emanuel and Emanuel model (1992), Pendleton (2003), to Kurtz (1996) among others.

Among these, Emanuel and Emanuel (1992) model which is the most widely studied (Agarwal and Murinson, 2012) is selected for analysis in the study. The four-part classification system described by Emanuel and Emanuel, in which the patient-physician interaction is described as one of four possible types: paternalistic, deliberative, interpretive, and informative distinguished by the formation of patient values, assignment of decision-making responsibilities (autonomy), and physician disclosure of medical information. This is expounded in section 2.4.2.

1.13 Summary

This chapter provides background to the study. The next chapter is focused on the review of relevant literature and theoretical framework adopted for analysis of data for the study.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

2.0 Introduction

This chapter explores existing literature related to the study and theoretical issues. In doing this, studies in doctor-patient interactions, discourse and neurolinguistics, pragmatics among others are reviewed. Also, relevant theoretical issues in the study are investigated.

2.1 Studies on doctor-patient interactions

Studies on doctor-patient interactions have occupied a significant space in medical communication among scholars within the shore of Nigeria and other parts of the world. Outside Nigeria, scholars like Korsch and Negrete (1972), Byrne and Long (1976), Wodak (1997), Coulthard and Ashby (1976), Heritage and Maynard (2006), Maynard and Hudak (2008), George (2010), Peck and Conner (2011) are notable contributors to the topic. Within the country, Odebunmi (2003, et cetera), Faleke (2005), Salami (2006) Adegbite and Odebunmi (2006) Akinola (2013), Qasim (2014) Nwabueze and Nwankwo (2016) and many others are some of the researchers, whose findings have giving credence to doctor-patient interaction as a worthy academic enterprise.

Coulthard and Ashby (1976) observed the recurrence of doctor-initiated exchanges in diagnostic interaction between doctor and patients in one of the earlier studies on doctor-patient interaction. They observe that if a patient attempts to initiate conversation, the doctor does not feel he/she has an obligation to respond. In the study, it was observed that the interaction is made up of transfer exchanges, in which information passes from the responding patient to the eliciting doctor, and matching exchanges, in which the patient presents information for the doctor to confirm. Through the study, it was concluded that the negotiation of a shared orientation between doctor and patient takes place through series (sequences) of exchanges in a sequence until the doctor is finally able to match a medical diagnosis with the patient's problem.

The significance of the use of language in medical discourse has been reflected in the serious attention paid to it in the literature (Odebunmi, 2010). A representative typification of studies on doctor-client interactions has been made by Heritage and

Maynard (2006). They identify two directions in the research, namely, process analysis and microanalysis of discourse. The former, developed by Barbara Korsch and other scholars with her intellectual conviction, was built on Bale's (1950) coding system tagged, "Interaction Process Analysis". Studies in this school focus on the role relationship in the encounter between the doctor and the client (Odebunmi, 2010:2-3).

Similarly, Adegbite and Odebunmi (2006) investigate the tactics employed when doctors communicate with their patients. They investigate the mutual contextual beliefs, speech acts patterns, linguistic patterns, and other pragmatic features of participants in the study. They opine that there is a predominance of doctor-initiated spoken exchanges through which doctors elicit and confirm information and give directives to patients, while the patients give information and attempt to respond appropriately to the doctors' moves. In the study, certain maxims, such as conversation and politeness are considered flouted as a result of the doctors' attempt at enhancing successful diagnosis in the interaction. These scholars, therefore, see doctor-patient interaction as one of the diverse aspects of medical communication in which the attention of language scholars is required so as to gain insight into language as an act of social behaviour and action, especially with respect to the institution of medicine.

The approach of Maynard and Hudak (2008) to doctor-patient interaction is by considering what they termed "small talk" using a clinic for orthopaedic surgery. In the study, "small talk enables *disattending* to the instrumental tasks" in which one or both participants (in the interaction) may be engaged. The scholars' approach is from the context of prosocial interaction of the participants. A distinction between "small talk" and "work talk" is made. Small talk and work talk are said to have an intimate connection in the sense that small talk helps to constitute social relationship that facilitates instrumental task in the hospital context.

George (2010) explores the interaction between doctors and patients from the point of view of care rendered to patients suffering from fever in the allopathic hospitals of Kerala. Using the narrative method of analysis, the scholar argues that clinical interaction is not merely a two-way communication desired for the exchange of information, but it is an outcome of socialisation of doctors and patients within their respective contexts. It was also assumed that voices in constant doctor-patient interaction vary and as such have a significant role in the process of medical care.

For Peck and Conner (2011), the change in doctor-patient interaction was the focus. They affirm that not all interactions between doctors and patients are collaborative. Using status characteristics theory, they hypothesise that medical encounters are more likely dominated by the physician when there are higher status differences between doctors and patients. Their deductions were based on the variables of race, gender and socio-economic status differences between doctors and patients. For example, Peck and Conner opine that doctor-patient interactions were most times physician-centred when the doctor has higher status than patients on race (white versus non-white) and gender (male versus female).

In a study by Akinola (2013), doctor-patient interaction is approached from the perspective of pragmatics with a focus on aphasics. An outpatient clinic of a university college hospital was sampled. Pragmatic acts utilised in the interaction were examined. In the study, he opines that doctor initiation of certain pragmatic acts is deliberate and purposeful. Some acts were identified as predominant. These include diagnosing, encouraging, declaring, advising and prescribing while among the least employed practs were empathising and veiling. The study concludes that the patients participate to a great extent by utilising their communicative prowess in the context of their situation.

Qasim (2014) provides insight into the aspect of power relations in clinical encounters between doctors and their patients using selected hospital in Lagos as the basis. The author, using “triangulation” method and Systemic Functional Linguistics coupled with Critical Discourse Analysis aver that use of relational and other related processes enhance diagnostic and therapeutic purposes of the encounter. He, therefore, construes the doctor as “the powerful discourse participant, (who) uses his power to the benefit of his clients through the judicious use of transitivity processes” (Qasim, 2014:182).

The interest of Nwabueze and Nwankwo (2016) is to examine the role of language, ethnicity and gender as factors that determine the relationship between doctor and patients’ interpersonal communication. In their findings, the opine that these variables have a significant influence on the interpersonal communication of the interactants. They, therefore, advocate improvement of doctors’ interpersonal communication skills which according to them “instil confidence in patients” and guarantees patients’ freedom in discussing salient health issues with doctors.

2.2 Related studies on neurologist-patient communication

Studies on communication between neurologists and their patients have enjoyed a wide range of attention in scholarship. At the moment, most of these interests have emanated from the medical discipline. However, there is growing attention in linguistics and related disciplines with regards to the discourse. Some of these, in linguistics, and the mainstream medical researches, are explored.

Gilliam, Penovich, Eagan, Stern, Labiner et al (2009) conducted a linguistic study in a State in the United States of America which investigates neurologist-patient discussions of epilepsy (a disorder of the central nervous system characterised by loss of consciousness and convulsions). In the study, twenty neurologists, and sixty patients diagnosed with epilepsy were involved. From the sociolinguistic perspective, the study reveals that a higher percentage of patients (seventy-five) discussed side effects with their neurologists. It is also observed that in “postvisits”, there are often disagreements regarding the nature of the side effects experienced between the patients and neurologists.

Further, in the study, it is observed that when the relative of the patient is present, the discussions tend to be lengthier with more details of the side effects based on the previous communication. Regarding the psychological acts, such as “mood and behaviour-related comorbidities”, this has an “infrequent” occurrence. The researchers observed that the neurologists involved in the study have the feeling that management of mood and behaviour-related comorbidities, in the context of their interactions with epilepsy patients, is “outside their area of expertise”. As a result of this communication gap discovered between neurologists and their patients suffering epilepsy with regards to their psyche, the scholars, advocate a further investigation into the treatment of patients with this ailment. The study is however deficient, in that, it did not give any information on the type of model of communication adopted by the interactants.

Unlike Gilliam et al (2009), Kanaan, Armstrong and Wessely (2009) investigated the dilemma faced by neurologists when communicating with their conversion disorder patients and attempted describing the model of communication as paternalistic. Kanaan et al (2009) observe that conversion disorder (also called hysteria) manifests through symptoms such “paralysis, which first appear at first to be neurological in origin which on closer examination do not fit with known anatomy, physiology or neuropathology”.

The study offers information on the communication methods used by the neurologists in the United Kingdom (UK) in describing the dilemma in medical practice. Using snowball sampling to recruit neurologists from a region in the UK, twenty-two of the neurologists were engaged through in-depth interview, which was analysed in a qualitative way.

The researchers discovered that neurologists hesitated in their disclosure of conversion disorder as a differential diagnosis until they were very sure. The interviewed neurologists gave three descriptions in which they communicated with their patients about diagnosis as “the differential; the management interview; and putting it in writing”. It was also discovered that neurologists described conversion as a “severe, neurologically unexplained disorder for which a psychological model might be available, albeit not usually from them (neurologists). This is assumed to have created gaps between neurologists’ beliefs and the discussion of both psychological models and feigning. In other words, the truth is conveyed in much of a prevarication rather than the absolute truth saying. The scholars, therefore aver, that the reasons for the gaps between preferred and achieved communication are mainly due to the neurologists’ desire for therapeutic effect and their wish to avoid confrontation, which often coincided. In this, the neurologist described a way of saying what they believed, more or less, while still helping the patients. This serves as piloting a middle way to resolving “the apparent stark dilemma- tell the truth and lose the patient, or dissemble and help them”. It is assumed further, that in the differential diagnosis, the neurologists were classified as paternalist because they defer the discussion until they are certain, sparing the patient and themselves an awkward, and hopefully unnecessary, a period of stress.

In the conclusion, Kanaan, Armstrong and Wessely observe that “communicating the diagnosis of conversion disorder was seen as potentially challenging by neurologists, who described adapting their communication to their patients’ receptivity to psychological thinking...”. By implication, they assume that in a situation where patients appear to disagree with a diagnosis, it does not translate to the idea that the patient has rejected the neurologist’s opinion. Empirical researches on optimum strategy for communicating diagnoses of unexplained neurology is therefore encouraged for its therapeutic benefits. It can be observed that the study merely provided information on paternalist communication model, leaving out other available models in the frame.

Another study similar to the neurologist-patient categorisation is Oyeleye and Sunday (2013). However, the study cannot be categorised as purely a neurologist-patient interaction. This is because the focus of the study was to examine researchers' interaction with aphasics within the theoretical foundation of the relevance theory. Their purpose was to identify the systematic ways in which the meanings of the utterances of aphasics can be decoded by someone who was not present during the time the speech of the aphasic was recorded by the researchers. The recording was done with the use of a tape recorder to record the speech of three Yoruba-English bilingual aphasics from a teaching hospital in a Southwestern state of Nigeria, the patients were purposively sampled after they have been attended to by consultants who are neurologists.

In the study, it is emphasised that processing the discourses of aphasics should not be dismissed as lacking relevance and coherence. Rather, the interlocutors (with aphasics) need to eschew patience, so as to be able to listen and try to assume what is being said by an aphasia person. Some strategies were suggested in achieving the communication success. These include constructing a special grammar for the aphasic using a lot of explicatures, showing interest and encouraging the patient, and asking a few relevant questions among others. Oyeleye and Sunday therefore, suggest that an interlocutor needs to "enter an aphasic world of experience to enjoy (the) discourse". Importantly, these scholars opine that the contextual resources brought by the interlocutors or analysts into the discourse situation are crucial in the understanding the speeches or discourses of aphasics. A gap in the study is borne out of the fact that the study was carried out by researchers who were not trained neurologists. Consequently, their interaction with the patients was purely academic, rather than neurologist's usual diagnostic and therapeutic-driven communication. The study is also silent on the type of the model of communication employed in the interactions with the observed aphasic. It, however, serves as a possible motivation to investigating interactions with neurology patients in the southwestern region of Nigeria by any researcher who is interested in the subject.

Akinola's (2013) study which fits into the categorisation of neurologist-patient interaction as the study investigated the interactions between neurologists and aphasia patients in a university teaching hospital in a state in the Southwestern part of Nigeria. Using pragmatic act theory, the focus was to identify the linguistic tools employed by doctors in tandem with the roles of aphasics towards diagnoses and treatments. The study

also sought to account for the most recurring communication strategies in doctor-aphasic interactions and how pragmatic features of the interactions are contextualised.

The researcher's investigation involved "five clearly identified doctor-aphasics interactions". He deployed audio recorder to store the conversations between neurologists and their patients. More insights were drawn from the patients' case notes and interview with neurologists. In the study, it is observed that "doctors" initiation of certain pragmatic acts is deliberate and purposeful, with predominant practs being the diagnosing, encouraging, declaring, advising and prescribing. It was also revealed that most of the aphasics, especially Wernicke's, possessed some linguistics prowess of which the response or responding pract was identified as the most prevalent. In the study, the peculiarity of the structure of doctor-aphasic interactions was emphasised. The scholar assumes that language and understanding of contexts are identified as the most useful tools which the doctors employed as they attempted to unravel the cause, nature, stages of improvement of the aphasics, through which necessary medications were prescribed. He also says that the choice of linguistic items selected by doctors in their meeting with aphasics is highly structured within pragmatics. He avers that it is through these that all behavioural and communicative patterns of the aphasic were decoded. He concludes that neurologist-aphasic interaction contextualises features of pragmatics and also provides insight into pragmatic and linguistic aspects of medical discourse in general. He sees pragmatic analysis as invaluable to the understanding of human interactions, social values and relevance. This study is also deficient, in that, the study was conducted in just one hospital in the southwestern region. The findings might be different when other hospitals in the region are included. Similar to previous and related studies on neurologist-patient interaction, there is no basis offered by Akinola's (2013) study in describing communication models adopted in the observed interactions.

Further, the focus of a research carried out by Elsey, Drew, Jones, Blackburn, Wakefield, et al (2015) is the profile of patients' interactional behaviour in memory clinic conversations with neurologists. The purpose is to ascertain whether the patients' profile of interactional behaviour contributes to the "clinical differentiation between functional memory disorders (FMD) and memory problems related to neurodegenerative diseases". They also seek at finding out whether patient's interaction is diagnostically a relevant resource to differentiating organic and non-organic causes of memory complaints. They were also focused on patients' participation in initial clinical encounters with

neurologists, in order to investigate the potential of using conversational features to distinguish memory complaints related to functional causes from those caused by non-organic. Their investigation was done with the use of the video recordings of the neurologist-patient interactions, backed with independent “Gold standard” diagnoses, clinical assessment, neuropsychological testing and brain imaging of those who were attending seizure and memory clinics in Sheffield in the United Kingdom. In all, thirty cases were included. The analyses were carried out in line with the Conversation Analysis (CA).

In the study, Elsey et al (2015) aver that there are two conversational profiles for patients with memory complaints, namely, patients who attend the clinic whether or not they are accompanied; and patients’ responses to neurologists’ questions about memory problems, such as 3 difficulties with compound questions and providing specific and elaborated examples and frequent “I don’t know” responses. The findings show that there is a diagnostic potential in the conversation profiles based on patients’ contributions to memory clinic encounters. This, as they aver, assist the screening and referral process in primary care, and in the secondary care, it assists the diagnostic service. As a result of this, the study is considered by the authors to be invaluable in primary and secondary care settings despite the fact that their investigation was conducted in a hospital-based specialist memory clinic. An advocacy was made with respect to other linguistic techniques and statistical method which are capable of yielding additional insights into the neurologist-patient interaction. The lacuna in the study is that it is purely patient-centred. There is also a glaring silence on the roles of neurologists in the interactions. The investigation of neurologists’ roles in the interaction could have aided readers’ understanding into the implication of participants’ roles in the discourse rather than those of the patients alone.

A study by Panasiuk (2015) was centred on the neurologists. It examines the neurologist’s procedure for speech therapy diagnosis of acquired speech disorders in neurological patients in Lublin, Poland. The focus was to examine “the principles of data interpretation in differentiating symptoms of aphasia, pragnosia, dementia, psychoorganic syndrome and dysarthria, based on three interactional categories: text, metatext and context”. This is pursued within the theoretical base of “Alexander Luria’s concept of functional system (1967)”. Panasiuk describes these interactional categories. He sees the text, as that which “substantially expressed verbal behaviours that are

grammatically, semantically and pragmatically coherent”. The metatext is understood as “an exponent of knowledge of the inventory of signs and rules of combining them in large wholes (which is) the knowledge actualised in a concrete act of speaking, writing, and reading”. By implication, the metatext connotes that each linguistic message “contains reference to a code in the selection and combination of its constituents...”. Regarding the third category, the context, it is construed as the “sender’s and the receiver’s knowledge about both textual determinants and non-textual determinants”. The textual determinants include the “structurally closest environment of units of the language system, that is, the verbal environment of a word in the text”. On the other side, the non-textual determinants include the “sender’s and the receiver knowledge about culture, social relations, a communicative situation and the like”.

Panasiuk emphasises the need for speech therapy diagnosis to answer the questions of the aetiology of speech disorders, their pathomechanism and symptomatology. He says that by indicating the disorder type, therapeutic procedures should be selected by neurologists, with attention on the degree of disordered language functions, and also the state of the patient’s interactive capabilities, so as to determine the duration and efficacy of rehabilitation. This study considered what can be termed “clinical procedures” rather than a pragmatic description of the interaction involving the participants, that is, the neurologists and patients. Hence, it also sustained the silence on neurologist-patient interaction as observed in the other existing studies.

Piccolo, Pietrolongo, Radice, Tortorella, Confalonieri, et al (2015) investigate patient expression of emotions and neurologist reactions during what they regarded as “first-ever MS (Multiple Sclerosis) consultations” with the use of the VR-CoDES (Verona Coding Definition of Emotional Sequences) on ten neurologists and eighty-eight adult patients at four centres in Italy. In the study which was purely scientific, four cues and one concern were observed during the consultations, with the most common cues observed being the verbal hints of hidden worries and references to stressful life events. They also found out that patient emotional expressions varied widely. The anxiety in patients was directly associated with emotional expressions; older age of patients and neurologists, and second opinion consultations (by providing medical advice, switching topics, or ignoring the content of the cue) were inversely associated with patient emotional expression. More so, as they observed, on the average, neurologists responded to emotional expressions by

reducing space, which happens more often after the patient expressed a concern, and also after the patient referred to stressful life events or situations.

Piccolo et al suggest that neurologists must improve their communication skills in dealing with patient's emotion. Specifically, they emphasise the need to empower Italian MS neurologists with better communication and shared decision-making skills. This is because of the observation that physicians too often fail to respond sensitively to the emotional cues expressed by their patients. Whereas sensitive responses are essential for effective shared decision-making. Their study provides a basis for literature on emotional communication during neurological consultations. However, the location of the study is Euro-centric. A similar study conducted elsewhere is capable of producing a varying result. Apart from this, there is no reference to the description of the type of the consultation or communication model employed in their observations.

In a similar study conducted by Messina, Costa, Rodegher, Moiola, Colombo et al (2015), a global perspective is provided to neurologist-patient communication with regards to multiple sclerosis (MS) (which is assumed to be the leading cause of nontraumatic neurological disability in young adults in Europe and in the United States). This study was also carried out at selected Italian neurological departments, involving one hundred and fifty patients (inpatients or outpatients) diagnosed with clinically isolated syndrome (CIS) or MS. An Italian survey was developed for the study so as to assess factors affecting patients' satisfaction with the diagnosis communication. Also, a questionnaire was used to collect additional information on the patients.

From the observation and other research methods adopted, it is reported that over half of the sampled patients (61.3%) were being moderately satisfied with the information provided at the diagnosis communication (by neurologists). 16% of the patients were highly satisfied, while 23.3% were not at all satisfied. The missing information required by those who were not satisfied were identified as MS diagnosis, prognosis, and available treatments. It was also noted that an adequate emotional support and a communication tailored to the patient's profile resulted in a higher satisfaction. The results show that a dedicated individual approach could help to ensure that patients assimilated and understand the provided information. In the study, it was also found that a higher percentage of patients suggested public meetings with other patients, sharing directly their experiences and perspectives, could be useful to improve their coping

strategies after the communication of the diagnosis. The researchers aver that their study prospectively evaluates evolving ways and strategies of disclosing the diagnosis of MS over the impact of new health-related technologies and providing information about the disease that meet patients' preferences and expectations. The research effort of these scholars is commendable because it provided additional individualised information on how to effectively improve acceptance of MS diagnosis which is capable of influencing the patients' quality of life. Conversely, the use of questionnaires as one of the methodologies employed makes the study somewhat less of a truly neurologist-patient interaction. It can be regarded as a patients' opinion-centred research since it did not account for the actual interaction that takes place between neurologists and their patients.

From the foregoing, it is observed that attention to neurologist-patient interaction is growing and becoming global too. Some of these studies have been centred on diverse issues, such as interactions with epilepsy patients (Gilliam, Penovich, Eagan, Stern, Labiner, et al 2009); patient expression of emotions and neurologist reactions in consultation with patients with multiple sclerosis (Piccolo, Pietrolongo, Radice, Tortorella, Confalonieri, et al 2015; Others include the applications of theoretical constructions to patients communicative ability (Oyeleye and Sunday, 2013); neurologist interactions with their patients (Akinola, 2013), and also multi-dimensional indices in the interactional contexts of the interactants (Panasiuk, 2015; Messina, Costa, Rodegher, Moiola, Colombo, 2015). Most of the studies reviewed have been silent on the description of the models of communication or consultation. Among a few like Kanaan et al (2009) that mentioned a similar issue merely restricted it to the paternalistic model of consultation, while many others have different areas of focus.

Consequently, this study investigates communication models in neurologist-patient interaction in selected university teaching hospitals in the southwestern Nigeria. As earlier hinted, the aim is to examine the communication goals and patterns, discourse strategies, pragmatic acts, and contexts that shape the interaction.

2.3 Theoretical framework

Pragmatic acts theory is adopted as the framework for the study. In this section, issues relating to the theory of pragmatics alongside tenets of its sub-theories are discussed. This enhances the understanding of the main theory and distinguishes its application in context from other possible adaptation in academic investigations. Apart from these,

some of the sub-theories of pragmatics will be applied in the analysis of data for the study.

2.3.1 Pragmatics and the notion of *pragmeme*

The concept, “pragmatics” has generated a lot of controversies among scholars, especially those in the field of linguistics and humanities. Some scholars such as Kempson (1982), Leech (1983); Yule (1996) see it as not too different from Semantics. Others argue that there are distinct separations. For instance, Morris (1938) defines Pragmatics as “the study of the relation of signs to the interpreters, thus making a case for Semiotics as synonymous with Pragmatics. Leech and Short (1981), Blakemore (1982), Levinson (1983), Adegbija (1995), Mey (2001) among others perceive pragmatics as “concerned with the mental structure underlying the ability to interpret utterances in context”. The common ground among these scholars is that pragmatics studies meaning in line with speech situation.

Pragmatics is a subfield of linguistics which studies the ways in which context contributes to meaning. It encompasses speech acts theory, conversational implicature, talk in interaction and other approaches to language behaviour in philosophy, sociology, and linguistics (Mey 1994). It studies how the transmission of meaning depends not only on the linguistic knowledge (for example, grammar, lexicon and so on.) of the speaker and listener, but also on the context of the utterance, knowledge about the status of those involved, the inferred intent of the speaker, and so on.

Pragmatics explains how language users are able to overcome apparent ambiguity, since meaning relies on the manner, place, time et cetera. of an utterance (Mey 2001). This gives birth to the concept, “pragmatic acts”. According to Odebunmi (2011), “the pragmatic acts theory is a theory of context which considers the verbal behaviour of an individual within the affordances of the context”. The object of study of pragmatic theory is a situated pragmatic act and its generalised theoretical equivalent, which Mey (2001) calls a *pragmeme*. This is explicated in the model shown below:

Fig 2.1: Mey’s Pragmatic Acts model (Mey 2001:222)

From the schema above, it can be deduced that the activity part covers speech acts, indirect speech acts, conversational (“dialogue”) acts, psychological acts, prosodic acts and physical acts. On the other segment to the right is the textual part which caters for the context elements. These are INF which stands for “inference”; REF represents “reference”, REL, refers to “relevance”; VCE points to “voice”; while SSK and MPH imply “shared situation knowledge” and “metaphor” respectively. The M is for “metapragmatic joker”.

Many scholars acknowledge that meaning in discourse must not be approached through an analysis of speech acts alone but should incorporate nonverbal aspects of conversation as well as aspects of the situation (Mey 1991: 1994: 2001). Mey opines that in order to implement this desideratum in a pragmatic theory, one has to generalise and abstract from a situation to a situation type, and from speech acts to speech acts type, or, better, to a generalised pragmatic act. This theoretical construct of a generalised pragmatic act is known as *pragmeme* (Mey, 2001: 221). This has been illustrated in the diagram above.

In the application of pragmatic acts, all other acts most especially non-verbal acts (verbal acts inclusive) which cannot be accounted for are taken into cognisance in pragmatic acts. Mey (2001) says “pragmatic acts theory focuses on the environment in which both speaker and hearer find their affordances, such that the entire situation is brought to bear on what can be said in a given situation, as well as what is actually said”. Odeunmi

(2008) opines that a Pragmatic act is instantiated through an ipra or a pract, which realises a pragememe. In other words, this suggests that every allopract, ipra or pract altogether leads to the formation of a Pragememe. To Mey (2001), the *instantiated* pragmatic act is the “ipras”. According to Odebunmi (2008), “what determines a pract is solely participants' knowledge of the interactional situation and the potential effect of a pract in a particular context. Thus, practicing resolves the problem of telling illocutionary force from perlocutionary force”.

Owing to the fact that pragmatic acts are determined by use of language in context, and context being the core of meaning, this theoretical construct is therefore applied to analyse the data collected for this study.

2.3.1.1 Speech acts theory

The speech acts theory is considered a theory of pragmatics in line with Austin's (1962) proposition. John Austin is a renowned philosopher, who uses sociological reality to contribute to the study of language. His work *How to Do Things with Words* was earlier overshadowed by the impressive success of transformational grammar in the late 1950s and early 1960s. Austin's work was posthumously published and it draws scholars' attention to the fact that, behind every utterance made, there is an underlying action. This was further accepted and developed by John Searle (1969), an American philosopher and a former student of Austin in the 1950s. In the speech acts proposition, Austin observes that some expressions are made in form of wishes and not propositions that can be exposed to truth-functional (that is, testing of the falsity or truthfulness) but rather, they are words used to perform certain actions.

According to Austin, actions performed alongside utterances made are put into three levels of analysis, namely: locutionary act, illocutionary act and perlocutionary act. Locutionary act is described as an act of producing meaningful utterance or expression. Illocutionary act refers to the function that drives the utterance or the intention behind the locution while perlocutionary act refers to the effect of the locution on the hearer. In other words, Cutting (2002:16) says, “the act of saying something is known as locutionary act, what is done in uttering the words means illocutionary act and perlocutionary act refers to the effect on the hearer (which stimulates) hearer's reaction”.

To Austin, the performative is further distinguished from the constative verb which its falsity or truthfulness can be verified. For example, in the utterance, *it is raining outside*,

one can verify whether this is true or false by going outside and confirm the state of the weather. However, in performative, what matters are some acts which are to be carried out by word of mouth. In line with this, Cutting (2002:16) states that Austin had to later discard the performative hypothesis that behind every utterance there is a performative verb such as “to warn” “to ask” “to admit” “to promise” and so on. In its replacement, he came up with explicit and implicit performative which now indicate that the earlier ignored constative has been considered as a kind of speech acts (Palmer, 1976:138).

Austin uses general classification of speech acts such as verdictives, exercitives, commissives, behabitives and expositives because of the uncertainty regarding the total number of performative in any specific language. He speculates that there could be overlapping in his speech acts classification. In Odebunmi (2006:91), Austin explains that

verdictives relate to giving a verdict; exercitives involve exercising power/influence such as appointing, ordering, urging, etc. commissives relate to promising or announcing intention; behabitives have a link with attitude and social behaviour such as apologising, congratulating, condoling, cursing etc.

Objecting the classification, scholars such as Leech (1983), Levinson (1983), Thomas (1995) and Mey (2001) among others state that the above Austin’s classification is defective; all observe that English verbs do not correspond with this classification.

In reaction to the faulty classification, Searle (1969) modified Austin classification of the illocutionary acts and emerged with representatives, directives, commissives, expressive and declarations. Representative act refers to an utterance of a speaker which indicates the belief or disbelief of a speaker. It can be a statement of fact, claims, description, conclusion and so on.

Directives refer to an utterance of a speaker intending to make someone do something. It comes in forms of commands, invitations, requests, challenges, et cetera. Commissives refer to utterances speaker employ to commit themselves to future tasks such as promising, offering, threatening, refusing, pledging and so on. Expressives refer to utterances that reveal the psychological state of mind, attitudes and emotions of a speaker. They are used to thank, apologise, console congratulate, greet and so on.

Declarations refer to the utterances of a speaker that change world, create new things and events.

Searle (1969) reveals an innovation that there is a difference between direct and indirect speech acts. Direct speech acts refer to the use of utterance in a literal manner, such that words are made to retain their conventional meanings. In other words, it means a speech situation where there is a direct relationship between structure (form) and function. Indirect speech acts refer to the use of speaker's use of words whose utterance meaning is quite different from surface meaning, that is, one speech acts is done through another, establishing an indirect relationship between the forms and functions.

Cutting (2002:19) argues that indirect speech acts features in everyday living. Through this assumption, he sees classification of utterances in categories of indirect and direct speech acts as an arduous task because of the same levels both operate on. The difficulty also prevails because utterances often have more than one of the macro functions.

Searle (1969:57-61) says that speech acts are examined in relation to the three felicity conditions which are preparatory, sincerity and essential conditions. In furtherance of Searle's felicity conditions, Yule (1996) classifies felicity conditions into five namely: general condition which refers to the fact that the participants understand the language they use and that they do not just play-act; content condition, which implies that the act must be in line with the locution uttered. For example, the content of promise and warning must be aligned with act in the future; the preparatory condition is considered a basic because participants are aware of the outcome of the intended acts. For example, the promising act is beneficial but that of warning is not beneficial. The fourth is the sincerity condition which supposes that the speaker must be sincere to carry out the intended act; while the essential condition states that the speaker considers himself or herself under an obligation to carry out the act revealed in his or her utterances.

Odebunmi (2006:92) sees Searle proposition as categorised into four felicity conditions. These are the propositional content, preparatory conditions, sincerity conditions and essential conditions. Here, propositional conditions point to the features that determine the meaning of utterances. For instance, an utterance points forward when making a promise or request and backwards, when making an apology. Preparatory conditions call for a conventionally recognised context. For example, when an utterance of warning is

made, it is not certain that the event will happen to the hearer, but the speaker knows the event will happen and it will not be favourable. Sincerity conditions state that the speaker must be sincere in his or her declaration. For instance, a speaker acknowledges with a sincere apology that an offence has been committed but not just to offer an unapologetic apology. Essential conditions point to the conventions that are featured in doing things with words. For example, for a promise, an utterance must be conventionally regarded as a promise since it contains an act of promising and the hearer must be told about it so as to make him or her do something.

In the perspective of Allan (1986), speaking or writing as an act is premised on language. Being different from the speech acts classification of both Austin (1962) and Searle (1969), the scholar distinguishes interpersonal acts which subsume other acts such as constatives, predictive, commissives, acknowledgements, directives and authoritative, from declaratory acts which subsume effectives and verdictives. Although this classification is an improvement on Bach and Harnish (1979), who classify illocutionary acts into communicative acts thus subsuming constatives, directives, commissives and acknowledgements; and non-communicative acts which subsume effectives and verdictives as sub-categories. Leech (1983) categorises illocutionary acts into four, namely; competitive, convivial, collaborative and conflictive.

One major issue noted in the speech acts theory is the proper classifications of the illocutionary act among other issues. As a result, various scholars have used related and diverse taxonomies. Beyond this, it is not an absolutely appealing linguistic analytical tool to some scholars because it deals with a fragment of spoken language. What happens to language when not verbally expressed? What about language in specific contexts? For example, Strawson (1971:48), in reaction to the speech acts theory, observes that Austin's speech acts was a wrong explanation of how language works. He says that christening and marrying, for example, take place at highly ritualistic and ceremonial settings/situations with rules that define their performance. As a result, what one says in such situations is part of formalised proceedings rather than example of common communicative behaviour. Therefore, it will be wrong to use them as typical of how language works in real life, everyday situations. Strawson rather argues in favour of Gricean intention theory because some commonplace speech acts such as accomplished by declarative sentences succeeded by arousing in the addressee the awareness of the speaker's intention to achieve a particular goal.

In the views of Lawal (2012:153), it is believed that at every stage of discourse, the speaker(s) and the hearer(s) require the acquisition of needed aspects of the pragmatic, social, syntactic, semantic and lexical competencies for the effective participation of the interactants. This is lacking in speech acts as the pragmatics of situation is relegated to the background.

2.3.1.2 Conversational act

It is widely known that in 1962, Austin developed through the course of his lectures, the concept of speech acts. This highly generalised and abstract concept became more articulated and concrete in the able hands of another philosopher, John Searle (1969). Searle extracted the essential features of the concept, developed a taxonomy of types, and articulated the theory necessary to construct a conceptual model. At the centre of his model is a speech utterance, which Searle refers to as a *locution* and so on

There have been many reactions to Austin's speech acts. One of such which actually led to another concept is that of Dore's (1979) classification scheme. What Dore did was to take the concept of speech acts and apply it to actual utterances of interpersonal speech. Dore invented the name "conversational acts", or "c-acts" to distinguish the applied version of speech acts from the conceptual one.

He devised a procedure for analysing children's speech utterances that enable a researcher to identify the basic speech acts being performed. Notice that there are several basic categories of conversational acts: assertions, requests, expressions, and responses. These are the basic acts that everyone performs when they speak. For instance, one can either *tell* someone about something, *ask* someone about something, *emote* to someone about something, or *respond* to someone about something. And one can do all of these things with just one utterance—if one is strategic about it. The status of the category "performatives" is still being debated, but Dore (1979) included these particular acts because the children in his experiment performed them. Performatives are acts that one accomplishes simply by saying the right words. "Regulatives" are acts that are useful for keeping conversations flowing smoothly.

One other noteworthy property of this classification scheme is the tight relation between some of the request types and their corresponding response types. In order to respond appropriately in a conversation, a developing child is faced with the difficult task of trying to comprehend the implicit rules of dialogue. With regard to the relationship

between one utterance and another in conversation, nowhere is that relationship manifested more clearly than in the relationship between a question and an answer. For that reason, question-answer exchanges may be just the type that children need to grasp the logic of dialogue. Dore (1979) introduces the category of “Responses” into the classification system because it is a meaningful category if one studies speech acts in real-life conversation. Neither Austin (1962) nor Searle (1969) noticed the need for this category when speech acts were still at a conceptual stage.

Furthermore, in Dore’s conversational acts, certain procedures for identifying basic conversational acts are devised for analysing children’s speech that enables a researcher to identify the basic speech acts being performed. The analysis is applied to one utterance at a time. The first step begins by determining the literal semantic meaning of the words contained in the utterance, which the philosopher of language Jerrold Katz (1972) articulated in grammatical terms. He described the semantic meaning of a sentence as a logical proposition, composed of a logical subject, a predicate, and modifying phrases. Not all turns at talk are complete sentences or even complete phrases, but for those utterances that do take the form of a sentence, this is certainly the first step. This part of the analysis answers the superficial question: What did the other person just say? Now it is time to ask the deeper question: What did the other person mean by saying that?

This is followed by step two which is one of the attempts of looking for clues about the speaker’s communicative intentions, in other words, their communicative act. The particular way that grammar is used or the vocal emphasis that the speaker places on a particular clause or word can be evidence of sarcasm, for example, thus signalling a joke has been made.

In the third step, the analysis moves on to *novel* information, that is, anything *new* that has been introduced either into the conversation or the ongoing activity. The pioneering work of Halliday (1970) revealed the importance of novel information in maintaining joint attention among participants in a conversation. As novelty flows, so flows the topic of attention. The task in step four is to ask the analyst to examine what the speaker has been saying and doing over the past few turns. That information could be relevant to determining the speaker’s communicative intentions. Step five looks at the interaction. Both the speech and the actions of the participants in relation to one another provide

clues that could enable a researcher, or a listener, to recognise one or more of the basic conversational acts.

Finally, in step six, the analysis shifts to the physical and social and cultural properties of the situation that might have a bearing on the interpretation of the utterance. Here, one would want to consult the numerous communicative channels that speakers conventionally use to convey speech acts: intonational stress on particular words, emotional tone, vocal timbre and volume, choice of words and syntax, as well as the relationship of the utterance to the conversational topic, to ongoing activity, the social situational, the physical circumstances, even the participants' awareness of one another's knowledge. Lewis (1972) described in detail the sorts of contextual features that could influence the interpretation of an utterance. Garvey (1975) did much of the groundbreaking work to establish an understanding of these relations.

2.3.1.3 Theory of relevance

The theory of relevance is important to the understanding of pragmatic related studies. The theory proposed by Sperber and Wilson (1986) is a notable phenomenon among various reactions to Gricean maxims of cooperation. Sperber and Wilson argue that there can be a reduction of all of the maxims of cooperative to just one. This is referred to as the maxim of relation or the theory of relevance. The scholars opine that relevance is natural in any speech situation that is meant to be successful. In relevance postulation, it is expected that the interactant must "give the right amount of relevant information" (as stated by the maxim of quantity), give sincere relevant information (maxim of quality), and give unambiguous relevant information (maxim of manner). All these are categorised as the theory of relevance.

Sperber and Wilson (1993) later came up with the concept of explicature which has a two-stage process to further expand the Gricean idea of conversational implicature. The two-stage process that explicature refers "to inferences a hearer first recovers which enrich underdetermined form of a speech, to a full propositional form". This is afterwards followed by "implicature, which is an inference that gives the hearer the most relevant interpretation of an utterance".

In the theory of relevance, it is believed that no expression is ambiguous if it is supported by the appropriate context. Cruse (2000:370) also notes that "normal language is full of potential ambiguities, but these are only rarely noticed because they are disambiguated

by context. This disambiguation process is relevance driven”. Nevertheless, relevance theory is not without its criticisms from scholars. Mey (1994:3268) opines that, since relevance theory claims to have subsumed the four conversational maxims of Grice, it becomes too superfluous, hence, the theory loses its explanatory force. Cutting (2002) observes that some scholars argued that the general indeterminacy of a language is not accounted for by relevance theory. Moreover, relevance theory cannot be validated across cross-cultural linguistic applications. In the theory, questions on socio-variable factors are muted because many people from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds have their various ways of exhibiting cooperative tendencies in any speech exchange or service encounter.

2.3.1.4 Politeness theory

The theory of politeness is an important theory to the study of pragmatics. It is one of the core bases of pragmatic as a linguistic discipline. Politeness theory is strictly context driven and highly influenced by culture. It shares a relationship with sociolinguistics, that is, it is in accordance with societal norms, customs and values. The concept, “politeness” is subject to many definitions. Nevertheless, it can be said to mean the exhibition of good manners and etiquette. Politeness is an act of behaving in a socially acceptable manner (Myers, 1989).

Adegbite (2000) construes politeness principles as similar to cooperative principles, in that, politeness principles, as well as the cooperative, is developed as a matrix of maxims which interlocutors observe in the assumption they hold for one another. Just like cooperative principle, any flouting on politeness maxim has an influence on the meaning, should it be perceived for what it is. However, the politeness and cooperative principles are in contrasts. According to Lakoff (1973), politeness principles is enumerated as follows:

- a) Do not impose
- b) Give option
- c) Make your receiver feel good

In consonance with the principles stated above, they are said to be the reasons for utterances where orders, requests and pleas are made in form of elaborate questions. for example

I am sorry to have sent you. (apology for imposing)

Would you mind doing this work? (request that gives option of refusal)

Going further, Lakoff opines that politeness can be studied using two approaches, namely: first order politeness and second-order politeness.

The first order politeness is conceived using the socio-cultural background of a group (Lakoff, 1973). To buttress Lakoff assumptions, one can exemplify the instance from Nigeria where an expression that is considered polite in Yoruba socio-cultural group may be considered otherwise in other ethnic groups. As a result, one can deduce that the Hausa ethnic group, for example, make use of diseuphemism because they do aim toward directness in describing things whereas the Yoruba aim towards the euphemistic use of language. In Yoruba, a leper or blind may not be directly referred to as a leper or blind because of the belief that it may sound offensive; and that, it is not appropriate to describe a disabled person by his or her true nature, rather a disable is described as a special person known as *akanda eniyan*. However, Hausa ethnic describe disable person exactly the way he or she is without taking any offence. Such names include *mekuturu*. Lakoff's (1973) first-order politeness can, therefore, be classified into expressive, classificatory and metapragmatic. Expressive politeness manifests in a speaker's polite intention and it may be expressed with some terms of address, honorifics, conventional formulaic expressions, linguistic chunks and devices. Some devices can be used to express politeness in mitigating the direct illocutionary effect of a request and also to reduce the negative effect of a refusal response. For instance, "I'm sorry, I may not be there". "I'm sorry, I may not be able to do that". "Please, can you come over here"

Classificatory first order politeness is referred to as a categorical tool. It deals with how to categorise the speaker's politeness or impoliteness and this classification is done through hearer's judgment. In any natural environment, hearers tend to judge the speakers to be polite or impolite. For example, in the Yoruba ethics, it is insulting to interrupt the elders when they are talking. A hearer may respond by saying, "I thought you would listen first and then give your opinion" or "it is uncalled for". This is immediate context dependent.

Metapragmatic first order politeness is closely related to classificatory first order politeness but they are not same. Politeness becomes an ideological concept of the

society. Metapragmatic politeness refers to how people talk about politeness in everyday interaction and what people perceive politeness to be in different practices of interactions. This could be determined based on some criteria such as age, educational status, sex, economic status and so on.

Second order politeness is conceived using scientific theory-driven construct and it is end-product of researches that reveal the universal principles governing human interactions. Second order politeness projects how first-order politeness works or functions in social interactions. It establishes universal notions that there are certain principles peculiar to people when interacting. As a result of these principles, one is able to distinguish between impoliteness and politeness in the various communicative transactions.

Leech (1983) premises his theory of politeness on interpersonal rhetoric and conflict avoidance. To further clarify his view on politeness, Leech introduces maxims of tact, generosity, approbation, modesty, agreement and sympathy. Brown and Levinson (1978; 1987) propose a universal model of linguistic politeness and claim that politeness is realised linguistically by means of various strategies (that is positive and negative) across cultures. Their model is a bit controversial because it is difficult to achieve as a result of differences in cultures. Brown and Levinson's model states that face invested, could be lost and regained. One of the weak points of this model is that it lumps face and politeness together.

Fraser and Nolan (1981) view politeness from a different perspective. This is later elaborated in Fraser (2005). In this, politeness is considered a notion of conversational contract in which there is room for readjustment or renegotiation of rights and obligations parties hold towards one another especially when interlocutors discover their new status. He further establishes the fact that discovery of individuals' new status brings about social equilibrium.

Lakoff (1987) sees politeness as a system of interpersonal relations designed to facilitate interaction by minimising the potentials for conflict and confrontation inherent in all human interchange. For instance, *Please, could you leave this place.* Arundale (1999) describes politeness as being interactionally co-constituted and co-maintained. This model identifies face threat, support and stasis.

2.3.1.5 Context and shared knowledge

The interpretation of linguistic items in verbal and non-verbal communication has generated a lot of interests in language studies. In pragmatics, context is the main determinant of any linguistic interpretation. According to Mey (2001:13), context is “invoked to determine what an ambiguous sentence mean”. He further asserted that by context, “we understand all the factors that play a role in producing and understanding utterances”. The term, context, is a major distinction between pragmatics and other linguistic disciplines such as semantics and semiotics. In the line of this, an exploration of context is attempted so as to enhance the understanding of the textual analysis in subsequent parts of this study.

El Rincón del Vago (1998) perceives context to be of three kinds namely linguistic, situational and sociocultural. The first consists of the linguistic material which precedes and follows a statement. Within this confinement, the linguistic context is also regarded as the co-texts. The situational context is said to contain the information about the immediate physical material surrounding the situation. The third, which is the sociocultural context, is the configuration of the data taken from social and cultural influence on verbal behaviour and its uses according to different circumstances. For example, there are social rules to greet or rules in order to know which linguistic register use in a particular situation. He posits further that “frames” are the structure containing the whole communicative system. They are one of the most interesting aspects of the sociocultural context. These, he identifies to be very important in relation to pragmatics “because statements are always interpreted within a meta-communicative frame which qualifies the situation of the communicative act and the participants”. These frames provide the data necessary for us to communicate. This information can be stereotyped structures of situations or concepts which allow us to associate some meanings with other meanings. For example, if someone says “library”, we will automatically think in a context in which there are books, shelves, librarians, and so on.

In situations of ritualised speaking like greetings, the sentences truth value is not so important because they are highly context-dependent. Therefore, we say what we want to say on every occasion. However, we also say what we are expected to say since our linguistic behaviour is codified by social rules. According to El Rincón del Vago, these codifications belong to the context because they determine the meaning of the statements. It is in this that context is conceived as the collection of knowledge and

beliefs shared by the participants in a verbal communication (El Rincón del Vago, 1998). Although this definition of context by El Rincón del Vago appears deficient, in the sense that, it does not consider context to include non-verbal variables in communication. This is because, the collection of knowledge, culture and shared beliefs are relevant to producing and interpreting correctly the linguistic items expressed in specific communicative situations.

Odebunmi (2006:25) opines that context is the spine of meaning. This implies that context is central to meaning. Odebunmi argues that the full meanings of words are best realised in context as against the arguments from other scholars (like Palmer, 1976) that context is excluded from meaning. In line with this, two types of contexts – linguistic and social contexts were identified. Linguistic context refers to the relationship that exists among a word with other words. This relationship thus serves as a way through which a word is associated with others in order to arrive at the meaning of what is communicated. The consideration of these other words in determining meanings is regarded as the co-texts. The second type, social context is borne out of the assumption that meaning often goes beyond the linguistic environment of a word (Odebunmi, 2006:39). This gives credence to the consideration of other factors in determining the meaning of a given expression or communicative situation. As a result of this, aspects such as the social, culture, religious and history are important variables from the standpoint of Odebunmi (2006). He reiterates that meaning can best be accounted for through contextual consideration. This aligns with Mey (2001:41) who says “context is more than just reference. Context is action. Context is about understanding what things are for; it is also what gives our utterances their true pragmatic meaning and allows them to be counted as true pragmatic acts”. Context is therefore not only vital to assigning proper values to reference but in dealing with other pragmatic issues.

Fromkin, Rodman and Hyams (2011) admit that pragmatics is concerned with our understanding of language in context. To them, context is construed from two angles. The first is called “linguistic context” while “situational context” is the second. They explain that *linguistic context* represents the “discourse that precedes the phrase or sentence to be interpreted”. To these scholars, virtually everything non-linguistic in the environment of the speaker is the *situational context*.

Odebunmi (2016) expands his earlier views on context. Here, context is considered “the confluence of language and society”. That is, context is that point at which individuals find their affordances. In addition, the scholar makes a distinction between “semantic minimalism and contextualism”. Contextualism “hinges the truth conditions of a sentence on its context”. On the other hand, semantic minimalism is assumed to be understandable without the contextual associations. From these two perspectives, context is defined as “the condition that constrains the determination of the propositions of an utterance or the understanding of an event or discourse” (Odebunmi 2016:13). It is also considered as the linguistic and extra-linguistic clues that aid the interpretation of a written or spoken discourse. It is the environment in which language is used.

Moreover, the concept of context is examined from the categorisation into two, broad and narrow. The broad concept of context, regarded context as a macro concept (Odebunmi, 2016:14-18) are examined. Four types of context in this category have been identified namely, the cognitive/psychological context, linguistic context, situational/physical context, and social context.

The cognitive, which can also be regarded the psychological context has to do with giving attention to the state of mind of the participants in a discussion. The lexical and sentential choices of a communicative participant can convey various emotions such as anxiety, desperation, exasperation, excitement, grief, joy, among others.

“The linguistic context is by function” (Odebunmi, 2016:14). This basis for the linguistic context has to do with the interrelatedness of text, or co-texts. In other words, it implies the association that a word enters into with other words. In understanding a given text, one needs to consider the other words that make up that sentence or statement for a proper and accurate understanding.

The situational context which can also be called the physical context has to do with the location where language is used. This implies that what a group of the word said in a particular place will connote a different understanding when it is said in another place. For example, a man tells a woman, let me “rig” myself into your life! If this is said by a politician to a group of people, the reaction will be different. The following examples extracted from Ogunsiji (2016) buttress this:

(a) A Chemistry lecturer asked his wife at home: “Why did you put too much SODIUM CHLORIDE in this soup?”

(b) A Chemistry student told his father at home: “There is no H₂O IN THE STOREX.”

As much as the expressions above are correct, having found themselves in some rather strange contexts, the instantaneous understanding can become problematic to the communicative participants in the situation. It is, therefore, deducible that the meaning which a particular expression will give is determined by the place where the expression is used. Aspects of the physical context will include the persons involved in a conversation, the location and the objects around the location. Language, therefore, only realises its actual meaning when consideration is made with reference to where or in what occasion such is deployed.

Social context refers to the constraints imposed on meaning and understanding of events by communicative encounters (2016:16). This implies that the social context prioritises the communicative participants, their physical locations and verbal and non-verbal actions. In the line of these, importance is placed on the values, beliefs and culture of a society where a specific language or communicative context is being utilised. The word “I have dropped you a tip” would connote different ideas based on the social situation that it is said. In a specific one, for example, part of Europe or the United States, when said to a waiter, it is a voluntary gift given by the customers to the waiter so as to augment the daily earnings of that waiter or to express appreciation voluntarily for the services rendered. However, the same expression, when said to a police officer in Nigeria, for example, it may lead to further questioning of the speaker by the addressee.

The identification of context and its different types as expounded by various scholars provides access to the understanding of the specific types of context employed in neurologist-patient interaction, which is one of the objectives of this study. Therefore, how specific context types shaped the interactions between the interactants is revealed in the analysis of data in the study.

2.4 Conceptual frameworks of the study

In academic research, the term “conceptual framework” can be confusing and has many times been misused. Scholars have attempted to clarify the difference between this term and theoretical framework. Gavin (2016) offers an insight into the idea of conceptual

framework citing other scholars. He begins by approaching the term from the root of the word “concept”. He says “concepts are abstract ideas that arise out of perception and experience and are used to label phenomenon, events, or processes”. He opines that concepts are used to generalise from particulars to create the abstract idea. To him, it is believed that a conceptual framework is a system of concepts, assumptions, expectations and beliefs in which graphics or propositions link broad abstract ideas or models as a way to guide a research study. Often a conceptual framework emerges from the literature review, as the researcher links the literature to real-world experiences or events to shape future thoughts or practices in the research study.

To Ravitch and Riggan (2012:6-7), a conceptual framework pulls together the entire research process... Miles and Huberman (1994:1-2) defined a conceptual framework as a visual or written product, one that “explains, either graphically or in narrative form, the main things to be studied—the key factors, concepts, or variables - and the presumed relationships among them” (p. 18). Gavin and other scholars (Maxwel, 2013; Robson, 2011; Babbie, 2007), agree, that the conceptual framework, offers researchers the opportunity to explain the importance of the research in terms of what has been studied before as well as proffers a reason as to why the topic needs to be extended in the manner as outlined by the researcher. Within these assumptions, Emanuel and Emanuel models of doctor-patient relationship (EDPR) is mainly selected as the major conceptual framework for the study. Based on the significance of the data and subjects involved in the study, pragmatic communicative principle (PCP) according to Mey (2001:68) is also put into consideration so as to fully understand how neurologist-patient interaction is approached in the study. These are expounded in the subsequent sections.

2.4.1 Pragmatic communicative principles (PCP)

There are many principles in linguistics and other academic disciplines. Principle, in itself, is that basic notion, perception or generalisation that guides conducts. To Mey (2001:68-71), communicative principle seeks at ensuring that “people engage in communicative activity whenever they use language; whether or not they observe a particular syntactic rule is not too important). In other words, grammaticality is deemphasised rather, the goal of every communicative endeavour is the ability of the interactants. For example, Mey, using various illustrations avers that communicative principle is “the hidden condition for all human pragmatic activities” and that what individual does communicate depends on what he/she “can communicate, given (the

person's) circumstances, and on what (such person) must communicate, given (the communicative partner's) expectations (2001:70). To the proponent of this principle, the communicative principle has the capability of unveiling utterances. And so, "unlike a grammatical rule, (it) operates in a concrete context, rather than in the abstract space of linguistic speculation".

Since the emphasis of PCP is on the context, it is not suitable for studies in which the focus is on grammaticality and other syntactic exigencies. However, it favours any discourse regarding language in use at a particular time, space and situation where communicative expectations are mutual by partners involved in the communication. Such aspect where the PCP is relevant include discourses involving peers, husband and wife, superior and subordinate (in a corporate environment), teachers and students, students to students, lawyers and judges, lawyers and accused, doctors and patients, and many others.

2.4.2 Emanuel and Emanuel's models of doctor-patient relationship (EDPR)

Model is a hypothetical description of a complex entity or process (WordWeb Dictionary, 2006). Due to this hypothetical nature, it is subject to questioning and further questioning. In doctor-patient interaction, doctor-patient relationship or doctor-client relationship among other existing terms; there are many models that have been employed to describe what happens when doctors meet their patients. Emanuel and Emanuel model, which is adopted for the study is presented in the Table below and explored.

Table 2.1: Four Models of the Physician-Patient Relationship

	Informative	Interpretive	Deliberative	Paternalistic
Patient values	Defined, fixed, and known to the patient	Inchoate and conflicting, requiring elucidation	Open to development and revision through moral discussion	Objective and shared by physician and patient
Physician's obligation	Providing relevant factual information and implementing patient's selected	Elucidating and interpreting relevant patient values as well as informing the patient and	Articulating and persuading the patient of the most admirable values as well	Promoting the patient's well-being independent of the patient's current

	intervention	implementing the patient's selected intervention	as informing the patient and implementing the patient's selected intervention	preferences
Conception of patient's autonomy	Choice of, and control over, medical care	Self-understanding relevant to medical care	Moral self-development relevant to medical care	Assenting to objective values
Conception of physician's role	Competent technical expert	Counsellor or adviser	Friend or teacher	Guardian

Source: Emanuel and Emanuel (1992)

Before exploring the model adopted for the study, an examination of other models that were not initially captured in chapter one is attempted. A review by Oprea (2009:125-135) offers some insights. These models according to Oprea, help “to understand the relationship between the empirical evidence on the effectiveness of hospital interactions... .” Some of them, within doctor-patient relationship, are described as consumerist, paternalist, and/or consequentialist. Others are essentialist, contractual, covenant, and relational. These are described as prescriptive in nature, (Oprea, 2009), among which is the Emanuel and Emanuel’s model of doctor-patient relationship (EDPR). EDPR is a critique of other existing and earlier models. Also, the proponents of this model try to recommend one of the four postulations as “the ideal” model for “physician-patient relationship”. In the discussion of the model, Emanuel and Emanuel emphasise the different understandings of “the goals of the physician-patient interaction, the physician’s obligations, the role of patient values, and the conception of patient autonomy” (see Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992:6). The EDPR model namely: the paternalistic model, informative model, interpretive model, and deliberative model are explored as follow.

2.4.2.1 The paternalistic model

This model was not the original idea of Emanuel and Emanuel. The authors refer to it among other two (informative and interpretive) as “Weberjan ideal types” (1992:5). The paternalistic model is also referred as “parental or priestly”. The ideology behind this is

that the relationship between doctor and their patients is to ensure that “patients receive the interventions that best promote their health and well-being”. In this, the physician acts as the guardian of the patients who helps to articulate and implement what is best for them. In this, there is the assumption that there are shared objective criteria for determining what is best. This objective drives the physician to play the omniscient role by discerning what is in the best interest with limited patient’s participation. In this case, it is expected that the patient will be grateful or thankful for decisions taken by the physician “even if he or she would not agree to them at the time”, (Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992:32).

This model is similar to Szasz and Hollender activity-passivity model of doctor-patient’s relationship, in that, the responsibility in doctor-patient interaction is placed on the doctors to execute medical interventions and patients are passive recipients of health care (see Oprea, 2009). The critics of the paternalistic model argue that the model is only suitable for medical emergencies where patients are unconscious lacking their capacity for decision-making. The other model categorised as paternalistic by Oprea (2009:126) is the guidance-cooperation, which presupposes that “the doctor will tell the patient what to do and patients will (simply) comply or obey”. This again is restricted to the acute medical situation with a clear medical cure. Although it is agreed that both patient and doctors are active, and contribute to the healthcare decisions in this model. The fact that the model assumes “doctors are experts and they can determine in an objective way the best interests of their patients” is faulted. This is because scholars assume that it is insufficient to merely rely on the patient’s inability in the medical situation as the “patients’ assent to doctor’s health care decisions”. In the opposing angle, proponents of paternalistic model justify the increased responsibility for healthcare decisions on doctors and a decrease responsibility on patients’ part, because “the conception of patient autonomy is patient assent, either at the time or later, to the physician’s determination of what is best” (Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992:5).

2.4.2.2 The informative model

This model is also known as the scientific, engineering or consumer model (Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992:6). Oprea (2009:127) recognises it as consumer model. The target in the utilisation of this model is to inform or, as Oprea puts it, “to give patients an absolute control and responsibility over health care decisions”. This model reduces the responsibilities of doctors to “providing factual information about medical

interventions”. Having been provided with the information, patients have the right to choose the intervention that suits best their values and interests. This is corroborated by Emanuel and Emanuel as they explain that the objective of this model is patient’s autonomy. The physician is expected to avail the patient “all relevant information, for the patient to select the medical interventions he or she wants, and for the physician to execute the selected interventions”. Some of the information expected to be divulged include the state of the patient’s health, nature of possible diagnostic and therapeutic intervention, the nature and probability of risks and benefits associated with the interventions, and any other uncertainties.

In all, the proponents agree that “patients could come to know all medical information relevant to their disease and available interventions” so as to “select the interventions that best realise their values. However, Oprea, adding his voice to the criticism of the informative model as a departure from the societal expectations of doctor roles in the interactions with their patient, opines that the model “reduces doctors’ roles to technical ones, such as plumbers or car mechanics that pursue technical tasks”. Further, he argues that the informative model prohibits doctors from giving recommendations, as this would impose their values on patients. Apart from this, the model is also criticised for “lacking caring approach”, an expectation of the society on anyone with the medical doctor’s tag. Even at that, one of the slogans associated with medical practitioner “we care, but God heals”, has been deemphasised by this model.

Scholars in favour of the informative model have however argued that the physician is

a purveyor of technical expertise, providing the patient with the means to exercise control”. As technical experts, physicians have important obligation to provide truthful information, to maintain competence in their area of expertise, and to consult others when their knowledge or skills are lacking. The conception of patient autonomy is patient control over medical decision-making.

(Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992:6)

The critique of the model disagreed to the submission above. Rather, they maintained that the model is a departure from the societal ideal, where doctors understand patients’ values and how patients’ illnesses impinge on their values and tailor their therapeutic recommendations based on knowledge. Although an informative doctor will provide

patients with information about the psychological aspects of their illnesses, a pure technical doctor lacks a compassionate approach. (Oprea, 2009).

In the identifiable characteristics of a doctor by many societies, compassionate and a caring attitude are “integral part of the diagnostic and therapeutic relationship and of the healing process” (2009:128). Oprea posits further that when there is a lack of rational deliberation between patients and their doctor, the tendency of having a “decreased autonomy” is high, “because people make meaning through interaction with each other”. Therefore, the interpretation of what is said, meant and the implication might be misapplied or abused outright. The argument for or against this and other earlier models has lent credence to the question of whether the doctor-patient relationship should be guided either by the ethical principle of beneficence or by broader societal ethical norms (Oprea, 2009:128), and has given reasons for the formulation of other models.

2.4.2.3 The interpretive model

This is the third among the four models of doctor-patient relationship. The idea being championed by this model is that “the aim of the physician-patient interaction is to elucidate the patient’s values and what he or she actually wants, and to help the patients select the available medical interventions that realise these values” (Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992:6). This model has been enhanced by Pellegrino (1979:23). He argues that “a doctor-patient relationship informed by ethical principle of beneficence can avoid paternalism. The healing goal of medicine determines the duties and virtues of medicine”. This scholar frowns at the consideration of societal traditions, customs, expectations, or acceptance as the basis of internal morality of medicine. Rather, he avers that morality of medicine comes from the healing end of medicine. He asserts that since medicine is a practice and not theory, the morality of the ideal doctor-patient relationship should stem out of the three facets of healing relationship, the act of profession and the right and good healing action for a particular patient.

Emanuel and Emanuel liken the interpretive model to the informative model. They said, “like the informative model, the interpretive physician provides the patient with information on the nature of the condition and the risks and benefits of possible interventions”. The role of a doctor, however, goes beyond the provision of information. The doctor, in this model, is expected to “assist the patient in elucidating and articulating his or her values and in determining what medical interventions best realise the specified

values, thus helping to interpret the patient's values for the patient". Oprea (2009) corroborates this "doctors have to understand patients' values and views, inform the patient with respect to therapeutic approaches and then make sure patients understand healthcare decisions and ultimately, they have to respect patients' values". Again, the emphasis is on patient's value. This to Pellegrino (2006:610), is explained as the role expected of a doctor. He affirms that a compassionate doctor-patient relationship is one that is

instrumental for patients' healthy behaviour via a better understanding on patients' parts of the meaning of health care intervention. Compassion is not empathy or a good bedside manner, but a moral quality enabling the doctor to interpret the meaning of illness through "suffering along with the patient" that will enable the doctor to take a good morally defensible clinical decision which is in accordance with patients' age, aspiration, and clinical situation. (Oprea, 2009:129)

In the interpretive model, therefore, the doctor is perceived as a "counsellor, analogous to a cabinet minister's advisory role to a head of state". The doctor is therefore saddled with the responsibility of "supplying relevant information, helping to elucidate values and suggesting what medical interventions realise these values. Unlike the informative model, the interpretive model requires the physician to engage "the patient in a joint process of understanding". Emanuel and Emanuel aver that the conception of patient autonomy in the interpretive model is "self-understanding; the patient comes to know more clearly who he or she is and how the various medical options bear on his or her identity.

The interpretive model of doctor-patient relationship has also been criticised. The viability of this model to all manner of patients is a serious question left unanswered by the proponents. Many scholars have criticised the model for its restrictive nature, and also for failing to explain the actual clinical reality. Oprea (2009:129) argues that there is a discrepancy with the realities of medical practice which has many other goals besides healing. He made allusion to the fact that there is an international consensus which accepts that besides healing, medicine has many other goals such as the prevention of disease and injury and promotion and maintenance of health, the relief of pain and suffering caused by maladies, the care of those with maladies which cannot be cured, and the avoidance of premature death.

Oprea questions further why the principle of beneficence in medicine should be restricted to only the healing role of medicine, while it is of many other beneficial “effects in individual patients”. He gives other instances to support his points. He claims that “many patients with chronic diseases live normal lives and their decision-making capacity is not altered by the state of sickness”, hence interpretive model of doctor-patient relationship “leads to an emphasis on doctor’s education and training, and can result in an unbalanced situation where doctor’s points of view on what the relationship should be were taken to override patients’ point of view. In summary, this model is capable of misleading the patient as the content of the interpretation is susceptible to being misconstrued, and when this happens, the question of who to blame becomes a challenge because the expertise of interpreting lies with the doctor and the comprehension of the required and adequate intervention behoves on the patient. In resolving this kind of scenario, the deliberative model is explored in the next section.

2.4.2.3 The deliberative model

Emanuel and Emanuel postulate that the most suitable model for the doctor-patient relationship is the deliberative model. This model, according to them, caters for the pitfalls of other models namely: paternalistic, informative and interpretive. The goal of this model is to assist the patient in determining and choosing the health-related values that can be realised in a clinical situation. In doing this, the objective of the physician includes “suggesting why certain health-related values are worthier and should be aspired to”. Regarding the practice expected in the utilisation of this model, doctors in the interaction act as teachers or friends engaging the patient in dialogue on what course of action would be best. The doctor does not only indicate what the patient could do but knowing the patient and wishing what is best, he/she indicates what the patient should do. According to Oprea, doctors using this approach is capable of providing patients with all relevant information regarding the available therapeutic options; help patients elucidate the values embodied in health interventions at hand; and suggest why certain health-related values are worthier and should be aspired to.

Unlike the informative and interpretive models, the aim of the doctor does not exceed persuading the patient with respect to what the health care intervention they should receive. And the patients, on the other hand, decide what they deemed valuable health care choice and then select the most preferred. To Emanuel and Emanuel, the

deliberative model advances “the moral self-development” which is a conception of patients’ autonomy upon which this model relies. In their actual words, they explain that

The conception of patient autonomy is moral self-development; the patient is empowered not simply to follow unexamined preferences or examined values, but to consider, through dialogue, alternative health-related values, their worthiness, and their implications for treatment. (1992:7)

As much as the deliberative model appear the “most suitable”, some objections were made in reaction to its suitability for all cases of the doctor-patient relationship. One of such is raised by Emmanuel. The fundamental objections to the model are centred on the question whether it is proper for physicians to judge patients’ values and promote particular health-related. They assume that physicians do not possess privileged knowledge of the priority of health-related values that are relative to other values. And that due to the “pluralistic” nature of the society in which “people espouse incommensurable values”, it is then likely that a physician’s values and views of which values are higher will conflict with those of other physician and those of his or her patients. Oprea says the model is capable of negating the right values because it could serve as a “vehicle for promoting the values of particular doctors”. Emmanuel say that the deliberative model misconstrues the purpose of the physician-patient interaction in that patients see their physician to receive care, not to engage in moral deliberation or to revise their values. The model, as Emmanuel warn, may easily metamorphose into unintended paternalism which is the main topic that steers the debates over proper physician-patient interaction.

Finally, an emphasis on the relationship between doctors and patients that moves from technicians as in the informative models towards advisor or friend makes doctors acquire more power in the relationship (Oprea, 2009:132). When there is so much power, it could be easily abused. Brody (1997:33) tries to downplay this power-abuse suspicion, he asserts that rather than deprive people of relationship that they may find helpful and supportive, they should watch carefully in various ways and circumstances in which doctors might be disengaged in power abuse, at a system level, so as to prevent possibility of such abuse.

In conclusion, since clinical circumstances in hospitals are different, different communication models are possible. This perception is supported by Emanuel and

Emanuel. They also allude to the fact that in different circumstances, different models may be appropriate and that at different times, all four models may justifiably guide physician and patients. However, Oprea (2009) argues that bioethics models of doctor-patient interaction are mainly prescriptive and normative being derived from ethical and social theories. He believes that the processes through which different models might reach their goals are not assessed empirically. He, therefore, questions their effectiveness at the level of care.

Notwithstanding, the linguistic exploration of these models, based on context, the heart of pragmatics, is invaluable towards validating the claim by Oprea or otherwise. It thus makes an investigation into communication model of neurologist-patient interaction a worthy academic enterprise. The understanding of the ideas of these models, as discussed earlier, will help to recognise how these models are interwoven and the pragmatic choices employed or deployed in the interactions, and how the adopted models helped in shaping communication between participants.

2.5 Doctor-patient communication

Communication is key to every human existence, even animals communicate. Language is, however, an exclusive gift that distinguishes humans from other vertebrates. Communication between two people is an outgrowth of methods developed over centuries of expression. Gestures, the development of language, and the necessity to engage in joint action all played a part (Lievrouw, 2009). The concept, “communication” has been perceived from varying angles. Irrespective of these many perceptions, the notion of communication as a “process” is agreed as an important word in describing the concept. Communication can thus be defined as the process of sharing ideas, information, and messages with others in a particular time and place. It is also conceived as the process of transmitting information and common understanding from one person to another (Lunenburg, 2010:1). Some linguists see it as the process of conveying intended meaning to another entity through the use of mutually understood signs and semiotic rules. Another important factor to note in describing communication is that it is the process of human beings responding to the symbolic behaviour of other persons.

According to Fong Ha and Longnecker (2010:1), “much patient dissatisfaction and many complaints are due to breakdown in the doctor-patient communication”. To them, effective doctor-patient communication is “a central clinical function in building a

therapeutic doctor-patient relationship”. It is in fact regarded as the heart and art of medicine. Interpersonal skills through communication involve the doctors’ ability to gather information, so as to facilitate accurate diagnosis, counsel appropriately, give therapeutic instructions and establish caring relationships with patients (van Zanten, Boulet, McKinley DeChaplain, and Jobe, 2007). However, studies on doctor-patient interaction have shown that even when many doctors considered the communication model employed in interacting with their patients adequate or even excellent, some patients still feel discontent by the communicative situation. This has given credence to the call for patient centred medicine among others. Scholars have therefore advocated for good, acceptable and satisfactory doctor-patient interaction through effective communication. Such is communication has the potential to help regulate patients' emotions, facilitate comprehension of medical information, and allow for better identification of patients' needs, perceptions, and expectations (Arora, 2003:793). On the part of the patients, good communication with their doctor are more likely to be satisfied with their care, and especially to share pertinent information for accurate diagnosis of their problems, follow advice, and adhere to the prescribed treatment (Kaplan, Greenfield and Ware 1989:112).

In the general perspective, effective doctor-patient communication can be a source of motivation, incentive, reassurance, and support. A good doctor-patient relationship is capable of increasing job satisfaction and reinforces patients' self-confidence, motivation, and positive view of their health status, which may influence their health outcomes, Fong Ha and Longnecker (2010:43). Moreover, issues of communication in doctor-patient interaction are therefore aimed at ensuring that communication takes place effectively and the goals of the interaction which may be diagnostic, therapeutic and others are achieved. Communication, in this case, will include writing and talking, as well as nonverbal communication such as facial expressions, body language, or gestures, visual communication and many others.

2.6 Concluding remarks

According to Kean (1988:74), human linguistic capacity is a biological endowment and should be studied as such. If this is done, we will be able to gain more insights into the link between language and mind/brain. Sunday (2008) advocates efforts into the study of nature of language with regards to the mind and brain. Citing (Smith 1995), Sunday

remarks that although some scholars think because language leaves no fossils, the study of language and the brain is challenging. He suggests that it is not proper to see every issue related to language and brain/mind as mysteries, but rather as partly problems and partly mysteries. Quoting Chomsky (1972), He says “problems are the issues that appear to be within the reach of approaches and concepts that we moderately understood well; while mysteries are issues that are obscure to us today”. He, therefore, offers the suggestion of demystifying the mystery which is by engaging in meticulous and objective research.

Relying on Chomsky (2000), Sunday says that as far as the issue of language and mind/brain is concerned, “the best theory is that the initial state of the language faculty incorporates certain general principles of language structure, including phonetics and semantic principles and that the mature state of competence is a generative procedure that assigns structure descriptions to expressions and interacts with the motor and perceptual system and other cognitive systems of the mind/brain to yield semantic and phonetic interpretations of utterances.”

Since pragmatics has a link with semantics, in the sense that each deals with one aspect of discourse and they together contribute to the overall picture of linguistics; probing into the significance of the communication of neurologists with their patients will help in bringing succour the way of the language impaired people and related nervous disorder. Most especially Such effort will not just be of immense benefit to medical discourse only but will create a basis for a pragmatic view of related issues. It will also help ascertain the role which context plays in human interactions.

2.5 Summary

In this chapter, issues in pragmatics were explored. The evolution of language in relation to the functioning of the brain was buttressed. Neurolinguistics was explained and distinguished from psycholinguistics. The basic assumptions of Pragmatic acts were explored. Existing studies on doctor-patient interaction and perspectives from diverse linguistic fields are explored.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

In this chapter, the method employed in the research is discussed. This includes the data, design, location, size, inclusion and/or exclusion criteria used for the study.

3.1 Research design

This study is analytical and descriptive, in that it was aimed at analysing and describing the recorded communication pattern in neurologist-patient interactions in university teaching hospitals in South-west Nigeria. State and Federal government owned tertiary institutions who have neurology clinic are included for sampling in the study.

3.2 Data collection

Data for this study were purposively collected from natural neurologist-patient interactions from the university teaching hospitals in South-west Nigeria which include Ekiti, Ogun, Osun, and Oyo. The other states excluded are Ondo and Lagos. The case for the exclusion of Ondo was due to the lack of university hospital and functional neurological clinic in the state as at the time of carrying out the research. In Lagos, industrial actions of doctors hindered the response and approval for access to the neurological clinics of the university teaching hospitals in the state. The collection of data in other selected states lasted several months. The entire data collection took place between July 2015 to September 2016. The data were collected with the use of electronic audio recording devices, patients' case notes and interviews conducted with neurologists.

3.2.1 Ethical considerations

The study was approved by the West African Bioethics with registration number NHREC/05/01/2008a. Also, the Research Ethics Committee of the four university teaching hospitals selected for the study gave individual approvals (as mentioned in the succeeding paragraphs). The involved neurologists and patients received written information about the study prior to the commencement of each consultation and were encouraged to freely discuss the information provided them with anyone that accompanied them to the clinic visit, so as to make an informed decision. Participants

gave written informed consent, having been told that they could withdraw from the study at any time. Patients lacking capacity to consent were excluded from the study. Confidentiality was assured and transcripts were pseudo-acronyms of participants' identifiers in any subsequent outputs. In all the university teaching hospitals observed, ethical behaviours guiding researches on human subjects were strictly adhered to. Where participants declined participation, no coercion was used. At other instances where the cooperation of the participants was initially secured and later revoked or did not want certain aspects of the interactions to be used, the entire interactions concerned were excluded in the analysis used for the study.

Before embarking on the collection of data for the study, it was observed that each of the hospitals selected (University College Hospital, Ibadan; Ladoke Akintola University of Technology University Teaching Hospital, Osogbo; Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital, Sagamu; and Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti), have similar but slightly different ethical which were adhered to.

At the University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan which was the first point of call, an application letter was written to the Research Ethics Committee. The researcher was asked to take an online mandatory training on "Human Research Curriculum" and "Nigerian National Code for Health Research Ethics" (as mentioned earlier. See appendix I). After the successful completion of the training programme which lasted about six weeks, a certificate was issued. Thereafter, a written proposal detailing the nature of the study was submitted to the institution with adherence to the criteria of the institution. The proposal was reviewed by the Research Committee. Criticisms and recommendations were made to the proposal in order to protect the participants in the study and to enhance the quality of the study by the reviewer(s). The recommendations made to the proposals were later effected by the investigator and re-submitted. These went through another stage of reviews after which a written approval was given to the researcher to carry out the study (see appendix I). Similarly, at the Ekiti State, Ogun State, and LAUTECH University Teaching Hospital, written letters of application to carry out a research were submitted alongside a statement of the proposed plan of the research. These were reviewed for some weeks, and suggestions were made by the reviewers and reacted to by the researcher. Having satisfactory fulfilled the set ethical standards, and upon presentation of evidence on the completion of the Human Research

Curriculum and Nigerian National Code for Health Research Ethics training, certificates of approval were issued by each of the institutions to the researcher. See appendix I.

3.2.2 Hawthorne's control

Hawthorne's effect emanates from the assumption that when participants in a research are aware of their participation, they tend to deliberately improve their performance. This has been construed as the "Hawthorne's control" (see Franke and Kaul, 1978; McCarney, Warner, Liffe, van Haselen, Griffin et al, 2007). To control Hawthorne's bias, participants were assured before the start of each observation about the nondisclosure of their identities and that their identities remain anonymous. Coupled with this, they were reminded of their right to voluntary withdraw from the observation by not permitting the researcher to observe their interaction if they are averse to the observation. In this case, the researcher obliged them their request.

3.3 Sample size

Forty natural conversations expressed in English between neurologists and patients, who were able to give informed consent, including relations of patients who were present during the consultations, were selected for analysis out of the total sixty-three recorded conversations. In the interactions, a total of thirty-three neurologists consented to participate but only twenty-five of them were actually observed and recorded. This implies that there were cases where some neurologists who have featured previously in one neurologist-patient interaction were observed again in another instance. However, no one patient was observed, recorded and analysed in more than one instance of the neurologist-patient interaction in the study.

Alphabetism was used as a coding system for the study. In the coding system adopted to stratify the observed NPIs in the study, alphabets bearing semblance with those already used in the study to represent other variables were deliberately omitted. The omitted letters were D, E, I, M, N, O, P, and R.

3.4 Research instruments

The study, being an analytical and descriptive approach to medical research, certain medical and research ethics suffice. Within this allowance, the use of electronic audio recording devices authorised by the institutions involved in the study nature was employed.

Having secured the consents of patients' in the interactions, notes were taken to cater for other observable non-verbal behaviours between interactants. These include gestures among other relevant behaviour regarded useful to interpretations in pragmatics. Also, the age and occupation of each patient were collected on a structured questionnaire. The age was then verified from the medical records of the patients in the study locations. Interviews with neurologists were conducted to extract information on aspects of the interaction that were unverifiable through observation method. Also, the interviews provided information on neurologists regarding their years in practice among other details.

3.5 Study location

The location of the study is the neurology section of the medical outpatient clinic of university teaching hospitals in selected states from the southwestern Nigeria. The university teaching hospitals included are University College Hospital, Ibadan, Oyo State; Ladoke Akintola University of Technology University Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State; Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital, Sagamu, Ogun State; and Ekiti State University Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State.

3.6 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

All consenting patients and neurologists at the consulting rooms in the neurology clinic of the hospitals studied were included. The level of recovery of patients in the clinics was also considered. In line with this, patients with acute language impairment were excluded. Those whose speeches were audible irrespective of the seeming incoherence were included. Other sections of the hospitals outside the neurology clinics were excluded. Also, some of the exempted conversations include those with overbearing background noises. Participants who withdrew their consents in the course of the interactions due to personal reasons were also excluded from the analysed data.

With regards to institutional inclusion/exclusion criteria, only institutions which gave ethical approval for the study to be conducted within their facilities were included. Those excluded due to declined approval were the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital, Ile-Ife, University of Lagos Teaching Hospital, Igbobi, and Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Ikeja. There is no University Teaching Hospital in Ondo State.

3.7 Method of data analysis

During the observation of the interactions, notes were taken to cater for non-verbal behaviours of the interactants. Also, the recorded audio conversations of the interactions were listened to, so as to document the interaction. These were transcribed following Arminen's (2005) notations of conversational analysis. The notations were slightly modified by the researcher to account for cues that were not accounted for in the original notation.

The transcribed data were subjected to pragmatic analysis in the tradition of Mey's (2001) notion of pragmeme. Jacob Mey's pragmatic acts theory has a wide range of principles and concepts. Among such principle is called the communicative principle (Mey 2001:69-70). In the analyses, the pragmatic communicative principle (PCP) is applied to identify the communication goals and patterns in the interactions. The PCP also accounted for grammatical infelicities in the interactions. It emphasises whether or not the attainment of goals is affected by participants' violation of grammatical rules through their communication.

The data transcribed were examined following the observation made when they were being recorded. The notes which were taken on the research field, patients' case notes and interviews conducted with neurologists aided the proper contextualisation of the actual events. They also helped to classify the data into proper perspectives for analysis.

The data were used as extracts for illustrations and were presented in the analysis. The interactions were done mainly in the English language. Where English is mixed with indigenous languages, an English translation was provided. The extracts indicated the communication goals and patterns, discourse strategies, pragmatic acts and contexts that shaped neurologist-patient interaction.

More so, Emanuel and Emanuel (1992) models of Doctor-Patient Relationship (EDPR) hitherto referred to as the EDPR, is adapted as (ENPI) in the analyses. The "E" in the acronym refers to the proponents, Emanuel and Emanuel, this is done for patent retention. The NPI of the ENPI acronym specifies that the focus is that of the Neurologist-Patient Interaction. In line with this, the four models, paternalistic, informative, interpretive, and deliberative were examined.

3.9 Summary

This chapter explores the methodology employed for this study. In line with this, the method of data collection and analysis, research instruments used, study design, location, sample size, ethical consideration, inclusion/exclusion criteria, and analytical frameworks are discussed. The next chapter is the commencement of data analyses.

CHAPTER FOUR

GOALS IN NEUROLOGIST-PATIENT INTERACTION AND PRAGMATIC STRATEGIES OF THE PATERNALISTIC AND INFORMATIVE MODELS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter is concentrated on the analyses of data with a focus on the communication goals in neurologist-patient interaction from the selected university teaching hospitals in Southwestern Nigeria. In particular, discourse strategies and context that shape interaction in only the paternalistic and informative models were analysed. For the entire analyses of data, the interactions were labelled NPI (signifying each Neurologist-Patient Interaction) ranging from one to forty. Background information was provided to account for the contextual variables of each NPI. Each patient was represented with letter “P”, neurologist with “N”, relation of patient with “R” while superscript is used on some of the letters to indicate instances where there are more than one neurologists (e.g. N¹ and N²) or relations of patient (R¹ or R²) contributing in specific interactions. In some cases, tables and diagrams were presented to buttress some of the findings. These tables and diagrams were interpreted so as to enhance quick and easy grasp of the analysed data.

4.1 Communication goals in neurologist-patient interaction

Identifying the goals of any communicative event depends on the contextual variables in the interaction. The communication goals in the consultative meeting between neurologists and their patients are best described as diagnostic and therapeutic. It is diagnostic in the sense that the patient in most hospital visits do so because he or she must have observed that something is possibly wrong with him or her. As a result, he or she sees the need or is compelled by other people to visit the hospital. The therapeutic nature of communication in hospitals is based on the professional role of doctors coupled with the society’s expectation of this role. For example, in the extract below:

Excerpt 1: NPI 23

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 3 years; Patient: male; Age: 13; Occupation: Pupil; Ailment: Dyslexia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Let him sit down. You can use the other sit.
2. R: Thank you ma. They said we should come here.
3. N: Yes. Your child was diagnosed of dyslexia.
4. R: It is true sir (0.8) that we can't...
5. N: Wait. You must know one thing. Dyslexia is not a disease or an identifiable physical condition. It is a learning style that usually can be assessed through a profile that shows whether the child has a typical pattern of strengths and weaknesses, coupled with assessment to rule out other possible causes of symptoms, such as vision or hearing problems. From the reports with me, some of the issues raised are common traits of what we are talking about. But there are things we can do.
6. R: So, that is how he would be?
7. N: I just told you it's not a disease. Of course, we can see it as a disorder but definitely not a disease as you appear to be feeling. Anyway, there are some things we can still do. I mean some interventions are possible.
8. R: Okay sir. (0.32) But like what.
9. N: Let me ask you some questions first.
10. R: Yes ma
11. N: When he was a toddler, did she have any serious injury? Like falling down or anything.
12. R: Yes
13. N: What happened?
14. R: We had a house girl then. ((sobs)) I was at the office when they called that she fell from her and hit on the flo:::or.
15. N: It's okay. Did you do anything? As in hospital and the rest.
16. R: We went to a private hospital.
17. N: Why?
18. R: Doctors were on strike then.
19. N: For how long?
20. R: I can say clearly now but *sha*, I know it's more than three months.

From the above, one can deduce the inherent goal of the interaction between these participants. Here, the parent of the patient. The opening lines show that the neurologist is well aware of the nature of diagnosis of the patient (through the patient case note). The parent of the patient, being worried about the neurologist's declaration in line 3, was ready to express her fears which is later revealed in line 6. This was interrupted by the neurologist's explanation on the nature of the ailment in lines 5 and 7. The neurologist's interruption of the patient in line 5 helped him to calm down the patient's parent from her anxieties (see lines 7-8). Having achieved this, he was able to explain in details what

the ailment is all about (line 5). After this, the neurologist systematically engaged the patient's parent in a bid to establish further diagnostic communication (lines 9-20).

In the same interaction above, the therapeutic goal of the interaction is revealed in the subsequent parts of the interaction. For example, in lines 21 of same NPI 23 (see appendix IV), the neurologist played the role of a speech or language therapist by engaging the patient in some question and answer drill. This activity in itself has a dual purpose of both diagnostic and therapeutic. The specific questions are to help ascertain the linguistic ability of the patient (diagnostic), while also helping to redirect the patient's ability to comprehend what was being said (therapeutic). In line 33, the neurologist appeared to have got sufficient diagnostic information. With this in mind, he made a recommendation on the patient in lines 35 – 51.

Further, in some communicative domains of neurologist-patient interaction, there is the possibility of the communication goal to be either covert or overt. Where the communication goal is covert, understanding some pragmatic principles will be required to fully have a grasp of the goal. In line with this, pragmatic communication principle (PCP) is of a significant importance. In the observed neurologist-patient interaction, PCP helps to identify the goals. For example in NPI 18:

Excerpt 2: NPI 18

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 4 years; Patient: female; Age: 26; Occupation: Student; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: When last were you here?
2. P: Last week
3. N: Okay ((reads through the case note)). But you were not given any appointment for today.
4. P: Yes. It's because I feel I need to come quickly.
5. N: So what brought you?
6. P: It's this thing again.
7. N: What's that? Oh! (0.2) Okay.
8. P: Last week Monday, as I was just about going to see my aunt in her shop.
9. N: You fell?
10. P: They said I fell.
11. N: Since that time have you experience it again?
12. P: No o. But this morning. I started having that feeling again.
13. N: That you'll have it again?
14. P: Yes.
15. N: The drugs we gave you to buy, did you get them?
16. P: I did. But since that thing has gone. I...

17. N: You don't use them again?
18. P: No! I used them. It's that other one I don't like to use.
19. N: Ehn ((writes)). Do you bring the pack?
20. P: Here is it.
21. N: Is it this one you said you don't like ((picks out the sachet))?
22. P: Hmmmmm: ehm ((0.4) it makes me to...
23. N: Feeling dizzy?
24. P: And as if I want to vomit too.
25. N: Apart from that what else?
26. P: Hmmm::: Nothing.
27. N: Tell me how you normally use this.
28. P: ((collects it from N)) It's twice a day.
29. N: What time of the day?
30. P: I used to use it (sic) in the morning after eating.
31. N: What time do you normally eat in the morning?
32. P: May be around 10 *sha*.
33. N: Why
34. P: Me I don't used to like (sic) eating too early o.
35. N: Okay. But do you know you are not helping us?
36. P: I am sorry ma.
37. N: No ooo. This drug in question ought to be used everyday before 8 but you don't use it until 10 or thereabout. When you use it, we told you that you should not rush to go out. At least you should give it about one hour or more. There are some drugs you cannot use when you are to be engaged in active activities. What we'll do is to keep you at it (0.8). Ehm You must keep using this drug.
38. P: This one?
39. N: Yes. You must always use it before 8 in the morning. In fact, 7.30 would be fine. And also use it at night. See! This is not a drug you skip o. Or you like the situation?
40. P: Haa no o!
41. N: So, you must continue using them ((brings out the drugs from the nylon being held by the patient)). This is for But don't do without using them, especially this one. 7.30 in the morning and also 7.30 at night please.
42. P: Thank you ma.
43. N: Have you use them today?
44. P: As I was coming.
45. N: Alright then. Around what time.
46. P: 9.30
47. N: Are you sure of that?
48. P: Yes
49. N: Did you eat?
50. P: Yes
51. N: What did you eat?
52. P: Tea and bread.
53. N: And you were okay with that?
54. P: Very okay
55. N: No *wahala*. Let me check your B.P and also...((examines the P)) Is this place paining you?
56. P: No
57. N: What about here?
58. P: No ma.

59. N: Okay. So, continue with your medication and see us in three weeks.
60. P: Okay ma. Should I buy more when the drugs finish?
61. N: The prescription I gave you will cover beyond your next time of visit.
62. P: Okay. ((exits))

From the excerpt above, it can be clearly seen how the neurologist attempted to establish the goal of the meeting. She has inquired from the patient what the purpose of the visitation was (lines 1-5). This question was necessitated by the seeming surprise of the neurologist in seeing the patient in the consulting room. This is a case of an overt goal identification.

Further, in line 6, the “it’s this thing again” foregrounded by the patient conveys the self-discovery of the need to see the doctor as seen later in lines 8-12. This is one of the ways the covert goal can be identified. By this, there was not a single mention of the precise purpose of the visit. Rather, both interactants, relying on shared situation knowledge, interact used euphemistic terms to arrive at the communication goal. The “fell” or “falling” in the context is a veiled name for seizure. In other sense, the patient had suffered a seizure prior to her visit to the hospital. Rather than using the term, both interactants were comfortable with a lesser expression in order to probably reduce the effect of the previous seizure experience on the patient.

As earlier mentioned, the patient in the interaction above in line 3 revealed that the decision to visit the clinic at the specific time without having booked any prior appointment was based on her desire to achieve a therapeutic goal. In order to successfully accomplish this, she supplied substantial information to the doctor with regards to the seizure she has previously experienced.

On the part of the neurologist towards the achievement of the therapeutic goal, the neurologist gave directive in the form of a warning to the patient in line 39:

N: Yes. You must always use it before 8 in the morning. In fact, 7.30 would be fine. And also use it at night. See! This is not a drug you skip o.
Or you like the situation?

To this, the patient responded as the neurologist gave further instructions (line 41). The index of diagnostic and therapeutic communication as goals was further buttressed as the neurologist went ahead to physically examine the patient (line 55) and give further instructions (59). Having attained the goal, the patient was scheduled for a further visit

(61) with an assurance by the neurologist on the wellbeing of the patient pending the next visit.

A noticeable feature in the interaction is some cases of grammatical infelicities. In other interactions, such errors are capable of disrupting communication and meaning. However, assumptions in the pragmatic communicative principle (PCP) is validated in many of the interactions where violations of grammatical rules has occurred. Here, the errors noticeable did not impart the mutual understanding or the intentions of participants. For example, in line 30:

P: I used to use it in the morning after eating.

The above is capable of misleading some other people who do not have a knowledge of the context or who are not familiar with the popular but wrong application of the word “used to” (especially among some fairly educated Nigerian speakers of English). This phrase comprising a lexical verb and a preposition, “used to”, would mean that the drug has since then stopped being used “after eating”. Rather, the patient intended to communicate her habitual adherence to the use of the drug to the neurologist “after eating”. The non-contextual equivalent should have been “I usually use it in the ...”. The assumption of PCP is exhibited through the response of the neurologist as he shows a full understanding of the speech situation through another diagnostic communication in line 32:

N: What time do you normally eat in the morning?

This question, though a follow-up to the previous, shows that there is a mutual linguistic situational knowledge between the interactants. It is obvious that the patient is not aware of the grammatical inadequacy as a result of the repeated use of the phrase as also seen in line 34:

P: Me I don't used to like eating too early o.

However, it is possible that the neurologist may or may not identify any “grammatical issue” from the patient’s use of the phrase. If this is true, then, that might have enhanced his understanding of what is said and how it was said. As a result of this possibility, another instance where PCP is exhibited is extracted from NPI 17, line 16 where the patient complains:

P: I don't know o. And I think their thing may be too cost for me.

The response from the neurologist in line 17

N: But what can be more important than your health? I know. Some things can be too costly. Yes, very costly. But is there anything that can be truly more costly than anybody's good health?

shows the intention of the physician to employ the practice of grammatical "correcting". This practice is evident in other parts of this interaction as seen in NPI 17, lines 19:

N: Money? Important than your health?

As a reaction to the patient's insistence on her financial incapability of purchasing the prescribed drugs:

P: It's money o. Things are too cost

Although it can be excused that the patient in the interaction is having a form of familiarity feeling with the doctor, the fact that she cannot identify the "correcting" practice employed by the neurologist shows she is unaware of the intention of the neurologist in the context.

According to Mey (2001), whether or not the interactant "observe a particular syntactic rule is not too important", rather their "intention to communicate something to somebody" is the "foundation of the linguistic behaviour". The achievement of a communicative goal is shown in the other parts of the interaction as the neurologist displayed a good awareness of the patient's communicative intention. For example, the neurologist offering therapeutic practice of "counselling" at a later stage of the interaction in line 23 of NPI 17 is a referent point to the validation of the PCP as proposed by Mey (2001):

N: You see. That drug that was finished is the main one that helps in the control of that problem in the leg. You should have got another one as we told you when you came here the other time. You will have to go and continue using it (0.8) I mean you will have to go and buy it and continue using it. Before we can look at other things. ((looks through the file)) I also feel you should do some tests. But buy the drugs and keep using it. ((writes)) "Don't want till your drugs are exhausted, always stick to the use of other ones here. ((continues writing)) You will have to see us next week. Then, we will take it up from there.

The implication of this is that grammatical infelicities are determined by the understanding of the discourse context between interactants. Although in situations

where the number of the interactants gets increased, the validity of PCP may be over-stretched. Thus, instead of leading to the achievement of the communication goal, it may lead to confusion due to the misinterpretation of the speaker's intended meaning. In the interactions collected, there are major and minor cases of PCP. In all cases of identifiable grammatical infelicities, shared mutual expectations of the interactants, (diagnostic and/or therapeutic communication) in this context, has helped to de-emphasize other instances of the PCP. As a result, they could be considered minor. Some of these were found in NPIs-2:18, 33, 45; 16:71; 17: 16, 18, and so on. (See appendix IV).

Furthermore, the identification of the communicative goals can also be found in the opening and the closing parts of most of the observed interactions. Considering the opening and closing conversation in lines 1-7 and 26-30 as an example:

Excerpt 3: NPI 25

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 3 years; Patient: female; Age: 45; Occupation: Artisan; Ailment: Migraine; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: What is the problem ma?
2. P: This my kneel (sic) is really disturbing me.
3. N: When did it start?
4. P: Four days ago.
5. N: Four days?
6. P: Actually. It was after I came back home from the travel (sic). I started feeling hot. So I said may be it's because of the stress. So I decided to use some drugs and Paracetamol. But the headache continued. So after two days of the headache (sic). Em... I used em the::::: *agbo* ((local herbal concoction)). So I was told to rest may be it will go. But the day after. I started feeling pain in my leg. I was even thinking maybe, it's because of the fasting. So when it did not go. I said I should come and see you today.
7. N: That's okay. ((Examines the patients)). Let me see your drugs.
8. P: ((Brings out the pack)) Em::: this one has finished and can't get it anywhere to buy.
9. N: ((smiles)) Okay. Since when?
10. P: Before I travelled.
11. N: And when you came back, what did you do?
12. P: When I searched searched searched (sic) and could not see it *nko*?
13. N: Did you check (...).
14. P: The one at (...) near (...)
15. N: Not that one. They may not have it. I mean the (...) pharmacy.
16. P: I don't know o. And I think their thing may be too cost (sic) for me.
17. N: But what can be more important than your health? I know. Somethings can be too costly. Yes, very costly. But is there anything that can be truly more costly than anybody's good health?
18. P: It's money o. Things are too cost (sic)

19. N: Money? Important than your health?
20. P: No o. I mean when I don't have the money nko?
21. N: But you can't just assume now.
22. P: It's true o. I will try to go check it.
23. N: You see. That drug that was finished is the main one that helps in the control of that problem in the leg. You should have got another one as we told you when you came here the other time. You will have to go and continue using it (0.8) I mean you will have to go and buy it and continue using it. Before we can look at other things. ((looks through the file)) I also feel you should do some tests. But buy the drugs and keep using it. ((writes)) "Don't want till your drugs are exhausted, always stick to the use of other ones here. ((continues writing)) You will have to see us next week. Then, we will take it up from there.
24. N: Do you normally sleep well?
25. P: Yes. Except when the pain wakes me up.
26. N: Okay. ((hands the prescription over to patient)) You will ask someone to help you get the drug at that place and make sure you use them as I told you. One in the morning and one at night.
27. P: Thank you sir.
28. N: You are welcome. Greet your people for me.
29. P: Thank you sir.
30. N: Take care.

it can be deduced that the extract above suggests an instance of the overt communicative goal. Here, the neurologist inquired from the patient "what the problem" was. To aid the therapeutic goal, typical to most interactions between doctors and their patients, the respondent (patient) revealed what her complaint was. This led to further diagnostic talks which featured specific mentioning of time (when the patient has been experiencing the ailment), the faithfulness of patient to prescribed drugs, attitude to life, patient's behaviour regarding own health among other details as seen in line lines 4-22. In fact, in line 23, the neurologist made allusion to the patient's behaviour to own health as contributory to the present state of the patient:

N: You see. That drug that was finished is the main one that helps in the control of that problem in the leg. You should have got another one as we told you when you came here the other time. You will have to go and continue using it (0.8) I mean you will have to go and buy it and continue using it. Before we can look at other things. ((looks through the file)) I also feel you should do some tests. But buy the drugs and keep using it. ((writes)) "Don't want till your drugs are exhausted, always stick to the use of other ones here. Then, we will take it up from there.

Having fulfilled the diagnostic communicative, the neurologist employed the pract of promising as the last sentence in line 23:

Then, we will take it up from there.

Usually, neurologists tend to discuss further diagnostic communication even when a part of such has been achieved in their interactions with patients. In the extract above for example, when the initial cause of the patient's complaint appeared to have been established, the neurologist still further engaged the patient by asking for more information (lines 24-26). The closing part of the interaction in line 26, gives the impression of a therapeutic communication. Here, a prescription was given to the patient after which a form of phatic communication was exchanged. The extract above is a replica of the pattern of communication with regards to the identification of communication goals in neurologist-patient interactions. Most of the interactions observed in the study have similar structure with the examples used in this section. Thus, it can be reiterated that communication goals of any doctor-patient interaction are best identified through consideration of both covert and overt linguistic items in the discourse.

4.2 Patterns of communication in the selected NPIs

As discussed in chapter two, Emanuel and Emanuel models of doctor-patient relationship is adopted for this study. These four models, which in this study, are modified as Emanuel and Emanuel's model of neurologist-patient interaction (ENPI). Two of these, paternalistic and informative are analysed in the subsequent sections so as to identify their pragmatic implications in the studied locations. In doing this in most cases, at least, an entire conversation between neurologist and patient is extracted in analysing each of the models. The relatives of patients involved in the interactions are also included as their role is considered significant to identifying the patterns of communication in each case.

4.2.1 Use of the paternalistic model in the observed NPI

In the paternalistic model, the neurologist plays the role of a parent in the interaction with the patient. As a result, he/she is expected to be the all-knowing expert, knowing everything that the patient needs and will need, when and how, towards the diagnostic and therapeutic goal of the interaction. To ascertain this, the interaction below is extracted. The analyses are presented in different sub-sections to identify the activity types and their strategies.

4.3.1 Activity type in paternalistic model

In the pragmatic grid, the activity part on the left provides analysts with the possible choices that are available to users of language in any communicative situation. Any type of these choices may be employed in the communicative situation involving the interactants and depending on the context. Some of these are explored in this study.

4.3.1.2 Speech acts activity in the paternalistic model

Mey (2001:93) opines that “the unit of linguistic communication is not, as has generally been supposed, the symbol, word or sentence”. Rather, it is the production of linguistic communication as evident in “the performance of the speech act” (:93). Speech acts are those linguistic behaviours performed in the actual situation of language use. This may or may not be expressed in “speech act verbs”. The extract below is an example.

Excerpt 4: NPI 1

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: male;
Age: 68; Occupation: Retired police officer; Ailment: Dementia;
Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: What they gave me there, I don't understand?
2. N: Ha! It means you have gained some weight (0.2) which is good: When you came earlier, it was 68.
3. P: This morning?:::
4. N: Yes. The first time was 68. Today is also 68. So it's fine. Ha! ((smiles)) that's good it's our own measurement we rely on. The 72 must been an error. Maybe the scale was faulty. It's fine //. So it means you have a steady weight (0.2) that's improvement.
5. P: Thank you sir.

The extracted interaction from NPI 1 above suggests that prior activities have taken place which are known to both interactants. The present interaction reveals that the patient has encountered some other personnel in the hospital, who have carried out some diagnoses on him. Here, the patient is meeting the neurologist to interpret the results of the earlier tests carried out (line 1). It should be noted that there is no one-to-one element of verbs to suggest the patient's intention, instead, the observable linguistic behaviours performed in the actual situation of the interaction help to identify the intention. In line 2, the neurologist, using (indirect speech act or) pract of declaring, responded based on the result presented. In line 3, the patient expressed the desire to really ascertain the declaration without using any known declaring verbs (like “I hereby declare...”). With the neurologist's understanding of the patient's intention, he reiterated the declaration with more details on the implications of the result. Apart from the pract of declaring used

above, the practs of informing, promising, instructing among others were used by the neurologist. These are further expanded in subsequent discussions with their peculiarities to the paternalistic model of neurologist-patient interaction. The following are major instances of speech acting discovered.

(a) Declaring

This, declaring is one of the major features of the paternalistic model in ENPI. This is due to its “priestly” status. The examples below are extracted from NPI 1:

2. N: Ha! It means you have gained some weight (0.2) which is good: When you came earlier, it was 68.

14. N: Your recall is coming back.

30. N: Now that you can recall two out of three. That’s great! That’s the only way we can measure improvement. So, you are doing well. You are really making progress.

A closer attention to the extract will show that this pract is responsible for the eventual pattern through which the interaction was paddled. The first instance of “declaring” occurs at the initial part of the conversation, about the middle and the end. This gives the neurologist some measures of influence on the determination of what is done and not done in the interaction. Other sets of extract taken from NPI 24 corroborate this (appendix IV). For examples:

20. N: The result you brought claims this one is normal but from what we see here. Certainly, this is not correct.

36. N: It’s just the blood test.

39. N: One a day should be fine. That will also give you extra potassium.

As earlier mentioned, the strategy employed by the neurologist in the utilisation of the “declaring” pract has a similar pattern with the previous extracts. The initial, middle and final positioning are indicators of a paternalistic model of communication. According to Emanuel and Emanuel, one of the ways of utilising this model is by presenting “the patient with selected information that will encourage the patient to consent to the intervention the physician considers best”. They also propose that the physician does “authoritatively inform the patient when the intervention will be initiated”. The pract of informing is found in the environments where the declaring pract was utilised. Thus, informing as a pract is considered as a co-text of declaring. These can be found in:

	Declaring	Informing
NPI 1:2	N: Ha! It means you have gained some weight (0.2) which is good:	When you came earlier, it was 68.
NPI 12	...So, you are doing well. You are really making progress.	N: Now that you can recall two out of three. That's great! That's the only way we can measure improvement.
NPI 24:20	...from what we see here. Certainly, this is not correct.	N: The result you brought claims this one is normal but

(b) Embedded pract of promising

The proponent of pragmeme and others critics of the speech act theory argue that speech acting is problematic as regards “wording of the act”. They argue that *exactness of words* is not a prerequisite to the determination of the speech act performed in a linguistic exchange, (words in italics mine). The only requirement championed by Mey is “circumstances of the promise” (Mey, 2001:97). In other words, so long the act of promise is performed in the communication, the lexical choice employed is immaterial, as much as the interactants conceive and understand each other in the context. Using the examples from NPI 1 as seen below:

8. N: ...I will ask you later whether you'll remember them.

30 N: ... So, I will give him three months.... I will see you in three months.

shows that although there is the use of the modal verb “will” and lexical “ask”, “give”, “see” in the extract, these were not mere communication, but they aligned with the pattern of the paternalistic model. In this context, the utterance in line 8 conveys the sense of expectation and duty, which the neurologist will revert to for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes in the communication. In the second extract, line 30, a sense of hope is transferred to the patient, as he looks forward to the “promised” “three months”. Therefore, pract of “controlling” is embedded in the promising pract as seen in the interaction. It is one of the most recurring strategies employed in all the observed NPIs. This is not to suggest that all the NPIs followed the paternalistic communication model. They are usually found in the closing part of the interactions, (see appendix IV). They perform the pragmatic act of *expecting* on the patients. The main reason why the patients look forward to the next appointment date.

(c) **Use of the pract of instructing**

Instruction can be described as an order or series of principles, moral guidelines and so on that **must** be carried out. In schools, instruction is handed out from the teachers to the students. Similarly, at homes, parents are responsible for the pattern of instructions their children or wards attend to. Within this frame of mind, instructing as a speech act strategy in NPI is of the paternalistic model. Here, the physician assumes the role of a parent in this model through which he/she orders, dictates, controls, inquires, counsels, and instructs the patient. For example, in an extract from NPI 2 (see appendix IV):

62. N: Yes ma. So (0.2) **you'll see the dentists and see me in** (0.4) ((writes) **in six weeks**.

the words in bold have the linguistic feature similar to one of the extracts used in the promising speech acting. However, these items “you'll see the dentists and see me...” are not related to the promising pract. This is because, the performer of the pract of “seeing” has been conferred on the patient, with the employment of the personal pronoun in the subjective case “you”. In this situation, the neurologist occupies the objective personal pronoun case “me”. Here, the responsibility of the “see(ing)” behoves on the patient rather than the neurologist. A similar scenario is portrayed in NPI 17:

Excerpt 5: NPI 17

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 2 years; Patient: male; Age: 40; Occupation: Self-employed; Ailment: Diabetes Mellitus; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Welcome. So How are you today?
2. P: I'm fine ma. It's just that saliva is coming out from this side of my mouth.
3. N: Okay. Is it that side only?
4. P: Hmmm: I think. Emmm (0.2) It's because.
5. N: Because of the drug?
6. P: Yes, ma. I was just thinking maybe it is.
7. N: You just think so. ((Goes closer to the patient)) Has your eyes been like this all along?
8. P: Yes, even my son has this kind.
9. N: And you think it's because of the drug? Does this place ((touching the cheek)) scratch you?
10. P: It is pinching me inside.
11. N: Have you ever had your tooth removed before?
12. P: Only twice.
13. N: Was it after we treated you for the (0.4). Em (0.2) for the ((checks case notes)). After the accident?
14. P: Yes ma. After the attack?
15. N: Which attack was that?

16. P: The one you treat(ed) me for.
17. N: ((rushes to check the case note again)) Oh I see. You actually had a quarrel with P^SP that led to your being treated. Okay (0.8). No problem. But when did you say the tooth was removed?
18. P: Hmmm (0.4). Let me say em. Em:: ((turns to the person accompanying him)). When was that sef(sic)?
19. R: It's up to two months now.
20. N: Who did the thing for him?
21. R: It's those people that remove teeth o!
22. N: In which hospital?
23. P: It was not an(sic) hospital per se. They were doing church outreach and I complained to their head doctor.
24. N: And they just remove your teeth like that?
25. P: It's not just like that?
26. R: They came (0.2) our house about two days after
27. N: And they remove it?
28. P: Something like that ma.
29. N: Something like that? ((changes sitting position)) So you mean?
30. R: Is that why (sic)?
31. N: Hmmm (0.8). You see (0.2). It is not proper that you allow just anybody to treat you medically.
32. P: But they are from our church.
33. R: Let them (sic) talk now.
34. P: I'm sorry
35. N: It's okay. I just know that you should have called us or better still, come back to complain here. Or is it the money?
36. P: It's part of it.
37. R: Ma. At that thing we had nothing on us. So we saw it as an opportunity to relieve him.
38. N: Well (0.2). That is logical but it's dangerous. You know that I cannot do anything without this file ((case file)). What we will do now is ((writes in the case note)). I'm going to let our dentists examine your teeth and other things and then see if the situation remains or not. Let me see your drug bag.
39. R: ((hands over the polyethene bag to her)) You have removed that one after the last time we came.
40. N: That was over twelve months ago.
41. P: Yes.
42. N: Okay. ((keeps writing in the case notes)) I just must warn you that you don't allow em em anybody who says he's a doctor treat you. It's not that they are necessarily not capable. But they need to know about your medical history.
43. R: They (sic) know ma.
44. N: How?
45. P: We told them we had accident (sic).
46. N: He knew you are being treated for a neurological disorder?
47. P: Not that one.
48. R: But we told them that we have been to this hospital before.
49. N: That's not the point. He does not have your medical history in detail.
50. P: Oh! Okay
51. N: When you have any problem, even if you don't have money, there should be someone you can call to ask question here.
52. R: We will not do it again ma.

53. N: It's okay.
54. P: Is that the reason for the spitting?
55. N: I am not necessarily saying so. What we need to do now is to see the specialists before we can do a follow-up. Is that clear?
56. R: Yes ma. We are sorry ma.
57. P: Don't be angry ma.
58. N: Ha no o! It's nothing. I just need you to be careful.
59. P: Thank you very much ma.
60. N: You are welcome.
61. R: We are so grateful ma.
62. N: Yes ma. So (0.2) you'll see the dentists and see me in (0.4) ((writes) in six weeks.
63. P and R: Thank you ma.
64. N: Make sure you continue with those drugs. The other doctor will help us with other things. The saliva and the main thing. My concern is for you to be fine always.
65. R: Yes ma.
66. N: Okay. That's it. Don't skip your drugs o.
67. P: ((Nods))
68. R: He won't ma. Thank you very much.
69. N: Thank you.

In the above, the patient complained is understood by the neurologist. Although the patient had a personal assumption as the cause of his health status, but the neurologist refuted the assumption (lines 2-7). Having done this, he continues to engage the patient in more diagnostic questions through which other causes were discovered. Throughout the conversation leading to the discovery, the doctor maintains the posture of a more knowledgeable person compared to the patient who occupies the role of someone in need of help (lines 17, 31). With this, the neurologist has a full control of the interaction through which he dishes out instructions to the patient. It is this uneven floor-holding, in lines 28-35, that made the patient apologised for own role that led him to the present predicament. This kind of a situation is one of the typical patterns of the paternalistic model. In the model, the neurologist and patient do not have an equal share of the turns. It should be noted that this uneven share of turns is not restricted to the paternalistic model alone as would be seen in subsequent parts of the study. The major distinguishing factor between the paternalistic model and others is that in the paternalistic, neurologists employ the pract of instructing (the patient) more than other models as seen in many lines of NPI 17 above, especially lines 63 "N: Make sure you continue with those drugs"; and 66 "N:...Don't skip your drugs o". It should be noted that the pract of instructing is usually employed towards the closing stage across NPIs of other models of

communication. However, in the paternalistic model, it can be employed at any point of the interaction.

4.3.1.3 Discourse strategies in the paternalistic model of NPI

The above interaction employs a persuasive conversational pattern. Scholars are at a consensus that dialogic strategy is common to doctor-patient interaction. This is also true regarding the observed neurologist-patient interaction. In the observed interactions, turns are taken by each participant. Each of the interactants obeyed and observed own role in the conversation. However, there is evidence of a doctor-centred NPI foregrounded by some slightly casual conversation and registers. The NPI 1 provides copious examples of these. This is presented below.

Excerpt 6: NPI 1

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: male; Age: 68
Occupation: retired police officer; Ailment: Dementia Visitation status:
accompanied by a relation

1. P: What they gave me there, I don't understand?
2. N: Ha! It means you have gained some weight (0.2) which is good: When you came earlier, it was 68.
3. P: This morning?:::
4. N: Yes. The first time was 68. Today is also 68. So it's fine. Ha! ((smiles)) that's good it's our own measurement we rely on. The 72 must been an error. Maybe the scale was faulty. It's fine //. So it means you have a steady weight (0.2) that's improvement.
5. P: Thank you sir.
6. N: Now, let me say three words to you. This is what we usually do. And I will ask you by the time we are finishing the interaction to see if you can remember them. The three words are "goat, shoe and broom"
7. P: Goat, shoe and broom
8. N: Not now, I will ask you later whether you'll remember them. That's good !!
9. P: Oh ok.
10. N: I will also like to know whether you still go to Ife or not?
11. P: Yes, I still do.
12. N: What for?
13. P: Hmm. I've spent about one year there. ((Other conversation ensued for 4:53sec minutes which are deliberately left out for P^{SP})).
14. N: Your recall is coming back.
15. P: Thank you Sir.
16. Nev: What are the three words I told you earlier? You'll need to remember
17. P: Hmm ... Em: : : br::oom
18. N: Yes !! One.
19. P: Shoe
20. N: Two! Excellent
21. ((Applause by R))
22. N: What is the third one?

23. P: Excuse Sir.
 24. N: Yes. Because during your first time here (0.4) But say the third one first.
 25. P: Broom, shoe, hmm, hmm! Ha! ((disappointed in self))
 26. N: You tried! Goat.
 27. P: Goat!
 28. N: You tried. So, the last time you couldn't remember any.
 29. P: Oh oh
 30. N: Now that you can recall two out of three. That's great! That's the only way we can measure improvement. So, you are doing well. You are really making progress. So, we will continue our medication. I won't change anything. The constipation will be taking care of. Just be rest assured. ((Other conversation))) > ((keeps writing)) (0:2) So I have removed the... I have included drugs to help his sleeping habit. ((explains other drugs and usefulness)). And then, we can now give him long appointment. So I will give him three months. They will write the exact date for you outside. So that we can then see if there are obvious changes. Thank you very much. I will see you in three months
 31. P: I' m grateful. ((smiles)) You have a very big passion for work.
 32. N: Thank you Sir . (and and and) Enjoy yourself Sir.

From the interaction above, the patient has entered the consulting room of the neurology clinic with a burden of questions requiring answers, most especially, the result of his earlier test by other medical personnel. Although the burden was immediately lifted off him by the neurologist who interprets the results (even without hesitation) as an indication of a “weight gain”, the patient stares in consternation and responds with a stretched “this morning?”. This is a reflection of expression of prior knowledge, one of the features of the “parental role” in the paternalistic model. It can be argued that the patient’s response in bewilderment, is a pract of “surprising”. In the process, in line 3, the pract enhances his surrendering to the “all-knowing” neurologist. It thus allows the neurologist to dictate the pace of the interaction. According to Emanuel and Emanuel the physician’s deployment of “their skills to determine the patient’s medical condition...encourages the patient to consent to the intervention the physician considers best” (p7). By this, pract of “knowing” is deployed. Thus, the neurologist is able to control the interaction, while the patient becomes a passive participant in the interaction. This is further buttressed through a scrutiny of the responses of the patient after the “knowing” pract by the doctor, as the patient’s subsequent responses are rendered in simple sentences. Lines 5, “Thank you, sir.”; 7, “Goat, shoe and broom”; 9, “Oh ok”; 11, “Yes, I still do” and many others. This re-emphasises the fact that in the paternalistic model of NPI, floor holding resides more with the neurologist. Most of the patient’s monotonous responses are some of the examples and evidence of the longer floor holding by the neurologist. Also, through this, the achievement of “transition relevant

places” (TRP) is revealed. The TRP as a pragmatic function is exploited when a speaker holds the floor. Across other NPIs in the study locations, there are visible instances of TRP in the interactions. These are seen in NPI 40: 1-6, for examples:

Excerpt 7: NPI 40

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 13 years; Patient: male; Age: 71 years; Occupation: Retired public servant; Ailment: Parkinson disease; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: Good afternoon ma.
2. N: Morning ma. Morning Sir. You are welcome. Come and have your seat ma.
3. R: Oh. Good morning sir. How are you sir?
4. N: I am very (0.2) very (0.2) very FINE. How are you too?
5. R: Fine thank God
6. N: And baba? How are you today sir?

Again, there is evidence of an uneven “floor-taking” in this conversation going by the loud “fine” in line 4. Although they can be considered a shared cultural knowledge expressed as “saluting” pract. The emphasis on “fine” due to its loudness and previous pauses between “very” by the neurologist in line 4 is suspect. This also can be argued because the neurologist has a shared situational knowledge of his client. He knows so much about the health record among others which might have informed his expression. However, it is clear from the interaction that the respondent was the relative of the patient, and such, she could not have been deemed unhealthy, so as to assume that whatever shared situational knowledge has of his patient is generalised and transferred to the relative. At the end of the floor holding “contest”, the neurologist introduces a TRP function in line 8:

N: Oh! Hope you are hearing from P^{SP}?

Through which he successfully holds the floor. Other examples of this can be seen in NPI 5: 1-5; 25: 1-5 and others. One important observation made in the interaction is that the issue of turn-taking and who eventually holds the floor in NPI are common and sometimes settled in the earlier parts of the conversations. This is a veritable reference to the identification of what model an NPI would take. This feature is therefore associated with the paternalistic model of NPI.

4.3.1.4 Psychological acts in paternalistic model

The acts of emotion are psychological. Paternalistic model of NPI, being characterised by “parenting” traits is deeply embedded in emotional strategies. Critics of the

paternalistic model such as Pellegrino (2001, 1987, 1979), argue that “medicine is practice and not theory” therefore “medical morality”. Therefore, issues such as the show of emotion are not necessary in medicine. Rather, medical morality is “constructed from the interaction of three facets of the *healing relationship: the fact of illness, the act of profession, and the right and good healing action for a particular*” (Oprea, 2009:128). To the proponent of the paternalistic model in NPIs, however, it is impossible to define “healing relationship” without a reference to “emotion”. Emotion as a psychological act is therefore recognised as one of the important features of the paternalistic model of ENPI. For example, in NPI 1:1-8:

Excerpt 8

1. P: What they gave me there, I don't understand?
2. N: Ha! It means you have gained some weight (0.2) which is good: When you came earlier, it was 68.
3. P: This morning?::::
4. N: Yes. The first time was 68. Today is also 68. So it's fine. Ha! ((smiles)) that's good it's our own measurement we rely on. The 72 must been an error. Maybe the scale was faulty. It's fine //. So it means you have a steady weight (0.2) that's improvement.
5. P: Thank you sir.
6. N: Now, let me say three words to you. This is what we usually do. And I will ask you by the time we are finishing the interaction to see if you can remember them. The three words are “goat, shoe and broom”
7. P: Goat, shoe and broom
8. N: Not now, I will ask you later whether you'll remember them. That's good!!

emotions are deployed through the pragmatic strategy of “encouraging, empathising”, and through some other politeness strategies. In line 2 above, the neurologist's addition of “which is good”, after a “(0.2)” seconds pause, is an indicator of the momentary display of emotion. Emotion does not necessarily need to be expressed in written symbols or uttered. Mey (2001:94) opines that intention is an ingredient through which the function of a communicative behaviour is determined. In the extract above, patterns of the psychological act (emotion) is also deduced from the “encouraging” pract performed by the neurologist (line 6-8), when the patient makes a pre-emptive attempt at carrying out the “recalling exercise” that was initiated by the neurologist. Further, the

intended emotion is clearly revealed in the subsequent parts of the interaction. See lines 16-32.

4.3.1.5 Physical acts in paternalistic model

“Pragmatic acts engage the whole individual in communication, not just the speech portion of his or her contribution” (Mey, 2001:223). This gives room to the consideration of the total communicative act features. This is where physical acts emanate. The physical act is the description of the “interactive feedbacks”, which is referred to as the “body language”, such as the body move, nodding, eye contact, among other gestures. Some of these are discussed. Example:

Excerpt 9: NPI 37

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 10 years; Patient: male; Age: 73 years; Occupation: Retired civil servant; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Good day Sir
2. P: ((Nods and looks on))
3. N: How are you today? ((looks on))
4. R: No changes
5. N: ((looks through the file)) IT IS the memory, it is still the short term.
6. R: As he was coming home from the church last Sunday. He lost control while driving ((Narrates the scenario)).... So, we rushed him to the hospital. Although there was no injury. He only damaged other cars. Now when he talks, he diverts talks a lot ... But since last month, he has been like this.
7. N: Does he feel dizzy often?
8. P: No sir
9. N: ((Examines the patient's B.P)) Does he still have all the drugs?
10. R: No. It's only these ones are remaining.
11. N: I see that he has done a CT, which shows there were some slight issues when the accident occurred (0.2) But (0.4) Don't worry. He would be fine.
12. R: I pray o.
13. N: He will. I am going to increase his dose. ((writes)). Initially, he was taking 5ml but I've increased it to 10ml.
14. R: For how long are we going to continue using this?
15. N: What I've written for you will cover up to the next time you'll visit us.
16. P: ((Nods))
17. R: Okay. Thank you sir.
18. N: Do you have any other complain? (0.8) Daddy, I'm talking to you. Do you have any other complain?
19. P: ((smiles))
20. N: ((smiling)). He would be fine. Just help him with the drugs. Let's see in four weeks' time.
21. R: Thank you sir.

In the interaction above, there is evidence of body moves as a pragmatic feedback in lines 2, 9, 19 and 20. The first three were performed by the patient, who was incapacitated in adequately expressing himself through spoken utterances. Instead of struggling to speak, despite that he could hear everything the neurologist was saying, he simply resolves into self-help by using the communicative tool available and at his disposal. This feedback was sufficient enough for diagnostic and communicative purposes in the interaction. This is in line with Mey's communicative principle. It is worthy of note that the physiological act as a pragmatic tool is invaluable to the description of the paternalistic communication model in NPI based on the peculiarity of the interactants. In this, the parent relationship to a growing child is a similar example. Such a child who is yet to acquire the speaking skill or is about attaining it will resolve into gesticulation, of which the parent is expected to understand. However, above the literal "parent" assumption, by training and certification, neurologists are equipped with the required knowledge in understanding the various characteristics of patients with speaking incapability such as the one in the context. In this vein, the employment of physiological acts as a pragmatic strategy is construed as a natural phenomenon to neurologists.

4.4 Textual features of paternalistic model

In the exploration of doctor-patient relationship, certain behaviours serve as the contextual features on which particular patterns of communication and behaviours can be described. These behaviours are not governed by the grammatical correctness of the speakers, nor determined by grammatical units of the co-texts. They are however useful for the identification of the praxis performed in each communicative situation. Mey's PCP suffices in the application of co-texts. Therefore, what is important is the understanding of the context by participants in the situated communication. The textual features are captured on the right-hand-side of the praxemic tree (see fig. 2). These represent an expandable list of "elements that are present in the textual chain" in any communicative endeavour. In the discussion of communication models, especially, in allusion to Emanuel and Emanuel's types, some models are more prevalent than the others. Many of these are more prevalent in a consultative model than the others. Some of these are examined in the next sub-sections.

4.4.1 Shared situational knowledge

Shared situational knowledge would refer to the mutual awareness shared by participants in a situated communicational enterprise. It is a reflection of their understanding of the communicative context. In other words, it involves assumptions which the interactants already have about the communicative situation. In the paternalistic model, shared situational knowledge play important roles in the diagnostic and therapeutic objectives of the participants. For example:

Excerpt 10: NPI 26

Context: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: male; Age: 58 years; Occupation: Retired Teacher; Ailment: Broca aphasia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: How are you feeling now?
2. P: Hmm I am:::::::::: i:::::in (0.10) te::
3. N: Can you tell me your name?
4. P: ((opens mouth, shakes his head)) I: ya::am EE:::mm P^{SP} (0.4) ((pronounces the name))
5. N: Good! Why did you initially do like this? Can you tell me again?
6. P: ((tries)) (0.8) hm:: ((then manages to pronounce the name))
7. N: Can you remember when last you came here?
8. P: ha:::
9. N: Can't you remember it?
10. P: *ba*:
11. N: Who is P^{SP}
12. P: My daughter
13. N: Fine! Tell me your name in full
14. P: O:::::y: P^{SP} ((says the name))
15. N: That's a good one.
16. P: Thank:: (0.4) you. ((smiling))
17. N: That's good. You are smiling. Can you tell me where you came from?
18. P: My:: my house.
19. N: ((laughing)) I mean your state of origin
20. P: Be:: be::: nue!
21. N: Great! Now, tell me your name again.
22. P: ((successfully mentions the name but with some difficulty mentions his name))
::::
23. N: Which town do you hail from? It may be where I hail from o. We may hail from the same town.
24. P: ha:::!
25. N: ((waiting for response, then writes and then looks up)) which town do you hail from? You don't remember? If I tell you – if I remember and tell you, I will collect something from you o
26. P: ((smiling)) huh:

27. N: I'm still waiting o. Now, tell me –you hail from which town?
28. P: (points to a direction) ():::
29. N: What is your occupation? You were a lawyer? (is it one child)
30. P: ((Nods in disagreement))
31. N: Teacher?
32. P: Ye ye::: ye::::s
33. N: Okay. You have tried. Where were you before this thing happened?
34. P: La:::g:os
35. N: Sorry. How did it happen? This sickness. How did it happen
36. P: ((feeling discomfort with the questions)) Hiii::::::::::sh ((long hiss))
37. N: Where were you exactly when it happened.
38. P: At:: ((raises hand to describe)) Ik::::::::::
39. N: You were going to have a bath right? You were inside the bathroom then right? You were inside the bathroom
40. P: ((nods))
41. N: ((to the R)) They said he fell at the bathroom right?
42. R: Yes. Bathroom
43. P: When I::: w:was
44. N: Okay.
45. P: I: I::: ((0.8)) fell
46. N: Go on
47. P: ((Nods))
48. N: ((Writes)) You are improving. The last time he was here ((to the R)) you know he could not even remember anything. For his speeches. It is gradual. It will come back. Just let's keep using his drugs. Is the physiotherapist still coming?
49. R: Yes.
50. N: How often?
51. R: Every Wednesday
52. N: And the exercise?
53. R: Yes. We still do it. It's only that he complains sometimes.
54. N: ((To the P)) They said you are not doing your exercise.
55. P: ((frowns and nods))
56. N: We will need it for your rapid improvement o. ((To the R)) Does he allow the therapist?
57. R: He has no choice with that one.
58. N: Okay. Let us keep him on these drugs for now. It is only this one I need to add. He'll get better and better as times go on. ((To the P)) When next you come, I want you to have been better o. So, if they tell me you don't use your drugs or refused to do exercise, we would fight o.
59. N: ((smiling and nodding))
60. R: So, we'll see you ((writes)) in a month's time. Do have a nice weekend sir. ((hands over some files to R)) Give this to the nurse. They will guide you.

Since the knowledge of the patient's situation is known to the neurologist, one is not bordered about the *questioning* pract employed by the doctor in the interaction above. However, the patient's attempt at giving responses to every string of questions posed by the neurologist is an indicator of the shared situational knowledge. The patient in the context assumes that the interaction will lead to the attainment of therapeutic goals, upon

which the interaction thrives. With this in mind, he plays his role actively, despite the difficulty experienced as a result of his ailment. The awareness that his (the patient's) responses or otherwise will help the neurologist in making proper prescription in line with the diagnostic result was a key determinant in the shaping of the communicative behaviour of the patient.

More so, the awareness of the nature of ailment of the patient helped the neurologist to apply a more paternalist posture as he relates with the patient. In line 5, the neurologist made an issue from a particular gesture exhibited by the patient. This is a part of the diagnostic procedure to helping the patient use language, through which more information can be derived towards the attainment of the goal of the interaction. Again in line 11-15, the neurologist continued to make the diagnostic attempt and was elated by the patient efforts in responding to his instruction.

Apart from the aforementioned, the presence of the shared situational knowledge allows interactants to have successful communication. In the extract above, line 25 shows that the neurologist often waited for the patient's response before documenting such. The patient, on the other hand, made a serious effort in ensuring that he carries out the communicative behaviours expected of him despite the difficulty as seen in lines 27-47. Due to shared situational knowledge, the neurologist deployed a practice of "encouraging" on the patient in line 48 up to 60. This is a pointer that there is a mutual understanding between the neurologist and the patient with regards to the successful juxtaposition of the patient's past state of health and the present.

While shared situation knowledge can be more driven by either of the interactants, doctors, in neurologist patient interaction, tend to control how shared situational knowledge is identified. These and other instances, where shared situational knowledge is doctor-driven, apart from the act of merely reading the case note is further examined. For example:

Excerpt 11: NPI 7

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 3 years; Patient: male; Age: 53; Occupation: Pensioner; Ailment: Parkinson; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: how are you
2. P: Thank God sir.
3. N: You did not ask after us since the last time you left.

4. P: = We thank God sir
5. N: Ehen? \$
6. P: We thank God sir
7. N: ((Gets up on the seat, exits)) sorry
8. P: ((Nods and looks on))
9. N: ((returns and sits)) Well-done sir
10. P: Thank you sir
11. N: How is it?
12. P: We're fine sir
13. N: how is your health?
14. P: We thank God
15. N: Well-done
16. P: *yes sir, e se a dupe*
17. N: £ha ha! You are looking great!
18. P: Thank God sir
19. N: £It's good to see you
20. P: Thank you sir
21. N: *E pele*
22. P: Yes sir. *ese gan*
23. N: *yeah e pele =*
24. P: = *e pele e wa joko*;
25. N: Madam has really been taking good care of you)
26. R: *Abi:: ()*
27. N: ((writes)) ((To the R)). He's really improved. His response is far better than before. Don't you see?
28. R: I'm also happy. We just want to make sure we are here based on the previous appointment given.
29. N: That's very good.
30. R: Thank you sir.
31. N: ((writes)) If there is any serious need, I think I'm going to give you three (0.2) No! Four months.
32. R: Okay sir.
33. N: By that time everything must have normalised.
34. R: Thank you sir.
35. N: ((Hands over the prescription note)) So, take care and tell those people to come in. Thank you.

The opening felicities were deliberate by the neurologist, who through this selected “family” feature of paternalistic communication showed that he is well aware of the patient’s situation. The greeting pract employed helped him in the floor holding strategy. At a point in line 7, the doctor exits the consulting room, and upon his return continued to apply the same communication pattern as employed initially. The

13. N: How is your health”, and

15.N: Well-done

are pragmatic signifiers of paternalistic communication strategy. One might have wondered that since the doctor knew the obvious, why was he asking. This is one of the common features of the paternalistic model of communication, which are usually employed for specific further diagnostic and therapeutic purposes.

4.4.2 Shared cultural knowledge

The notion of shared cultural knowledge (SCK) is not listed with regards to Mey's pragmeme. Rather, SCK, is an idea which is "operationally introduced" by Odeunmi (2006:159), with the intention of accounting adequately, for the cultural factor in a communicative context, (see Odeunmi, 2008:78). Due to its significance in hospital communicative outcomes on how meanings are encoded and interpreted, and also what further actions are taken for diagnostic and/or therapeutic goals. Because of its significance to this study, some of the identifiable SCK features are examined. For example:

Excerpt 12: NPI 32

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 7 years; Patient: female; Age: 62 years; Occupation: Retired Civil Servant; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: ((coughing)) My son ((coughs)). I'm lu::cky it's you.
2. N: Good afternoon ma. Mrs P^SP, right?
3. P: Yes Sir
4. N: I'm Dr P_SP. How do you feel now?
5. P: It's about two weeks now that I started feeling the pain on this part (touches the head).
6. N: ((looks through the case file))
7. P: When we came in the ((coughs)) mor:::ning. This is what they gave us.
8. N: Who did you come with?
9. P: My daughter. I have a complain (sic).
10. N: Okay. What is it this time.
11. P: Whenever I sleep, I used to see myself fighting some masquerades. Although, I usually kill them. So when I wake up in the morning, I used to have shaking body. Even, I won't be able to get up from bed sometimes. I will just be shaking throughout the day.
12. N: How often have you been having such dreams and the shaking too?
13. P: For the past one week.
14. N: ((smiles)) Have you been sleeping well lately?
15. P: Em Hmm (0.8) It's not that I don't sleep *naa o*
16. N: What time do you normally go to bed.
17. P: You know true true (0.4), I used to struggle before sleep can come. And may be because of that drug you said we should not use again.
18. N: Which one is that?

19. P: That small one. Hmmm. I think it's (the name of the drug was mentioned by the neurologist)
20. N: But you have not answered my question o. I said what time do you normally sleep?
21. P: I don't know. But em (0.2).
22. N: Okay. Tell me what happens between seven to ten o'clock in your house.
23. P: Nothing used to happen o.
24. N: Okay. When do you eat your dinner usually?
25. P: Hmmm::::: Around 9.30
26. N: 9.30?
27. P: Yes. You know my children close late.
28. N: So until they come, no food?
29. P: Not like that but that time is good for all of us.
30. N: Mama! *Se'fe gbo oto oro?*
31. P: Sir?
32. N: Do you know what? (0.8) Okay. When you finish eating, what do you do?
33. P: I watch television with my children until sleep come (sic)
34. N: What television station is that?
35. P: Africa Magic
36. N: Which of them?
37. P: Igbo and Yoruba
38. N: Okay. (smiles) Like how many films do you normally watch before you go to bed?
39. P: You know those plays are very interesting o.
40. N: Mama! Okay. So you'll watch up to two or three?
41. P: ((laughs))
42. N: Answer me mama.
43. P: Is it because of that?
44. N: You see. Mama, all we told you not to do is what you have been doing.
45. P: No oo
46. N: You are not helping yourself with good rest. The time you sleep is too late. You should be eating early too. Why don't you come with any of your children today?
47. P: They didn't give them chance (sic) at work.
48. N: You know what we'll do? (0.8) ((looks straight into the woman's eyes. Then writes)) Em (0.8). That's it ((hands over the prescriptions note)). Tell them to get you those drugs. Tell P^{SP} to call me. When can they come with you to this clinic?
49. P: I don't know sir.
50. N: I need them to come with you when next you are coming.
51. P: They will try.
52. N: Let them not try o. If you want those things you dreamt of to die *patapata*, they must follow you when next you are coming.
53. P: How many?
54. N: Any one of them. Especially P^{SP}.
55. P: Thank you sir. I will tell them to call you.
56. N: Okay ma. We should see you in three weeks. Please tell the next person to enter.

In the excerpt above, the patient has approached the clinic with a complaint of a cough. She observes the cultural felicity by initiating a greeting with the neurologist, in the

opening line, she has referred to the neurologist as “my son” (line 1). This expresses a cultural phenomenon of oneness which is an “associating” pract. The patient complements her show of emotion with an “appreciating” pract which signifies her fulfilment to have had the privilege of being assigned to the neurologist in this interaction. The neurologist understands the context of which the phrase, “my son” was used. However, the shared cultural behaviour being championed by the patient is punctured by the neurologist, with the use of “distancing” pract through polite pract of “naming” and rhetorical questioning in line 2 “Good afternoon ma. Mrs P^{SP}”. This is further corroborated in the unusual self-introduction by the doctor in line 4:

N: I’m Dr P_sP. How do you feel now?

The previous information from the interaction is an index that he is well-known and recognised by the patient. The pract of distancing is deliberately evoked. This shows that shared cultural knowledge is capable of being used as a pract of associating or distancing.

Furthermore, in the course of the diagnosis, there are linguistic items to show that there is a close link between shared cultural knowledge and shared situational knowledge. For example, the distancing pract employed by the neurologist at the outset of the interaction is purposeful, so as to deploy the paternalistic model of interaction in the NPI. For example, the neurologist has to code-switch in line 30, so as to give a frank talk to the patient, having identified the possible causes of the patient’s previous complaints.

Through this pract, the neurologist is able to control and dictate the pattern of the NPI by evoking the practs of asserting, commanding, and instructing, all which are common features of the paternalistic communication model.

4.5 Pragmatic acts in the paternalistic model of the NPI

On the pragmeme tree, there are the activity and the textual nodes. The practs performed by each of them are identified as choices utilised by each interactant in the paternalistic model of the NPI. These are presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1: Practs utilised by neurologist in paternalistic model of NPI

Neurologist’s activity pattern	Practs
--------------------------------	--------

Speech acts	declaring, informing, promising, instructing, ordering, dictating, controlling, inquiring, counselling
Conversational acts	dialoguing, turn-taking, floor-holding, role-playing, controlling
Psychological acts	parenting, persuading, empathising, encouraging, persuading, leading
Physical act	smiling, laughing, frowning, clapping, illustrating, demonstrating,

From the Table 4.1. above, the neurologists in the NPIs employ practs such as declaring, informing, promising, instructing, ordering and others. These were generated from the speech acts activity. They, for example, seen in many of the NPIs. The extracts below from NPI 18 (earlier in excerpt 2) buttress the neurologists' choice of these practs, especially in the paternalistic model:

Excerpt 13:

60. N: Yes! The Prestor is over-working we'll have to stop it. All your lipids are low. All that can cause it.
61. R: And so the dose
62. N: Yes. Any derailment in the body chemistry can result in this. The Prestors (0.4) there is no need. We must stop all the Prestors. All and, (0.2) lipid agents. You don't need them. I think maybe the effect of drug and maybe the viral thing caused what you saw. Here it is showing everything was low. Too low. Your cholesterol is 107. Normally, it should be like 180. Something below 200 will be fine. Your (...) is normal, that one is great. That's great. But HDL which is the one that is a good one. That is the one that keeps the blood vessel and all that. It's low! We want it to be high. So, usually. How to treat that is do some exercise and drink red wine.
63. R: Red wine? Isn't that alcoholic?
64. N: A glass of red wine. Usually, that will make a difference. But LDL is low too 62. It means that both high cholesterol and very low cholesterol are bad. High cholesterol will cause clogging. When it is too low, it means the blood vessel are thin and can break easily. So the Presto has to be stopped. (0.8) And give him a glass of red wine. That would help. And do some exercise around the house. The next is the electrolyte imbalance which seems to have been corrected.
65. R: Has it been corrected?
66. N: Yes. This one, sodium is 144, it was 125 here. He should just eat a little salt in his meals. If there is no salt at all. That's not good for you. All these will affect brain function. Slokay will correct that one.

Moreover, conversational acts produce practs of dialoguing, turn taking, floor holding, controlling and so on. See all NPIs in appendix IV.

The promising, pacifying, empathising, instructing and others were generated from the psychological acts in the paternalistic. Examples are seen in the extracts from NPI 1 as in:

Excerpt 14:

- 14. N: Your recall is coming back.
- 15. P: Thank you Sir.
- 16. Neu: What are the three words I told you earlier? You'll need to remember
- 17. P: Hmm ... Em: : : br::oom
- 18. N: Yes !! One.
- 19. P: Shoe
- 20. N: £ Two! Excellent
((Applause by R))
- 21. N: What is the third one?
- 22. P: Excuse Sir.
- 23. N: Yes. Because during your first time here (0.4) But say the third one first.
- 24. NP: Broom, shoe, hmm, hmm! Ha! ((disappointed in self))
- 25. N: You tried! Goat.
- 26. P: Goat!
- 27. N: You tried. So, the last time you couldn't remember any.
- 28. P: Oh oh
- 29. N: Now that you can recall two out of three. That's great! That's the only way we can measure improvement. So, you are doing well. You are really making progress...

Concerning the physical acts, the following practs were produced. These are, laughing, frowning, clapping among others. The applause in the text which is preceded by the continuous talk and smile of the neurologist is represented with “£” (see list of notations in the preliminary section). The applause is to encourage the patient in his bid to carry out the task given by the neurologist. Eventually, this is achieved. Other examples are found in the extracts above, especially from lines 21 to 30. The extracts below, taken from NPI 27:20 shows the excitement derived from the patient's success in the given task by the neurologist. This is represented by the laughter in The “\$” by the laughter in the voice of the neurologist as seen in line 50 of NPI 27:

N: You can see that I said three months, I don't say you should rush him. So that you'll not give him food again o \$.

Table 4.2: Practs utilised by patients' in the paternalistic model of NPI

Patient's activity pattern	Practs
----------------------------	--------

Speech acts	hoping, appreciating
Conversational acts	listening, responding, dialoguing
Psychological acts	observing, obeying
Physical act	nodding, pointing, exercising

Table 4.2 above presents the activity choices utilised by patients' in the paternalistic model of NPI. Hoping and appreciating were identified as patient's practs in speech act activity. They are employed at the beginning of the interaction as a means of exchanging a pleasantry with the neurologists but are prominent in the closing part of the communication. There are many examples of these in the observed interactions. A few from NPI 25 are extracted below:

Excerpt 15:

26. N: Okay. ((hands the prescription over to patient)) You will ask someone to help you get the drug at that place and make sure you use them as I told you. One in the morning and one at night.

27. P: Thank you sir.

28. N: You are welcome. Greet your people for me.

29. P: Thank you sir.

In NPI 1, this belongs to the phatic communication category as in:

30. P: I' m grateful. ((smiles)) You have a very big passion for work.

Also, From NPI 33, the following are exchanged:

46. N: You'll have to try and get the drugs we asked you to buy before now. It's after then that we can then say this or that.

47. P: And the test?

48. N: You'll do it and make sure you bring me the results before my shift is over. You'll buy these ones though ((hands over the written prescription))

49. R: Do we need to queue again?

50. N: Not really, just tell whoever you see that you want to give me your results.

51. P: Thank you sir".

The above helps the patient in entrusting care about her ailment to the neurologist. This is a frequent scenario in most of the observed interactions.

Moreover, from the Table, it can be deduced that conversational acts produce practs of listening, responding and dialoguing. All observed interactions also followed this pattern. There are, however, different practs performed in each of them. Some of them that were

non-verbal were aided by the relatives of the patient as they pract dialoguing while the patient pract both listening and responding. An example of this is found in NPI 4. See appendix IV for details.

The following practs: nodding, pointing, smiling, and exercising were observed as physical acts' activity from the perspective of the patients. All these are expected and are regular practs in the paternalistic model.

Table 4.3: Contextual choices utilised by neurologists in paternalistic model of NPI

Neurologist's textual pattern	Practs
Inference	studying, observing, requesting
Reference	diagnosing, listening, questioning and re-questioning, speculating
Relevance	relating, clarifying, prescribing
Voice	authorising, parenting, guarding, instructing, controlling, commanding, demanding
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	distancing, associating, identifying, pacifying, promising, prescribing, recognising, greeting

On Table 4.3. above, the contextual choices utilised by neurologists in the model under discussion are presented. In this, studying (of patients' case notes), observing, and requesting were employed as practs in the contextual inference. This is visible in NPI 4, from lines 18 to 27:

Excerpt 16:

- 18. N: I understand. So, he missed out the other exams?
- 19. R: Yes. He even pass well at the NECO.
- 20. N: That's good. So what have you done since then?
- 21. sR: We have prayed?
- 22. N: Prayed? You have taken him to some places?

- 23. P: Yes. They said...
- 24. N: It's spiritual?
- 25. R: Yes sir. They even said we should...
- 26. N: Go spiritual? Oh I see. ((looks through the case note)) But you were here sometimes last year. Why did you not come back for the follow-up?
- 27. R: It's a long story sir.

Furthermore, diagnosing, listening, questioning and re-questioning were recognised as practs employed in reference. Moreover, practs of relating (to known information on the patient), clarifying and prescribing were identified in relevance. The voice of the neurologist, in the NPIs of the paternalistic model, accounted for the practs of authorising, parenting, guarding, controlling, commanding and demanding. An example can be found as the interactions begin, but the voice, practicing authorising is common in the issuance of next appointment day by the neurologists to their patients. Reflecting on the example extracted from NPI 33:49-52:

Excerpt 17:

- 49. R: Do we need to queue again?
- 50. N: Not really, just tell whoever you see that you want to give me your results.
- 51. P: Thank you sir.
- 52. N: It's okay.

it can be discovered that for any of Shared Situational, Shared Cultural Knowledge or Shared Personality Knowledge, the identifiable practs employed by neurologists are those of distancing, associating, identifying, prescribing, recognising, greeting. Another example of SSK-based identifying pract is also seen in NPI 4, lines 22 to 26 as seen below:

Excerpt 18:

- 1. N: Prayed? You have taken him to some places?
- 2. P: Yes. They said...
- 3. N: It's spiritual?
- 4. R: Yes sir. They even said we should...
- 5. N: Go spiritual? Oh I see. ((looks through the case note)) But you were here sometimes last year. Why did you not come back for the follow-up?

Moreover, the expression "Go spiritual? Oh I see" has a significant impact on the role of SSK and the attendant practs deployed.

To discuss the utilisation of the associating pract, NPI 31 lines 51 to 52 are extracted

Excerpt 19:

51. P: Eh Ehn. Help me put it. Thank you, Sir. How about all my children?
52. N: They are all fine ma.

The above example supports the assumption in the SSK. Based on the data consulted during this research and confirmation from the neurologist in the excerpt, there was no family relationship between the patient and neurologist. The question and response between the interactants is a reflection of the mutual cultural values in the situated communication. The patient's question would have dazzled some other interactant without the shared knowledge of the context. This situation buttresses the impact of culture on any discourse situation and the importance of the mutual understanding of interactants about the norms of the culture.

Regarding dissociating pract, some examples suffice:

Excerpt 20: NPI 32:1-4

1. P: ((coughing)) My son ((coughs)). I'm lu::cky it's you.
2. N: Good afternoon ma. Mrs P^SP, right?
3. P: Yes Sir
4. N: I'm Dr P_SP. How do you feel now?

In the extract above, the patient has used the pract of associating, but the neurologist who did not want to be involved in the association employs some other practs. First, he employs greeting pract, a politeness strategy which is useful as a face-saving pract. Then, he graduated into the pract of naming or recognising, which was veiled in questioning pract. Having succeeded in doing these, he was able to finally dissociate himself by employing the pract of introducing (himself), a rare pract in neurologist-patient interaction. Dissociating pract in other observed NPIs were also employed when neurologists do not want to go beyond their statutory duties, irrespective of the pattern of communication adopted. An example is extracted from 3:59-66 to support this:

Excerpt 21:

59. R₂: Sir, I want to find out about the socks thing. I saw people using it. Do we need to buy it?
60. No o o! I mean (0.8) you can buy it. It's a pressure socks.
61. R₂: You'll give us a measurement.
62. N: There's a house officer to do that.
63. R₁: I hope they will sir?
64. N: It's their job. They will.

In some other arguments in pragmatics, the statement extracted from NPI 17:29 below can be perceived as a dissociating pract:

Excerpt 22:

28: N: You are welcome. Greet your people for me

The neurologist intended to pract greeting as a form of politeness, but the manner of which it was said in the frame of SSK is suspect. The question that arose was why did the neurologist choose the phrase “your people” rather than my people? The latter would have captured the shared cultural knowledge very aptly if so. However, the argument may not be tenable outside SSK, SSC or SPK. Other may also perceive this as an associating pract, even when the co-texts have been considered.

Since grammaticality is not a basis for solving pragmatic puzzles, excerpt 22 is considered best as both dissociating as well as associating pract in the context of SSK, SCK and the SPK in the studied NPI.

Table 4.4: Contextual choices utilised by patients’ in paternalistic model of NPI

Patient’s textual pattern	Practs
Inference	Narrating
Reference	narrating, explaining, complaining, provoking
Relevance	narrating, mentioning
Voice	submitting, subordinating
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	associating, identifying, describing, recognising, greeting

The Table in 4.4. above shows the contextual choices utilised by patients’ in the paternalistic model of NPI. By implication, co-texts of inference were reflected in the narrating practs of most of the patients. This is visible in virtually all the studied NPIs with slight differences. See appendix IV for more, however, some of the examples are extracted from NPI 18 with focus on lines 8 to 36.

Excerpt 23: NPI 18

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 4 years; Patient: female; Age: 26 years; Occupation: Student; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: When last were you here?
2. P: Last week
3. N: Okay ((reads through the case note)). But you were not given any appointment for today.
4. P: Yes. It's because I feel I need to come quickly.
5. N: So what brought you?
6. P: It's this thing again.
7. N: What's that? Oh! (0.2) Okay.
8. P: Last week Monday, as I was just about going to see my aunt in her shop.
9. N: You fell?
10. P: They said I fell.
11. N: Since that time have you experience it again?
12. P: No o. But this morning, I started having that feeling again.
13. N: That you'll have it again?
14. P: Yes.
15. N: The drugs we gave you to buy, did you get them?
16. P: I did. But since that thing has gone. I...
17. N: You don't use them again?
18. P: No! I used them. It's that other one I don't like to use.
19. N: Ehn ((writes)). Do you bring the pack?
20. P: Here is it.
21. N: Is it this one you said you don't like ((picks out the sachet))?
22. P: Hm... ehm ((0.4) it makes me to...
23. N: Feeling dizzy?
24. P: And as if I want to vomit too.
25. N: Apart from that what else?
26. P: Hm...: Nothing.
27. N: Tell me how you normally use this.
28. P: ((collects it from N)) It's twice a day.
29. N: What time of the day?
30. P: I used to use it (sic) in the morning after eating.
31. N: What time do you normally eat in the morning?
32. P: May be around 10 *sha*.
33. N: Why
34. P: Me I don't used to like (sic) eating too early o.
35. N: Okay. But do you know you are not helping us?
36. P: I am sorry ma.

(see NPI 18 in appendix IV for the complete conversation.)

Like in other NPIs, patients utilise narrating practs in expressing their challenges, and in some cases, worldviews. All these are considered necessary by patients for the diagnosis of their ailments and also in achieving proper therapeutic objectives. In a paternalistic model, patients may feel secure and comfortable even if it is their privacy they are

sharing with the neurologist. More of these are seen across some of the observed NPIs. For examples, see NPIs 16:10-17, 24:3-9 and some others in appendix IV.

4.6 Application of the informative model

The informative model in the description of the communication pattern of doctor-patient relationship is categorised as an essentialist type (Oprea, 2009:128). The proponents of this model argue that “the internal morality of medicine” should be guided by “the ethical principle of beneficence”. In fact, scholars in this school of thought, such as Pellegrino (1979), Miller and Brody (2001) and many others, suggest that all doctor-patient relationship should avoid “paternalism”, that is, the paternalistic model. Rather, the medical practice should sustain its “scientific, engineering or consumer” status with regards to physicians’ interaction with patients. This can be regarded a formalist approach. The goal of a formal communicative endeavour is that each of the participants plays his or her own role as honest and objective as much as possible towards the attainment of the communicative goal. In this approach, no other pragmatic expectations, more than the ethical requirements of the profession are necessary.

The proponents of informative model maintain that the model assumes a fairly clear distinction between facts and values. This suggests that patients’ values are well defined and known, what the patient lacks and need is facts, (Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992:6). In other words, physician’s role is to provide all the available facts, while the patient controls what treatments are to be given from the facts available. Oprea (2009:129-130) explains that “the informative model attempts to give patients an absolute control and responsibilities in health care decisions” and that the responsibilities of doctors are “limited to providing factual information about medical interventions” so that patients can “select the intervention that best suits their values and interests”. An attempt is, therefore, made in this study, to investigate the informative model of communication in university teaching hospitals in the South-west region of Nigeria. This is carried out in the succeeding subsections.

4.6.1 Activity type in the informative model

Following the theoretical framework adopted for this study, consideration of activity in the informative model of communication in NPI will include speech acts, conversational patterns, among others. These are therefore explored.

4.6.1.1 Speech acts in the informative model

In the observed NPIs, some of the strategies adopted are actual violations to the tenets of the informative model. In fact, there are scant cases of an exclusively isolated model of informative NPI in the studied location. However, there are some instances where neurologists intentionally adhered strictly to these principles. Examining the given NPI 13 below:

Excerpt 24: NPI 13

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: undisclosed; Patient: female;
Age: 47 years; Occupation: Self-employed; Ailment: Migraine; Visitation status:
accompanied by a relation

1. P: Good afternoon sir.
2. N: Good afternoon madam.
3. P: I have done the test ((searches her bag)).
4. N: Okay. ((Nodding and looks on, waiting for the result))
5. P: These are them (sic) sir. ((Hands the papers and other documents to the N))
6. N: Oh! Okay. ((Nodding)) Yes.
7. P: What is that sir?
8. N: Em.. the record with us shows that you have been visiting this clinic for about two years and em (0.4) six weeks now. Also, you used to be treated for recurrent headache. Now all those have stopped for a moment. But you complained last week. That was why you were asked to do those tests.
9. P: And what is in the result sir?
10. N: It's your right to know. I'm going to tell you one by one. Now. This brain that we use is made up of many specialised areas that work together. The cortex controls the cortical activity. You see (0.4) that outermost layer of brain cells. It is here ((raises the CT scan higher against the equipment). Thinking and voluntary movements begin from here. So, basic functions like breathing and sleep are controlled here ((pointing to a part in the scan result)). So when this thing keeps recurring, our options are (0.8) give me a second (long pause. goes). ((powers on the computer)). Do you normally vomit?
11. P: Yes
12. N: What about when they put on the light?
13. P: Yes. I get disturbed. I used to sleep everyday with light off. I don't allow anybody to (put) on the light at all.
14. N: You (0.2) are al::so sensitivity (0.4) to light ((writes)). When they play music *nko*? Especially loud one?
15. P: I don't like it at all
16. N: You don't like it or it affects you?
17. P: Yes
18. N: It gives you Yes, serious headaches?
19. P: Yes.

20. N: Trig::ger (0.4). Light, sound ((silent)). Migraine. ((writes and talks))
Sensitivity to sound:::. Ok.
21. P: ((Cuts in)) Sir?
22. N: Em.. em.. This is it. In this situation, ((busy with the computer, probably reading from it)) (0.8) since it's a recurring one, which actually is a proof that you have em... em (0.4) Migraine. You have to find a way of stopping the triggers. That is one. Two. You must be getting enough sleep. I mean enough sleep. Then you will also have to reduce stress for yourself. You must cultivate the habit of (0.8). Look here ma!
23. P: I am with you
24. N: What did I say last?
25. P: You said I should look here.
26. N: And before then?
27. P: That I should (0.8) reduce stress.
28. N: I just need to be sure you are fully involved in this. Okay. As I was saying, you will need to make it a duty of drinking plenty of water. It's good for your health. There are some certain food you'll need to avoid. Do you react to any?
29. P: I can't remember. I don't think so? Except okraw.
30. N: You may have to avoid that too. Do you ever have time for exercise?
31. P: Exercise? I walk a lot. To my place of work.
32. N: Not that one. You may have to dedicate special time for exercise, either early in the morning or in the evening. I mean moderate exercise. Then you must always have a bath after doing it. That is if you want o!
33. P: But what about drugs?
34. N: Yes. All those will complement any drug we prescribe here. But you have a choice to make in making sure that you observe all those things I told you.
35. P: All of them are compulsory.
36. N: Are you asking me.
37. P: No. I mean they are compulsory. I will try.
38. N: That will be fine. ((writes prescriptions)). So you may need to buy this.
39. P: What if I continue the Aspirin?
40. N: No. You cant't use Aspirin when you have ulcer. Just continue with the drugs we prescribed. Do you have any other comment?
41. P: No sir
42. N: Any reservation?
43. P: No
44. N: Alright. When will you like to come again?
45. P: Do I need to come?
46. N: Except you have any complaints.
47. P: Okay.
48. N: You can go now. ((Patient gets up and exit))

it can be seen that the interaction above presents different practs that are identifiable in the speech acts pattern of the informative model. Deductions from the excerpt above are further classified below in this section.

(a) Use of the practs of presenting, alerting and declaring in the informative model

The extract above offers insight into the practs of “presenting and alerting” as choices in the informative model of communication of some NPIs. For example, in line 10:

N: It’s your right to know. I’m going to tell you one by one.

the neurologist employs alerting or informing pract in situated speech acting. Mey refers to this as a situation in communication, where the specific verb that depict the action being performed is employed (see Mey, 2001:105). In the interaction above, the patient had evoked the pract of inquiring in a pattern of an indirect speech acting, in line 9:

P: And what is in the result, sir?

as a reaction to the psychological delay, she seems to be experiencing due to the neurologist’s deployment of pract of informing, which is performed in line 8. Further, the declaring pract which often coalesces with informing pract then gives a vivid picture of the speech act strategy in the informative model of the observed NPI. This is exemplified in the example above, line 10, where the neurologist relies on the informing strategy by going into some series of lectures (as an expert). Then the patient listens:

10. N: ... Now. This brain that we use is made up of many specialised areas that work together. The cortex controls the cortical activity. You see (0.4) that outermost layer of brain cells...Thinking and voluntary movements begin from here...

Although it would appear that the patient was passive at this time, pragmatic evidence shows that she was fully at alert, practicing listening in the process of the mini-presentation by the neurologist. The scenario thus affirms the description of the pattern of communication in the informative model, based on what the uttered “words did”. Pellegrino’s insistence on respect for patient autonomy, which is incorporated by the ethical principle of beneficence is advanced in the communicative context. Here, the neurologist understands the need for patient’s value, (knowing, so as to choose from the best options). As a result, he meticulously engages the patient in the diagnosis. At a point, when it appears that the patient was about allowing her own value eroded, the neurologist alerted her in line 22, emphasis in bold:

Excerpt 25:

22. N: Em.. em.. This is it. In this situation, ((busy with the computer, probably reading from it)) (0.8) since it’s a recurring one, which actually is a proof that you have em... em (0.4) Migraine. You have to find a way of stopping the triggers. That is one. Two. You must be getting enough sleep. I mean enough

sleep. Then you will also have to reduce stress for yourself. You must cultivate the habit of (0.8). **Look here ma!**

23. P: I am with you

24. N: **What did I say last?**

25. P: You said I should look here.

26. N: **And before then?**

27. P: That I should (0.8) reduce stress.

28. N: **I just need to be sure you are fully involved in this.** Okay.

In addition, the scholarly perception of physicians as “competent technical experts” is enhanced by the speech acts strategy exhibited by the neurologist in the speech situation above.

(b) Practs of expressing, controlling, and selecting in informative model

On the other hand, going by excerpt 24, the patient employs some speech acts strategies that have the potentiality of control. The strategy shows her no lack of activity in the communication. Major proponents of consultative communication models have called for greater patients’ participation in their relationship with physicians. Succinctly, as Emanuel and Emanuel (p.8) put it:

In recent decades, there has been a call for greater patient autonomy or, as some have called it “patient sovereignty” conceived as patient choice and control over medical decisions. This shift towards the informative model is embodied in the adoption of business terms for medicine, as when physicians are described as health care providers and patients as consumers

In line 9 of excerpt 24, the patient exhibited the pract of expressing as she requested to know “what is in the result”, of which the neurologist declared the “patient sovereignty” as “it’s your (the patient) right to know”, similar conferment of autonomy was also deployed as a pract from lines 30 to 38 of the same excerpt. The emphatic use of “may” by the neurologist is an indication of the neurologist recognition of the patient’s autonomy as seen in these extracts, emphasis in bold:

30. N: **You may have** to avoid that too. Do you ever have time for exercise?

31. P: Exercise? I walk a lot. To my place of work.

32. N: Not that one. **You may have** to dedicate special time for exercise, either early in the morning or in the evening. I mean moderate exercise. Then you must always have a bath after doing it. That is if you want o!
33. P: But what about drugs?
34. N: Yes. All those will complement any drug we prescribe here. **But you have a choice to make in making sure that you observe all those things I told you.**
35. P: All of them are compulsory.
36. N: Are you asking me.
37. P: No. I mean they are compulsory. I will try.
38. N: That will be fine. ((writes prescriptions)). **So you may need** to buy this.

The implication from the situated communication above is that patient was not ordered nor commanded to do anything, rather, the neurologist, within the purview of the informative model simply utilises the pract of *suggesting*. Thus, it behoves on the patient to take a decision he or she considers best towards the fulfilment of the diagnostic and therapeutic goal.

Other instances of speech acting in the interaction, such as controlling, expressing and selecting are seen in lines 23, 25 and 27 respectively. In lines patient's practs of deciding is visible in 35 and 37:

35. P: **All of them are compulsory.**

36. N: Are you asking me.

37. P: No. **I mean they are compulsory. I will try.**

In the above, the patient expresses her selection of the choices put before her and thus makes a commitment to play her part towards the therapeutic goal of the interaction. This is understood by both actors in the interaction. In this context, the understanding of pragmatic marker is established between them. According to Zienkowski, Ostman and Verschueren (2011:8), pragmatic markers “assist in the (inter)subjective establishment of coherence” that is, “they comment on the utterance and thus assist in the interpretation of the utterance”. However, the strict adherence to the interpretive communication in the context above is capable of discouraging the patient from making more comments and other enquiries possible. This is co-indexed in line 39 but becomes subtle in 40 going by the neurologist use of words. The proponents of interpretive model warn that technical specialisation is important in the deployment of this model in doctor-patient interaction. Also, it is said that “physicians may unwittingly impose their own values under the guise of articulating the patient’s values. And patients overwhelmed by their medical condition and uncertain of their own views may too easily accept this imposition”. This appears to

be playing out in lines 34-39 but was quickly adjusted in line 40 when the doctor asked if the patient had “any other comment”. Going further, in the identification of the speech act pattern in the informative model, discursive conversational pattern plays a significant role. This is considered in the next sub-section.

4.6.1.2 Discourse strategies in the informative model

The pattern of conversation in the informative model of NPI is mainly formal. The excerpt below from NPI 14, lines 1 to 61 offer some insights:

Excerpt 26: NPI 14

Background information: Neurologists: (two) females; Experience: 1 year; Patient: female; Age: 54 years; Occupation: Trader; Ailment: Panic attack; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Are you Mrs. P^SP?
2. P: Yes ma
3. N: What is your occupation?
4. P: I am a trader
5. N: What do you sell?
6. P: Clothes?
7. N: Okay. What is it that is disturbing you?
8. P: I dey always shock.
9. N₁: You are always shocked?
10. Yes ma
11. N₁: How do you mean you dey always shock?
12. R: The issue ma is that when any small thing happen, mummy behaves somehow?
13. N₁: Feel somehow? Do you mean she does not behave well?
14. R: Not like that. The thing makes her to be easily afraid (sic).
15. N₂: Wait. You need to tell us exactly what you say she is doing.
16. R: Okay ma. You see, when people shout outside, mummy will suddenly fear.
17. N₂: You mean she gets frightened so often?
18. R: She is always afraid (sic)
19. N₁: She is always afraid?
20. R: Afraid. She is always afraid
21. N₂: Apart from shout outside, does she feel any pain or discomfort in her body?
22. R: Yes. Sometimes headache will be doing her. She will not sleep.
23. N₁: Who are you to her?
24. R: Son
25. N₁: Where are you living before now?
26. R: Before mummy came back?
27. N₁: Came back from where?

28. R: She used to stay in the abroad.
 29. N₁: Oh! Okay. Where was she?
 30. R: Libya
 31. N₁: Madam, your son said you used to live in Libya
 32. P: Yes
 33. N₁: Where in Libya do you lived?
 34. P: Tripoli
 35. N₁: When did you come back to Nigeria?
 36. P: When dem killed Gaddafi
 37. N₂: That must be after the war
 38. N₁: Something like that. Ma, how and why did you come back.
 39. P: The government brought us back.
 40. N₁: It's okay. *Oga* ((referring to the relation)) when this fear-fear happens, does her body shake?
 41. R: Yes ma o. In fact, she would shake for hours.
 42. N₁: When last did she experience this?
 43. R: The day after yesterday.
 44. N₂: But when did you start noticing this?
 45. P: Around the time she came back. Even sef, we think (sic) that it was change of environment.
 46. N₁: Okay. So, what did you do about it?
 47. R: Our pastor prayed for her.
 48. N₂: She went for deliverance?
 49. R: Ehn. It was when we became worried that we took her there. When the church in our backyard are doing their night vigil. Mummy would just wake up and start running about the house.
 50. N₁: That was when?
 51. R: It's been long but when I see that it is like as if, as if, as if
 52. N₂: Like going mental
 53. R: Ehn ehn. That was why we say we should take her to hospital.
 54. N₂: How long was she at the church?
 55. R: It may be up to two years.
 56. N₂: Two years?
 57. R: Yes. Our brother abroad say that we must bring her here.
 58. N₁: ((To the other neurologist)) This is Panic Disorder.
 59. N₂: Yes. She must have been affected by the experience of the war.
 60. N₁: The violence and all trauma.
 61. R: Ma?

(Complete conversation in NPI 14 of appendix IV)

From the excerpt above, lines 1-6 appear as diversionary. The occupation of the patient is inquired alongside the specific nature of the goods or services she renders. All these preceded the main diagnostic question in line 7. However, in the consideration of Mey's pragmatic acts, the preceding texts are co-texts that provide relevance to the other discussion as discovered in lines 62-100. Thus, the interaction represents the use of the institutional talks in NPI. Moreover, the exchange also exhibits the use of adjacency pair (a kind of routine conversation where the respondent gives his/her response in polarity or

in short phrases or sentences). Although this discourse strategy is most common within the informative communication model in the observed SWUTHs, it is also a possible feature in other models.

4.6.1.3 Psychological acts in the informative model

The assumption in informative communication model is that physicians are scientist or engineer. Therefore, the role expected of the physician in the consultation should not be based on emotion or empathy. This features in interaction NPI 34: 15-29 below:

Excerpt 27: NPI 34

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 9 years; Patient: female; Age: 36 years; Occupation: Artisan; Ailment: Post-concussive syndrome; Visitation status: accompanied by two relations

1. N: Sorry
2. R: Yes sir
3. N: What did you say happened to him?
4. R: He was involved in an accident
5. N: When was that?
6. R: May 1
7. N: This year?
8. R: Yes. It was here we brought him at the other ward. But when the strike started, we were discharged and went to a private hospital.
9. N: Is it ward 12?
10. R: Up there. When we got home. He started causing trouble. He said he was going to Ado.
11. N: Where do you live?
12. P: Aramoko. So when he speaks, he forgets things.
13. N: Let's leave the story. Why did he come here today? Why were you referred? Does he forget things? In this place, we are physicians. We are not plumber. We are into medicine. That you give this and that. Anything affecting the brain is what we treat. That he forgets things easily, right?
14. R: Yes
15. N: Apart from that, what else does he do?
16. R: When we are talking, he would be saying something else.
17. N: Out of context. Okay. ((calls the name of the patient)) *Bawo ni? Pele. Ise wo lo'nse.* (How are you? What is your occupation?)
18. P: Welder
19. N: *Ki'le je laaro yi?* (What did you eat this morning?)
20. P: *Isu* (Yam)
21. N: *Isu ati kini?* (Yam and what?)
22. P: *At'eyin* (And egg)
23. N: ((To the relations)) Is he correct?
24. R: No. He ate beans.
25. N: *Isu l'oje abi?* You ate yam right? *Wo won.* Look at them. *Bawo l'ose je si'yin?* Who are they to you?
26. P: My mummy
27. N: Your mummy? And him. *At'awon naa?*

28. P: Daddy *mi*.

29. N: Where do you live? *Kini address adugbo yin l'Aramoko?* (What's your street address at Aramoko?)

(Complete interaction in NPI 34 in appendix IV)

In the extract above, it can be understood that the patient appears to be straying away in the interaction. Any factor could have been responsible for this. Besides, the neurologist is fully aware of this possibility, especially with a patient diagnosed with migraine. The physician, in a bid to observe the informative communicative goal, ensures that the attention of the patient remains focused on the information he (the neurologist) was passing across. This is revealed in lines 22 to 28 "...look here ma... what did I say last... (and)... I just need to be sure you are involved in this"... The indices that are derivable from the extracts confirms the consumer-client posture of the neurologist to the patient. It should be noted that *frowning* was employed as a pragmatic act to retain the client's attention in this interaction.

Similarly, in the excerpt below which is extracted from NPI 14, lines 58 to 73;

Excerpt 28

58. N₁: ((To the other neurologist)) This is Panic Disorder.

59. N₂: Yes. She must have been affected by the experience of the war.

60. N₁: The violence and all trauma.

61. R: Ma?

62. N₁: Well. Your mum is affected by a mental illness that we call "Panic Disorder". This affects a person to experience repeated, unexpected panic attacks and persistent anxiety about the possibility that the panic attacks will reoccur (sic).

63. R: Ha!

64. N₁: Don't shout. See, that panic attack comes with intense fear, apprehension, or discomfort.

65. N₁: When it happens, it usually comes without warning. For you to know. You'll notice she sometimes have her heart beating so fast. Madam, do you find it difficult breathing sometimes?

66. P: Sometimes. I won't be able to breath down.

67. N₂: That's shortness of breath.

68. N₁: Do you sometimes fear you are going crazy, or you lose control?

69. R: That's our fears.

70. P: I reject it in Jesus name.

71. N₂: But do you feel scared that your enemies want you to go mad?

72. P: Yes and they would fail always in Jesus name.

73. N₂: When these things, I mean running around and feeling scared happens, it is like how many minutes.

it shows that despite the patient's practs of *rebuking*, the neurologist maintains a neutral, non-emotive disposition. Here, the physician sustains the ascribed consumer appendage in informative consideration. He achieved this through his deployment of the information at his disposal for the service of the patient, who in a similar vein, is the client. Further, it is noticeable that the neurologist non-emotive disposition is achieved in somewhat an *officious* manner. This is because in line 33 of NPI 34 in the excerpt below:

Excerpt 29

33. P: But what about drugs?

34. N: Yes. All those will complement any drug we prescribe here. But **you have a choice to make in making sure that you observe all those things I told you.**

35. P: All of them are compulsory.

36. N: Are you asking me.

37. P: No. I mean they are compulsory. I will try.

it reveals that the patient had sought more information on the “drugs”, of which the neurologist responded in a suggestive way (with the prevalent use of the modal “may”). However, when the patient tries to clarify this in line 35 whether “all of them are compulsory”, the physician responded with a rhetorical question “are you asking me?”. This serves as a face-threatening strategy. From this, it is evident that emotion or empathy, which is the norm in the paternalistic model, has no place of tolerance in the informative. It confirms the “say-it-as-it-is” nature of the informative model with regards to psychological act. Ordinary perception to the scenario would have labelled the neurologist as a “hostile” doctor. However, in the situation at hand, the neurologist was simply fulfilling the dictates of the informative pattern of communication. The “rightfulness” or otherwise in the context is subject to debates.

Notwithstanding, the psychological act's benefit of the informative model can be deduced from the insistence of physicians to ensure that the patient understands the information being passed across, for the purpose of helping the patient to make an informed decision regarding own health. For example, the last sentence in line 22: “look here ma”, and the response of the patient: “I am with you” in line 23, coupled with the ensuing conversations are a reference to this. Also in NPI 14

Excerpt 30: NPI 14

Background information: Neurologists: (two) females; Experience: 1 year; Patient: female; Age: 54 years; Occupation: Trader; Ailment: Panic attack; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N₁: Well. Your mum is affected by a mental illness that we call “Panic Disorder”. This affects a person to experience repeated, unexpected panic attacks and persistent anxiety about the possibility that the panic attacks will reoccur.
2. R: Ha!
3. N₁: Don’t shout. See, that panic attack comes with intense fear, apprehension, or discomfort.
4. N₁: When it happens, it usually comes without warning. For you to know. You’ll notice she sometimes have her heart beating so fast. Madam, do you find it difficult breathing sometimes?
5. P: Sometimes. I won’t be able to able to breath down.
6. N₂: That’s shortness of breath.
7. N₁: Do you sometimes fear you are going crazy, or you lose control?
8. R: That’s our fears.
9. P: I reject it in Jesus name.
10. N₂: But do you feel scared that your enemies want you to go mad?
11. P: Yes and they would fail always in Jesus name.
12. N₂: When these things, I mean running around and feeling scared happens, it is like how many minutes.
13. R: It stays long sometimes o.
14. N₁: Like ten minutes or more?
15. R: More than that sometimes. Although at the beginning. It was not more than ten to twenty.
16. N₁: That’s it. Your mum needs to be treated for panic attacks. ((0.3₂)) Panic attack that she is experiencing is not without a recourse to her war experience in Libya. Although, Ehm, other anxiety disorders, such as phobias, ((0.8)) I mean fear of specific object or situation is also a possible trigger of this attack. Let me ask you. When you are travelling in a vehicle, does she fear?

The neurologist ignored all the rebuttals of the patient and the relations regarding the diagnostic information being given. Rather, she keeps supplying more details on the ailment discovered in the patients. By so doing, the neurologist in the excerpt above appears to be adhering to the requirement of the informative model of consultative communication without paying so much attention to emotion and other related considerations discussed in some of the other models of communication.

4.6.1.4 Physical acts in the informative model

Usually, across all other models, physical act is a common and effectively utilised pragmatic strategy. However, there are some physical acts that are more common to a

model than the others. For example, in the model under discussion, frowning, nodding, and pointing are common features of the physical acts. An act such as smiling is rare in the informative acts. This can be explained by the conscious or sub-conscious attempt of the physician to maintain the professional stance (scientist) devoid of emotions. It will be recalled that the informative model argues that physicians should be guided by professionalism rather than emotion. The “no smile”, oftentimes seems to help the physicians in maintaining a strict non-emotional face, which aligns with the ideals of the model. See NPI 13:23-27 (background information in excerpt 24 and complete interaction in appendix IV)

Excerpt 31

- 23. N: ...look here ma!
- 24. P: I am with you
- 25. N: What did I say last?
- 26. P: You said I should look here.
- 27. N: And before then?

In some cases, where the physical act is not managed minimally, the conversation may be confused for the paternalistic model, but in this case, the co-texts help in the understanding of the communication type being deployed. Issues relating to co-texts in the informative model are discussed in the succeeding section.

4.7 Textual features of the informative model

The co-texts of the interactions in the informative model reveal that there is the preponderance of useful diagnostic information more than the therapeutic. In the observed neurologist-patient interactions, the physicians who employed informative communication pattern provided information with an emphasis on the nature of the health challenge of the patients. For instance, in NPI 13:8-22 a quick glance at discoverable co-texts from the observed interactions is presented below.

Table 4.5: Contextual choices utilised by neurologists in informative model of NPI

Neurologist’s textual pattern	Practs
Inference	analysing, suggesting, informing
Reference	providing, questioning and re-questioning
Relevance	relating, prescribing, alerting

Voice	declaring, asserting, allowing, detailing, engineering
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	identifying, prescribing, remarking

The deductions from the Table show that practs such as *analysing* and *suggesting* were co-texts of inference, *providing*, *questioning and re-questioning*, *referring* featured as the co-reference's index. Further, for relevance, *relating* and *prescribing* practs are deployed. From the voice perspective, the neurologists pract *asserting*, *allowing*, *detailing*, and statutorily *engineering* the situation of the interaction towards diagnostic and therapeutic goals. Regarding the Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge, identifiable practs include: *identifying*, *prescribing*, and *remarking*. See NPIs 13 and 14 in appendix IV for examples.

On the part, the contextual choices utilised by patients in the informative model of the observed NPIs are presented in Table 4.6 below.

Table 4.6: Contextual choices utilised by patients in the informative model of NPI

Patient's textual pattern	Practs
Inference	Selecting
Reference	Inquiring
Relevance	Narrating
Voice	choosing, requesting, consuming
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	requesting, promising

In the above, the voice identified on the part of patients shows that they utilised the practs of *choosing*, *requesting*, *consuming*. This confirms the contractual nature of the informative model.

4.7.1 Shared situational knowledge in the informative model

Within the pragmatic acts principle, the focus is not attempting to explain language use from the inside out...rather, its explanatory movement is from the outside in. This implies that the focus “is on the environment in which both speaker and hearer find their affordances, such that the entire situation is brought to bear on what can be said in the situation, as well as on what is actually being said” (Mey 2001:221). In this respect, the informative model of communication, therefore, requires that the patient is detailed on the “situation” that necessitated his/her visit. How this is done in the observed NPI is explored. A similar trend can also be found in NPI 14. Examples from NPI 13 are given.

Excerpt 32:

NPI 13

5. P: These are them (sic), sir. ((Hands the papers and other documents to the N))
6. N: Oh! Okay. ((Nodding)) Yes.
7. P: What is that sir?
8. N: Em.. the record with us shows that you have been visiting this clinic for about two years and em (0.4) six weeks now. Also, you used to be treated for recurrent headache. Now all those have stopped for a moment. But you complained last week. That was why you were asked to do those tests.
9. P: And what is in the result sir?
10. N: It's your right to know. I'm going to tell you one by one....

From the above, the patient (through the relation) exhibits the desire to “know” what the results connote. Recall that one of the principles of the informative model is patient's values over physician values. In this, “a fairly clear distinction between facts and values” is emphasised. The implication is that the share situational knowledge in the context behoves on the doctor to provide all the available facts. This is started in line 10 as the doctor responded:

N: It's your right to know. I'm going to tell you one by one. Now. This brain that we use is made up of many specialised areas that work together. The cortex controls the cortical activity. You see (0.4) that outermost layer of brain cells. It is here ((raises the CT scan higher against the equipment)). Thinking and voluntary movements begin from here. So, basic functions like breathing and sleep are controlled here ((pointing to a part in the scan result)). So when this thing keeps recurring, our options are (0.8) give me a second (long pause. goes). ((powers on the computer)). Do you normally vomit?

The neurologist's explanation above validates Emanuel and Emanuel's assertion that "the physician is a purveyor of technical expertise, providing the patient with the means to exercise control". And as such, "the physician must maintain competence in their area of expertise" (1992:6). Even the advice to doctor to consult others is visible during some of the observed consultations. However, the patient's values which "determine what treatments are (to be) given" cannot be said to be observed in the context. As a result, the SSK in the context of the interactants is incomplete. This is because the patient is (within the informative communication tenet) expected to "select the medical interventions he or she wants, and for the physicians to execute the selected interventions", based on the information provided by the physician to the patient.

In another informative NPI as seen in 13:22, 28, however, there is a form of adherence to patient's values. Example

N: Em.. em.. This is it. In this situation, ((busy with the computer, probably reading from it)) (0.8) since it's a recurring one, which actually is a proof that you have em... em (0.4) Migraine. **You have to find a way of stopping the triggers. That is one. Two. You must be getting enough sleep. I mean enough sleep. Then you will also have to reduce stress for yourself. You must cultivate the habit** of (0.8). Look here ma!

Here, the doctor provides diagnostic information to the patient as well as providing her choice of interventions. Although this can be argued that the therapeutic values placed before the patient are patient-driven. No matter how one looks at it, the neurologist has satisfied the expectation of the informative communication by the strategy employed. This is also evident in the pract of interest *sustaining* deplored when it appears (to the neurologist) that the patient was not following the flow of the doctor's explanation in line 22, 24 and 28.

The deduction from the situations discussed is that in the SSK domain of the informative communication, the neurologist pract *providing* relevant and detailed diagnostic communication and *allowing* patient's choice, while the patient is expected to pract *selecting* from the interventions provided. It should be noted that out of the observed interactions that aligned with the informative communicative model, patient's utilisation of the *selecting* strategies is rare and occur in fewer cases. For example, considering more from NPI 13:

Excerpt 33

33. P: But what about drugs?
34. N: Yes. All those will complement any drug we prescribe here. But you have a choice to make in making sure that you observe all those things I told you.
35. P: All of them are compulsory.
36. N: Are you asking me.
37. P: No. I mean they are compulsory. I will try.
38. N: That will be fine. ((writes prescriptions)). So you may need to buy this.
39. P: What if I continue the Aspirin?
40. N: No. You can't use Aspirin when you have ulcer. Just continue with the drugs we prescribed. Do you have any other comment?
41. P: No sir
42. N: Any reservation?
43. P: No
44. N: Alright. When will you like to come again?
45. P: Do I need to come?
46. N: Except you have any complaints.
47. P: Okay.
48. N: You can go now. ((Patient gets up and exit))

It can be seen that in the above, the neurologist has given allowance to patient's value, even when the patient was about to lose it in line 35. On quickly realising the body language of the doctor by the response given in line 36, the patient adjusted. However, in the other part of the conversation, the patient surrenders to the superiority of the physician through some of the other questions asked the patient. As result, more values are placed on the doctor's decision, rather than that of the patient. It can be assumed that lack of patient's understanding of the expected role in hospital context is largely responsible for the statutorily conferred values to be lost or eroded. It is also the reason for the partial or non-completion of SSK in doctor-patient interaction.

4.7.2 Shared cultural knowledge

The shared cultural knowledge is mutual but resides more with the neurologist in the informative model. The "culture" being referred to in this context is purely a professional ethical requirement. Here, the mutuality starts at that point where the patient explains or narrates the "known" circumstances surrounding the ailment that necessitated the hospital visit. This, he/she does to empower the physician in accessing relevant information towards making a proper diagnosis. On the other side, the mutuality ends when the neurologist provides the necessary information regarding the situation being brought to him/her, to either the patient and/or his/her relations. For example, in NPI 14, the initial diagnostic strategy of SCK starts from the conversation in lines 7-57 as seen below:

Excerpt 34

7. N: Okay. What is it that is disturbing you?
8. P: I dey always shock.
9. N₁: You are always shocked?
10. Yes ma
11. N₁: How do you mean you dey always shock?
12. R: The issue ma is that when any small thing happen, mummy behaves somehow?
13. N₁: Feel somehow? Do you mean she does not behave well?
14. R: Not like that. The thing makes her to be easily afraid (sic).
15. N₂: Wait. You need to tell us exactly what you say she is doing.
16. R: Okay ma. You see, when people shout outside, mummy will suddenly fear.
17. N₂: You mean she gets frightened so often?
18. R: She is always afraid (sic)
19. N₁: She is always afraid?
20. R: Afraid. She is always afraid
21. N₂: Apart from shout outside, does she feel any pain or discomfort in her body?
22. R: Yes. Sometimes headache will be doing her. She will not sleep.
23. N₁: Who are you to her?
24. R: Son
25. N₁: Where are you living before now?
26. R: Before mummy came back?
27. N₁: Came back from where?
28. R: She used to stay in the abroad.
29. N₁: Oh! Okay. Where was she?
30. R: Libya
31. N₁: Madam, your son said you used to live in Libya
32. P: Yes
33. N₁: Where in Libya do you lived?
34. P: Tripoli
35. N₁: When did you come back to Nigeria?
36. P: When dem killed Gaddafi
37. N₂: That must be after the war
38. N₁: Something like that. Ma, how and why did you come back.
39. P: The government brought us back.
40. N₁: It's okay. *Oga* ((referring to the relation)) when this fear-fear happens, does her body shake?
41. R: Yes ma o. In fact, she would shake for hours.
42. N₁: When last did she experience this?
43. R: The day after yesterday.
44. N₂: But when did you start noticing this?
45. Around the time she came back. Even sef, we think (sic) that it was change of environment.
46. N₁: Okay. So, what did you do about it?
47. R: Our pastor prayed for her.
48. N₂: She went for deliverance?
49. R: Ehn. It was when we became worried that we took her there. When the church in our backyard are doing their night vigil. Mummy would just wake up and start running about the house.
50. N₁: That was when?
51. R: It's been long but when I see that it is like as if, as if, as if
52. N₂: Like going mental

53. R: Ehn ehn. That was why we say we should take her to hospital.
54. N₂: How long was she at the church?
55. R: It may be up to two years.
56. N₂: Two years?
57. R: Yes. Our brother abroad say that we must bring her here.

From the discussion, the patient with the help of the relation of hers provided background information about the ailment to the doctors, with the awareness of the possibility of being helped through accurate diagnosis. In some other cases, patients employ this strategy more than is required for the context. When this happens, the doctor will tactically redirect the conversation towards extracting relevant details only. Example

Excerpt 35

68. N₁: Do you sometimes fear you are going crazy, or you lose control?
69. R: That's our fears.
70. P: I reject it in Jesus name.
71. N₂: But do you feel scared that your enemies want you to go mad?
72. P: Yes and they would fail always in Jesus name.
73. N₂: When these things, I mean running around and feeling scared happens, it is like how many minutes.

Again, in the extract above, the relation has tried expressing their “our fears” on the patient’s situation in response to the question posed by the doctor. Out of anxiety, the patient tried to “reject” the “going crazy” mentioned by the doctor. In order to sustain and redirect the diagnostic purpose, the doctor introduced a familiar term of “enemies” as the feared causative of the ailment. This gained an affirmation from the patient, thus, the conversation is successfully redirected. Furthermore, by the conversational *redirecting* pract, the doctor is able to start and fulfil own part of the SCK within the professional ethical affordances in line with the principles of the informative model.

4.8 Summary

In this chapter, communication goals in neurologist-patient interaction were identified and analysed. Similarly, discourse strategies, practs and context of two out of the four identified patterns or models of communication in the interactions namely paternalistic and informative were analysed. In the next chapter, analyses of discourse strategies, practs and context of the remaining two models (interpretive and deliberative) are carried out.

CHAPTER FIVE

PRAGMATIC STRATEGIES AND CONTEXT IN THE INTERPRETIVE AND DELIBERATIVE MODELS OF NEUROLOGIST-PATIENT INTERACTION IN SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA

5.0 Introduction

This chapter is devoted to the analyses of the remaining two models of neurologist-patient interaction in the selected university teaching hospitals from the southwestern states of Nigeria. Similar to the previous chapter, tables and diagrams were presented to buttress some of the findings. However, figures or illustrations which cover the four models identified were presented and interpreted. This is done so as to classify and compare the model as deployed the interactants in the study.

5.1 Application of the interpretive model

The interpretive model of communication is the third among Emanuel and Emanuel's view on the doctor-patient relationship. As earlier mentioned, "the aim of the physician-patient interaction is to elucidate the patient's values and what he or she actually wants,

and to help the patient select the available medical interventions that realise these values” (Emanuel, 1992:6). This model has a close affinity with the informative model in its application, in that, the doctor provides information to the patient regarding the nature of the condition and the risks and benefits of possible interventions. These are discussed by identifying the type of pragmatic activities and also the textual features which are realised as practs.

5.1.2 Activity type in interpretive model

In identifying the activities in the observed SWUTHs, there are observed cases of doctors that can be labelled “interpretive neurologists”. NPI 23, 9 and 15 provide some examples where the interactions can be said to be purely interpretive in isolation. These are examined in the sub-section.

5.1.2.1 Speech acts in interpretive model

Mey sees speech acting in general as “any way of using words to do things” (2001:219). In line with this, the interpretive communication model in NPI presents diverse deductions towards the identification of the speech acts performed by the interactants. For example, in NPI 23 below:

Excerpt 36: NPI 23

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 3 years; Patient: male; Age: 13; Occupation: Pupil; Ailment: Dyslexia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Let him sit down. You can use the other sit.
2. R: Thank you ma. They said we should come here.
3. N: Yes. Your child was diagnosed of dyslexia.
4. R: Is is true sir (0.8) that we can't...
5. N: Wait. You must know one thing. Dyslexia is not a disease or an identifiable physical condition. It is a learning style that usually can be assessed through a profile that shows whether the child has a typical pattern of strengths and weaknesses, coupled with assessment to rule out other possible causes of symptoms, such as vision or hearing problems. From the reports with me, some of the issues raised are common traits of what we are talking about. But there are things we can do.
6. R: So, that is how he would be?
7. N: I just told you it's not a disease. Of course, we can see it as a disorder but definitely not a disease as you appear to be feeling. Anyway, there are some things we can still do. I mean some interventions are possible.
8. R: Okay sir. (0.32) But like what.
9. N: Let me ask you some questions first.
10. R: Yes ma
11. N: When he was a toddler, did she have any serious injury? Like falling down or anything.

12. R: Yes
13. N: What happened?
14. R: We had a house girl then. ((sobs)) I was at the office when they called that she fell from her and hit on the flo:::or.
15. N: It's okay. Did you do anything? As in hospital and the rest.
16. R: We went to a private hospital.
17. N: Why?
18. R: Doctors were on strike then.
19. N: For how long?
20. R: I can say clearly now but *sha*, I know it's more than three months.
21. N: Okay. Baby girl. How are you?
22. P: Fine
23. N: What class are you?
24. P: Four?
25. N: Is that correct ((to the relation))
26. R: ((Shakes her head from left to right))
27. N: Okay. ((Writes some sentences in a plain sheet of paper, gets up from her seat and stands beside the patient)) Can you read this for me?
28. P: ((Looking))
29. N: *Oya*. Let's try
30. P: I:::::am girl ((missing the words "beautiful little"))
31. N: I am a beautiful little girl. Say it
32. P: I litt::::le girl.
33. N: It's alright. ((Goes back to her seat)) Like I said, what we need to do are interventions.
34. R: Yes ma.
35. N: ((Removing some notes from the table)) What I mean is that we will observe some things to help your girl. I hope you will be ready.
36. R: I'm ready. (0.8) We are ready, anything.
37. N: Okay then. The issue is that young people with this kind of challenge can benefit from speech therapy. Emmm, what did they call that o? (0.8) Yes! Phonetic (0.4), no, phonemic awareness. Where you were referred in Abeokuta, did you hear this?
38. R: No o o. Maybe that is why we were told to come here.
39. N: Okay then. I think the teaching in the ability to hear and work with the sounds of letters and letter combinations is what I referred to. I mean the phonemic awareness. That is one of the things they can do to help him readjust. What normally happens is that a speech therapist may also work on what they call phonics. This will make her know the relationship between letters and the sounds they make. That is just a part, other things would still be done.
40. R: But ma, how do we get that?
41. N: Well, in some cases, a specially trained reading specialist may do this type of therapy instead of a speech therapist. You may also want to explore educational therapy.
42. R: Meaning?
43. N: It is a kind of therapy that could reduce some of your child's anxiety about school and make it easier for her to perform in class. It is possible that dyslexia affects her self-esteem or causes anxiety or stress. If that is the case, psychological counselling could also help her perform better in school.
44. R: O:::kay.

45. N: you also need to talk to her teachers about what instructional strategies they use in her school. The ideal thing is for her to be taught in multisensory ways. I mean that kind of teaching that connect what they see, hear and feel. You live in Lagos, you should be able to get a good school like that. Here, we have some schools we do recommend to our patients. And they do come back with good report. I hope this is not too much?
46. R: ((smiles))
47. N: You are smiling. That is the truth. Your daughter is not really sick. She just needs help to readjust.
48. R: So, ma, what else can help people in this situation?
49. N: Yes. I was coming to that. You can (0.2) Oh! I mean, you should also support your child at home. You might try and get audiobooks or dictation software and other things that can help her learn. If you get these android phones, there are apps for children that you can use. I can remember Chu-chu TV. If you can do some of these things and may be get some games, if possible, they that can make reading easier for her.
50. R: Okay ma.
51. N: I will get you some links with specialist that will help the situation. But it's not really anything to gloat about. ((Writes)) (0.32) So that's it. I'll give you my phone number, so that you can get in touch easily. ((writes)). So we'll see again. Go and give that to the Matron, she will guide you.
52. R: Thank you ma. ((exits with the patient))

The exchange between the relation of the patient and doctor can stand as the speech acting in the informative model. However, since in the interpretive model, the patient's values are not necessarily fixed and known to the patient, (Emanuel and Emanuel described this as inchoate), the neurologist conveys the value to the patient (represented by the relation) by employing the *declaring* pract in line 3.

It is true that the patient is aware of this information but lacks the understanding of the next steps to be taken, which itself is the value. The physician allays her presupposed fear about the ailment in line 4 in adherence to the principle of the interpretive model, making coherent patient's values. In this, the pract of *informing* and *clarifying* are deployed. Also, to achieve the goal of the interpretive model, it is expected that "physician works with the patient to reconstruct the patient's goals and aspirations..." (Emanuel and Emanuel 1992:6). This again is evident in the extract above in lines 6 and 7. Here, the texts give a pragmatic connotation of the patient's goal, that is, possible healing or solution to the ailment. To effectively confer and achieve the patient's value, the neurologist asked a further diagnostic question from the relation (line 11), and also carried out ethically relevant test on the patient by requesting her to read from the piece of paper written by the doctor. By this, the goal of communication in the interpretive model was achieved.

In another observed NPI, NPIs 9, discoverable speech acting from the perspective of the neurologist include *construing* or *interpreting*, for example, line 7 of NPI 9 as seen below:

Excerpt 37

N: Yes, I said it's more realist than your previous result 140/80. So, I think he's fine. I won't change your drug sir.

As typical of the interpretive model, the "resultive" impact of the conversation is achieved. In this context, the pragmatic force and its affordances are brought to bear. In line 16 of NPI 14, a similar strategy was employed as:

Excerpt 38

N: O yes! We can recommend ((Flips across the pages of a book)) (0.40) COGNITIVE-BEHAVIOURAL therapy. It is a type of psychotherapy that helps to eliminate panic attacks in 80 to 100 percent of patients. (0.8) What the therapists need to do is to help her re-create the physical symptoms of a panic attack. Then, teach her coping skills. (0.4) then (0.2) help her to alter the beliefs about the danger of these sensations. It can be expensive, but it can be done.

From the excerpt, the place of the interpretive model as an applicable communication strategy is buttressed. However, most of the scenarios show that the speech acting is mainly resultive. Some other instances, even where there is an interplay of the model with others, the interpretive model achieves slightly its goal, as the patient themselves usually surrender their autonomy or values. An exploration of the complete conversations in NPI, NPIs 9 and 15 align with this observation.

5.1.2.2 Discourse strategies in the interpretive model

The discursive interpretive communication which has the colouration of monologic pattern is common in the post-initial visitation of patients to the neurological clinics. The monologic here would imply a situation where the neurologist holds the communication floor much more than the patients. The monologic communication is prevalent in situations where a patient has previously visited the hospital in a certain case. In some instances, some tests must have been carried out, and the result is yet discussed between the patients and their physicians. In such case, the result is then often interpreted and further therapeutic advice is rendered. However, there are instances where patients might be referred from a hospital to another. In this, and where pre-tests might have been carried out, the neurologists usually interpret the situation to the patient. Nonetheless, the

interpretive model performs a metapragmatic function beyond mere interpretation of results. This is further advanced with examples from NPIs 8, 9 and 15.

Excerpt 39: NPI 9

The retired public servant patient is a 66-year old male. He is diabetic. A male neurologist attends to him.

1. N: How are you today?
2. P: I'm fine.
3. N: You still live in the same Kongi area?
4. P: Yes ((gives some documents to the neurologist))
5. N: Okay. ((reads the document)) You have improved! 110/70. This is more realistic than the ones I saw before.
6. P: You said it's realistic
7. N: Yes, I said it's more realist than your previous result 140/80. So, I think he's fine. I won't change your drug sir.
8. P: Will I still take all?
9. N: Yes
10. R: That's true
11. P: Who is the doctor here?
12. N: I am, but she is your nurse ((laughs))
13. P: She always support you on this.
14. N: That means I'm doing the right thing. ((General laughter)) We are always working together. Do you agree with our treatment sir?
15. P: Are you satisfied?
16. N: I'm satisfied.
17. P: That I'm alright
18. N: Yes sir.
19. P: If anything goes wrong I'll sue you ((jokingly))
20. N: No problem sir ((jokingly)). But before you sue me, we'll go to the radio. Then we'll see who the people would believe in (general laughter). No problem. I think I'll see him in two months or three.
21. P: Let's make it two months
22. N: Okay. That two-month is okay. If I make it four months you'll complain. That, it's too long. TWO MONTHS. We won't change the drugs. They
23. P: Alright
24. R: Thank you
25. N: Stay well.

The above interaction portrays on the surface, an ordinary interpretive role of doctor as seen in lines 4 and 7. The patient here was obviously asked to carry out a test, and he is here to see the neurologist with the result. The doctor appears to be excited or optimistic about the improvement as seen in line 5. However, at the meta-pragmatic level, in line 7, when the doctor informed the patient: "...I won't change your drug sir." and the patient further inquired although jokingly if he would keep to the drugs; the last sentence in line 14 shows the neurologist's understanding of the patient's values and views. As a result,

he informs the patient with respect to the therapy, of which the patient exhibits the understanding of the healthcare decision taken on his behalf (presumably, at previous meetings) See lines 11-16. By this, the patient practs *assuring* as his response to the doctor's "Do you agree with our treatment sir?". Here, the pragmatic act strategy employed by the neurologist is that of *offering*. It should be noted that the length and duration of conversation are short. Here, the contribution of the interactants is more of *monologic* than interactive. For emphasis, the term "monologic" is technically used to interpret the utterances of the neurologist which is more of a monologue. In the situation, the patient is confined to merely paying attention to what the neurologist has to "declare" with regards to the patient's health. This is common in some instances in neurologist-patient interactions because the major actors in the conversation understood own role, and stick to it accordingly. An important factor worth mentioning regarding the extract above is that the neurologist is a much more experienced physician and the patient has also been known to him for a longer period of time. Hence, their conversation was patterned in the way described. For instance in another scenario from NPI 8.

Excerpt 40: NPI 8

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: undisclosed; Patient: female; Age: 27; Occupation: Law intern; Ailment: Recurring headache; Visitation status: unaccompanied

1. N: Yes ma. Welcome. You are P^SP. How old are you?
2. P: Twenty-seven
3. N: What work do you do?
4. P: Civil servant but I'm working with a lawyer.
5. N: You are working with a lawyer? Where?
6. P: At Kwara state.
7. N: So, why are you here?
8. P: My head used to disturb me.
9. N: But there are doctors in Ilorin. Why leave Kwara for here. Any reason?
10. P: Because my lawyer parents are here.
11. N: Okay. No problem. That's why you are here. You are welcome. So what's the problem?
12. P: The head used to disturb me whenever I entered a vehicle.
13. N: Your head (0.4) will start disturbing you? What kind of disturbance?
14. P: My body will be hot here ((touching the head)) and when I stop from the vehicle it will stop.
15. N: Will stop. So, it you are going from here to (0.8) let's say Ilorin. The head will do like that through?
16. P: Yes
17. N: So, it's when you get to Ilorin that it will stop.
18. P: Yes
19. N: But what if you are not in the vehicle? It won't happen?

20. P: Yes
21. N: Is it headache?
22. P: Yes
23. N: It's headache that you are having? And it's like they are beating on your head?
24. P: Yes
25. N: When you have it, do you see flashes of light? As if someone is shining light.
26. P: No
27. N: No, do you hear voices?
28. P: No
29. N: Do you feel like vomiting?
30. P: No
31. N: Where do you feel this pain?
32. P: ((Touching the head)) here.
33. N: Just the front? Not at the back? Or the side?
34. P: No
35. N: Are you scared of travelling?
36. P: Sometimes, I used to be scared but when I am scared I'll use anointing oil to spray my head and if I feel the headache I will now use like (0.8) paracetamol
37. N: So, if you use the anointing oil and paracetamol, you will be able to travel, you won't have headache?
38. P: Yes

(Complete interaction of NPI 8 in appendix IV)

Here, the patient is a first-time visitor to the hospital, the patient has narrated her case to the neurologist with various references to palpable concerns for her health. In the ensuing conversation, various suggestions were made which show the desire of the interactants to attain both diagnostic and therapeutic goals. However, after the neurologist has used the pract of *asserting* by explaining the possible cause of the "headache", the discursive conversational pattern reveals the ideational flow with regards to the intended actions and goals between the interactants. This implies that, in neurologist attempt at deploying the interpretive communication strategy, the patients do not always determine the adherence to the communicative pattern, rather, the physicians do. In the observed NPIs, the patients do surrender their autonomy and communicative value irrespective of their educational attainment. This is the peculiarity of the monological nature of the discourse strategy in the interpretive model. This is also visible in NPI 23 (see appendix IV). In the exchange, the neurologist lectured (mother of) the patient and interpreted the situation to her (them). Through this, the pract of *reassuring* was employed by the neurologist as seen in line 5 of NPI 23:

Excerpt 41

5. N: Wait. You must know one thing. Dyslexia is not a disease or an identifiable physical condition. It is a learning style that usually can be assessed through a profile that shows whether the child has a typical pattern of strengths and weaknesses, coupled with assessment to rule out other possible causes of symptoms, such as vision or hearing problems. From the reports with me, some of the issues raised are common traits of what we are talking about. But there are things we can do.

When the mother retorted:

6. R: So, that is how he would be?

The neurologist provided her with a co-reference of the previous statement in:

7. N: I just told you it's not a disease. Of course, we can see it as a disorder but definitely not a disease as you appear to be feeling. Anyway, there are some things we can still do. I mean some interventions are possible.

At the end of the conversation, the patients' values were understood by the relation who doubles as the mother. Through this, there is a clear indication that the values were not derived by the patient but the doctor's expertise. This makes the adoption of this model, suspect to criticism, as according to Oprea "what is good for patients deeply depends on their own values and doctors are not best positioned to know what those values are" (2009:130).

5.1.2.3 Physical acts in the interpretive model

In conversational analysis, physical acts such as body move(ment), gestures, facial expressions, and other physical display of emotions are usually represented with notations. Although the use of these notations cut across all the models being studied, in the interpretive communication model, depending on the type of patients in the interaction, these are scanty. This does not imply that no physical acts took place, but a consideration of NPIs 8, 9, 15 and 23 which are categorised as interpretive, featured regular physical act, such as reactions to questions, and explanatory gestures such as "touching the head" among others. It is not unusual that this is the case because of the expatriate posture of the neurologists in the interactions. Since, it is the duty of the doctor to reflect and communicate the implications of the patients' medical state to them, so as to have a clear idea of patients' own health and take a decision, what the majority of the patients did in the interactions was to just listen and show great concentration. See NPI 8 lines 32, 73, 78 in appendix IV.

5.3.1 Pragmatic acts in the interpretive model

From the observed interactions between neurologists and patients in NPIs NPI 23, 9 and 15 among others, the following textual features are realised. These are presented in the Table below:

Table 5.1: Pragmatic acts of the co-texts of neurologists and patients in the interpretive model

Neurologist's textual pattern	Practs
Inference	deducing, interpreting, questioning
Reference	presenting, prioritising, situating
Relevance	relating, clarifying
Voice	engineering, suggesting, predicting
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	distancing, prescribing, recognising, greeting
Patient's textual pattern	
Inference	listening, inquiring
Reference	selecting
Relevance	questioning, requesting
Voice	deciding
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	recognising, greeting

The Table 5.1 above indicates that the practs of deducing, interpreting, and questioning are neurologists' inference pattern, which were derived in the textual part of the pragmeme. For the reference, presenting, prioritising, situating practs were found. Similarly, in terms of relevance, relating, clarifying practs were deduced (see NPIs 23, 9). The voice showed the engineering, suggesting, and predicting practs. Found in the Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge were distancing, prescribing, recognising, and greeting practs. The reference pointed towards selecting pract, showing the voice, which deploys the deciding pract.

Further, the patients pract listening, inquiring with regards to inference. Questioning, and requesting were generated from relevance. Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge accounted for recognising and greeting practs.

In the consideration of interpretive model, greeting and gratitude are optional, however, due to the SSK, this practs featured in some instances such as NPI 8:108, 9:24, 23:52, and 15 respectively. This reflects the socio-cultural values of the people in the studied locations.

5.4 Utilisation of activity choices in the deliberative model of neurologist-patient interaction

One of the reasons the proponents of the models being studied asserted that the deliberative model is the most suitable model of communication, is that the DM utilises the factual information provided in the informative, elucidated in the interpretive-the patients' values, and offer as optional recommendations in the deliberative. In the consideration of some of the observed interactions, this is expounded.

5.4.1 Choice of activity in the deliberative model

The activity in the deliberative model features the indirect speech acts, dialogue acts, prosody, and physical acts. All these are considered in (slightly) isolated cases among the observed interactions. Some of the isolated NPIs include 2, 24, 25 and a few others. The discoverable features are explored in the subsequent sections.

5.4.1.1 Speech acts in the deliberative model

In human interactions, there are some expressions that perform certain "force" in order to do things. Speech acts in order to be effective, have to be situated, that is, they must actively create the situation they are realised (Mey 2001:219). Mey avers that speech act

is capable of realising all sorts of indirect ways and still produce same effects (2001). In essence, in the consideration of speech acts deplored in the deliberative model of the observed, it would be noted that some of the linguistic and non-elements do not necessarily exhibit the pract of *deliberating*, but are implied. For instance, in lines 32-36 of NPI 24 below:

Excerpt 42: NPI 24

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: male; Age: 66 years; Occupation: undisclosed; Ailment: Stuttering; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: ((To the researcher)) Please just observe and note whatever you can but don't record this. I will tell you when you should. Or you are not okay by that.
2. I: No problem sir. As you wish sir.
3. R: ((goes into a lengthy narration. The N signals the I to go ahead with audio recording after the R narration))
4. N: So since when did you notice the stuttering and his slow body movement? Is it not about 2 weeks?
5. R: Since last two Monday.
6. N: ((Writes)). Is he walking any differently then?
7. R: I usually take him to walk, since he can't walk normally.
8. N: Is he diabetic
9. Pat R: he is . : -
10. N: Which drug was he placed?
11. P: Bor:::der::li::ne
12. N: So, it's Borderline? You are not on any strong indication. And does he use it regularly?
13. R: No
14. N: But if he eats it on empty stomach, that could be the cause too.
15. P: Dr P^{SP}
16. N: So, it is Dr P^{SP} that manages you. So how do you it? You see Dr P^{SP} and cross again \$\$ How do you did it?
17. R: Let's meet Dr P^{SP} and tell him it's not a problem.
18. N: What has he been using for the control of the hypertension? ((R responds)). ((writes on and talks intermittently)) Cholesterol 107. HDL 62... The urinalysis is normal.
19. P: O::kay £.
20. N: The result you brought claims this one is normal but from what we see here. Certainly, this is not correct.
21. R: Okay
22. N: So, there is no cause for alarm sir. I think it's all metabolic-related and (0.2) and all that.
23. P: I:::wa:::s (0.4) a bit wo:::ried at a point
24. N: Too long
25. R: No. No. for medication (0.4)
26. N: Too many drugs. Ok sir.
27. P: I:::know I can't do any:::thing about it
28. N: Yes. It's true.
29. P: But em : : : (0.4)

30. N: If you can cut down on them (0.32) I think it's the : : : 00 (...) Does he use Aspirin ((R nods in disagreement)). Any multi-vitamin?
31. R: This one ((referring to the one in the drug bag)).
32. N: He should follow his medication. That should clear some of these ... And then we'll wait till we have the result. Then we can decide on the next thing ...) > So let him do the test at (...). we won't add any drugs now until we have the results
33. P: For good or bad?
34. N: No No No No: We just need to be sure so as to:: We'll just wait for 6 weeks or 2 months.
35. R: So what is actually outstanding how?
36. N: It's just the blood test. And then we would adjust your medication, but you can continue the banana supplement.
37. P: Should it be once in a day?
38. R: One a day? Should it be once in a day?
39. N: One a day should be fine. That will also give you extra potassium.
40. R: Thank you so much sir.
41. P: Thank you sir.
42. N: Thank you sir-sorry. Just go home and rest sir.
43. R: Thanks for your care for him.
44. N: We thank God. He's doing so well. Just have a good rest at home sir and enjoy yourself. Sorry. Thank you : : :

the *deliberating* pract was evoked as an indirect speech acting to allow the choice and involvement of the patient through the help of the relations in adhering to prescription. In this, the neurologist deplores an *assuring* pract, which in itself is a form of persuasion. Recall, one of the strategies the physicians aims at in DM, is "moral persuasion" and that "patient must define his or her life and select ordering of values to be espoused" (Emanuel and Emanuel 1992:2). In some cases, the social variable may determine what and how neurologist deploys this strategy. For example, in NPI 2, taking the extract from lines 19 to 26.

Excerpt 43: NPI 2

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: female; Age: 32 years; Occupation: Teacher; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: Good morning
2. N: Well done. How are you? What's the situation? So, what's the situation?
3. P: Yes. I've seen the gynaecologist. And by the time I went to see him for the scan, my baby was already gone.
4. N: Okay
5. P: And they have to evacuate as soon as possible. And so they evacuated the baby. And they said it was due to (...)
6. N: Okay. Alright (0.4) so that's not necessarily correct. That's not necessarily correct. It's not. At least we've had patients like yours (...). We can change your drugs. There is no drug in this world that is safe for the first trimester of

- pregnancy. There is no drug. The only drug that is not recommended in pregnancy is sodium (...). So it's not that drug that caused what happened. What has happened had happened. Not because of (...). Certainly, that wasn't at all.
7. P: So what would have happened?
 8. N: The baby might have been malformed:- But not the effect of the drug. You could check your Google. You could check it on the internet.
 9. P: I goggled with my sister. Drugs could be responsible in (...)
 10. N: Any drug:- Not just Benotoin.
 11. P: Benotoin
 12. N: Not just Benotoin. No! Any drug. The only drug that is not recommended is (...Biotrate) So:: Any drugs. Any drugs.
 13. P: According to Dr P^{SP}, the Benotoin was too high. Probably, the baby was just (...)
 14. N: How experience is the gynaecologist?
 15. P: Professor P^{SP}
 16. N: P^{SP}. Probably its ... (0.4). You see the thing is like maintaining a balance between a neurological disease and a pregnancy. And the choice is yours. To find a drug that will work. And you have a foetus.
 17. P: It (0.2) that's special.
 18. N: No drug is recommended in first trimester. There is no where somebody will say use this drug. Any drug taken in the first twelve weeks of pregnancy can result into anything. That's the standard in the world. So (0.2) but they have varying degrees of affectation. If Kepra is good, you take it along with vitamins. The usual thing you do in first trimester is take vitamins, take Folic Acid. And then (0.2) After 20 weeks. Then do amino synthesis to check overdose. But there is nothing we can do before then.
 19. R: Okay. What I want to ask is whether we should change this to any of the brands. Whether Kepra or any of the brands or she should continue. Is it not going to cause any deformation?
 20. N: We are always optimistic. When you read about it. The thing they caused. They could cause abnormalities in the foetus. Any drug. And if the abnormality is severe enough, the nature will put up a natural defence.
 21. R: Okay. Because Em. Dr P^{SP} said the foetus doesn't (...)
 22. N: Yeah. Most drugs will cause (...)
 23. P: And when we read about it. It's like, that was part of the (...) em side effects of the drugs.
 24. N: Well I asked you before, you said you preferred it.
 25. P: I was thinking it had no side effects.
 26. N: All drugs have side effects, in pregnancy all.
 27. P: So there is none you can recommend?
 28. N: No. No. Not at all. Not at all. NOT (0.2) AT ALL
 29. P: But Prof P^{SP} said that there are some drugs that are milder.
 30. N: You were controlled on that one. You've forgotten our first conversation. Maybe one should be recording conversation. And you said you were happy with these drugs. Not that I was going to change it, but you said you were happy with them. And so, what else does one do. If they are milder drug, we could try, but it's at the expense of you having seizure. And if you have seizure, anything could happen as well. So, the best thing is keep your mind at rest. Hmm:: You were taking 300ml, that was a big dose but (0.2) that's what the dose that's controlled the seizure. So be it. If you reduce the dose to 200, you may have seizures. If you have seizures, the foetus is in jeopardy as well.

In the excerpt above, the patient's exhibition of knowledge of her health situation makes the neurologist approach the issue differently. The patient is aware of the possible side effects of the previously prescribed drug. Here, she negotiates the continuation of the drug in line 19. The neurologist on a subtle tone has shown optimism about the discussion. However, from lines 23 to 30, a form of linguistic repression was introduced by the doctor. This is because the patient did not appear to have been persuaded by the neurologist's explanation. As a result, the "good" patient ideology was eroded. As seen in line 30 of excerpt 43:

N: You were controlled on that one. You've forgotten our first conversation. Maybe one should be recording conversation. And you said you were happy with these drugs. Not that I was going to change it, but you said you were happy with them. And so, what else does one do. If they are milder drug, we could try, but it's at the expense of you having seizures. And if you have seizures, anything could happen as well. So, the best thing is keep your mind at rest. Hmm:: You were taking 300ml, that was a big dose but (0.2) that's what the dose that's controlled the seizures. So be it. If you reduce the dose to 200, you may have seizures. If you have seizures, the foetus is in jeopardy as well.

Mey (2001) explains the term linguistic repression to connote a strategy employed by physicians to show that they are more knowledgeable than their patient. The deliberative communication model does not favour such strategy, however, in the studied location, the strategy was utilised as a form of a *persuading* pract, which mainly helps to "institutionalised" the conversation, (see Mey 2001:300-301). In the other parts of the conversation, evidence of patient's decision regarding the definition of valuable health care choice and want cannot be ascertained, (see Oprea, 2009:132). Rather, the patient in trying to attain "good" patient status succumbed to the superior knowledge of the physician in line 48 to 70.

5.4.1.2 Discourse strategies in the deliberative model

The deliberative model gives more room for turn-taking through its negotiating conversation than the other models in the categorisation of Emanuel and Emanuel (1992) model of DPR. This is in accordance with its deliberative tendency. As the doctor presents the patients with facts, values and the risk factors in the available therapeutic options, the patient is empowered to consider the information of different therapeutic alternatives and their health-related values (Oprea, 2009:132). Considering this, some parts of NPI 2 is examined from excerpt 44 below:

Excerpt 44: NPI 2

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: female; Age: 32 years; Occupation: Teacher; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: Good morning
2. N: Well done. How are you? What's the situation? So, what's the situation?
3. P: Yes. I've seen the gynaecologist. And by the time I went to see him for the scan, my baby was already gone.
4. N: Okay
5. P: And they have to evacuate as soon as possible. And so they evacuated the baby. And they said it was due to (...)
6. N: Okay. Alright (0.4) so that's not necessarily correct. That's not necessarily correct. It's not. At least we've had patients like yours (...). We can change your drugs. There is no drug in this world that is safe for the first trimester of pregnancy. There is no drug. The only drug that is not recommended in pregnancy is sodium (...). So it's not that drug that caused what happened. What has happened had happened. Not because of (...). Certainly, that wasn't at all.
7. P: So what would have happened?
8. N: The baby might have been malformed:- But not the effect of the drug. You could check your Google. You could check it on the internet.
9. P: I goggled with my sister. Drugs could be responsible in (...)
10. N: Any drug:- Not just Benotoin.
11. P: Benotoin
12. N: Not just Benotoin. No! Any drug. The only drug that is not recommended is (...Biotrate) So:: Any drugs. Any drugs.
13. P: According to Dr P^{SP}, the Benotoin was too high. Probably, the baby was just (...)
14. N: How experience is the gynaecologist?
15. P: Professor P^{SP}
16. N: P^{SP}. Probably its ... (0.4). You see the thing is like maintaining a balance between a neurological disease and a pregnancy. And the choice is yours. To find a drug that will work. And you have a foetus.
17. P: It (0.2) that's special.
18. N: No drug is recommended in first trimester. There is no where somebody will say use this drug. Any drug taken in the first twelve weeks of pregnancy can result into anything. That's the standard in the world. So (0.2) but they have varying degrees of affectation. If Kepra is good, you take it along with vitamins. The usual thing you do in first trimester is take vitamins, take Folic Acid. And then (0.2) After 20 weeks. Then do amino synthesis to check overdose. But there is nothing we can do before then.
19. R: Okay. What I want to ask is whether we should change this to any of the brands. Whether Kepra or any of the brands or she should continue. Is it not going to cause any deformation?
20. N: We are always optimistic. When you read about it. The thing they caused. They could cause abnormalities in the foetus. Any drug. And if the abnormality is severe enough, the nature will put up a natural defence.
21. R: Okay. Because Em. Dr P^{SP} said the foetus doesn't (...)
22. N: Yeah. Most drugs will cause (...)
23. P: And when we read about it. It's like, that was part of the (...) em side effects of the drugs.

(Complete interaction in NPI 2 of appendix IV)

In the above, the role of turn-taking mechanism here is more of the “adjacency in pair-wise structure” (Mey 2001:158), which is a form of collaboration between the patient and neurologist. At the outset, the adjacency pair was symmetrical (where the floor-holding by the interactants was in similar proportion). However, towards the middle to the ending as seen from lines 16 to 90 (see NPI 2 in appendix IV), the adjacency pair gradually faded away and went asymmetrical. In this situation, the doctor controls the floor by giving longer talks than the other interactant in the conversation. In doing so, many persuasive behaviours are exhibited by neurologist where the pract of persuading is evoked.

In the ordinary makeup, the deliberative model allows persuasion without coercion, but using the linguistic repressive strategy, the patient was coercively persuaded. This is not the case in all observed interactions that follow this pattern of communication. The example below is an indicator and affirms this.

Excerpt 45: NPI 29

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: female; Age: 54 years; Occupation: undisclosed; Ailment: Brain aneurysm; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: We have been kept waiting sir.
2. N: It's not our own doing, we have many patient today. (0.8) So, how is it?
3. P: It's her we have come to see you for.
4. N: Okay. ((looks into the case file)) You have the results?
5. P: Yes sir. ((hands them over to the doctor))
6. N: ((Looking at the result on a machine)) Well, we have a case of aneurysm. I mean (0.4) Brain aneurysm. As a medical doctor in practice, Is that not who you are?
7. P: I'm in training sir. Penultimate year in school.
8. N: Oh I see. Are you the one that followed her the last time?
9. P: No sir.
10. N: Okay. As I was saying. This result tells us she has aneurysm ((spelling it)) A-N-E-U-R-Y-S-M. Well. (0.24) A brain aneurysm is a balloon or bubble-like growth that typically develops where a major artery branches into smaller arteries, often at the base of the brain. This em naturally has the potential of leaking or rupturing. She is 54 years old now.
11. P: Yes sir
12. N: The aneurysm condition, according to research, em ehen, (0.8) most commonly affects adults between the ages of 35 to 60 years old. In fact, it affects women more frequently than men. ((discussing with student doctor present)) Brain aneurysms typically don't cause symptoms until they leak or rupture. When that happens, it will cause bleeding into the brain. This can only be discovered during tests for other conditions. Even when they cause no symptoms, these aneurysms should be treated to prevent future ruptures. Talking about the

symptom. This can show through a sudden and extremely severe headache that may occur with nausea, vomiting, stiff neck, impaired consciousness, seizures or coma. A ruptured brain aneurysm is a very serious condition that in some cases can be fatal. ((a student asks a question)) ((in response)) The only way out is a quick and accurate diagnosis. Yes, recovery is very possible. It's good you responded fast.

13. P: Thank God

14. N: Alright sir, for your mum, I will tell you the available options. Okay?

15. P: Thank you sir.

16. N: No o, you would have to make a choice for her.

17. P: Okay sir.

18. N: For this kind of situation ehm, almost all brain aneurysms should be treated to prevent them from rupturing or repair ruptured aneurysms as quickly as possible and strengthen the arteries to prevent future ruptures. So

19. P: I don't understand sir

20. N: I mean, she must to prevent them from rupturing or repair ruptured aneurysms as quickly as possible.

21. P: How sir?

22. N: There are options. They can place her for surgery. For instance, they can use microsurgical clipping. This is what they use for majority of aneurysms to treat aneurysms. Usually, they are accessed through an opening in the skull ((demonstrates)). Alternatively, they can use skull (...) surgery. This is typically used for deep and complex aneurysms located beneath the brain. The aneurysm is accessed through the bone at the base of the skull. The other is the Vascular Bypass (...) A vein is taken from the leg and used to connect an artery in the neck and an artery in the brain to bypass the aneurysm. There is also endovascular Therapy which is a minimally invasive alternative to surgery in treating brain aneurysms. They also call it endovascular coiling. To do this, the procedure does not require an incision in the head. (0.12) It is performed under general anaesthesia or light sedation, and has a shorter recovery time and hospital stay compared to conventional surgery. The problem is you cannot recommend it for all patients. ((facing the relation of the patient)), which of these will you prefer?

23. R: Ha sir, I don't think I understand them enough sir. Maybe we will come back.

24. N: The situation does not give us much time. I'm even considering placing her on admission.

25. R: I'll have to contact my people sir for money.

26. N: Alright, go and find a way out of that. It's alright.

27. R: Okay sir.

28. N: Let me know your decision. I'll still be here till afternoon.

29. R: Thank you sir. ((Exit with the patient))

Unlike the previously discussed NPI, the neurologist in the above interaction, using the deliberative model as a consultative strategy, begins the consultation by presenting facts to the patient (through the relative). The allowance for patient's inclusion in the process was brought to bear in line 22 when the family of the patient is asked to select from the options presented, having been "conversational influenced". Rather than the relative of the patient to hurry himself, he adapts himself to the situation, thus practicing *requesting* so as to be able to make an informed decision by asking to "contact (his) people".

In the above, despite that there were some linguistic repressive strategies deployed by the doctor, who presumed that the relative was a medical student as seen in lines 6 to 9, the listener (patient's relation) was equipped with "situational information in establishing the expectations that will allow" him to take the right decision that is capable of "yield(ing) the desired result" (see Mey, 2001: 227).

5.4.1.3 Physical acts in the deliberative model

In the deliberative model of NPI, there is usually a lot of demonstrations in the communicative context. Here, the neurologist uses all manners of physical gestures in first, presenting factual information to the patient. Second, the information is made clearer to the patients (and in some cases the relatives). Then reflect with the patients, all the possible values in terms of risks and advantages. The goal of any physical act through the persuasive strategy is for proper diagnosis and therapeutic choices with the full consent and involvement of the patient or his or her relations. In doing this, neurologist often demonstrates various physical acts among others. See NPIs 21:5; 36:22. Another example (excerpt 46) of this is taken from NPI 22, line 69 to 71 (see appendix IV for background information and the complete interaction).

Excerpt 46

69. N: I'm surprised you did not notice this early enough. What happened mama?

70. R: I've had some other children before. I have lost a male child to this before ((kneeling down)). He had an injury about one and half years.

71. N: I know you want this child to marry. But we would have to refer you. We cannot say because he has erectile illness, we would stop his treatment. Maybe he should go to endocrinologist to examine him. He might also need to see a psychiatrist so they can help him in the aspects of the desire for the opposite sex. It is possible that he has desires for a woman later and be productive. You don't need to cry. They'll check him up and advise you properly. I'll want you to come back next week. So, we'll re-present your matter to the other specialist. Have you had sex with a girl before?

5.4.1.4 Prosody in the deliberative model

Doctors deploying the deliberative communicative model employs a lot of nuances during consultation with patients. This is a recurring strategy of being convincingly persuasive. The various variations in the utterances (intonation and emphasis) of some neurologist observed establish that their tones are instrumental in shaping the behaviours and responses of patients. For example, in NPI 22: 73-90:

Excerpt 47: NPI 22

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 1 year; Patient: male; Age: 35 years; Occupation: Artisan; Ailment: Neurotic dysfunctional erectile; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

73. N: Let him ANSWER, you are not the one we are asking. You can't know.
74. P: I have not done it before.
75. N: ARE YOU SURE?
76. P: Only when I was small that I did it
77. N: You (0.8) PUT IT INSIDE?
78. P: Yes
79. N: When?
80. P: When I was small.
81. N: How old were you then
82. P: Twelve?
83. N: Are you sure? What class were you? Primary or secondary?
84. P: I was about twelve years. I was about going to secondary school.
85. N: You'll come next week. We don't want you to spend for nothing. So, you'll come next week.
86. R: Please, I need your help so that there won't be operation sir ((to the researcher)).
87. N: Don't worry. Just come next week.
88. R: Should he eat before coming?
89. N: Yes. He should eat.
90. R: Thank you ma. Thank you sir.

Here, is a case of a male patient diagnosed with neurotic dysfunctional erectile. The mother has been pleading with the neurologist for a prompt intervention. The doctor, having realised that the case cannot be urgently attended to demands the understanding of the patient's relative by detailing the information to her and the patient. In the process, the doctor apportions speech prominence on certain words. Also, in line 85 of the same extract, the neurologist has reduced her pitch. In a bid to persuade the patient further, she adds:

We don't want you to spend for nothing

When the patient relative was not convinced, she turns to the researcher, convincing him for a doctor in line 86. The deployment of linguistic empathy is introduced by the neurologist in line 87, and in the process, she employs the pract of *assuring*. Here, the "just come next week" has pragmatic implication and suggests in other sense, the pragmatic act of offering help or *helping*.

5.5 Textual features of the deliberative model

The Table below presents a quick glance at the observable features of co-text in the NPIs within the perspective of the deliberative model.

Table 5.2: A glance at the observed contextual features of the deliberative model in NPI

Neurologist's textual pattern	Practs
Inference	elucidating, suggesting,
Reference	negotiating
Relevance	clarifying, teaching
Voice	persuading, convincing
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	guiding, helping
Patient's textual pattern	
Inference	listening, questioning
Reference	selecting, considering
Relevance	demanding
Voice	deciding
Shared Situational/Cultural/Personality Knowledge	appreciating

From the Table, the green segment entails the pragmatic choices utilised in context by neurologists in the interactions. These include elucidating, negotiating, clarifying, persuading and helping. All these for inference, reference, relevance, voice and share knowledge. On the other part, the pink refers to the practs exhibited by the patient, including their relatives. Some of the choices deployed are considering, selecting, questioning, demanding, deciding, appreciating. Also, all were located in the for inference, reference, relevance, voice and share knowledge.

5.6 Analysis of activity types utilised by subjects within the four models identified in the study

Table 5.3: Polarity of activity type in the NPI

Model	Conversational Acts	Speech Acts	Indirect Speech Acts	Psychological Acts	Prosody	Physical Acts
Paternalistic	+	+	+	+	+	+
Informative	+	+	-	-	-/+	+
Interpretive	+	+	-	-/+	-/+	+
Deliberative	+	+	-/+	-/+	+	+

The Table above accounts for the differences in the use of some features of pragmatic activity in the observed NPIs. These involve both interactants at all instances. The addition sign indicates the presence of the identified activity in the corresponding model while the subtraction indicates otherwise. By these, it can be deduced that conversation, speech, and physical acts are regular present features across all the four models studied. However, psychological acts may and/or may not be found in the interpretive and deliberative model, depending on the doctor's expertise, and other variables on the part of the patient. The paternalistic model utilises the activity type features acts in most of the studied situations.

The indirect speech acting is rare to the informative and interpretive act in an ideal neurologist-patient communication unlike the paternalistic and deliberative models, but when it appears, it performs a reactionary purpose in the NPI, (see 13:36). Furthermore, intonation, stress and other prosodic features are unavoidable cues in the human speech activities, the glaring emphasis is common in paternalistic and deliberative models but is

occasional in the other two models. The reason for this was unclear and can be a research interest to other scholars.

Table 5.4: Factors determining interaction in the study

Model	Inference	Reference	Relevance	Voice	Shared (S., C., P.) Knowledge	Metaphor	Metapragmatic Joker
Paternalistic	+	+	+	+	+	-/+	-
Informative	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Interpretive	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Deliberative	+	+	+	+	+	-/+	-

Table 4.10 above captures the textual features of the four models. Remarkably, they all featured positively with regards to inference, reference, relevance, and voice, all of which can be categorised under the shared information knowledge. The assumption here is based on the two recognised factors (in Mey 2001:116) that suggests the power that one brings with one, in virtue of one’s status as a physician or patient; and second, the successful negotiation in the course of the interaction. Both of these are considered mutual and actually help in achieving the goals of communication. Mey emphatically observes that doctors rely on the patients to obtain “crucial information” as the patients also rely on the doctors for a remedy to the ailment. The other item in the notion of pragmeme, the metaphor is absent in the informative and interpretive models. The metapragmatic joker is not found in any of the four models in the study.

5.7 Structures of the discourse strategies in the study

Table 5.5: Structures of the discourse strategies employed by subjects in the study

Model	Linguistic repression	Turn taking	Conversational pattern	Discourse strategies	Relationship	Dialogic Acts (BM)	Institutionalised talks	Politeness strategy
Paternalistic	rare	sequential	slightly casual	simplified conventions & registers	asymmetry	both	lax	consequential
Informative	neutral	doctor-controlled	adjacency pairs	Precise detailing	symmetry	doctor mediated	strict	inconsequential
Interpretive	rare	interactive	monologic	confirmatory & routine talks	symmetry	doctor mediated	formal	inconsequential
Deliberative	common	bargaining	negotiating	deliberative	asymmetry	both	semi-formal	consequential

Table 5.5 presents the structure of the neurologist-patient interactions of the studied locations and subjects in line with the Emanuel and Emanuel 1992 model of doctor-patient communication. Regarding the aspect of linguistic repression, the practice is rare among neurologist who selected paternalistic or interpretive communication model. It is not realised in the informative but common in the deliberative model. The implication of this is that patients of the studied location tend to benefit from the factual presentation of their health needs and would be able to take an informed decision where necessary. The reason identified with the common use of the linguistic repression is due to the persuasive aim of the neurologist concerned.

For turn-taking, this is sequential in the paternalistic and doctor-controlled in the informative. The interpretive has an interactive turn, while it is paired in the adjacency form in the deliberative model. The conversational pattern of the paternalistic model is slightly casual with neurologists using familiar terms and easy to identify registers as the discourse strategies in the interactions with patients, (see NPI 32). The informative pattern of conversation is mainly adjacency paired, (see NPI 13). In this, the discourse strategies include turn-taking which is expressed in formal linguistic choice with precise details coupled with a whole lot of institutional talks (See NPI 14). The communication in the interpretive is more of a monologically patterned. Within this context, the routine opening and closing interpersonal communication strategy are observed. Through this, the neurologists merely start and end the interactions at that point that he/she deems the interpretive situation is completed, see (NPI 23).

The paternalistic model reflected slightly casual conversational conventions and registers. With regards to the informative model, the use of adjacency pairs, formal turn-

taking, precise detailing, institutional talks, and dialogic strategies were the order. Monologic contribution was the norm in the interpretive model with the confirmatory and routine opening-and-closing as its discourse strategies. The deliberative model follows the negotiating or deliberating pattern and conversational interactions as strategy.

Further, both paternalistic and deliberative models have the relationship between neurologists and patients patterned asymmetrically, whereas the informative and interpretive are symmetrical. Similarly, body move(ment) was prominent by both neurologist and the patients in paternalistic and deliberative models. However, this is mainly doctor-mediated in both informative and interpretive models.

Mey (2001:301) says that in institutionalised discourses, “the value of the individual’s linguistic expression is measured strictly by the place he or she has in the institution”. In such situation, Mey avers that “only utterances which meet the criteria of the official discourse are allowed and registered; others are rejected...”. At the studied locations, the observed NPIs show that institutional talks are not tense nor compelled on the patients through the communicative strategies employed. However, among NPIs that adopt the informative model, institutional talks are strictly adhered to, as information required from the patient were strictly those that bear on the diagnosis or therapy, (see NPI 34:13). In the interpretive model, the institutional talks were formally engaged. In most cases, what most patients do is to sit and listen to the doctor as he or she gives his or her interpretation of their health status. Institutional talks in the deliberative model are often semi-formal. This is because as much as the neurologist attempt at deliberating with the patient, there is an inherent aim of persuasion, so as to ensure that the therapeutic options selected by patients are those that are capable of benefiting the patient in terms of improved health outcome.

The socio-cultural influence such as the age of the patients, language spoken and duration of the visit to the hospitals, coupled with the doctor’s experience, his or her social mien and worldviews is significant only in the paternalistic model. In the other, the significance of these cannot be sustained. Finally, politeness strategies such as exhibited through greetings, courtesies, news delivery and so on, do not have much bearing on both informative and the interpretive models. However, these are prevalent in the paternalistic and deliberative models.

5.8 Quantitative descriptions of the models in the observed NPIs

The chart below provides a summary of the communication models observed in the NPIs of SWUTH.

Fig 5.1: Frequency distribution of the models in the observed NPIs

The figure above depicts the frequencies of the different communication models studied across the University teaching hospitals in the Southwestern, Nigeria. Although, the pragmatic communication indices suggest that there is a prominent interplay among the four models in the forty (40) interactions observed, in discursive isolated cases, paternalistic communication model, features prominently in twenty-seven (27) interactions representing sixty-seven percent (67%), thus becoming the predominantly

employed model. This model was mainly employed by consultants. It is worth mentioning that the requirement to becoming a consultant in the studied hospitals is six years. This is followed by the deliberative model which features prominently in seven (7) interactions, representing eighteen percent (18%). The Informative model, which is the least, featured in two (2) interaction interactions only. This gives a representation of five percent (5%) of the observed NPIs. For Interpretive communication model, it is prominent in four (4) interactions representing ten percent (10%) representation. From the study, other models of communication, namely: deliberative, informative, and interpretive were mainly deployed by those within the rank of registrar and below across the selected university teaching hospitals.

From the data analysed for the study, the goal and patterns, discourse strategies, pragmatic acts, and contexts that shaped the entire interactions are represented in with schema below.

Fig. 5.2: Representation of neurologist-patient interaction in selected southwestern university teaching hospitals

Source: This researcher, 2017

The schema above represents the findings in neurologist-patient interaction in the selected southwestern university teaching hospitals in Nigeria. This implies that the goals in the interaction are both diagnostic and therapeutic. The goals were achieved with the adoption of various consultative or communicative models: paternalistic, informative, interpretive and paternalistic. Each of these has varying discourse strategies that were deployed by the interactants. The utilisation of these strategies in each model of communication produced varying pragmatic acts (practs). In the study, the relationship between neurologist and patients is mainly uneven in the paternalistic model but even in the informative model. There is slight unevenness in the interpretive model. Similarly, in the deliberative model, the relationship is more uneven as the neurologist has more control on the negotiation than the patient. Irrespective of this, the relationship is shaped by the shared knowledge of both interactants based on the experience of neurologists and the peculiarities of patients at each instance of neurologist-patient interaction. It should be noted that the schema is a distinct description of the studied neurologist-patient interaction. From this, a more generalisable structure is deduced.

5.9 Generalisable structure of NPI from the observed SWUTH

From the analysis, it is discovered that selection of communication model in doctor-patient relationship is a challenging task. Therefore, the schema below is construed.

Fig. 5.3: Generalisable structure of NPI from the observed SWUTH

Source: This researcher, 2017

From the scheme above, the black dotted green oval represents available communication models like the Emanuel and Emanuel's four. The box suggests doctor-patient setting. It would be noticed that there is a big black dot in the isolated oval. This is to emphasise that the model being studied is not the biggest, nor the most preferred. Again, the separation of the green oval from others implies that these models are available by default as choices to be made between doctors and their patients. On the co-joined oval, is the environmental factor that may impair or benefit the patient in terms of language, exposure, experience, age, education and others, towards the procurement of health services. Next is the doctor's environment, which includes training, certification, experience, professional and work ethics, and so on. All these factors have significant influences on the hospital interaction which lead to the achievement of the goals which

the patients and the doctors intend to achieve. The understanding of all these variables to the hospital context is capable of bringing about motivated doctor-patient relationship. In consequence, engenders a healthy society.

5.10 Summary

In this chapter, analyses of the remaining two of the four Emanuel and Emanuel communication models for doctor-patient relationship were carried out. Topics involving the general comparison and categorisation of the other two models discussed in Chapter four were also presented. The next chapter is the summary and conclusion of the study with recommendations and suggestions for further studies.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.0 Introduction

This chapter is the concluding part of the study. It provides the summary of the previous chapters, findings of this study and recommendations for future research.

6.1 Summary

This study has been primarily preoccupied with the investigation of communication models in neurologist-patient interaction. In chapter one, the general introduction to the study was made. In doing this, missing links in the body of existing studies that necessitated this research were identified. Also, issues such as human communication; language processing and its components; language and speech disorder, causes, types and interventions among other issues were explored. Similarly, the study, being an exposition on model of communication in doctor-patient relationship, different models of communication or consultation were investigated. This led to the discovery of the Emanuel and Emanuel models which are adopted for testing in this study. Further, information on medical practice in Nigeria was provided, and then, how discourses are approached in hospital interactions was also unravelled. Information on the studied location and operational definition of term concluded the chapter, with a summary of the topics discussed.

The second chapter provides a body of review of related literature to the study. Particularly, existing researches on doctor-patient interaction and neurolinguistics. Pragmatics, which is the theoretical construct on which the study relies was explored, tracing the various school of thoughts in the discipline. Other related sub-topics useful for pragmatic-based study were also mentioned and their importance highlighted. Furthermore, the conceptual framework, that is, Emanuel and Emanuel's model of doctor-patient relationship (EDPR) was discussed after which the chapter was concluded with a remark.

In the third chapter, method of data collection and analysis were presented. Here, the ethical consideration for the data gathering was also highlighted. Approaching this study

from the perspective of pragmatics, in chapter four and five, Mey's pragmatic postulation was used to test the data collected from University teaching hospitals from the Southwestern part of Nigeria. Emanuel and Emanuel four models of communication in doctor-patient relationship were explored and adapted to verify their application to consultative communication. The summary, discussion of findings, conclusions, recommendations, and suggestions for further studies climaxed the research in chapter five.

6.2 Findings

The study is premised on examining communication model in neurologist patient interaction, with attention on selected University teaching hospitals in the Southwestern region of Nigeria. In the study, neurologist-patient interaction is tested from the conceptual framework of Emanuel and Emanuel's models which are paternalistic, informative, interpretive, and deliberative. The major discoveries of this study are as follows.

1. Communication goals

i. Diagnostic communication is an important goal towards achieving success in the NPI.

From the study, diagnostic communication is a very important goal and it is mainly spearheaded by the neurologists through the use of various practs, especially questioning. The attainment of this goal is enhanced by the patients' ability or otherwise at responding to the questions asked by neurologists. The diagnostic goal is also an institutional goal.

ii. Therapeutic communication is also a corresponding communication goal in neurologist-patient interaction.

In the observed neurologist-patient interactions, both diagnostic and therapeutic intertwine. Although, therapeutic goal is the major motivation for the patients (or their relations) in the consultative meeting with neurologists. The attainment of both goals is mutual between the interactants as each of them plays significant roles towards the attainment of the goals. In this, the patients supply information to the doctor as much as

he or she is capable of giving. The neurologists also rely on the information to make appropriate diagnosis and suggestions.

2. The patterns or models of communication in SWUTH's NPI vary.

Depending on other varying circumstances like the year of experience of neurologists, age and nature of ailments of patients, the identified patterns of communication in the observed hospitals are the **paternalistic, informative, interpretive** and **deliberative**. These can be packaged into the acronym, PIID.

i. There is an interplay among the four communication models in SWUTH NPIs.

An obvious observation in the course of the study is that there is a regular interplay among the four communication models in SWUTH NPIs.

ii. Paternalistic model is predominantly used by neurologists who are more experienced.

Despite the interplay of the four models of communication, the paternalistic model of NPI is the predominantly selected pattern in SWUTH. The deployment of this model is common in both the diagnostic and therapeutic stages of doctor-patient relationship in the observed interactions, especially with neurologists with over six years in practice. Most of the neurologists in this category were found in the SWUTHs observed but were fewer in LAUTECHUTH, Osogbo.

iii. The informative model is rarely employed.

The informative model is rarely employed in isolated cases of SWUTH NPIs. It was noticed that the deployment of this model is common only at the level of diagnostic communication such as when the result of the already executed clinical test is about being delivered.

iv. The interpretive model also has a rare selection instance in the studied NPIs.

In the isolated consideration where a communication model is used from the beginning of an NPI to the ending, the interpretive model also has a rare case of being selected in the entire NPIs. The interpretive is however found in some pre-therapeutic communication. In other words, it is often deployed as a follow-up consultation for

previous diagnoses and therapies done by neurologists. It is the second least adopted communication model in SWUTH NPIs.

v. The deliberative model is the second most prominent model employed in NPI.

The deliberative model is often employed through persuasion, especially in therapeutic discussions. The neurologists adopt this pattern more with certain patients, especially those with better ability to make their own therapeutic choices from the available options provided by the neurologists.

3. Distinguishing discourse strategies of SWUTH's NPI

i. Regarding the strategies for each communication model, it is observed that the paternalistic model conveys slightly casual conversational conventions and registers.

ii. In the informative model, the use of adjacency pairs, formal turn-taking, precise detailing, institutional talks, and dialogic strategies were found.

iii. Monologic contribution was the norm in the interpretive model involving the confirmatory and routine opening-and-closing discourse strategies.

iv. In the deliberative model, the negotiating conversational strategy was the norm.

4. Distinctive pragmatic acts in the SWUTH's NPI

i. Activity features and practs in the paternalistic model

Paternalistic model featured the deployment of the situated speech acts, psychological and physical acts, via patients' quarrel-induced acts, controlled and managed through neurologists' shared situation knowledge. Neurologists' practs were empathising, pacifying, promising and instructing practs. While the patients' practs were explaining, provoking, associating and greeting in the paternalistic model.

ii. Activity features and practs in the informative model

The informative model revealed the use of the speech, prosody and physical acts, the practs of declaring, alerting and informing were utilised by neurologists, while the patients exploited adapting, requesting and selecting practs.

iii. Activity features and practs in the interpretive model

The interpretive model involves the communicative activities of the speech, prosody and physical acts. Practs utilised were those of deducing, predicting, prioritising and

interpreting practs by neurologists; while patients adopted conforming, inquiring, requesting and deciding practs.

iv. Activity features and practs in the deliberative model

In the deliberative model of neurologist-patient interaction, the speech, prosody and physical acts were also utilised. In this model, practs of suggesting, teaching, persuading and convincing were utilised by the neurologists, while the patients deployed the practs of questioning, demanding, considering and deciding.

5. Contexts that shape SWUTH's NPI

i. Neurologist experience is key to communication model selection and attainment of communicative goals.

Neurologist's expertise backed by experience usually helps in determining the selection of model(s) and utilisation towards the achievement of the communicative goals through which many pragmatic acts were performed.

ii. Mutual cultural values play a very significant role in the determination of the communication model adopted by the interactants.

The role of culture here reflects an adaptive tendency towards the achievement of diagnostic and therapeutic goals. It was noticed that the neurologists' personality, cultural awareness coupled with the patients' social awareness in the communicative context are major contributors to the patients' health outcomes.

iii. Patients' need, ability and emotions often influence the selection of varied patterns of communication in some NPIs.

Patient's occupation, age and nature of ailment are significant to the determination of linguistic choices and strategies such as appropriate turn-taking, controlled institutional talks, and principled utilisation of politeness strategies. The variables also help in checkmating instances of linguistic repression by neurologists and repositioning the patients in making informed health decisions. In some other cases, patients' need, ability and emotions also often influence the selection of various communication models in some of the NPIs.

iv. Consideration for patient's peculiarity, not the application of a generalised body of theories, helps neurologists in their selection of communication models.

Communication model in neurologist-patient interaction in the observed university teaching hospitals in the Southwestern states of Nigeria is determined by pragmatic communication variables such as context of discourse (like patient's ability and neurologist's expertise), shared situation knowledge, shared cultural knowledge, and shared personality knowledge rather than neurologists' strict adherence to scholarly theoretical prescriptions.

6.3 Recommendations

The proponents of various communication models discussed in the study (including others not discussed) make attractive assumptions in their recommendations of the models. The consensus among scholars (like Emanuel and Emanuel, 1992, Pellegrino, 2006; Oprea, 2009) is that the adoption of the paternalistic pattern in doctor-patient interaction should be discarded. For instance, some critics of the paternalistic model assumed that it is capable of reducing respect for patients' opinion. However, in the studied SWUTHs, paternalistic model is found to be the most convenient communication model between neurologists and their patients. Does this imply that patients in the studied location are poorly medically cared for? This perhaps can be a topic in another research. Therefore, a model of communication is best utilised in specific contexts. Rather than advocate specific communication model in an opened blanket situation, what is required is to investigate the suitability of such model to which patient-doctor relationship, when and how. This understanding is capable of engendering a functional and effective doctor-patient relationship towards the improvement of the societal well-being.

In any doctor-patient interaction, one of the goals of such meeting is information. Again, the question is, while attempting to respect the values of patients in health decision, will the goal be attained by the mere supply of information? The answer is obviously no. Many of the critics of the informative model have also made similar reservations. Some of them aver that the informative model is mainly therapeutic (Emanuel and Emanuel 1992; Frosthalm, Fink, Oernboel, Christensen, Toft, et al, 2005; Pellegrino, 2006; and Oprea, 2009). Since the provision of information alone on the patients' ailment does not provide a cure on its own but rely on interpretive communication for necessary action towards therapy, the over-reliance on this model may not be suitable. Therefore, doctors

employing the informative should ensure that the model is employed in the proper and necessary contexts.

In a nutshell, theoretical assumptions and recommendations are necessary for doctor-patient relationship. However, since context and socio-cultural values shared by interactants in doctor-patient relationship override theoretical values in the selection of relevant communication patterns, the role of context in diagnostic and therapeutic consultation as a major determinant of suitable communication model in hospital interactions should be sustained. In line with this, training of neurologists and other medical practitioners alike with regards to the best practices towards the improvement of quality healthcare delivery should be encouraged.

A good knowledge of communication model, especially in Nigerian hospitals is capable of enhancing performance among medical practitioners. This includes the experienced and the up and coming medical doctors such as the medical students. The medical students might be able to form an opinion regarding useful communication models in their later practice in hospitals if they have unhindered access to efficient doctor-patient communication in the teaching hospitals and concentrate on varying dimensions. Apart from this, the exposure is capable of fostering in them the various dynamics of hospital interactions, and also avail them the privilege of understanding how studies in language examine their communicative roles.

There is the possibility of medical practitioners not being up-to-date with the modern dimension of the practice, especially in the aspect of communication. The danger this portends is ineffective and inefficient medical care. This is affirmed by Murray, Lo, Pollack, Donelan, Catania, et al (2003) that if the patients feel that a physician is being challenged communicatively, a deteriorating patient-physician relationship is possible. This has a negative consequence to the well-being of the patients. Hence, selection of appropriate communication in consultative and other communicative instances cannot be over-emphasised but must be sustained. Some other studies have shown the patients' displeasure regarding their doctors' communication skills which often leads to loss of faith or trust in the medical practitioner. It thus implies that medical practitioners must be fully alerted to the role of language choice in consultative communication with patients. Since a poor linguistic-exchange in doctor-patient relationship is capable of influencing

the success or otherwise of the communication goal, such as threatening or improving patient healthcare, doctors must be well informed and be encouraged to adapt to the available communication model considered best for self and their patients.

6.4 Conclusion

Communication models are important diagnostic and therapeutic tools. Where not incapacitated, patients in hospital interactions must be encouraged to play active roles as stakeholders in the diagnostic and therapeutic communication contexts. Physicians must familiarise themselves with existing communication models and must not over-generalise due to scholars' advocacy for a specific model. Rather, practitioners should allow pragmatic communication indices and context to guide them in making choices in their relationship with patients. Public and relative of patients in doctor-patient interaction must be aware of their status as stakeholders in the interaction. Through this, the sustenance of a healthy society with proper utilisation of communication models in hospital interactions is achievable.

6.5 Suggestions for further studies

This study investigated pragmatics of neurologist-patient interaction in selected university teaching hospitals within the southwestern region of Nigeria only. This has excluded the other five geopolitical regions of the country, namely, the south-east, south-south, north-east, north-west, and north-central. In any of these regions, researchers should carry out analysis of neurologist-patient interaction in the other existing university teaching hospitals. The restriction of this study to university teaching hospitals can also be jettisoned in future research, in order to include specialist hospitals, federal medical centres and any other hospitals, private or public, where the target subjects can be located.

Similarly, a comparative study of the communication in the neurologist-patient interaction between one region to the other can be attempted. This is capable of describing the uniqueness of hospital interactions from one region of the country to another if any. Again, researchers may be interested in finding out why certain patterns are exhibited in one region and such is repeated or non-existence in the other. It is worthy of note that there are many theoretical applications to neurologist-patient

interaction other than pragmatics. Such theories considered suitable by any future researches can be used in analysing the data collected from the various locations.

Since this study examined the communication goals, patterns, discourse strategies, pragmatic acts, and contexts that shape the hospital situation of only the neurologist-patient discourse, other researchers might be interested in exploring these communication goals, patterns, discourse strategies and others in other specialised hospital situations, such as the gynecologist-patient, urologist-patient, paediatrician-patient's parent, optician-patient, psychiatrist-patient among many others. Further, the role of context in the determination of neurologist-patient interaction and peculiarity to specific study location other than those identified in this study can also be attempted.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I

List of certificates and documents of approval for bio-ethics research

APPENDICES

Appendix I

Certificates of Approval for Bio-Ethics Research

West African Bioethics

Wednesday, July 01, 2015

NCHRE Training Trial

Certificate of Completion

In recognition of successful completion of the revision of the Nigerian National Code for Health Research Ethics online training program of the West African Bioethics Training Program and the National Health Research Ethics Committee of Nigeria. This certifies that

Ayodele James Akínola

- ♦ *reviewed regulatory and informational documents on human-subject protection*
- ♦ *passed a quiz on the responsible conduct of human studies*
- ♦ *signed a statement of commitment to the protection of the rights and welfare of human subjects participating in research.*

Dr. Clement A. Adebamowo
BM ChB (Hons), FWACS FACS scD
Professor of Surgery
Director, West African Bioethics Training Program

Cc: Program Administrator, WAB

**EKITI STATE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL
ADO-EKITI, NIGERIA.**

ETHICS AND RESEARCH COMMITTEE

CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

PROTOCOL NUMBER: EKSUTH /A67/2016/05/007
PROJECT TITLE : PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF COMMUNICATION
IN NEUROLOGIST-PATIENT INTERACTIONS IN SOUTH-WEST
NIGERIA'S EKSUTH.

INVESTIGATOR(S) : AKINOLA AYODELE JAMES.
SUPERVISOR(S) : A.B SUNDAY PH.D .
DEPARTMENTS : ENGLISH.
INSTITUTION : DEPARTMENT OF ENGLISH UNIVERSITY
OF IBADAN.

DATE CONSIDERED: 16/05/2016.

DECISION OF COMMITTEE:

CHAIRMAN: Dr. J.O FADARE

APPROVED

SIGNATURE & DATE:

J.O Fadare
19/5/16

DECLARATION BY INVESTIGATOR/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

PROTOCOL NUMBER (Please quote in all enquires) EKSUTH /A67/2016/05/007

*To be completed in three copies and two copies returned to the Secretary; Ethics
and Research Committee, University Teaching Hospital, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.*

I/we fully understand the conditions under which I am/we are authorise to
conduct the above-mentioned research and I/we guarantee that I/we will ensure
compliance with these conditions. Should any departure be contemplated from
the research procedure as approved, I/we undertake to resubmit the protocol to
the Ethics and Research Committee.

Signature *[Signature]*

Date: 20-07-2016

NB: Any erasure, cancellation or alteration renders this certificate invalid.

RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE

LADOKE AKINTOLA UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY TEACHING HOSPITAL
OSOGBO, OSUN STATE, NIGERIA.

Address:
P.M.B 5000, Osogbo
039-200309,
e-mail: researchethicscommittee.lth@gmail.com

PROF. OLUWADIYA K.S - CHAIRMAN
MRS SAM-ASIEGBU Y.U - SECRETARY

Our Ref: LTH/REC/2016/04/29/271
Your Ref:
Date: 29th April, 2016

CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

PROTOCOL NUMBER LTH/EC/2016/04/271
PROJECT TITLE: *Pragmatic Study of Communication in Neurologist-Patient Interactions in Tertiary Health Facilities in South-West Nigeria.*
INVESTIGATOR(S): Akinola Ayodele James
DEPARTMENT / INSTITUTION: Department of English, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State.
SUBMISSION OF PROTOCOL: FEBRUARY, 2016.
FINAL CONSIDERATION: APRIL, 2016.
DECISION OF THE COMMITTEE: APPROVED
CHAIRMAN: Prof. Oluwadiya K. S (FMCS)
SIGNATURE & DATE:

NOTE: THE COMMITTEE IS EXEMPTED FROM LIABILITY OF THE PROPOSAL AND THIS CERTIFICATE WILL BE REVOKED IF PROTOCOLS STATED IN THE PROPOSAL IS DEVIATED FROM.

DECLARATION BY INVESTIGATOR (S)

PROTOCOL NUMBER (Please quote in all enquiries): LTH/EC/2016/04/271

To be completed in four and three copies returned to the secretary, Ethics and Research Committee, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria.

I/We fully understand the conditions under which I am/we are authorized to conduct the above – mentioned research and I/We will ensure compliance with these conditions. Should any departure be contemplated from the research procedure as approved, I/We undertake to resubmit the protocol to the Ethics and Research Committee.

Signature.......... Date..... 05-08-2016

PROF. OLAITAN P.B | PROF. ADENIJI A.O | PROF. AYODELE O.E | DR. EEGUNRANTI B.A | DR. ADEKANLE D.A | DR. OPARINDE D.P | DR. OWOLADE O.A
DR. OYEDEJI O.A | DR. OLAOSUN A. O | DR. AREMU A.A | BARR. AKIRINADE O | MR. MUHIBI M.A | MR. ADEYEYE A.D | MR. ABIOYE S.A
PST. OWOLABI G.O | MRS. ADEYEYE O.O | MRS. LAWAL R.O | MRS. OYEWOLE C.A | MRS. OYEDEJI O.I | MRS. ADEWUYA O.A

OLABISI ONABANJO UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL, SAGAMU P.M.B. 2001, SAGAMU, NIGERIA.

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Website: www.oouth.com

Chairman, Medical Advisory Committee:

Dr. O. B. Ogunfowora
MBBS, FWACP (Paed)
Tel: +234-805-638-0426
E-mail: olufowora5@yahoo.com
cmac@oouth.com

Our Ref: OOUTH/HREC/46/2016

Your Ref: _____

Date: 25th May, 2016

HREC REG. NUMBER: NHREC/08/10/2012

Mr. Akinola Ayodele James,
Department of English,
University of Ibadan,
Ibadan.

CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL

Re: Pragmatic Study of Communication in Neurologist-Patient Interactions in Tertiary Health Facilities in Southwest Nigeria

I wish to inform you that following appropriate review, the OOUTH- Health Research Ethics Committee has granted you an approval to proceed on the above study for a period of one year from Wednesday, 25th May, 2016 to Wednesday, 24th May, 2017.

You are to note that this approval is given on the basis of your corrected Protocol. Any proposed change in the protocol should be communicated to the Committee for consideration ahead of execution.

Kindly inform the Committee when the study is to commence to facilitate monitoring by designated representative(s) of the OOUTH Health Research Ethics Committee.

Prof. P.O. Olatunji
Chairman, OOUTH-HREC

SAVE A LIFE: DONATE TO OOUTH

INSTITUTE FOR ADVANCED MEDICAL RESEARCH AND TRAINING (IAMRAT)

College of Medicine, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Director: **Prof. Catherine O. Falade**, MBBS (Ib), M.Sc, FMCP, FWACP

Tel: 0803 326 4593, 0802 360 9151

e-mail: cfalade@comui.edu.ng lillyfunke@yahoo.com

UI/UCH EC Registration Number: NHREC/05/01/2008a

NOTICE OF FULL APPROVAL AFTER FULL COMMITTEE REVIEW

Re: Pragmatic Analysis of Diagnostic Communication in Neurologist-Patient Interactions in South-West Nigeria's University Teaching Hospitals

UI/UCH Ethics Committee assigned number: UI/EC/15/0389

Name of Principal Investigator: **Ayodele J. Akinola**

Address of Principal Investigator: Department of English,
Faculty of Arts,
University of Ibadan, Ibadan

Date of receipt of valid application: 16/10/2015

Date of meeting when final determination on ethical approval was made: **28/01/2016**

This is to inform you that the research described in the submitted protocol, the consent forms, and other participant information materials have been reviewed and *given full approval by the UI/UCH Ethics Committee.*

This approval dates from **28/01/2016 to 27/01/2017**. If there is delay in starting the research, please inform the UI/UCH Ethics Committee so that the dates of approval can be adjusted accordingly. Note that no participant accrual or activity related to this research may be conducted outside of these dates. *All informed consent forms used in this study must carry the UI/UCH EC assigned number and duration of UI/UCH EC approval of the study.* It is expected that you submit your annual report as well as an annual request for the project renewal to the UI/UCH EC early in order to obtain renewal of your approval to avoid disruption of your research.

The National Code for Health Research Ethics requires you to comply with all institutional guidelines, rules and regulations and with the tenets of the Code including ensuring that all adverse events are reported promptly to the UI/UCH EC. No changes are permitted in the research without prior approval by the UI/UCH EC except in circumstances outlined in the Code. The UI/UCH EC reserves the right to conduct compliance visit to your research site without previous notification.

Professor Catherine O. Falade

Director, IAMRAT

Chairperson, UI/UCH Ethics Committee

E-mail: uiuchec@gmail.com

APPENDIX II

Prototype of some of the instruments used for data collection in the study

UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN

DEPARTMENT OF ENGLISH

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

IRB Research approval number:

Title of research: Pragmatic study of communication model in neurologist-patient interactions in university teaching hospital, South-west Nigeria

Name and affiliation of researcher of applicant: This study is being conducted by Akinola Ayodele James of the University of Ibadan

Sponsor of research: The study is self-sponsored and it is in partial fulfilment of the award of a Ph. D. in English Language of the University of Ibadan.

Purpose of research: The purpose of this research is to provide a contextual framework on the pragmatic features of neurologist - patient interactions. Because interest and works in this area remain scanty in Nigeria, with a high rate of ignorance of the subject, the study is to complement existing studies on neurolinguistics and medical discourse in Africa and the world at large.

Procedure of the research: The procedure of data collection involves structured questionnaire, note-taking of observed non-verbal behaviours of the interactants (neurologist - patient) and also with the use of audio recording device for verbal communication.

Expected duration of research and of participants' involvement: You are expected to participate in the study whenever you are on (consultation) duty within the twelve (12) months of the study.

Risk: You will not be exposed to any risk by your participation in the study.

Cost: Your participation in this research will not cost you anything.

Benefit: The study will be beneficial to speech pathologists, communication specialists, neurolinguists, neurologists, psycholinguists, psychologists, language teachers, discourse analysts and the general populace. The findings are to provide a contextual framework for interactions with people suffering from language or communication disorder.

Confidentiality: The identity of personalities involved in the interactions would not be revealed as they remained confidential. No information will be shared in regards to the persons observed in this study; rather they are to be coded as 'P 1, 2, 3 and N 1, 2, 3 respectively and so on.

Voluntariness: Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary.

Alternative to participation: If you choose not to participate, this will not affect you in any way.

Due inducement: There will not be any form of due inducement.

Consequences of participants' decision to withdraw from research and procedure for orderly termination of participant: The researcher promises to make all efforts in complying with your wishes as much as is practicable.

Modality of providing treatment and actions to be taken in case of injury or adverse events: The study does not involve any form of treatment and as such, no injury or adverse event is envisaged.

What happens to research participants and communities when the research is over: The study is to be submitted as a research in partial fulfilment of the award of a Ph. D. in English language in the Department of English, University of Ibadan, Ibadan. During the course of this research, you will be informed about any information that may affect your continued participation.

Statement about sharing of benefits among researchers and whether this includes or excludes research participants: If this research leads to commercial products, the researcher shall own it. There is no plan to contact any participant now or in future about such commercial benefits.

Any apparent or potential conflict of interest: The researcher does not own shares in the University College Hospital, Ibadan or its associated institutions. I am unaware of any other information that may cause me not to do this research with fear or favour.

Statement of person obtaining informed consent:

I have fully explained this research to _____

And have given sufficient information, including about risks and benefits, to make an informed decision.

DATE: _____ SIGNATURE _____

NAME _____

APPENDIX III

Instrument used for the background information of the subjects observed

NPI	Neurologist's		Patient's				
	Gender	Years of Experience	Gender	Age	Occupation	Ailment	Visitation status
1	Male	6	Male	68	Retired	Dementia	A
2	Male	6	Female	32	Civil Servant	Seizure	A
3	Female	3	Female	58	Self-employed	Insomnia +	A
4	Male	11	Male	20	Student	Epilepsy	A
5	Male	6	Female	28	Not employed	Seizure +	A
6	Male	undisclosed	Female	20	Student	Seizure	A
7	Male	3	Male	53	Retired	Parkinson	A
8	Male	Undisclosed	Female	27	Law graduate	Migraine +	UA
9	Male	6	Male	66	Retired	Diabetes +	A
10	Male	2	Male	43	Lecturer	Hypertension +	UA
11	Male	4	Male	69	Retired	Alzheimer	A
12	Female	3	Female	75	Self-employed	Stroke	A
13	Male	Undisclosed	Female	45	Self-employed	Migraine	A
14	Female	1	Female	54	Self-employed	Panik attack	A
15	Male	6	Female	65	Civil servant	Amnesia	A
16	Male	15	Female	55	Civil servant	Seizure	A
17	Female	2	Male	40	Self-employed	Diabetes +	A
18	Male	4	Female	26	Student	Seizure	A
19	Female	2	Female	60	Retired	Aphasia	A
20	Female	8	Female	64	Retired	Seizure	A
21	Male	4	Male	37	Undisclosed	Migraine	A
22	Female	1	Male	35	Self-employed	Dysfunctional erectile	A
23	Female	3	Male	13	Pupil	Dyslexia	A
24	Male	2	Male	66	Undisclosed	Stuttering +	A
25	Female	3	Female	45	Self-employed	Migraine	A
26	Male	2	Male	58	Retired	Aphasia	A
27	Female	4	Female	48	Civil servant	Seizure	A
28	Female	5	Male	71	Retired	Stroke	A
29	Male	2	Female	54	Undisclosed	Aneurysm	A
30	Female	6	Female	47	Retired	Stroke	A
31	Male	2	Female	51	Civil servant	Seizure +	A
32	Male	7	Female	62	Retired	Stroke	A
33	Male	5	Female	66	Undisclosed	Dementia	A
34	Male	9	Female	36	Self-employed	Post concussive	A
35	Male	9	Female	75	Undisclosed	Migraine	A
36	Male	4	Male	68	Retired	Stroke	A
37	Male	10	Male	73	Retired	Stroke	A
38	Female	4	Male	43	Self-employed	Hysteria	A
39	Male	5	Male	23	Student	Comprehension +	A
40	Male	13	Male	71	Retired	Parkinson	A

Keys: A= Accompanied; UA= Unaccompanied; + = additional ailment

APPENDIX IV

Transcribed data collected for the study

NPI 1

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: male; Age: 68
Occupation: retired police officer; Ailment: Dementia Visitation status: accompanied
by a relation

6. P: What they gave me there, I don't understand?
7. N: Ha! It means you have gained some weight (0.2) which is good: When you came earlier, it was 68.
8. P: This morning?:::
9. N: Yes. The first time was 68. Today is also 68. So it's fine. Ha! ((smiles)) that's good it's our own measurement we rely on. The 72 must be an error. Maybe the scale was faulty. It's fine //. So it means you have a steady weight (0.2) that's improvement.
10. P: Thank you sir.
11. N: Now, let me say three words to you. This is what we usually do. And I will ask you by the time we are finishing the interaction to see if you can remember them. The three words are "goat, shoe and broom"
12. P: Goat, shoe and broom
13. N: Not now, I will ask you later whether you'll remember them. That's good !!
14. P: Oh ok.
15. N: I will also like to know whether you still go to Ife or not?
16. P: Yes, I still do.
17. N: What for?
18. P: Hmm. I've spent about one year there. ((Other conversation ensued for 4:53sec minutes which are deliberately left out for P^SP)).
19. N: Your recall is coming back.
20. P: Thank you Sir.
21. Nev: What are the three words I told you earlier? You'll need to remember
22. P: Hmm ... Em: : : br::oom
23. N: Yes !! One.
24. P: Shoe
25. N: £ Two! Excellent
26. ((Applause by R))
27. N: What is the third one?
28. P: Excuse Sir.
29. N: Yes. Because during your first time here (0.4) But say the third one first.
30. P: Broom, shoe, hmm, hmm! Ha! ((disappointed in self))
31. N: You tried! Goat.
32. P: Goat!
33. N: You tried. So, the last time you couldn't remember any.
34. P: Oh oh
35. N: Now that you can recall two out of three. That's great! That's the only way we can measure improvement. So, you are doing well. You are really making progress. So, we will continue our medication. I won't change anything. The constipation will be taking care of. Just be rest assured. ((Other conversation))) > ((keeps writing)) (0:2)

So I have removed the.... I have included drugs to help his sleeping habit. ((explains other drugs and usefulness)). And then, we can now give him long appointment. So I will give him three months. They will write the exact date for you outside. So that we can then see if there are obvious changes. Thank you very much. I will see you in three months

36. P: I' m grateful. ((smiles)) You have a very big passion for work.

37. N: Thank you Sir . (and and and) Enjoy yourself Sir.

NPI 2

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: female; Age: 32; Occupation: Teacher; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

31. P: Good morning

32. N: Well done. How are you? What's the situation? So, what's the situation?

33. P: Yes. I've seen the gynaecologist. And by the time I went to see him for the scan, my baby was already gone.

34. N: Okay

35. P: And they have to evacuate as soon as possible. And so they evacuated the baby. And they said it was due to (...)

36. N: Okay. Alright (0.4) so that's not necessarily correct. That's not necessarily correct. It's not. At least we've had patients like yours (...). We can change your drugs. There is no drug in this world that is safe for the first trimester of pregnancy. There is no drug. The only drug that is not recommended in pregnancy is sodium (...). So it's not that drug that caused what happened. What has happened had happened. Not because of (...). Certainly, that wasn't at all.

37. P: So what would have happened?

38. N: The baby might have been malformed:- But not the effect of the drug. You could check your Google. You could check it on the internet.

39. P: I goggled with my sister. Drugs could be responsible in (...)

40. N: Any drug:- Not just Benotoin.

41. P: Benotoin

42. N: Not just Benotoin. No! Any drug. The only drug that is not recommended is (...Biotrate) So::: Any drugs. Any drugs.

43. P: According to Dr P^{SP}, the Benotoin was too high. Probably, the baby was just (...)

44. N: How experience is the gynaecologist?

45. P: Professor P^{SP}

46. N: P^{SP}. Probably its ... (0.4). You see the thing is like maintaining a balance between a neurological disease and a pregnancy. And the choice is yours. To find a drug that will work. And you have a foetus.

47. P: It (0.2) that's special.

48. N: No drug is recommended in first trimester. There is no where somebody will say use this drug. Any drug taken in the first twelve weeks of pregnancy can result into anything. That's the standard in the world. So (0.2) but they have varying degrees of affectation. If Kepra is good, you take it along with vitamins. The usual thing you do in first trimester is take vitamins, take Folic Acid. And then (0.2) After 20 weeks. Then do amino synthesis to check overdose. But there is nothing we can do before then.

49. R: Okay. What I want to ask is whether we should change this to any of the brands. Whether Kepra or any of the brands or she should continue. Is it not going to cause any deformation?
50. N: We are always optimistic. When you read about it. The thing they caused. They could cause abnormalities in the foetus. Any drug. And if the abnormality is severe enough, the nature will put up a natural defence.
51. R: Okay. Because Em. Dr P^{SP} said the foetus doesn't (...)
52. N: Yeah. Most drugs will cause (...)
53. P: And when we read about it. It's like, that was part of the (...) em side effects of the drugs.
54. N: Well I asked you before, you said you preferred it.
55. P: I was thinking it had no side effects.
56. N: All drugs have side effects, in pregnancy all.
57. P: So there is none you can recommend?
58. N: No. No. Not at all. Not at all. NOT (0.2) AT ALL
59. P: But Prof P^{SP} said that there are some drugs that are milder.
60. N: You were controlled on that one. You've forgotten our first conversation. Maybe one should be recording conversation. And you said you were happy with these drugs. Not that I was going to change it, but you said you were happy with them. And so, what else does one do. If they are milder drug, we could try, but it's at the expense of you having seizure. And if you have seizure, anything could happen as well. So, the best thing is keep your mind at rest. Hmm:: You were taking 300ml, that was a big dose but (0.2) that's what the dose that's controlled the seizure. So be it. If you reduce the dose to 200, you may have seizures. If you have seizures, the foetus is in jeopardy as well.
61. R: So, she should just continue with the 300 and (...)
62. N: Either that or we can trail it off. Maybe start with a (...)
63. P: Benytohin
64. N: Yea: (...) we try to keep you on a small dose of it. Then you can take in.
65. P: Sir, I've tried to take in
66. N: And what happened?
67. P: No: it was just Dr P^{SP} that told me to use Kepra to...
68. N: Why did you take Kepra?
69. P: He said Kepra was one of the new::: em drugs.
70. N: Women in child bearing age, we don't use Benitohin and it's not because of side effect and it's not because of foetus. It's just because of cosmetic side effect. That's the main reason.
71. P: So we should (..)
72. N: They are all the same. They are all drugs that can cause damage. and AS IF ANYONE IS LIKE A MESSIAH. There is none. NONE. For the first 12 weeks of pregnancy, nowhere in the world.
73. R: How to avoid seizures. That's?
74. N: Two ways. I mean Three ways. First one is (0.4) back down on the dose. So that you use a lower dose.
75. R: We've tried it. That week that we called you. That...
76. N: (You) had seizures
77. R: (We) had seizures ((simultaneous with neurologist))
78. N: That means that was the dose that is ideal for stopping seizure. So, you can't go lower. Second option is cut down the drug, substitute another drug. We usually tried

to use one drug not two drugs. There is a risk of interaction between the drugs, more side-effects, more cost and more damage.

79. R: Ehn ehn?
80. N: So, you'll bring one down, start building the other one.
81. P: So which one do we use?
82. N: So you've used (not clearly heard) Why do you stop it, If wasn't controlling seizures?
83. P: It was (0.8) my doctor said Kepra was a new drug (...)
84. N: We don't just pick drugs just like that. There is a scientific basis for treating anybody. You start with one drug. Keep the drug up at.
85. P: I used (...) for over a year.
86. N: Was it helpful?
87. P: Yeah
88. N: Why did you change to Kepra?
89. P: He didn't specify
90. N: Did you have seizures?
91. P: Yes I did.
92. N: So, seizures were uncontrolled?
93. P: Well, I had seizures then.
94. N: At what dose at that time?
95. P: I can't even remember how many ML I was using. I've taken (...)
96. N: How many? 200, 400 twice a day?
97. P: 200 once a day
98. N: Once a day won't work. The lifeline is about 12 hours. So, if you take once, it won't cover the whole 24 hours. So, chance of having a seizure will occur. So, what they should have done was to have put either a small dose in the evening or make it 200. Which is what we will try and do.
99. R: Okay.
100. N: So that before you take in again, we would try and stabilize you (...) much later you'll take folic acid and see what happens. If you stop Benotoil abruptly or cut it down and add (...) cut it down again, build up (...). Then you'll stop (...) and remain on (...) and then we'll see what happen.
101. P: How do we cut it?
102. N: I'll tell you when I'm ready.
103. R: Do we need to liaise with any O and G person?
104. N: Until she takes in.
105. R: Okay.
106. N: It's when she takes in that we advising need to register with O and G. When she takes in and I think she should just give herself time to recover. Let the drugs be stabilized. Let the leisure be controlled. Then she can take in. Then we'll notify prof P^{SP} who know about the case, that so so, and so had happened and make additional recommendations.
107. R: Okay Sir
108. N: No problem. The thing is that you can't be juggling drugs. Just because a new drug has come, you change people to the new drugs. No! You keep people on the same medication free of side effects and effective seizure control. If seizure is not controlled, you'll add another one and then, start small and slowly build on that. It's unfortunate (0.8) Ehn (0.4) Dr, Ehn Prof P^{SP} did not see you, the person who saw you, did so on behalf of professor P^{SP}. The person who did the procedure was

((checks ease note)) Doctor P^SP. You see! This is probably a senior registrar or registrar. And if he had seen you and he felt there was a need to discuss, he should have called me. That would be the proper thing in managing a patient. Not just give you information they don't know about. We refer you to them because that's the standard thing to do. They should have found out why you are on a particular medication. Rather...

109. R: Okay Sir.
110. N: Rather than saying it was a wrong drug, it was a wrong dose. It's not for them to decide. It's only the physician that should tell them what dose you are using. (He writes) 120 point 53. So what we'll do is that, you try 200 in the evening. Then, that we'll do for one week. Then we go for 100ml for another week. Then we'll start again. 200ml twice a day. So we'll just keep you on that one (0.8) for two weeks.
111. R: Thank you sir
112. N: So, we'll see probably in first week of April, that's April 1. Four weeks.
113. P: You said we should use (...)
114. N: I'll write it, I'll explain when I finished. In a minute ((He writes)). So that's it. ((Explain further)). If there is anything between it, just call me. ((He writes, explain assuring the prescription again)). All thing being equal, when we see, there should be no problem. So, four weeks. That's the first April.
115. R: Okay Sir
116. N: I'll be in the clinic
117. P: Thank you sir
118. N: No problem, you are welcome
119. R: Thank you very much sir.
120. N: Alright, All the best.

NPI 3

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 3 years; Patient: female; Age: 58; Occupation: Trader; Ailment: Insomnia/developing skin rashes; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Are you Mrs. P^SP?
2. P: Yes sir
3. N: What is your occupation?
4. P: Trader
5. N: What do you sell?
6. P: Beans in bags?
7. N: Okay. What is it that is disturbing you?
8. P: It's this hand ((goes into a narrative code-mixing Yoruba and English)) I did some tests.
9. N: Which test?
10. P: Sugar
11. N: What was the result?
12. P: 95
13. N: Which other test did you do?
14. P: Here is it sir
15. N: Ha! Since when has this happened
16. P: Three months sir.

17. N: Why did you keep this to yourself?
18. P: Na money o!
19. N: I'm going to refer you. ((writes)) So take this to the dermatologist, they would address us proper. Any other problem?
20. P: No sir. I *dey* use my drugs well-well
21. N: That's fine. Go and see them.
22. P: Thank you sir. *Wetin make I tell them?*
23. N: Just give them the note. They will take it up from there.
24. P: Thank you sir o.
25. N: Have a nice day.
26. P: Bye-bye sir.

NPI 4

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 11 years; Patient: male; Age: 20 years; Occupation: Student; Ailment: Epilepsy; Visitation status: Accompanied by a relation

1. N: This is not your first time here *abi?*
2. R: Yes sir
3. N: What is the problem?
4. Patient: I use to run?
5. N: You used to run?
6. R: He was brought from school after he suddenly started running and then fall
7. N: ((looks through the case note)) Did has been there before. When did this start again?
8. P: Mummy.
9. R: Sometimes last year
10. N: When precisely?
11. R: Before they write WAEC (sic)
12. N: That's around June or July
13. R: Yes sir
14. N: Did he write the exams?
15. R: It's only NECO he did. The thing really disturbed him when *dem dey do am*.
16. N: Sorry?
17. R: He was able to do NECO alone.
18. N: I understand. So, he missed out the other exams?
19. R: Yes. He even pass well at the NECO.
20. N: That's good. So what have you done since then?
21. R: We have prayed?
22. N: Prayed? You have taken him to some places?
23. P: Yes. They said...
24. N: It's spiritual?
25. R: Yes sir. They even said we should...
26. N: Go spiritual? Oh I see. ((looks through the case note)) But you were here sometimes last year. Why did you not come back for the follow up?
27. R: It's a long story sir.
28. N: It's alright. Ma, I want to ask you a few questions. When he was small, has he fallen from you before. Try and remember.

29. R: Can that be the cause? I don't think he ever fell ehm ehm but...
30. N: What about from other people
31. R: That's what I want to say. Yes
32. N: The fall, was it much?
33. R: I was not there. They said it was not but we saw the mark ((shows the mark to the doctor)).
34. N: Okay ((writes)). We'll need to re-examine him. At that first time that you came. If you had continued with the instructions as I can see here ((touching the case notes)), perhaps you'll not be here now. Okay. Ehm Ehm (0.8) what do you want us to do for you now.
35. R: I am just tired sir. Please help us. My son must not bring me to shame.
36. N: It's not him. It's his neuron system that are imbalanced. They work faster than normal. And when that happens, they cause him to react in any funny way possible. What we'll do is to ask you to do some tests.
37. R: We already did some.
38. N: Yes. But that was last year. We cannot rely on that same test for the present possibilities. What we just need to do is to carry out some other tests.
39. R: Are they different from the previous ones.
40. N: Not all of them. If I may say ma, is this how your boy is last year? He must have grown up higher than the stage he was last year. You may even be surprised that what we will discover may not be as big as it presently appears. We just need to do the right thing. Also, please don't forget that after we carry out our tests, you will have to abide by everything we ask you to do. This is necessary for the boy's quick and may be, (0.4) permanent recovery. I must also plead that you limit those places you take him to. I am not saying they are bad o, (0.8) but we must do the right thing at all times. ((writes)) So, you'll take this one down stairs, see the people, they will direct you. Okay?
41. R: Yes. What about this ((separating the prescription note))?
42. N: Yes. You'll buy those drugs. This will stabilise whatever he is making him to do that. Although, based on his record. I know it will help. The CT scan and other things will help us further. ((To the patient)) *Pele o!* Bro. All will be well, you hear?
43. P: *Amin sir*
44. R: Thank you sir. When are we supposed to bring the results?
45. N: I'm seeing you next week.
46. R: What about the thing?
47. N: Don't worry about the running. Just make sure you get those drugs and make sure he's using them as I put there.
48. R: How sir?
49. N: ((collects the note)) This in the morning 300ml, and this only one at night, but you'll repeat this morning own at night too. Every TWELVE HOURS. That's it.
50. R: Thank you sir.
51. N: In case, there is any question, you can call my number.
52. R: I don't have it sir.
53. N: ((writes the number on a sheet of paper)) Ma, I rarely give my number to patients o because they do abuse it. It's only if you have genuine reason that you should call o. You know we are very busy.
54. R: I won't disturb sir.
55. N: Okay. Help me call the next person.
56. R: Yes sir ((stands for the exit))

57. P: Thank you sir.

NPI 5

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: female; Age: 28;
Occupation: Unemployed graduate; Ailment: Seizure-motivated missed
abortion; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: How is life with you?
2. P: Thank God.
3. N: How is your business? You're still in fashion design?
4. P: Not it really. I 'm still in it, last year, I was placed on bed rest because I was pregnant.
5. N: You have a baby?
6. P: Yes. I lost it
7. N: When?
8. P: 23rd of December.
9. N: I was out of the country. I was away.
10. P: Yes, I tried your number.
11. N: At what time?
12. P: 33 weeks
13. N: Ha! But that should survive. What happened?
14. P: I just started bleeding
15. N: Yes, but should survive 33 weeks. They survive at 28th week. So what was the problem? Where did it happen? At home?
16. P: At home. Yes. I was lying down so the blood just GUSHED. It was serious. The blood that came out at once was over a litter. By the time, I
17. N: You? Did they induce you?
18. P: They did
19. N: What about the baby? The baby came out (0.4) at home?
20. P: No
21. N: The baby came out in the hospital?
22. P: I was induced.
23. N: You had the baby? The baby cried?
24. P: No! The baby was ...
25. N: Stillbirth?
26. P: Yes
27. N: That's the second one
28. P: Yes. I called you when I was taken-in.
29. N: I was here
30. P: Yes. It just happened. I was lying down, like three days before the time I was having on this leg. So, I didn't even count it because it was bearable. So, when I got down, they said it was a sign of cramp that made it or sometime.
31. N: At that time.
32. P: When the blood came. They said I might have been bleeding.
33. N: ...A long time. They should have brought you.
34. P: Huh huh.
35. N: I feel sad. Who was the obstetrician?
36. P: I've forgotten his name

37. N: Like I always said. We need to have a pre-meeting to have a kind of proactive plan. So, that by 30 weeks they should admit you. You said, you were on bed rest for how long?
38. P: I've been
39. N: Throughout?
40. P: Yes
41. N: At home or the hospital?
42. P: At home, I just avoided walking I couldn't walk because of my leg
43. N: I'm just thinking of what the best way to do may be the ideal thing is that (0.8) we should admit you in hospital or (0.8) we should get an obstetrician who is interested in this kind of (.). So, when you came, who was the consultant?
44. P: I was rushed here.
45. N: It was emergency? We'll talk to one of the experienced obstetrician so that maybe they'll admit you at 30 weeks and then they can induce the labour maybe at 32 weeks. That's what I would suggest. You had a cramp at 28 weeks.
46. P: No, it was at 33 weeks.
47. N: The baby should survive. That was just bad management!
48. P: Had it been (0.8) just saw things. It was when I started bleeding that I was rushed down here.
49. N: We have to plan. Planned admission and planned hospital stay from 30 to 32 weeks. Then they should induce the baby. Have the baby out. The baby would survive in special care. I think so it's beyond as this is nature working . but we can help. that means we need to get a senior obstetrician to look after you I will talk to P^{SP}.
50. P: I went for a scan yesterday because I was feeling some kind of movement..... ((gives scan result))
51. N: ((collects)) Let me see what it is ((reads)) okay! You have fibroids. Is he a gynecologist? The person who did this (result). Well, we'll have to refer you to a gynaecologist to take care of this. Because, it is also going to reduce the size of the uterus. They will assess you and all that. Do you have your blue card?
52. P: No, I just have the number
53. N: Okay. I will write a letter for you. Call the number.
54. P: 6...
55. N: How old are you?
56. P: 28
57. N: Two recent miscarriage (02:14) you'll see them. So, they can book you for their clinic. I will discuss with them to take over your care. I will discuss with them (0.32). Just go with this. And then (0.8), once we clear this one, we will plan your obstetrics management with him. ((Patient exits))

NPI 6

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: undisclosed; Patient: female; Age: 20; Occupation: student; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: The name is what?
2. P: ((Says the name))
3. N: Okay fine. Hmm ::: What's the problem? ((repeats the given name)) What is it that you are here for? Nigeria Air force. Who is with the Air force? ((Checks file))
4. P: None of us. It's just the hospital that we used.

5. N: How come you went to collect a letter?
6. P: That's where we use.
7. N: Family hospital? Are you in the Air force?
8. P: No.
9. N: So, it's opened to anybody
10. P: Yes
11. N: Oh ok. Fine. I didn't know that. So, what's the problem o.
12. What is happening? Why did you come?
13. P: The symptoms I have are somehow. Like if I want to have a malaria. I have a serious headache. And then maybe for a few days, I' ll start having that sensation, then it goes on, then I have seizure.
14. N: Okay. This has happened how many times?
15. P: It started last year.
16. N: It started last year? When last year?
17. P: Around march
18. N: So, it's about a year now?
19. P: Yes
20. N: How often do you have such experiences?
21. P: At times, two-month interval.
22. N: Two-months interval. Is it at night or in the morning?
23. P: Anytime
24. N: It can occur anytime? When was the last time it occurred?
25. P: That was in January.
26. N: January this year? Two months' interval. Are you on any treatment?
27. P: No
28. N: You 've not been on treatment?
29. P: Yes
30. N: The very first time it happened last year, what happened on that day? Were you sick?
31. R: (0. 8) Not really
32. N: ((The relative)) have you witnessed any attack or you have never been there?
33. R: The incidence?
34. N: Yes
35. R: The one that she is saying now. Immediately we finished at the shop. I prepared the food for them.
36. N: So, you prepare the food and then what happened?
37. R: For them to come and eat, she just faint.
38. N: She fainted? Did she shout?
39. R: No o. She just falls down
40. N: Did she fall to the ground?
41. R: I hold (sic) her
42. N: She did not fall
43. R: She just want to fall (sic).....
44. N: And you held her. Was there any shaking of the hand?
45. R: Yes
46. N: Which one?
47. P: Both hands.
48. N: What about the leg?
49. P: No

50. N: After that, what happened? What did you observe?
51. R: So, I take her (sic) to the hospital. They attend to her
52. N: Okay. And they didn't give her any medication to take on a regular basis.
53. R: No o. it's only the: : (0.8) Coartem abi what they call hmm ((brings out the drug))
54. N: ((To the patient)) how old are you?
55. R: Twenty
56. N: Twenty? What do you do now?
57. P: I'm a student
58. N: Where?
59. P: P^SP university
60. N: P^SP university? Which course?
61. P: Medicine
62. N: Medicine! Oh o! That's nice. What level?
63. P: 100 level
64. N: 100 level. Ha ha. That's terrible. How come you ...(0.8) Physician to be, you can't cure yourself?
65. R: She is trying to ...
66. P: I'm trying to cure myself.
67. N: What have you tried to do?
68. P: 1, (0.8) During my period, I miss drugs after then I And after that I prepared Maltina and milk.
69. N: You prepared?
70. P and R: Maltina and milk
71. N: Maltina and milk?
72. P: Yes
73. N: That's all you 've been doing to protect yourself.
74. P: And I sleep early
75. N: And then you go to night vigil (0.4) to pray?
76. P: No
77. N: You don't?
78. P: Maybe once in a while
79. N: What about feeding? You eat well?
80. P: Yes
81. N: And avoid stress?
82. P: Yes
- N: So, you are in P^SP? So, in the school did it occur?
83. P: Yes
84. N: How many times?
85. P: Two times
86. N: And Your friend what did they do? Or they were not there
87. P: I didn't remember anything. The only thing I could remember was that the girl was just calling my name. Then I responded. (0.8) No she said I responded... I did not fall down but I just bent down.
88. N: Before any of these events do you notice anything?
89. P: Yes, I do. If I remember any event that happened I would want to picture what really happened, then it will just come.
90. N: So, that's when it occurs. Anytime you had that kind of feeling you know that it's coming?
91. P: Oh. Not all the time, (0.8) but most of the time.

92. N: ((To the R)) You are the mother?
93. R: Yes sir
94. N: Where was she delivered?
95. R: At Agbala Itura.
96. N: How many month?
97. R: Nine month sir
98. N: She cried?
99. R: Immediately
100. N: Immediately?
101. R: Yes
102. N: Yes
103. N: Was there any problem when she was a child?
104. R: No
105. N: Did she have convulsions?
106. R: No o. no anything.
107. N: She was well?
108. R: She is well
109. N: And the other (0.8). the other aburo are okay?
110. R: Everybody. So after a year sha, she just fall sick. That's all.
111. N: You said she is in P^SP University but she assists you in the shop?
112. R: No o. no
113. N: She doesn't ((writes)) After the attack, what do you feel?
114. P: I just can't explain it.
115. N: Any headaches
116. P: Yes
117. N: Just put your phone here. I want to check your blood pressure. But first close your eyes. Open stretch your arm..... ((finishes the physical examination)). So well start you on treatment We will start with..... We will start it small dose and slowly build it up. (0.32). The drug you 'll use is called Tesretol and you 'll start with half tablet, twice a day for one – week and then you can increase it to one full tablet. 200 milligrams twice a day for three weeks and then vitamin B-Co. And then we 'll see you in one month. You should be fine. Then you 'll do a test for brain recovering, it's called EEG. (0.8) And that should tell us what is causing this.
118. P: After a month?
119. N: No. you can do that before you come. I'll fill a form for you.
120. P: Ok
121. N: You can – do – that ::: ((Writes and speaks aloud what he writes)). “You were coming to P^LP before”. Is that not so?
122. R: Yes. When she was a child.
123. N: Why did you change to Air Force Hospital
124. R: Because it's more closer (sic) to ...
125. N: Because it's closer to your house?
126. R: Yes
127. N: ((Keeps writing prescription and other details)). This is for the EEG ((shows it to the P)) It's a test that they would do on the 3rd floor. So you can set a booking for that. So when are you going back to P^SP.
128. P: On the 4th .
129. N: You 'll start your treatment and everything should be fine. So use your drugs. Stay well. Don't let it bother you. So we'll see you in one month.

130. P and R: Thank you sir.
131. N: Alright. ((calls the next patient))

NPI 7

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 3 years; Patient: male; Age: 53;
Occupation: Pensioner; Ailment: Parkinson; Visitation status: accompanied by
a relation

36. N: how are you
37. P: Thank God sir.
38. N: You did not ask after us since the last time you left.
39. P: = We thank God sir
40. N: Ehen? \$
41. P: We thank God sir
42. N: ((Gets up on the seat, exits)) sorry
43. P: ((Nods and looks on))
44. N: ((returns and sits)) Well-done sir
45. P: Thank you sir
46. N: How is it?
47. P: We're fine sir
48. N: how is your health?
49. P: We thank God
50. N: Well-done
51. P: *yes sir, e se a dupe*
52. N: £ha ha! You are looking great!
53. P: Thank God sir
54. N: £It's good to see you
55. P: Thank you sir
56. N: *E pele*
57. P: Yes sir. *ese gan*
58. N: *yeah e pele =*
59. P: = *e pele e wa joko;*
60. N: Madam has really been taking good care of you)
61. R: *Abi::* ()
62. N: ((writes)) ((To the R)). He's really improved. His response is far better than before. Don't you see?
63. R: I'm also happy. We just want to make sure we are here based on the previous appointment given.
64. N: That's very good.
65. R: Thank you sir.
66. N: ((writes)) If there is any serious need, I think I'm going to give you three (0.2) No! Four months.
67. R: Okay sir.
68. N: By that time everything must have normalised.
69. R: Thank you sir.
70. N: ((Hands over the prescription note)) So, take care and tell those people to come in. Thank you.

NPI 8

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: undisclosed; Patient: female; Age: 27; Occupation: Law intern; Ailment: Recurring headache; Visitation status: unaccompanied

39. N: Yes ma. Welcome. You are P^SP. How old are you?
40. P: Twenty-seven
41. N: What work do you do?
42. P: Civil servant but I'm working with a lawyer.
43. N: You are working with a lawyer? Where?
44. P: At Kwara state.
45. N: So, why are you here?
46. P: My head used to disturb me.
47. N: But there are doctors in Ilorin. Why leave Kwara for here. Any reason?
48. P: Because my lawyer parents are here.
49. N: Okay. No problem. That's why you are here. You are welcome. So what's the problem?
50. P: The head used to disturb me whenever I entered a vehicle.
51. N: Your head (0.4) will start disturbing you? What kind of disturbance?
52. P: My body will be hot here ((touching the head)) and when I stop from the vehicle it will stop.
53. N: Will stop. So, if you are going from here to (0.8) let's say Ilorin. The head will do like that through?
54. P: Yes
55. N: So, it's when you get to Ilorin that it will stop.
56. P: Yes
57. N: But what if you are not in the vehicle? It won't happen?
58. P: Yes
59. N: Is it headache?
60. P: Yes
61. N: It's headache that you are having? And it's like they are beating on your head?
62. P: Yes
63. N: When you have it, do you see flashes of light? As if someone is shining light.
64. P: No
65. N: No, do you hear voices?
66. P: No
67. N: Do you feel like vomiting?
68. P: No
69. N: Where do you feel this pain?
70. P: ((Touching the head)) here.
71. N: Just the front? Not at the back? Or the side?
72. P: No
73. N: Are you scared of travelling?
74. P: Sometimes, I used to be scared but when I am scared I'll use anointing oil to spray my head and if I feel the headache I will now use like (0.8) paracetamol
75. N: So, if you use the anointing oil and paracetamol, you will be able to travel, you won't have headache?
76. P: Yes
77. N: So, that's an easy solution. But you don't want to use anointing oil all the time?

78. P: I used to use it sometimes. Whenever the headache comes.
79. N: And you don't feel like vomiting at all?
80. P: No
81. N: And this headache has been there for how long?
82. P: One year
83. N: And you have it everyday or only when you travel?
84. P: Or when I'm sick.
85. N: So, if you are not sick, no headache? If you don't travel, no headache?
86. P: No
87. N: If you are not travelling, how often will it affect you? That will determine whether I'll treat it or not. That's the reason why I want to know.
88. P: (0.32) since, (0.8) is it not two weeks ago, now I have serious headache.
89. N: Serious headache.
90. P: Yes
91. N: It was just like that? Like they were beating something on your head?
92. P: Yes and until I try to sleep that the they
93. N: Will go down
94. P: Yes
95. N: Okay. We'll try something to make sure that the headache doesn't bother you. Your blood pressure is nice. Do you have any medical problem?
96. P: No
97. N: You see well
98. P: Yes
99. N: You hear well? You don't have any medical problem. You don't have sore throat?
100. P: No
101. N: No catarrh?
102. P: No
103. N: Is there anything you don't like? Like when you take it, it would make you fall sick? Anything at all that you don't tolerate?
104. P: It's only beans.
105. N: Fortunately, you are the one who cooks your own food. So you won't cook beans for anybody?
106. P: I cook it sometimes.
107. N: So, what happens when you eat beans? What happens if you eat beans?
108. P: I don't eat it at all.
109. N: I don't like it at all.
110. N: That's fine. Now let's check what is causing this. Sit down. Be comfortable.
111. Can you close your eyes... touch your nose... That's fine, you are doing so well. ((touches other parts around the head and neck)) Any pain. Any pain... Any pain?
112. P: Yes.
113. N: Ok. Open your eyes. ((carries out a BP check)) So when you have the headache, how long does it last?
114. P: One week
115. N: One week. ((continues examining her)) Have you used any treatment for it.
116. P: ((shakes head in negation))
117. N: Are you a lawyer?
118. P: I'm a baby lawyer.

119. N: Have you finished from law school
120. P: I just finished from the University of P^SP.
121. N: Okay. You are now (0.8) kind of internship?
122. P: Yes, at High Court.
123. N: High Court. Are you going to go to Law School?
124. P: Yes
125. N: When?
126. P: Next year.
127. N: What course did you read from the university?
128. P: Law
129. N: Law! You've finished law?
130. P: Yes
131. N: How come you didn't go straight to Law School? What's causing your delay?
132. P: I just think if I work
133. N: You'll have enough money. Are they paying you well?
134. P: They are trying.
135. N: How much?
136. P: Fifty
137. N: Fifty! Ha (0.8) That's good o! That's more than what they earn here. That's good. Those baby lawyers earn about fifteen thousand. So, you are lucky then. That's good. So you'll have to safe. That could also be a reason for headache. Stress. Do you have any marital problem?
138. P: No
139. N: You are okay? Your husband is fine. What does he do?
140. P: He's a police officer
141. N: And you are happy? He's based in P^LP as well?
142. P: ((Nods in agreement))
143. N: ((Writes)) I'll start you on treatment for this headache. It's a drug called (.). So, you'll take the half tablet at night. So, you'll still use your anointing oil, since it seems to help you. ((waits for the prescription note having exhausted those with him. A nurse brings it in. He writes)) You'll use this drug. It'll make you a little bit sleepy. It's good to try it over the weekend. The headache should not bother you if you use it. Make sure you don't fall asleep too much at work. I'll see you, what did I write? One month. Hopefully, we'll see and see how you get along.
144. P: After one month
145. N: Yes, you can come. Except the headache is back.
146. P: Thank you sir. My regards to your family.
147. N: Okay.

NPI 9

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: male; Age: 66; Occupation: Retired Public Servant; Ailment: Diabetes; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: How are you today?
2. P: I'm fine.
3. N: You still live in the same Kongi area?

4. P: Yes ((gives some documents to the neurologist))
5. N: Okay. ((reads the document)) You have improved! 110/70. This is more realistic than the ones I saw before.
6. P: You said it's realistic
7. N: Yes, I said it's more realist than your previous result 140/80. So, I think he's fine. I won't change your drug sir.
8. P: Will I still take all?
9. N: Yes
10. R: That's true
11. P: Who is the doctor here?
12. N: I am, but she is your nurse ((laughs))
13. P: She always support you on this.
14. N: That means I'm doing the right thing. ((General laughter)) We are always working together. Do you agree with our treatment sir?
15. P: Are you satisfied?
16. N: I'm satisfied.
17. P: That I'm alright
18. N: Yes sir.
19. P: If anything goes wrong I'll sue you ((jokingly))
20. N: No problem sir ((jokingly)). But before you sue me, we'll go to the radio. Then we'll see who the people would believe in (general laughter). No problem. I think I'll see him in two months or three.
21. P: Let's make it two months
22. N: Okay. That two month is okay. If I make it four months you'll complain. That, it's too long. TWO MONTHS. We won't change the drugs. They
23. P: Alright
24. R: Thank you
25. N: Stay well.

NPI 10

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: male; Age: 43;
Occupation: Lecturer; Ailment: Hypertension; Visitation status: unaccompanied

1. P: Well-done sir
2. N: Good to see you. What about your wife?
3. P: She is fine.
4. N: Okay?1
5. P: Yes. I've completed the drugs and I felt a lot better.
6. N: You are much okay now?
7. P: Very much. The pains had gone except once in a while but I guess that with time because I've just completed the drug. One week and three days, but the only thing I observed is that the feverish feeling is there. Around 3am to 6. But as soon as I get up may be pray and brush, the thing would go that's the only thing I observed.
8. N: Okay
9. P: The lady that was with you the time I came asked me to do these tests because I was still coughing ((brings out the result)) this is what they gave me.
10. N: You are done using the drugs now?
11. P: Yes
12. N: Which anti-hepatitis are you now using now?

13. P: The one they gave me
14. N: Are you coughing?
15. P: The cough has gone. except when I'm close to the fan or air-conditioner. It would want to come but the last two days nothing.
16. N: Everything is going on smoothly?
17. P: Yes, except last Sunday, when I was directly under the fan
18. N: (Carries out BP check) your BP is still a bit up.
19. P: Really?
20. N: Which drug are you still using apart from the Artacan?
21. P: Except Moduretic
22. N: And you are sure you using if very well? Did you use it this morning?
23. P: I used it yesterday night.
24. N: No! you can't be using it at night now
25. P: I do prefer it at night so that I'll sleep with it.
26. N: No, it's a morning drug. Although some prefer it that way but this BP is not funny. And I need to be convinced that you are using the drugs very well. So, what do we do now? And you are not with the drugs here, the Artacan and Moduretic.
27. P: They are at home
28. N: What dose of Artacan are you using?
29. P: 8ml
30. N: You will increase it to 16ml. Can you call your wife?
31. P: Huh?
32. N: As in, call your wife. I want to be sure that you are using these drugs very well.
33. P: Okaay!
34. N: ((Writes)) See this is Artacan dosage. Where do you buy your own?
35. P: .Maybe a (.)
36. N: Okay. I'm worried about the dosage. ((writes prescription and reads aloud)). How is your salt consumption?
37. P: I do avoid it, but sometimes....
38. N: What about your sugar?
39. P: I have since stopped all those
40. N: You are not diabetic?
41. P: No
42. N: All these tests I'm giving you today are not as if it's a must. Assuming that and (0.8). Now that the chest pain has been resolved and sorted out. This your BP I'll give you three times. Let us look more into your BP and check all these. Because of your BP, I'll give one more... Perhaps you can check it but if you are not able just come here so I'll check it again I'm assuming that you'll have started using the Artacan and others.
43. P: I'll try to do all those tests. Thank you very much. But how do I get you?
44. N: Whenever you want to come, just tell Dr. P^{SP}, he'll get me for you. It's for me to adjust my time.
45. P: Alright ((Gets up and exits))

NPI 11

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 4 years; Patient: male; Age: 69 years; Occupation: Retired public servant ; Ailment: Alzheimer; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: How is it? What's happening?
2. R: Well, I have not been around for some times now. But last month, I had to come.
3. N: What happened?
4. R: I discovered that my dad forgets things easily now.
5. N: Like what did you see? How did you know?
6. R: Ma, it's pathetic talking to dad and asking me who is speaking.
7. N: Could it be that the network was bad?
8. R: Network *ke*? I'd thought so initially, but when it became a norm. I was like (0.8) dazed.
9. N: What other things did you notice as in hmmm (0.32) that really frightened you about him?
10. R: I noticed that his words were becoming confusing...
11. N: Incoherent?
12. R: Exactly ma
13. N: When you then got back home, what happened?
14. R: I noticed that he drops things anyhow.
15. N: Anyhow? He misplaces common household objects easily?
16. R: Yes ma.
17. N: ((To the patient)) Hello sir
18. P: Hmmm
19. N: How are you?
20. P: ((Nods)) Ffff::ine
21. N: What did you eat this morning?
22. R: ((Points to the relative))
23. N: Where did you come from, this morning?
24. P: Hmmm my h::ouse
25. N: Yes. Where is your house?
26. P: ((Looks on))
27. R: Dad
28. N: ((Gesticulates to the relation to leave the patient to answer the question)) I said where do you live?
29. P: ((Nodding))
30. N: ((After some minutes of non-communication)) Ok. Well, I'll explain the situation to you. Your dad is showing the symptoms of Alzheimer's disease.
31. R: What's THAT?
32. N: Em (0.8), usually at the onset, Alzheimer is usually very gradual. In the early stages, Alzheimer's patients (0.12) em have relatively mild problems, especially in learning new things, em and information and remembering where they have left common objects. He may be looking for keys or money kept somewhere by himself or, may be em (0.8) a wallet. Later, they may begin to have trouble recollecting recent events and finding the right words to express themselves. So, as the disease progresses, patients may have difficulty remembering what day or month it is, or finding their way around familiar surroundings and so on. What we however have are choices to make. Okay?

33. R: Yes ma.
34. N: Yes. Em, if left unattended to patients often become easily irritated. They sometimes get angry over a little thing. It is a kind of frustration because of the struggle with fear. Even things they used to do easily before (0.8) can become unfamiliar and intimidating, I mean, big in their eyes. We are lucky because later, they may become paranoid or delusional and unable to engage in normal conversation. This can lead to complete incapacity to function in basic activities. Did he not walk-in here?
35. R: Yes, he did
36. N: Does he still use the bath?
37. R: Ma?
38. N: Does he go to toilet himself?
39. R: Before now, but recently, we used to help him
40. N: When you were coming here today, where did you tell him you were going?
41. R: I told him, I have to take you to the hospital.
42. N: What did he do?
43. R: I think he preferred it.
44. N: Alright then. You did the right thing. I just hope you are right enough.
45. R: That's why we're here.
46. N: The truth is that if one delays, it might be dangerous. In other cases of Alzheimer, from initial diagnosis, some don't last beyond seven to ten years. However, age is a factor. Hmmm (0.8) How old is baba?
47. R: Sixty-nine
48. N: Sixty-nine? Okay then ((writes))
49. R: So, ma, does it mean he...
50. N: It depends. I have mentioned the age at the onset.
51. R: He's too old?
52. N: Hmmm (0.8) It's just that other medical conditions present, and the care patients receive are other important factors. You understand?
53. R: No ma? What do we do?
54. N: A lot
55. R: A lot?
56. N: Yes, a lot. Just a moment (.0.32). Okay. You see, the main choices available is care.
57. R: We are ready.
58. N: Good. The major choice is care for baba by all of you. This is what I mean. How many are you, his children?
59. R: Six
60. N: Fine
61. R: Four of us are overseas.
62. N: Who stays with him presently?
63. R: Our relatives
64. N: What about the other two?
65. R: They are in their husband's house
66. N: Okay then. The choice available is that you must find some people who will always be around to take care (0.8), good care of him. Generally, caring for Alzheimer's patients falls on the spouses and children. The people that must be in charge of his wellbeing must constantly be on guard. If not, at some points, Alzheimer's patient may wander away or become agitated or confused. And this is not

good for him. ((Writes)) I've written some drugs for him. Make sure, you get them and em, use them. The most important thing for me is if you can get someone permanently that is passionate about taking care for him. Talk to others if possible.

67. R: I will ma.

68. N: ((Hands over the prescription note to the relation)) You can check again in one month.

NPI 12

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 3 years; Patient: female; Age: 75; Occupation: Trader; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: Well-done sir.
2. N: You are welcome.
3. R₁: Mama came for operation on Sunday night. And we've done some tests. We now say that we should come and see you for advice concerning her. The last time she was hospitalized, that was in 2014. She was diagnosed with R.T.I
4. N: U.T.I?
5. R₁: R.T.I., Respiratory Tract Infection
6. N: Oh! Okay R.T.I
7. R₁: Yes, this time again, it was R.T.I again.
8. N: Okay
9. R₁: So, we now conclude that we should come.
10. R: R .T .I Respiratory Tract Infection.
11. N: Oh! Okay.
12. R₁: This time again it is RTI and last year it was stroke. Then, we came to P^LP but the doctors were on strike. You know it has been re-occurring so we decided to come and see you for advice on how to take care of her.
13. N: How old is Mama?
14. R₁: She is 75.
15. N: She is on admission now?
16. R₁: Yes.
17. N: Which ward?
18. R: ((Mentions the ward))
19. N: Is she conscious?
20. R₂: Not :: very.
21. N: ((looks through the case notes for a while)). That's the reason why she is prone to this chest infection because in an attempt to feed her, the thing goes the wrong way. I think that's the reason.
22. R₁: Okay.
23. N: It's tough, because elderly people who have all types of unconsciousness are prone to such things. And (0.2) all we need to do is :: as must as possible, try to be careful especially when one is feeding them. And if they have an infection to treat.
24. R₂: She was even diagnosed with dementia before. When we were coming here. Before the :: (0.4)
25. R₁: She didn't even communicate.
26. R₂: After the stroke, she didn't talk at all ... She didn't talk again.
27. N: Can you get a Nurse? May be that's one thing you should do as well. Because if you have a Nurse, she can come and provide care. So that there won't be much stress for both of you and the whole family, it would be multiple casualties more or less. But

- if you can get a Nurse to nurse her and in turn... that might be a way out to take the stress off you. It costs money but that is better.
28. R₁: We even got one woman but she is not a Nurse.
29. N: Yes (0.4) That's good. If you can get her here to understudy other Nurses, that will be perfect. You could talk to the Chief Matron of the ward and tell her the situation. You'll bring the person along and tell the Matron you want the person to learn few things on how to care of Mama.
30. R₁: Yes sir. We were given these files to go and do the tests. ((presents another file.N collects it))
31. N: That's a lot of tests.
32. R₁: We already did this one ((picks up a note from others still in her hands))
33. N: ((collects it and continues)) This one is because her leg is swollen and they tried to (0.8) do... I think they are worried about a clot in her leg.((Reads others loudly)). Maybe we should review her. Ehn (0.4). I think we have a ward round on (0.4) Wednesday. I think that was when (0.4) these tests were ordered. The result is just to help us.
34. R₂: And to discover a way out?
35. N: Yeah: To know what and what is wrong. She is not even diabetic.
36. R₁: When they transferred her was when they noticed.
37. N: All these. Yes. They are usually a lot of tests. But (°) I think after this, there will be none again.
38. NPR₁: What is the sir? Fungel?
39. N: It's D – dyma test. It's to confirm the effection so as to make her better. I think after this, there won't be anyone again.
40. R₁: Sir. Thank you very much sir. I don't know if you can use your good office to look into this matter?
41. N: Okay. What is that?
42. R₂: Actually, they are doing a good job. Sometimes (0.8). But (0.4) ehm you know. It was even stated in our case notes that there should be close observation. And that is why we make it a point of duty to come first thing in the morning. Sometimes we are a bit late in coming and it tallies with the time they want to do handover and some othe::r thing. The next thing they do is :: is that they chase us out.
43. N: They send you away?
44. R₁: And I think there should be corrective methods on both parts.
45. N: Yeah.
46. R₂: Like this morning now, I got here and noticed that the oxygen wasn't running. And (0.8) when they saw me. They didn't tell me anything. I just took the initiative...
47. N: To change the (0.4)
48. R₂: And I just asked one of the hospitals guys 'please check which one is not running', and he said "it's empty". I had to run around and get another oxygen....
49. N: Okay
50. R₂: So, I said why didn't they tell me? I said I was HERE! The only thing they were interested in is chasing me out!
51. R₂: And it has been repeating
52. R₂: So as a result, she didn't take her antibiotic this morning.
53. R₁: Even, day before yesterday, we had a quarrel with them. They said she didn't take her drugs and my siblings have been around since morning. They didn't tell them...
54. N: Eh yah! That's ehm... We'll talk with the matron. Usually... that's the thing we do. It's like comp.. compart... compartmentalisation of care. Nurses do their own...

55. N; R₁ and R₂ ((together)) DOCTOR DO THEIR OWN
56. N: You can't cross profession, you can only advise.
57. R₁ and R₂: Yes sir
58. N: My own philosophy is that never keep a patient longer than it's necessary.
59. R₂: Sir, I want to find out about the socks thing. I saw people using it. Do we need to buy it.
60. N: o o! I mean (0.8) you can buy it. It's a pressure socks.
61. R₂: You'll give us a measurement.
62. N: There's a house officer to do that.
63. R₁: I hope they will sir?
64. N: It's their job. They will.
65. R₂: Thank you very much sir.
66. N: No problem. No problem.
67. R₂: One more thing sir.
68. N: Okay
69. R₂: I know this place is big but ehm (0.4) but as far as the issue of mum is concerned, can we (0.8) just have your number?
70. N: 080P^{SP}
71. Thank you very much sir. (0.2) God bless you.
72. N: No problem
73. R₁: May the Lord continue to assist you.
74. R₂: I'll try to call you.
75. N: What's your name?
76. R₂: PSP
77. N: Okay. Have a nice day. She'll be fine.
78. R₁ and R₂: We are grateful sir.

NPI 13

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: undisclosed; Patient: female; Age: 47; Occupation: Self-employed; Ailment: Migraine; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

49. P: Good afternoon sir.
50. N: Good afternoon madam.
51. P: I have done the test ((searches her bag)).
52. N: Okay. ((Nodding and looks on, waiting for the result))
53. P: These are them (sic) sir. ((Hands the papers and other documents to the N))
54. N: Oh! Okay. ((Nodding)) Yes.
55. P: What is that sir?
56. N: Em.. the record with us shows that you have been visiting this clinic for about two years and em (0.4) six weeks now. Also, you used to be treated for recurrent headache. Now all those have stopped for a moment. But you complained last week. That was why you were asked to do those tests.
57. P: And what is in the result sir?
58. N: It's your right to know. I'm going to tell you one by one. Now. This brain that we use is made up of many specialised areas that work together. The cortex controls the cortical activity. You see (0.4) that outermost layer of brain cells. It is here ((raises the CT scan higher against the equipment). Thinking and voluntary movements begin from here. So, basic functions like breathing and sleep are controlled here ((pointing

- to a part in the scan result)). So when this thing keeps recurring, our options are (0.8) give me a second (long pause. goes). ((powers on the computer)). Do you normally vomit?
59. P: Yes
60. N: What about when they put on the light?
61. P: Yes. I get disturbed. I used to sleep everyday with light off. I don't allow anybody to (put) on the light at all.
62. N: You (0.2) are al::so sensitivity (0.4) to light ((writes)). When they play music *nko*? Especially loud one?
63. P: I don't like it at all
64. N: You don't like it or it affects you?
65. P: Yes
66. N: It gives you Yes, serious headaches?
67. P: Yes.
68. N: Trig::ger (0.4). Light, sound ((silent)). Migraine. ((writes and talks)) Sensitivity to sound:::. Ok.
69. P: ((Cuts in)) Sir?
70. N: Em.. em.. This is it. In this situation, ((busy with the computer, probably reading from it)) (0.8) since it's a recurring one, which actually is a proof that you have em... em (0.4) Migraine. You have to find a way of stopping the triggers. That is one. Two. You must be getting enough sleep. I mean enough sleep. Then you will also have to reduce stress for yourself. You must cultivate the habit of (0.8). Look here ma!
71. P: I am with you
72. N: What did I say last?
73. P: You said I should look here.
74. N: And before then?
75. P: That I should (0.8) reduce stress.
76. N: I just need to be sure you are fully involved in this. Okay. As I was saying, you will need to make it a duty of drinking plenty of water. It's good for your health. There are some certain food you'll need to avoid. Do you react to any?
77. P: I can't remember. I don't think so? Except okraw.
78. N: You may have to avoid that too. Do you ever have time for exercise?
79. P: Exercise? I walk a lot. To my place of work.
80. N: Not that one. You may have to dedicate special time for exercise, either early in the morning or in the evening. I mean moderate exercise. Then you must always have a bath after doing it. That is if you want o!
81. P: But what about drugs?
82. N: Yes. All those will complement any drug we prescribe here. But you have a choice to make in making sure that you observe all those things I told you.
83. P: All of them are compulsory.
84. N: Are you asking me.
85. P: No. I mean they are compulsory. I will try.
86. N: That will be fine. ((writes prescriptions)). So you may need to buy this.
87. P: What if I continue the Aspirin?
88. N: No. You cant't use Aspirin when you have ulcer. Just continue with the drugs we prescribed. Do you have any other comment?
89. P: No sir
90. N: Any reservation?
91. P: No

92. N: Alright. When will you like to come again?
 93. P: Do I need to come?
 94. N: Except you have any complaints.
 95. P: Okay.
 96. N: You can go now. ((Patient gets up and exit))

NPI 14

Background information: Neurologists: (two) females; Experience: 1 year; Patient: female;
 Age: 54; Occupation: Trader; Ailment: Panic attack; Visitation status: accompanied
 by a relation

62. N: Are you Mrs. P^{SP}?
 63. P: Yes ma
 64. N: What is your occupation?
 65. P: I am a trader
 66. N: What do you sell?
 67. P: Clothes?
 68. N: Okay. What is it that is disturbing you?
 69. P: I dey always shock.
 70. N₁: You are always shocked?
 71. Yes ma
 72. N₁: How do you mean you dey always shock?
 73. R: The issue ma is that when any small thing happen, mummy behaves somehow?
 74. N₁: Feel somehow? Do you mean she does not behave well?
 75. R: Not like that. The thing makes her to be easily afraid (sic).
 76. N₂: Wait. You need to tell us exactly what you say she is doing.
 77. R: Okay ma. You see, when people shout outside, mummy will suddenly fear.
 78. N₂: You mean she gets frightened so often?
 79. R: She is always afraid (sic)
 80. N₁: She is always afraid?
 81. R: Afraid. She is always afraid
 82. N₂: Apart from shout outside, does she feel any pain or discomfort in her body?
 83. R: Yes. Sometimes headache will be doing her. She will not sleep.
 84. N₁: Who are you to her?
 85. R: Son
 86. N₁: Where are you living before now?
 87. R: Before mummy came back?
 88. N₁: Came back from where?
 89. R: She used to stay in the abroad.
 90. N₁: Oh! Okay. Where was she?
 91. R: Libya
 92. N₁: Madam, your son said you used to live in Libya
 93. P: Yes
 94. N₁: Where in Libya do you lived?
 95. P: Tripoli
 96. N₁: When did you come back to Nigeria?
 97. P: When dem killed Gaddafi
 98. N₂: That must be after the war
 99. N₁: Something like that. Ma, how and why did you come back.

100. P: The government brought us back.
101. N₁: It's okay. *Oga* ((referring to the relation)) when this fear-fear happens, does her body shake?
102. R: Yes ma o. In fact, she would shake for hours.
103. N₁: When last did she experience this?
104. R: The day after yesterday.
105. N₂: But when did you start noticing this?
106. P: Around the time she came back. Even sef, we think (sic) that it was change of environment.
107. N₁: Okay. So, what did you do about it?
108. R: Our pastor prayed for her.
109. N₂: She went for deliverance?
110. R: Ehn. It was when we became worried that we took her there. When the church in our backyard are doing their night vigil. Mummy would just wake up and start running about the house.
111. N₁: That was when?
112. R: It's been long but when I see that it is like as if, as if , as if
113. N₂: Like going mental
114. R: Ehn ehn. That was why we say we should take her to hospital.
115. N₂: How long was she at the church?
116. R: It may be up to two years.
117. N₂: Two years?
118. R: Yes. Our brother abroad say that we must bring her here.
119. N₁: ((To the other neurologist)) This is Panic Disorder.
120. N₂: Yes. She must have been affected by the experience of the war.
121. N₁: The violence and all trauma.
122. R: Ma?
123. N₁: Well. Your mum is affected by a mental illness that we call "Panic Disorder". This affects a person to experience repeated, unexpected panic attacks and persistent anxiety about the possibility that the panic attacks will reoccur.
124. R: Ha!
125. N₁: Don't shout. See, that panic attack comes with intense fear, apprehension, or discomfort.
126. N₁: When it happens, it usually comes without warning. For you to know. You'll notice she sometimes have her heart beating so fast. Madam, do you find it difficult breathing sometimes?
127. P: Sometimes. I won't be able to able to breath down.
128. N₂: That's shortness of breath.
129. N₁: Do you sometimes fear you are going crazy, or you lose control?
130. R: That's our fears.
131. P: I reject it in Jesus name.
132. N₂: But do you feel scared that your enemies want you to go mad?
133. P: Yes and they would fail always in Jesus name.
134. N₂: When these things, I mean running around and feeling scared happens, it is like how many minutes.
135. R: It stays long sometimes o.
136. N₁: Like ten minutes or more?
137. R: More than that sometimes. Although at the beginning. It was not more than ten to twenty.

138. N₁: That's it. Your mum needs to be treated for panic attacks. ((0.3₂)) Panic attack that she is experiencing is not without a recourse to her war experience in Libya. Although, Ehm, other anxiety disorders, such as phobias, ((0.8)) I mean fear of specific object or situation is also a possible trigger of this attack. Let me ask you. When you are travelling in a vehicle, does she fear?
139. R: She did that today very well.
140. N₁: And when you get here *nko*?
141. R: She was okay.
142. N₁: Till you enter here?
143. R: Yes ma.
144. N₁: Has she been behaving this way whenever you board a bus or car?
145. R: Many times but not all the time. She will just be shouting and complaining that the driver was running too much even when they are not running.
146. N₁: It's okay. She is also going agoraphobia.
147. R: What is that ma?
148. N₁: People with agoraphobia typically fear situations, ehm, such as traveling in a bus, train, car, places where (0.8) there are many people like shopping centres, going to markets, crossing over bridges or roads. Ehm, even sometimes, they fear being alone in unfamiliar places, places they don't know before. Even sef, people like that are usually reluctant to leave their home.
149. R: Is that why she drinks?
150. N₁: What does she drink?
151. R: Alcohol
152. P: Small small
153. N₁: Well, the truth is that, people with panic disorder can have an increased risk of alcoholism and they sometimes depend, depend (0.8) on hard drug. ((Writes))
154. R: Please help us.
155. N₁: I will have to refer you to the consultant for further treatment. And you will do some tests too. So, ((writing)) so, you will have to do these tests ((hands a piece of paper to the relation)) You can come back next week or (0.8) go and do the test and bring it today. You can wait till after the break so that *Oga* will see you, or you come next week.
156. R: When that will be? (sic)
157. N₁: Just one hour.
158. R: We will wait.
159. N₂: You can wait outside.
160. P: Okay o. ((Exits with her son))
161. N₁: See you later.

NPI 15

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 6 years; Patient: female; Age: 65 years; Occupation: Teacher; Ailment: Functional amnesia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. R: They said we should see you sir.
2. N: Okay sit down.
3. R: Thank you sir.
4. N: So, how far with Mama's health?
5. R: We thank God o

6. P: ((interrupts)) At Oshodi before we gave you.
7. N: What is that?
8. R: Hmmm
9. N: Mama, what happened at Oshodi?
10. P: No o. We want to bring the money.
11. N: Which money is that?
12. R: Don't mind her.
13. N: No. Let her express herself. (0.8) So, Mama (0.8) what did you say happened at Oshodi
14. P: Hmmm:::::hmhhh
15. N: Okay. I mean what did you give at Oshodi?
16. P: Tola
17. N: Who is Tola?
18. P: Hmmm
19. N: ((To the relation)) were you at Oshodi?
20. R: No sir
21. N: Did she go to Oshodi?
22. R: No sir
23. N: I see. She was trying to regain her memory. Mama, what did you eat yesterday night?
24. P: I eat hmm: hmhhh:: Ama:: Amala.
25. N: ((whisper to the relation)) Is that what she ate?
26. R: We ate rice.
27. N: What about her?
28. R: She ate the same food.
29. N: Okay. It's small by small. Are you still using the prescribed drugs.
30. R: We still use them.
31. N: ((To the relation)) She will get better. We need to and we will be patient with her. It's small by small. Okay?
32. R: Yes sir.
33. N: You see. The challenge with her is not a disease. It is just (0.4) just a symptom of those things that she went through. With time, she will get better. We must make all efforts to help her make use of her remaining memory skills. (0.32) ((writes)) I will place you on these drugs. ((hands the prescription note over)). I will see you in em. say 6 weeks.
34. R: Thank you sir
35. N: Mama take care o
36. P: Thank you
37. N: Greet you people.
38. P: I will sir.

NPI 16

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 15 years; Patient: female; Age: 55; Occupation: Teacher; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Welcome ma.
2. P: Thanks sir for the other time sir.
3. N: Okay ma. Thank you. How are you feeling now?
4. P: It's that same leg sir.

5. N: What happened to your leg?
6. P: It's like *pajapaja*
7. N: You are still feeling it?
8. P: It's still disturbing me o!
9. N: Okay. Alright. Em:_ I was trying to look at our old records.
10. P: Okay sir. Thank you sir.
11. N: So, the leg where you are experiencing the seizures is the only problem?
12. P: Yes sir.
13. N: No other problem?
14. P: I can eat.
15. N: You can eat.
16. P: \$ I can eat.
17. N: That's good ((looks through the case note)) That's fine. That's the only thing you came for ((looks on into the case note, then to the patient)) 2005! And it's still there?
18. P: Yes sir o
19. N: Have you checked your blood sugar level?
20. P: It's *pajapaja o*
21. N: Did you do your blood sugar?
22. P: Yes
23. N: Do you have it with you?
24. P: No_:
25. N: I've asked you to do it. I thought I requested for that.
26. P: Oh o o! Sorry. I've done all of them before.
27. N: Really?
28. P: Yes
29. N: Let me look through the file. I'll check ((Attempts looking into the file))
30. P: They did not put it in the file sir. It was during the long strike.
31. N: But you supposed to have the result with you then.
32. P: They did not give them to me sir o.
33. N: Where?
34. P: Downstairs at Pharmacology. Down down. They did not give me the result.
35. N: ((Looks into the case file)) Yes. Hmm. This is::: You have done this one. 2004_: This is obsolete. That is 2004.
36. P: They did not give me the results.
37. N: Anyway, no problem. So: As you are here seated. You feel you have seizure in that leg?
38. P: It's there sir o!
39. N: From where to where? Up to where?
40. P: ((Touches leg)) from here to this.
41. N: So, it's on the right leg?
42. P: Yes. It's much here.
43. N: Okay. Neurovite did not help you?
44. P: Sir?
45. N: The one I prescribed to you?
46. P: I'm using it. But it's finished. It's what I've been using.
47. N: I'll check your blood pressure now.
48. P: I told them there. They said :::

49. N: We'll check it now. ((Checks)) 170/90. It's still high ((writes)). If I decide to write (0.8). It's very expensive. I'm not certain of its ability to help but we can try it. Let's try it for two weeks. I think it's better.
50. P: Thank you sir.
51. N: For the blood pressure. I've included (...)
52. P: Thank you sir.
53. N: We want it to go down.
54. P: Ehn ehn. (0.4) Help me put it. Thank you sir. How about all my children?
55. N: They are all fine ma.
56. P: Thank you very much sir. I sometimes do have severe headaches.
57. N: Hmm. Okay. ((Writes))
58. P: Thank o
59. N: this is the prescription note. So we'll see you in about eight weeks.
60. P: thank you so much sir.
61. N: Ok ma. Alright. Bye bye ma.
62. P: Thank you sir ((gets up and exits the room)).

NPI 17

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 2 years; Patient: male; Age: 40; Occupation: Self-employed; Ailment: Diabetes Mellitus; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

70. N: Welcome. So How are you today?
71. P: I'm fine ma. It's just that saliva is coming out from this side of my mouth.
72. N: Okay. Is it that side only?
73. P: Hmmm: I think. Emmm (0.2) It's because.
74. N: Because of the drug?
75. P: Yes, ma. I was just thinking maybe it is.
76. N: You just think so. ((Goes closer to the patient)) Has your eyes been like this all along?
77. P: Yes, even my son has this kind.
78. N: And you think it's because of the drug? Does this place ((touching the cheek)) scratch you?
79. P: It is pinching me inside.
80. N: Have you ever had your tooth removed before?
81. P: Only twice.
82. N: Was it after we treated you for the (0.4). Em (0.2) for the ((checks case notes)). After the accident?
83. P: Yes ma. After the attack?
84. N: Which attack was that?
85. P: The one you treat(ed) me for.
86. N: ((rushes to check the case note again)) Oh I see. You actually had a quarrel with P^SP that led to your being treated. Okay (0.8). No problem. But when did you say the tooth was removed?
87. P: Hmmm (0.4). Let me say em. Em:: ((turns to the person accompanying him)). When was that sef (sic)?
88. R: It's up to two months now.
89. N: Who did the thing for him?
90. R: It's those people that remove teeth o!

91. N: In which hospital?
92. P: It was not an (sic) hospital per se. They were doing church outreach and I complained to their head doctor.
93. N: And they just remove your teeth like that?
94. P: It's not just like that?
95. R: They came (0.2) our house about two days after
96. N: And they remove it?
97. P: Something like that ma.
98. N: Something like that? ((changes sitting position)) So you mean?
99. R: Is that why (sic)?
100. N: Hmmm (0.8). You see (0.2). It is not proper that you allow just anybody to treat you medically.
101. P: But they are from our church.
102. R: Let them (sic) talk now.
103. P: I'm sorry
104. N: It's okay. I just know that you should have called us or better still, come back to complain here. Or is it the money?
105. P: It's part of it.
106. R: Ma. At that thing we had nothing on us. So we saw it as an opportunity to relief him.
107. N: Well (0.2). That is logical but it's dangerous. You know that I cannot do anything without this file ((case file)). What we will do now is ((writes in the case note)). I'm going to let our dentists examine your teeth and other things and then see if the situation remains or not. Let me see your drug bag.
108. R: ((hands over the polyethylene bag to her)) You have removed that one after the last time we came.
109. N: That was over twelve months ago.
110. P: Yes.
111. N: Okay. ((keeps writing in the case notes)) I just must warn you that you don't allow em em anybody who says he's a doctor treat you. It's not that they are necessarily not capable. But they need to know about your medical history.
112. R: They (sic) know ma.
113. N: How?
114. P: We told them we had accident (sic).
115. N: He knew you are being treated for a neurological disorder?
116. P: Not that one.
117. R: But we told them that we have been to this hospital before.
118. N: That's not the point. He does not have your medical history in detail.
119. P: Oh! Okay
120. N: When you have any problem, even if you don't have money, there should be someone you can call to ask question here.
121. R: We will not do it again ma.
122. N: It's okay.
123. P: Is that the reason for the spitting?
124. N: I am not necessarily saying so. What we need to do now is to see the specialists before we can do a follow-up. Is that clear?
125. R: Yes ma. We are sorry ma.
126. P: Don't be angry ma.
127. N: Ha no o! It's nothing. I just need you to be careful.

128. P: Thank you very much ma.
 129. N: You are welcome.
 130. R: We are so grateful ma.
 131. N: Yes ma. So (0.2) you'll see the dentists and see me in (0.4) ((writes) in six weeks.
 132. P and R: Thank you ma.
 133. N: Make sure you continue with those drugs. The other doctor will help us with other things. The saliva and the main thing. My concern is for you to be fine always.
 134. R: Yes ma.
 135. N: Okay. That's it. Don't skip your drugs o.
 136. P: ((Nods))
 137. R: He won't ma. Thank you very much.
 138. N: Thank you.

NPI 18

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 4 years; Patient: female; Age: 26 years; Occupation: Student; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

63. N: When last were you here?
 64. P: Last week
 65. N: Okay ((reads through the case note)). But you were not given any appointment for today.
 66. P: Yes. It's because I feel I need to come quickly.
 67. N: So what brought you?
 68. P: It's this thing again.
 69. N: What's that? Oh! (0.2) Okay.
 70. P: Last week Monday, as I was just about going to see my aunt in her shop.
 71. N: You fell?
 72. P: They said I fell.
 73. N: Since that time have you experience it again?
 74. P: No o. But this morning. I started having that feeling again.
 75. N: That you'll have it again?
 76. P: Yes.
 77. N: The drugs we gave you to buy, did you get them?
 78. P: I did. But since that thing has gone. I...
 79. N: You don't use them again?
 80. P: No! I used them. It's that other one I don't like to use.
 81. N: Ehn ((writes)). Do you bring the pack?
 82. P: Here is it.
 83. N: Is it this one you said you don't like ((picks out the sachet))?
 84. P: Hmmmmmm: ehm ((0.4) it makes me to...
 85. N: Feeling dizzy?
 86. P: And as if I want to vomit too.
 87. N: Apart from that what else?
 88. P: Hmmmm::: Nothing.

89. N: Tell me how you normally use this.
90. P: ((collects it from N)) It's twice a day.
91. N: What time of the day?
92. P: I used to use it (sic) in the morning after eating.
93. N: What time do you normally eat in the morning?
94. P: May be around 10 *sha*.
95. N: Why
96. P: Me I don't used to like (sic) eating too early o.
97. N: Okay. But do you know you are not helping us?
98. P: I am sorry ma.
99. N: No ooo. This drug in question ought to be used everyday before 8 but you don't use it until 10 or thereabout. When you use it, we told you that you should not rush to go out. At least you should give it about one hour or more. There are some drugs you cannot use when you are to be engaged in active activities. What we'll do is to keep you at it (0.8). Ehm You must keep using this drug.
100. P: This one?
101. N: Yes. You must always use it before 8 in the morning. In fact, 7.30 would be fine. And also use it at night. See! This is not a drug you skip o. Or you like the situation?
102. P: Haa no o!
103. N: So, you must continue using them ((brings out the drugs from the nylon being held by the patient)). This is for But don't do without using them, especially this one. 7.30 in the morning and also 7.30 at night please.
104. P: Thank you ma.
105. N: Have you use them today?
106. P: As I was coming.
107. N: Alright then. Around what time.
108. P: 9.30
109. N: Are you sure of that?
110. P: Yes
111. N: Did you eat?
112. P: Yes
113. N: What did you eat?
114. P: Tea and bread.
115. N: And you were okay with that?
116. P: Very okay
117. N: No *wahala*. Let me check your B.P and also...((examines the P)) Is this place paining you?
118. P: No
119. N: What about here?
120. P: No ma.
121. N: Okay. So, continue with your medication and see us in three weeks.
122. P: Okay ma. Should I buy more when the drugs finish?
123. N: The prescription I gave you will cover beyond your next time of visit.
124. P: Okay. ((exits))

NPI 19

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 2 years; Patient: female; Age: 60; Occupation: Pensioner; Ailment: Wernicke aphasia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. R: Good morning
2. N: How are you
3. P: We thank God
4. N: Do you remember what you ate this morning?- What did you eat?
5. P: um::::: some of the drugs (0.8)
6. N: Where are you living?
7. P: um::::: some of the:: drugs that:: was (sic) given there in this paper
8. N: ((to R)) have you been able to notice what's an::d – but I'm trying to communicate – but he's telling me what's recorded. So what he has is em: Wernicke's em: aphas:: aphasia. Wernicke's aphasia. Such that he's not able to comprehend (.) but he can talk. So: he now makes up for it by confabulating. Yes. I guess that's it – but he's improving (.) compared to=
9. R: =he's improving=
10. N: At least we can talk to him, he can greet people properly.
11. R: He communicates well. He also...
12. N: = It's over time. He will: he will get better with time. But (.) at least he's improving compared to:: any other problem?
13. R: He has temperature yesterday
14. N: Hum hum:
15. R: He couldn't complete his physiotherapy: something (.) when we got here yesterday (.) he was having temperature. So when we checked his B.P. his B.P was 162 over ()
16. N: But (.) at least. For how long has he been having that temperature?
17. R: It was just yesterday.
18. N: Did it sustain after the: physiotherapy? The temperature.
19. R: It subsides.
20. N: Does it cont – as in – as in – as in temperature – as in – have you notice any temperature: (). Has any fever since that time he had this=
21. R: = No no _:
22. N: What was it when it was checked? Or you just touched his body=
23. R: = Ehen ehn. The body=
24. N: =But since that time it has not been hot?
25. R: In the night ()
26. N: Is he eating well?
27. R: He's eating well
28. N: He's not complaining of bone pain? Body ache::?
29. R: Um:: like (.) initially he was complaining of them when they discharged him. So when he's coming for the physiotherapy and other routine. But it's only when they are massaging the hands and legs=
30. N: what was the last time you treat- ted: - did you treat him for malaria while he was on bed?
31. R: Yes. He was treated for malaria
32. N: (To the P) Sir, sir, when you urinate, (0.8) do you feel hotness in your urine? ((N interprets this in Yoruba))
33. P: As a:::t th:::at ti::me ()=

34. R: () I used to follow him ()
35. N: Does it lead to pain?
36. R: No, it doesn't lead to
37. N: and he's not coughing?
38. R: No
39. N: Just treat him for malaria. Let's think it's malaria again. ((writes)) (0.8) Do you have any outstanding test that you ought to have done for him?
40. R: I gave him the last one.
41. N: Okay. He's done with it already? () So we just continue treating his hypertension
42. R: O_:kay
43. N: And he's on Epital already
44. R: O_:kay. His drugs, they only gave us Artesuna_:te=
45. N: =Hehen just for two weeks. Now if you are () (pauses)
46. R: Bu:t there was no any analgesic?
47. N: Is he have:: is he still having any pains like that?
48. R: No_:
49. N: The physiotherapy::: he shouldn't be anal:: on analgesic now! If he does, why would why would he be on analgesic when there is no need for it henh? But anytime he complains of pain, you can just give him Paracetamol. Paracetamol would do. It's enough analgesic. ((writes in the case notes))
50. R: ((Nods in affirmation))
51. N: So go on with that. We'll see next time.
52. R: Thank you ma.

NPI 20

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 8 years; Patient: female;
Age: 64; Occupation: Retired Teacher; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status:
accompanied by a relation

1. N: So, what is it mama?
2. P: ((Goes into a lengthy narrative in an indigenous language to indicate that she has been struggling with her knees despite previous treatments and drugs))
3. N: Okay. We'll just adjust your drugs. These ones that she has been using before, she'll have to continue, except this Ketra and all these ones. All others that I have written should be continued.
4. R: What about this? The one she was given last week
5. N: Don't worry. Let her continue with that. It's only these you must help her avoid. Let her continue with all these that I wrote.
6. R: Okay.
7. N: So, I'll see you in four weeks' time.
8. R: Thank you sir.

NPI 21

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 4 years; Patient: male; Age: 37;
Occupation: undisclosed; Ailment: Migraine; Visitation status: unaccompanied

1. N: ((Collects the case note)). ((Reads aloud)) How has it been?
2. P: The hand has not been shaking anymore. But, (0.8) When I was taking the drug maybe 12 hourly before. Like 10 hours, I will be having this very serious headache, so, they change it. I'm now taking it (0.8) morning, maybe 6.am 12noon, 6pm.
3. N: You increased it on your own?
4. P: No, they increased it. sometime: : like now I'm supposed to have take: : This is 12 o clock. In the next 30 minutes if I don't take it. I'll be having this very serious headache. (0.32) And if I don't take this, I won't be able to sleep.
5. N: It's okay. Go and see him ((points to another neurologist at the other corner of the consulting room)). ((to the other neurologist)). When I finished I'll talk with him.

NPI 22

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 1 year; Patient: male;
Age: 35 years; Occupation: Artisan; Ailment: Neurotic dysfunctional erectile;
Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: Good afternoon ma.
2. N: Good afternoon. What is the problem?
3. P: My thing is not rising?
4. N: Huh? You mean?
5. P: This one ((pointing between the thighs)) is down.
6. N: (0.32) ((reads the case file)) Ehn ehn. Mummy, when did it happen? How did you know it's down? When
7. P: Last month
8. N: Last month, July or June
9. R: It was last month he noticed. He didn't know whether it was there or not, but it was last month he noticed.
10. N: Please...
11. R: He has mental illness before.
12. N: Yes. I know. But ehm (0.8) some of the drugs that they give for people in his case can cause erectile dysfunction. Please ask him how he knew ((to the person interpreting)). "How do you know it's not erect"?
13. P: Whenever I eat and drink water, it will come and go.
14. N: "Go down? Is it when you eat that it comes down?"
15. P: Whenever I eat and drink water.
16. N: "And when you urinate, it will come down? "
17. P: Yes.
18. N: "You are the one assuming so"
19. R: He said, it gets strong sometimes
20. N: "Yes, you are the one thinking so. When it's not that you want to copulate with a woman. It can't just stay erected. Why would it stay? What for?" That's what I'm asking him. Do you understand?
21. R: I understand ma?

22. N: ((To the interpreter)), mummy understands.
23. R: He has not asked a woman out before. He doesn't flirt with woman.
24. N: Does he go to school?
25. R: Yes
26. N: Which secondary school
27. P: P^SP Grammar School in Ekiti state.
28. N: Do you have girlfriend?
29. P: No?
30. N: But you planned of getting married?
31. P: Yes
32. N: You said
33. N: How did you notice it?
34. P: I check am now.
35. N: Why did you check it
36. P: I don dey aware of it (sic). When I checked the two things here, Na only one I come see dey here. "when I heard some people advertising that we should check our scrotum, so that was when I checked and discovered it was only one".
37. N: ((checks the case file)) You were here last week?
38. R: Yes, we came for the other thing about his mental illness and we were given one month on the 7th of October, before we should come again. But when he checked and was disturbed about this thing. We decided to come again today.
39. N: You know what. Can you hear what I'm saying? That thing eh, if (0.8) right from when you were small, it's only one you have, now (0.8) we cannot do anything about it. Is it only one you have when you were small?
40. P: I didn't take note.
41. N: Did you ever check ma?
42. R: I also didn't take note. I didn't check because he's not the only male child I have.
43. N: Is there any other of your children that have similar challenge?
44. R: None.
45. N: Have they all have children?
46. R: One already has.
47. N: What about the other? Is he married?
48. R: Is a female
49. N: The male has a child, right?
50. R: He has three children.
51. N: The thing is (0.8) usually, what they called descent of the testis. Listen to me because you understand English. Normally, when you are in the stomach...
52. R: There was a time he had pains here ((touching below the stomach))
53. N: Have they cut it?
54. R: That time that he complained of the pains, we put some drugs and it left him.
55. N: Traditional herbs, right?
56. R: It's like *Oyinbo* drugs
57. N: Which hospital did you go to?
58. R: It's not a hospital
59. N: Where was that?
60. R: In Ekiti their hometown
61. N: A local doctor?
62. R: Yes, they just gave us some drugs to mix inside water which he used. It didn't disturb him again since then.

63. N: Well, what I was going to tell you is that. That thing, huhn? Every man is supposed to have two. So usually, when you are inside your mother's stomach, the two of them are inside your stomach first. But as the baby is growing growing is growing, those two things will be coming down. I'll like to draw them, so that you'll understand ((draws on a sheet of paper)). This is your penis, this's your leg, this is your side. When you are in the stomach, huh? The thing will be here, it will be coming down. But immediately they give birth to you, it's supposed to be inside here. Immediately you are nine month, even seven month *sef* to eight month in your mother's stomach, the thing is supposed to be somewhere here, down here. Immediately you are born, the two of them would enter. But for some people, one of them would come down, the other one would just stay there, *nibi* waist (near the waist). It would just be there, but if their mother notices it the day that the gave birth to them, the people they called surgeon, we call them paediatric surgeons, people that do surgery for small children. They would open that place and bring the thing inside here. So, your own would be down here. That's just because you are small. But if that thing stays for more than one months, some surgeons (0.8) they don't even wait for the child to be two months. If the thing stays there for more than three months. This thing is not supposed to where there is heat. The sperms that are there, they don't need to be where there is heat. Just like when you sit down, you try and open your leg small, so that breeze would touch you. So, that place, heat is not supposed to touch that place at all. But now that it has stayed in your body for thirty-four years, the thing is already dead. I've not checked you but I will still check. If what you are telling me is true that it is not there. It supposed to have come down. And if he doesn't come down, and you didn't do anything about it, your stomach would just be paining you. It can turn cancerous. Usually, X-cell would die and can turn into cancer. So, do you understand?
64. P: Yes
65. R: He didn't
66. ((the interpreter then re-explained in Yoruba))
67. N: Now, come and lie down here ((carries out physical examination of the patient)). ((a senior neurologist enters)) Sir, this patient is not medical, it is surgical o.
68. R: ((Weeping)) Please ma
69. N: I'm surprised you did not notice this early enough. What happened mama?
70. R: I've had some other children before. I have lost a male child to this before ((kneeling down)). He had an injury about one and half years.
71. N: I know you want this child to marry. But we would have to refer you. We cannot say because he has erectile illness, we would stop his treatment. Maybe he should go to endocrinologist to examine him. He might also need to see a psychiatrist so they can help him in the aspects of the desire for the opposite sex. It is possible that he has desires for a woman later and be productive. You don't need to cry. They'll will check him up and advise you properly. I'll want you to come back next week. So, we'll re-present your matter to the other specialist. Have you had sex with a girl before?
72. R: He has never.
73. N: Let him ANSWER, you are not the one we are asking. You can't know.
74. P: I have not done it before.
75. N: ARE YOU SURE?
76. P: Only when I was small that I did it
77. N: You (0.8) PUT IT INSIDE?
78. P: Yes

79. N: When?
 80. P: When I was small.
 81. N: How old were you then
 82. P: Twelve?
 83. N: Are you sure? What class were you? Primary or secondary?
 84. P: I was about twelve years. I was about going to secondary school.
 85. N: You'll come next week. We don't want you to spend for nothing. So, you'll come next week.
 86. R: Please, I need your help so that there won't be operation sir ((to the researcher)).
 87. N: Don't worry. Just come next week.
 88. R: Should he eat before coming?
 89. N: Yes. He should eat.
 90. R: Thank you ma. Thank you sir.

NPI 23

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 3 years; Patient: male; Age: 13; Occupation: Pupil; Ailment: Dyslexia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

21. N: Let him sit down. You can use the other sit.
 22. R: Thank you ma. They said we should come here.
 23. N: Yes. Your child was diagnosed of dyslexia.
 24. R: Is is true sir (0.8) that we can't...
 25. N: Wait. You must know one thing. Dyslexia is not a disease or an identifiable physical condition. It is a learning style that usually can be assessed through a profile that shows whether the child has a typical pattern of strengths and weaknesses, coupled with assessment to rule out other possible causes of symptoms, such as vision or hearing problems. From the reports with me, some of the issues raised are common traits of what we are talking about. But there are things we can do.
 26. R: So, that is how he would be?
 27. N: I just told you it's not a disease. Of course, we can see it as a disorder but definitely not a disease as you appear to be feeling. Anyway, there are some things we can still do. I mean some interventions are possible.
 28. R: Okay sir. (0.32) But like what.
 29. N: Let me ask you some questions first.
 30. R: Yes ma
 31. N: When he was a toddler, did she have any serious injury? Like falling down or anything.
 32. R: Yes
 33. N: What happened?
 34. R: We had a house girl then. ((sobs)) I was at the office when they called that she fell from her and hit on the flo:::or.
 35. N: It's okay. Did you do anything? As in hospital and the rest.
 36. R: We went to a private hospital.
 37. N: Why?
 38. R: Doctors were on strike then.
 39. N: For how long?
 40. R: I can say clearly now but *sha*, I know it's more than three months.

41. N: Okay. Baby girl. How are you?
42. P: Fine
43. N: What class are you?
44. P: Four?
45. N: Is that correct ((to the relation))
46. R: ((Shakes her head from left to right))
47. N: Okay. ((Writes some sentences in a plain sheet of paper, gets up from her seat and stands beside the patient)) Can you read this for me?
48. P: ((Looking))
49. N: *Oya*. Let's try
50. P: I:::am girl ((missing the words "beautiful little"))
51. N: I am a beautiful little girl. Say it
52. P: I litt:::le girl.
53. N: It's alright. ((Goes back to her seat)) Like I said, what we need to do are interventions.
54. R: Yes ma.
55. N: ((Removing some notes from the table)) What I mean is that we will observe some things to help your girl. I hope you will be ready.
56. R: I'm ready. (0.8) We are ready, anything.
57. N: Okay then. The issue is that young people with this kind of challenge can benefit from speech therapy. Emmm, what did they call that o? (0.8) Yes! Phonetic (0.4), no, phonemic awareness. Where you were referred in Abeokuta, did you hear this?
58. R: No o o. Maybe that is why we were told to come here.
59. N: Okay then. I think the teaching in the ability to hear and work with the sounds of letters and letter combinations is what I referred to. I mean the phonemic awareness. That is one of the things they can do to help him readjust. What normally happens is that a speech therapist may also work on what they call phonics. This will make her know the relationship between letters and the sounds they make. That is just a part, other things would still be done.
60. R: But ma, how do we get that?
61. N: Well, in some cases, a specially trained reading specialist may do this type of therapy instead of a speech therapist. You may also want to explore educational therapy.
62. R: Meaning?
63. N: It is a kind of therapy that could reduce some of your child's anxiety about school and make it easier for her to perform in class. It is possible that dyslexia affects her self-esteem or causes anxiety or stress. If that is the case, psychological counselling could also help her perform better in school.
64. R: O::kay.
65. N: you also need to talk to her teachers about what instructional strategies they use in her school. The ideal thing is for her to be taught in multisensory ways. I mean that kind of teaching that connect what they see, hear and feel. You live in Lagos, you should be able to get a good school like that. Here, we have some schools we do recommend to our patients. And they do come back with good report. I hope this is not too much?
66. R: ((smiles))
67. N: You are smiing. That is the truth. Your daughter is not really sick. She just needs help to readjust.
68. R: So, ma, what else can help people in this situation?

69. N: Yes. I was coming to that. You can (0.2) Oh! I mean, you should also support your child at home. You might try and get audiobooks or dictation software and other things that can help her learn. If you get these android phones, there are apps for children that you can use. I can remember Chu-chu TV. If you can do some of these things and may be get some games, if possible, they that can make reading easier for her.
70. R: Okay ma.
71. N: I will get you some links with specialist that will help the situation. But it's not really anything to gloat about. ((Writes)) (0.32) So that's it. I'll give you my phone number, so that you can get in touch easily. ((writes)). So we'll see again. Go and give that to the Matron, she will guide you.
72. R: Thank you ma. ((exits with the patient))

NPI 24

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: male; Age: 66 years; Occupation: undisclosed; Ailment: Stuttering; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

45. N: ((To the researcher)) Please just observe and note whatever you can but don't record this. I will tell you when you should. Or you are not okay by that.
46. I: No problem sir. As you wish sir.
47. R: ((goes into a lengthy narration. The N signals the I to go ahead with audio recording after the R narration))
48. N: So since when did you notice the stuttering and his slow body movement? Is it not about 2 weeks?
49. R: Since last two Monday.
50. N: ((Writes)). Is he walking any differently then?
51. R: I usually take him to walk, since he can't walk normally.
52. N: Is he diabetic
53. Pat R: he is . : -
54. N: Which drug was he placed?
55. P: Bor:::der:::li::ne
56. N: So, it's Borderline? You are not on any strong indication. And does he use it regularly?
57. R: No
58. N: But if he eats it on empty stomach, that could be the cause too.
59. P: Dr P^SP
60. N: So, it is Dr P^SP that manages you. So how do you it? You see Dr P^SP and cross again \$\$ How do you did it?
61. R: Let's meet Dr P^SP and tell him it's not a problem.
62. N: What has he been using for the control of the hypertension? ((R responds)). ((writes on and talks intermittently)) Cholesterol 107. HDL 62... The urinalysis is normal.
63. P: O:::kay £.
64. N: The result you brought claims this one is normal but from what we see here. Certainly, this is not correct.
65. R: Okay

66. N: So, there is no cause for alarm sir. I think it's all metabolic-related and (0.2) and all that.
67. P: I:::wa::s (0.4) a bit wo::rried at a point
68. N: Too long
69. R: No. No. for medication (0.4)
70. N: Too many drugs. Ok sir.
71. P: I:::know I can't do any:::thing about it
72. N: Yes. It's true.
73. P: But em : : : (0.4)
74. N: If you can cut down on them (0.32) I think it's the : : : 00 (...) Does he use Aspirin ((R nods in disagreement)). Any multi-vitamin?
75. R: This one ((referring to the one in the drug bag)).
76. N: He should follow his medication. That should clear some of these ... And then we'll wait till we have the result. Then we can decide on the next thing ...) > So let him do the test at (...). we won't add any drugs now until we have the results
77. P: For goo:::d or bad?
78. N: No No No No: We just need to be sure so as to:: We'll just wait for 6 weeks or 2 months.
79. R: So what is actually outstanding how?
80. N: It's just the blood test. And then we would adjust your medication, but you can continue the banana supplement.
81. P: Sho:::shou:::uld it be:::be once in::: a day?
82. R: One a day? Should it be once in a day?
83. N: One a day should be fine. That will also give you extra potassium.
84. R: Thank you so much sir.
85. P: Tha:::nk you sir.
86. N: Thank you sir-sorry. Just go home and rest sir.
87. R: Thanks for your care for him.
88. N: We thank God. He's doing so well. Just have a good rest at home sir and enjoy yourself. Sorry. Thank you : : :

NPI 25

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 3 years; Patient: female; Age: 45; Occupation: Artisan; Ailment: Migraine; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

31. N: What is the problem ma?
32. P: This my kneel (sic) is really disturbing me.
33. N: When did it start?
34. P: Four days ago.
35. N: Four days?
36. P: Actually. It was after I came back home from the travel (sic). I started feeling hot. So I said may be it's because of the stress. So I decided to use some drugs and Paracetamol. But the headache continued. So after two days of the headache (sic). Em... I used em the::: *agbo* ((local herbal concoction)). So I was told to rest may be it will go. But the day after. I started feeling pain in my leg. I was even thinking maybe, it's because of the fasting. So when it did not go. I said I should come and see you today.
37. N: That's okay. ((Examines the patients)). Let me see your drugs.
38. P: ((Brings out the pack)) Em::: this one has finished and can't get it anywhere to buy.
39. N: ((smiles)) Okay. Since when?

40. P: Before I travelled.
41. N: And when you came back, what did you do?
42. P: When I searched searched searched (sic) and could not see it *nko*?
43. N: Did you check (...).
44. P: The one at (...) near (...)
45. N: Not that one. They may not have it. I mean the (...) pharmacy.
46. P: I don't know o. And I think their thing may be too cost (sic) for me.
47. N: But what can be more important than your health? I know. Somethings can be too costly. Yes, very costly. But is there anything that can be truly more costly than anybody's good health?
48. P: It's money o. Things are too cost (sic)
49. N: Money? Important than your health?
50. P: No o. I mean when I don't have the money *nko*?
51. N: But you can't just assume now.
52. P: It's true o. I will try to go check it.
53. N: You see. That drug that was finished is the main one that helps in the control of that problem in the leg. You should have got another one as we told you when you came here the other time. You will have to go and continue using it (0.8) I mean you will have to go and buy it and continue using it. Before we can look at other things. ((looks through the file)) I also feel you should do some tests. But buy the drugs and keep using it. ((writes)) "Don't want till your drugs are exhausted, always stick to the use of other ones here. ((continues writing)) You will have to see us next week. Then, we will take it up from there.
54. N: Do you normally sleep well?
55. P: Yes. Except when the pain wakes me up.
56. N: Okay. ((hands the prescription over to patient)) You will ask someone to help you get the drug at that place and make sure you use them as I told you. One in the morning and one at night.
57. P: Thank you sir.
58. N: You are welcome. Greet your people for me.
59. P: Thank you sir.
60. N: Take care.

NPI 26

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: male; Age: 58 years; Occupation: Retired Teacher; Ailment: Broca aphasia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

61. N: How are you feeling now?
62. P: Hmm I am:::::::::: i:::::in (0.10) te::
63. N: Can you tell me your name?
64. P: ((opens mouth, shakes his head)) I:: ya::am EE::::mm P^SP (0.4) ((pronounces the name))
65. N: Good! Why did you initially do like this? Can you tell me again?
66. P: ((tries)) (0.8) hm:: ((then manages to pronounce the name))
67. N: Can you remember when last you came here?
68. P: ha::
69. N: Can't you remember it?
70. P: *ba:*
71. N: Who is P^SP

72. P: My daughter
73. N: Fine! Tell me your name in full
74. P: O::::y: P^SP ((says the name))
75. N: That's a good one.
76. P: Thank:: (0.4) you. ((smiling))
77. N: That's good. You are smiling. Can you tell me where you came from?
78. P: My:: my house.
79. N: ((laughing)) I mean your state of origin
80. P: Be:: be::: nue!
81. N: Great! Now, tell me your name again.
82. P: ((successfully mentions the name but with some difficulty mentions his name)) :::
83. N: Which town do you hail from? It may be where I hail from o. We may hail from the same town.
84. P: ha:::!
85. N: ((waiting for response, then writes and then looks up)) which town do you hail from? You don't remember? If I tell you – if I remember and tell you, I will collect something from you o
86. P: ((smiling)) huh:
87. N: I'm still waiting o. Now, tell me –you hail from which town?
88. P: (points to a direction) ():::
89. N: What is your occupation? You were a lawyer? (is it one child)
90. P: ((Nods in disagreement))
91. N: Teacher?
92. P: Ye ye::: ye::::s
93. N: Okay. You have tried. Where were you before this thing happened?
94. P: La:::g:os
95. N: Sorry. How did it happen? This sickness. How did it happen
96. P: ((feeling discomfort with the questions)) Hiii::::::::::sh ((long hiss))
97. N: Where were you exactly when it happened.
98. P: At:: ((raises hand to describe)) Ik::::::::::
99. N: You were going to have a bath right? You were inside the bathroom then right?
You were inside the bathroom
100. P: ((nods))
101. N: ((to the R)) They said he fell at the bathroom right?
102. R: Yes. Bathroom
103. P: When I::: w:was
104. N: Okay.
105. P: I:: I::: ((0.8)) fell
106. N: Go on
107. P: ((Nods))
108. N: ((Writes)) You are improving. The last time he was here ((to the R)) you know he could not even remember anything. For his speeches. It is gradual. It will come back. Just let's keep using his drugs. Is the physiotherapist still coming?
109. R: Yes.
110. N: How often?
111. R: Every Wednesday
112. N: And the exercise?
113. R: Yes. We still do it. It's only that he complains sometimes.
114. N: ((To the P)) They said you are not doing your exercise.

115. P: ((frowns and nods))
 116. N: We will need it for your rapid improvement o. ((To the R)) Does he allow the therapist?
 117. R: He has no choice with that one.
 118. N: Okay. Let us keep him on these drugs for now. It is only this one I need to add. He'll get better and better as times go on. ((To the P)) When next you come, I want you to have been better o. So, if they tell me you don't use your drugs or refused to do exercise, we would fight o.
 119. N: ((smiling and nodding))
 120. R: So, we'll see you ((writes)) in a month's time. Do have a nice weekend sir. ((hands over some files to R)) Give this to the nurse. They will guide you.

NPI 27

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 4 years; Patient: female; Age: 48 years; Occupation: Teacher; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: You've seen me before sir?
2. P: Yes
3. N: I notice some improvements now. Or, how is your body? Respond
4. P: Shey::
5. R: =How is your body? *Won ni* how is your body=
6. N: *How do you feel in your body?* = *Bawo 'lara yin se?*
7. P: It's is::::: fine
8. N: ((to the R)) Small small. (*it's*) little by little=
9. P: ^ =Very ve::::ry annoying=>. We have been here since some minutes to eight in the morning. We are three. Hmmm number three.
10. R: Yeah.
11. P: ^ It was number three >that ()< and for two::: At the end of the day, we could not get anyone, any::::where. we waited. At the end of the day, we didn't see anything again.
12. N: Don't be offended
13. P: No: not you:: you know that she was the one holding and distributing them, is she the one that should hold it?...She ought to inform people that, those things are with her.
14. N: It's classical now. Neologism. They have this neo (.) neologism and then – ehn?
15. R: ((interrupts)) he's going back to what has happened before. ehn?
16. N: No. he doesn't- he's trying to - [he's expressing::]=
17. P: It's not fair now! Very early this morning, I gave it to that woman (.) and I checked in the morning, it was there. Instead of waiting for the breakfast, I refused to eat tha::at before:: ten, I should finish breakfast but up till now. Nothing is found. ((faces the N)) You understand?
18. N: Okay. Don't be offended
19. P: No! Not you! No, it's not you. You are looking at job. You are hardworking on your job.
20. N: ((to R)) How is his body
21. R: It's better _:

22. N: It's bit by bit. Small small.. Ehn Have you seen the dietician – I think I saw him the last time=
23. R: Yes. The last time. We did not see them, before we were ready, they have gone – but it was this morning that we saw...
24. N: So, what did he say
25. R: They have given us what we are going to use.
26. N: okay _:
27. P: ((tries to give a note to the Doc))
28. N: *E maa* worry () ... okay. ((collects the paper)).
29. R: The fruits he ate
30. N: This one of the 27th, what did he eat?
31. R: You see that of the 27th. He ate, what is it (.) GRAPE.
32. N: That's okay but but this one is high.
33. R: It's the one that I...
34. N: Our target is hundred. It should not exceed hundred. These ones are okay. Do you understand? It shows that=
35. R: When I control it here)
36. N: Ehn::
37. R: It's high here. It's that morning time, they initially said that it's not high. After:: - I can't even remember again now.: But at this place, he just eat just meat-pie and vegetable. So two hours after, it was controlled.
38. N: Control? So, now (0.4). You know that you have really juggle around with his meal?
39. R: I have increase his ehm to one gram). Increase (metomill) to one gram
40. N: so I think it's fair=
41. R: So, so it's the Mill we would control.
42. N: Yes. It's the mill we would control... control- now with the dietetic advice. We'll be able to- -and I want-the next time when you come (0.8)... what is his weight today?
43. R: They didn't measure his weight.
44. N: He did measure his weight.
45. R: ((looks into a paper)) One thirteen point five (113.5) =
46. N: =It's still very much!
47. R: Point five
48. N: One time () as in proper decrease-not a sharp one-as in::: slow decrease in his weight. Let's work him up to like:::ehm::: hundred. So in the next three months. I want him to lose this, thirteen point five.
49. R: Okay.
50. N: You can see that I said three months, I don't say you should rush him. So that you'll not give him food again o \$. But, does he do exercise round the house? Has he started exercise?
51. R: He has started walking::: around
52. N: Around]?
53. R: Like yesterday, when he went to barb his hair. He did a little trekking ((N writes on, long pause)) he has been angry since.
54. N: He should not be angry o
55. R: \$
56. N: It's because there are many people in the clinic today. It's not that one is really playing. Do you know? People are many.

57. R: And when they come...
58. N: And shuffle like that, they will distribute across board like that.
59. R: When did that (0.8) start?
60. N: The previous day. Three days ago.
61. P: Yesterday's catarrh have stop o
62. R: All these drugs would ha:::ve been::: okay
63. N: Is he not running temperature
64. R: No. ()
65. N: He was not hot?
66. R: He sneeze
67. N: Ehn, just Vitamin C would do ((writes)). Continue your medication _: so a little by little, you can begin to teach him words like... Like you are teaching a small child. ((pauses)) Do you still have your drugs?
68. R: Yes. But we don't have (.) again. Only a sachet is left
69. N: I will include it for you ((writes prescriptions)). So, we would see you let's say in one month's time.
70. P: Let it be two months.
71. N: Do you hear? ((to the R)) what did he say?
72. R: He said two months.
73. N: Oh! you prefer two months because of the distance *abi*?
74. P: Yeah
75. N: okay, no problem. Two months! ((hands over the prescription and other notes to the relative)).

NPI 28

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 5 years; Patient: male; Age: 71 years; Occupation: Retired Civil Servant; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: Morning sir
2. N: Welcome
3. P: You said we should come back for the BP today.
4. N: Yes, get him seated. ((carries out the BP examination)) This is still high o
5. R: Maybe became of the travelling stress.
6. N: This drug, are you going to use it? Then changing it now (0.8) is it still remaining?
7. R: ((checks the drug pack)) Here are few.
8. N: Let's do this. Let me add. Can you still get it to buy for him here?
9. R: He lives in Lagos. I don't know if we can get it here
10. N: He live in Lagos, right?
11. R: we should get it
12. N: This is a combination of 40/10.5 ((demonstrates with the drug pack)). Now this is our target. Since the stroke has happened we must prevent another one from happening. So, we must control blood, sugar level and
13. R: Cholesterol.
14. N: Yes. Once those one are controlled. We can smile ((writes)) please take time to use his drugs for him. We are stopping this one ((remove a drug pack)) for now. It's only the recommended ones and Neurovite you should continue. Has he done physiotherapy before?

15. R: He come here to do it.
16. N: It's the BP that must go down for now, you'll see us every one month, later we'll increase it to two months, four months and later six month ((Gives out the prescription))

NPI 29

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: female; Age: 54 years; Occupation: undisclosed; Ailment: Brain aneurysm; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. P: We have been kept waiting sir.
2. N: It's not our own doing, we have many patient today. (0.8) So, how is it?
3. P: It's her we have come to see you for.
4. N: Okay. ((looks into the case file)) You have the results?
5. P: Yes sir. ((hands them over to the doctor))
6. N: ((Looking at the result on a machine)) Well, we have a case of aneurysm. I mean (0.4) Brain aneurysm. As a medical doctor in practice, Is that not who you are?
7. P: I'm in training sir. Penultimate year in school.
8. N: Oh I see. Are you the one that followed her the last time?
9. P: No sir.
10. N: Okay. As I was saying. This result tells us she has aneurysm ((spelling it)) A-N-E-U-R-Y-S-M. Well. (0.24) A brain aneurysm is a balloon or bubble-like growth that typically develops where a major artery branches into smaller arteries, often at the base of the brain. This em naturally has the potential of leaking or rupturing. She is 54 years old now.
11. P: Yes sir
12. N: The aneurysm condition, according to research, em ehen, (0.8) most commonly affects adults between the ages of 35 to 60 years old. In fact, it affects women more frequently than men. ((discussing with student doctor present)) Brain aneurysms typically don't cause symptoms until they leak or rupture. When that happens, it will cause bleeding into the brain. This can only be discovered during tests for other conditions. Even when they cause no symptoms, these aneurysms should be treated to prevent future ruptures. Talking about the symptom. This can show through a sudden and extremely severe headache that may occur with nausea, vomiting, stiff neck, impaired consciousness, seizures or coma. A ruptured brain aneurysm is a very serious condition that in some cases can be fatal. ((a student asks a question)) ((in response)) The only way out is a quick and accurate diagnosis. Yes, recovery is very possible. It's good you responded fast.
13. P: Thank God
14. N: Alright sir, for your mum, I will tell you the available options. Okay?
15. P: Thank you sir.
16. N: No o, you would have to make a choice for her.
17. P: Okay sir.
18. N: For this kind of situation ehm, almost all brain aneurysms should be treated to prevent them from rupturing or repair ruptured aneurysms as quickly as possible and strengthen the arteries to prevent future ruptures. So
19. P: I don't understand sir

20. N: I mean, she must to prevent them from rupturing or repair ruptured aneurysms as quickly as possible.
21. P: How sir?
22. N: There are options. They can place her for surgery. For instance, they can use microsurgical clipping. This is what they use for majority of aneurysms to treat aneurysms. Usually, they are accessed through an opening in the skull ((demonstrates)). Alternatively, they can use skull (...) surgery. This is typically used for deep and complex aneurysms located beneath the brain. The aneurysm is accessed through the bone at the base of the skull. The other is the Vascular Bypass (...) A vein is taken from the leg and used to connect an artery in the neck and an artery in the brain to bypass the aneurysm. There is also endovascular Therapy which is a minimally invasive alternative to surgery in treating brain aneurysms. They also call it endovascular coiling. To do this, the procedure does not require an incision in the head. (0.12) It is performed under general anesthesia or light sedation, and has a shorter recovery time and hospital stay compared to conventional surgery. The problem is you cannot recommend it for all patients. ((facing the relation of the patient)), which of these will you prefer?
23. R: Ha sir, I don't think I understand them enough sir. Maybe we will come back.
24. N: The situation does not give us much time. I'm even considering placing her on admission.
25. R: I'll have to contact my people sir for money.
26. N: Alright, go and find a way out of that. It's alright.
27. R: Okay sir.
28. N: Let me know your decision. I'll still be here till afternoon.
29. R: Thank you sir. ((Exit with the patient))

NPI 30

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 6 years; Patient: female; Age: 47 years; Occupation: Retiree; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: How are you today ma?
2. P: We are here a:::gain o
3. N: God will answer your prayers
4. P: I pray o
5. N: Don't worry
6. P: We can only be hopeful.
7. N: Have you been using those drugs?
8. P: Yes
9. N: When last did you use this?
10. P: I just feel that before using this one ((the relation gives the drugs pack to the neurologist)) we should ask you.
11. N: ((Collects it) Hmm. Are you still feeling the pain
12. P: There are time I don't feel pain at all.
13. N: ((Physically examines the patient)) (0.32) What about it presently?
14. P: It is paining me seriously

15. N: Okay. We know what to do. You should just follow what we ask you to do. It's alright. ((writes)) I have written what you will need for you. ((Turns to the relation)) Please take care of him o and regards to your people at home. And please call the next patient ((mentions name))

NPI 31

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 2 years; Patient: female; Age: 51 years; Occupation: Teacher; Ailment: Seizure; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

N: Welcome ma

P: Thanks for the other time sir.

N: Okay ma. Thank you. How are you feeling?

P: It's that same leg sir.

N: What happened to your leg?

P: You are still feeling it?

P: Its's still disturbing me o!

N: Okay. ((gazing at the case notes as the woman keeps talking)) Alright. Em:- I was trying to look at our old records.

P: Okay sir. Thank you sir.

N: So, the leg where you experienced the seizure is the only problem?

P: It is o.

N: No other problem?

P: I can eat:-

N: You can eat

N: That's good (looks through the case note). That's fine. That's only thing you came for ((looks on into the case note, then to the P)) 2005! And it's still there?

P: Yes sir o

N: Have you checked your blood sugar level?

P: It's *pajapaja* o

N: Did you do your blood sugar?

Pat: Yes

N: Do you have the results with you?

P: No _:

N: I've asked you to do it. I thought I requested for that?

P: Oh 00. Sorry I've done all of them before.

N: Really?

P: Yes

N: Let me look through the file. I'll check.

P: They did not put it in the file sir. It was during the long strike.

N: But you suppose to have the result with you then.

P: They did not give them to me sir o

N: where?

P: Downstairs at pharmacology. Down down. They did not give me the result.

N: ((Looks on into the case works)) Yes Hmm. This is:. You have done this one. 2004__:
This is obsolete. That is 2004 _:

P: They did not give me the results.

N: Anyway! No problem. So: as you are here seated. You feel you have seizure in that leg?

P: It's there sir o?
 N: From where to where? Up to where?
 P: ((Touches leg)) from here to this.
 N: So it's on the right leg?
 P: Yes. It's much here.
 N: Okay. Neurovite did not help you?
 P: Sir?
 N: The one I prescribed to you?
 P: I'm using it. But it's finished. It's what I have been using.
 N: I'll check your blood pressure now.
 P: I told them there. They said::
 N: We'll check it now. ((checks)) 170/90. It's still high. ((Writes)) if I decide to write (...).
 It's very expensive: I'm not certain of its ability to help but we can try it for two weeks. I think it's better.
 P: Thank you sir.
 N: For the blood pressure, I've included (...)
 P: You have put it sir?
 N: We want it to go down.
 P: Eh Ehn. Help me put it. Thank you Sir. How about all my children?
 N: They are all fine ma.
 P: Thank you very much sir. I sometimes do have severe headache.
 N: Hmm, okay. ((Writes on))
 P: Thank you greatly
 N: This is the prescription note. ((hands it to P)) So we'll see you in about two weeks
 P: Thank you so much Sir.
 N: Ok ma. Alright. Bye bye ma
 P: Thank you sir o.

NPI 32

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 7 years; Patient: female; Age: 62 years; Occupation: Retired Civil Servant; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

57. P: ((coughing)) My son ((coughs)). I'm lu::cky it's you.
58. N: Good afternoon ma. Mrs P^{SP}, right?
59. P: Yes Sir
60. N: I'm Dr PsP. How do you feel now?
61. P: It's about two weeks now that I started feeling the pain on this part (touches the head).
62. N: ((looks through the case file))
63. P: When we came in the ((coughs)) mor:::ning. This is what they gave us.
64. N: Who did you come with?
65. P: My daughter. I have a complain (sic).
66. N: Okay. What is it this time.
67. P: Whenever I sleep, I used to see myself fighting some masquerades. Although, I usually kill them. So when I wake up in the morning, I used to have shaking body. Even, I won't be able to get up from bed sometimes. I will just be shaking throughout the day.

68. N: How often have you been having such dreams and the shaking too?
69. P: For the past one week.
70. N: ((smiles)) Have you been sleeping well lately?
71. P: Em Hmm (0.8) It's not that I don't sleep *naa o*
72. N: What time do you normally go to bed.
73. P: You know true true (0.4), I used to struggle before sleep can come. And may be because of that drug you said we should not use again.
74. N: Which one is that?
75. P: That small one. Hmmm. I think it's (the name of the drug was mentioned by the neurologist)
76. N: But you have not answered my question o. I said what time do you normally sleep?
77. P: I don't know. But em (0.2).
78. N: Okay. Tell me what happens between seven to ten o'clock in your house.
79. P: Nothing used to happen o.
80. N: Okay. When do you eat your dinner usually?
81. P: Hmmm::: Around 9.30
82. N: 9.30?
83. P: Yes. You know my children close late.
84. N: So until they come, no food?
85. P: Not like that but that time is good for all of us.
86. N: Mama! *Se'fe gbo oto oro?*
87. P: Sir?
88. N: Do you know what? (0.8) Okay. When you finish eating, what do you do?
89. P: I watch television with my children until sleep come (sic)
90. N: What television station is that?
91. P: Africa Magic
92. N: Which of them?
93. P: Igbo and Yoruba
94. N: Okay. (smiles) Like how many films do you normally watch before you go to bed?
95. P: You know those plays are very interesting o.
96. N: Mama! Okay. So you'll watch up to two or three?
97. P: ((laughs))
98. N: Answer me mama.
99. P: Is it because of that?
100. N: You see. Mama, all we told you not to do is what you have been doing.
101. P: No oo
102. N: You are not helping yourself with good rest. The time you sleep is too late. You should be eating early too. Why don't you come with any of your children today?
103. P: They didn't give them chance (sic) at work.
104. N: You know what we'll do? (0.8) ((looks straight into the woman's eyes. Then writes)) Em (0.8). That's it ((hands over the prescriptions note)). Tell them to get you those drugs. Tell P^{SP} to call me. When can they come with you to this clinic?
105. P: I don't know sir.
106. N: I need them to come with you when next you are coming.
107. P: They will try.
108. N: Let them not try o. If you want those things you dreamt of to die *patapata*, they must follow you when next you are coming.
109. P: How many?
110. N: Any one of them. Especially P^{SP}.

111. P: Thank you sir. I will tell them to call you.
112. N: Okay ma. We should see you in three weeks. Please tell the next person to enter.

NPI 33

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 5 years; Patient: female; Age: 66 years; Occupation: undisclosed; Ailment: Dementia; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Welcome. This morning is good o. See how you are shinning.
2. P: Thank you sir.
3. N: How is home? My people *nko*?
4. P: They are fine sir.
5. N: Have you eaten today
6. P: Yes sir
7. N: What did you have for breakfast this morning?
8. P: What did we even eat ((calls the R))
9. N: No o. I want you to tell me yourself.
10. P: Ha!
11. N: Yes
12. P: Hmmm Ehm Ehm::: ehn
13. N: What did you eat in the morning
14. R: Rice
15. N: But I have told you not to tell us now.
16. R: I'm sorry sir
17. N: So what brought him today
18. P: (0.3) It's mala(0.2)ria problem.
19. N: How did you know you have malaria?
20. R: He has been complaining of headache and his body has been hot?
21. N: Any other thing?
22. R: He has pain in his mouth.
23. N: Okay. We'll look into that.
24. R: In fact, he did not sleep on Monday
25. N: So what happens on Tuesday till now?
26. R: He was sleeping. Although, I travelled but came back on Sunday night.
27. N: Has he been using his drugs.
28. P: It finished
29. N: Since when?
30. P: The day she went.
31. N: Is that so?
32. R: Actually ehm ehm
33. N: You see.
34. R: It was because...
35. N: Why did you then conclude he has malaria? ((To the patient)) who told you, you have malaria
36. P: Hmmm::: Hmmm
37. R: When we see that...

38. N: It's okay. It is dangerous you just assume things like this. It is possible that due to the drugs he missed, some of his immune system were broken. But we can't just assume. Do you have some money with you?
39. R: Yes but like how much?
40. N: We'll have to carry out some tests so we can be sure what the problem is. ((writes)) Have you then bought his drugs again since you came back?
41. R: The one he was using before?
42. N: Yes
43. P: It's money o
44. N: Money? That's serious o. But from possible indication, the fact that he stops his drug suddenly is enough to trigger all manners of sickness. Do you have your pack here?
45. R: It's only this.
46. N: You'll have to try and get the drugs we asked you to buy before now. It's after then that we can then say this or that.
47. P: And the test?
48. N: You'll do it and make sure you bring me the results before my shift is over. You'll buy these ones though ((hands over the written prescription))
49. R: Do we need to queue again?
50. N: Not really, just tell whoever you see that you want to give me your results.
51. P: Thank you sir.
52. N: It's okay.

NPI 34

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 9 years; Patient: female; Age: 36 years; Occupation: Artisan; Ailment: Post-concussive syndrome; Visitation status: accompanied by two relations

30. N: Sorry
31. R: Yes sir
32. N: What did you say happened to him?
33. R: He was involved in an accident
34. N: When was that?
35. R: May 1
36. N: This year?
37. R: Yes. It was here we brought him at the other ward. But when the strike started, we were discharged and went to a private hospital.
38. N: Is it ward 12?
39. R: Up there. When we got home. He started causing trouble. He said he was going to Ado.
40. N: Where do you live?
41. P: Aramoko. So when he speaks, he forgets things.
42. N: Let's leave the story. Why did he come here today? Why were you referred? Does he forget things? In this place, we are physicians. We are not plumber. We are into medicine. That you give this and that. Anything affecting the brain is what we treat. That he forgets things easily, right?
43. R: Yes
44. N: Apart from that, what else does he do?

45. R: When we are talking, he would be saying something else.
46. N: Out of context. Okay. ((calls the name of the patient)) *Bawo ni? Pele. Ise wo lo'nse.* (How are you? What is your occupation?)
47. P: Welder
48. N: *Ki'le je laaro yi?* (What did you eat this morning?)
49. P: *Isu* (Yam)
50. N: *Isu ati kini?* (Yam and what?)
51. P: *At'eyin* (And egg)
52. N: ((To the relations)) Is he correct?
53. R: No. He ate beans.
54. N: *Isu l'oje abi?* You ate yam right? *Wo won.* Look at them. *Bawo l'ose je si'yin?* Who are they to you?
55. P: My mummy
56. N: Your mummy? And him. *At'awon naa?*
57. P: *Daddy mi.*
58. N: Where do you live? *Kini address adugbo yin l'Aramoko?* (What's your street address at Aramoko?)
59. P: ((Mentions it correctly))
60. N: Number *kini?* (what number?)
61. P: Number 30
62. N: Is that so?
63. R: No. it's number 12
64. N: He said 30. Okay. Apart from that. How are you feeling in your body now?
65. P: ((mumbles))
66. N: Okay. Is that all? ((writes))
67. P: ((Nods in affirmation))
68. N: ((Examines and analyses the scan results submitted by the patient)) (0.52). Since when has he been forgetful? Up to three weeks?
69. R: He was on admission from May 1. He just mumbles something on the 25.
70. N: After a month
71. R: His eyes were wide opened from that 1 until the 25 of May.
72. N: Is it a motor accident? ((Writes))
73. R2: He was crossing an express road and was hit by a vehicle.
74. R: When he wakes and goes back to sleep, anytime he wakes, he would greet people good morning. Sometimes, after taking his bath in the morning and goes back to sleep, he would say, he has not had his bath today.
75. N: ((To the patient)) *Se e'ma n ri nka t'awon 'yoku o ri?* Do you see what others don't see?
76. P: Yes.
77. N: What do you see?
78. P: *Ise mi* (My job)
79. N: *Ise t'ense?* (Your job) *Se ema n gbo nkan t'awon 'yoku o gbo?* Do you hear what others don't hear?
80. P: No
81. N: No. ((continues to examine the scan results with another doctor (N₂) in the consulting room)). When did you do these tests?
82. R: May 4
83. N: Okay. It just happened then. It happened May 1 and you did this May 4. And it's like this. ((Writes.)) (2.14) We would give you a letter to the neuro-surgeon. We

discovered that there is a stagnant blood deposit in a part of his brain. That is why he speaks incoherently. Those neuro-surgeon, there is something they would do. When they remove it. He should be okay. But that is not our job here. Do you understand?

84. R₂: Is it here that they'll do it?

85. N: It is here they would do it. But if it is one they cannot do here. You'll be referred to Osogbo. Just make sure, you see them first. You can wait outside. The letter will be brought to you there.

86. R₂: Should we be going out?

87. N₂: Yes, I'll bring it for you outside.

NPI 35

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 9 years; Patient: female; Age: 75; Occupation: undisclosed; Ailment: Migraine; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: ((looking at the case note)) How is it doing you? When did the headache start?

2. P: It's about three days now.

3. N: Only three days

4. R: That she has been having headache.

5. N: Is it affecting your eyes. I mean your eye-balls or how is it doing you?

6. P: My head goes empty.

7. N: Is your shaking hand still shaking?

8. P: It's still shaking

9. N: It's still shaking?

10. P: Yes

11. N: But not like before? It has reduced than before?

12. P: Yes

13. N: Are you using the recommended drugs?

14. P: Yes

15. N: Where are they?

16. P: They are here ((opens her bag))

17. N: How many of the drugs are you using?

18. P: These ones are finished.

19. N: ((Picks a call. Ends call)) Sorry o! It's only one person we allow to sit here.

20. R₂: Yes, I understand ((about exiting the room))

21. N: No, if you can stand, you can wait here.

22. R₁: Please help us add this one ((brought out an empty sachet))

23. N: That I should add that?

24. R₁: Yes

25. N: Who prescribed this for you?

26. R₁: It's from here they prescribed this for us. They said it's good for her body if she uses it.

27. N: The last time you came, I wrote some drugs for you. I can't see them here.

28. R₁: She used them. It's because she has exhausted the drugs. There is none we didn't use.

29. N: There is one she didn't buy

30. R: She bought them.

31. N: Do you use this daily?
32. P: Yes
33. N: And you didn't talk about this.
34. P: It was three days ago, it finished.
35. N: There is another one I'm looking for. The one you break into two.
36. P: This?
37. N: O yes. Did you use this?
38. P: I finished it three days ago too.
39. N: You will still continue with it. I've seen it.
40. R₁: She was using them.
41. N: Okay. This one that she used to break into two, don't break it again. Let her use a full dose of it. Do you understand?
42. R₁: Yes
43. N: These drugs will relieve you of the headache ma. It's gradual ((writes, then hands the notes to the relations))
44. R₁ and R₂: Thank you sir o.
45. R₁: Is there need to buy this one?
46. N: No, there is no need
47. R₁: Okay sir
48. N: No problem. Those drugs we wrote for her would be sufficient for her complain. Just make sure you are using them for her.
49. R₁: Thank you sir.
50. N: Please tell ((mentions name) to come in.
51. R₁: Okay sir. Odabo (bye) sir.

NPI 36

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 4 years; Patient: male; Age: 68 years; Occupation: Retired civil servant; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: How are you today? Hope there is no problem?
2. P: No problem, except the one that is there.
3. N: You've been to this clinic before? When were you here last?
4. P: Me?
5. N: Yes.
6. P: It's been a while.
7. N: Is it up to a year or eight months? When were you here last?
8. P: One year or em.
9. N: What I have here is that it's up to a year you were last here.
10. P: Yes
11. N: Are you on any drug presently.
12. P: I've been using these before ((gives the drug bag to the neurologist))
13. N: When last did you use this?
14. P: I just feel that before I use any, I should complain, so that you can use your own experience.
15. N: There is a reason why we are asking you.
16. P: Because doctor's experience sometimes...
17. N: How is the hand that was shaking? Can you lift it
18. P: ((Tries to lift the hand but was unable))

19. N: You've not been using your drugs properly. And that is a big factor.
20. P: Before, my steps were sharp when I came here regularly. There was a drug...
21. N: When you came.
22. P: Yes and I was treated. But the doctor at that time stopped me from using a particular drug among the ones I have been using. It was the other doctor that (0.8) stopped the one, the first doctor gave me. That was why the thing worsened.
23. N: That's what you think. And that may not be so.
24. P: You don't get me. I just feel I should express myself.
25. N: No Baba. You see this clinic, this is a specialist clinic. We understand what is wrong with you. I'm just explaining to you. If there is any drug that you'll need that will improve your condition. Why should we hesitate to give you? We can't hesitate.
26. P: You don't get what I'm saying.
27. N: I get what you are saying. That you said that there is a drug that has been omitted now. You feel the drugs working for you has been missed. ((Another neurologists (N₂) enters))
28. P: Is not that they deliberately eliminated the drug. There is what I was experiencing that I no longer experience.
29. N: Eh ehn. How come you don't get the other drugs to use again. Is it the doctor's fault or you? Or what do you want to say now? According to what you said, there was a certain drug you have been using before and that was given to you by the doctor that you initially consulted. And that he was treating you well. Now after the first visit, that effective drug, you feel they removed it from them. And the condition got deteriorated.
30. P: Not knowingly.
31. N: That's what I'm saying Baba. You know when one is to be insulted, there are ways one can do it ((frowning)) gently, right?
32. P: No, I'm not insulting you
33. N: No, I'm just saying it. We are saying the same thing.
34. P: I'm not insulting you. I know doctors are experience. I want to tell you something. As an elder, if I tell someone based on my age. For example, I can ask a child to get some herbs to drink for some ailments. You as doctors can tell him to get something else.
35. N₂: I understand Baba's analogy
36. N: ((smiling)) I also understand him
37. P: For example, you using your experience that "I know this thing". It's not that I'm insulting you.
38. N: No that's not even what I'm saying.
39. P: I just feel I should express myself.
40. N: So, Baba
41. P: All over my body now is pain.
42. N: When did that start?
43. P: It's up to two weeks
44. N: Hope it's not you couldn't eat well. Is it at night or everytime.
45. P: There are time I don't feel pain at all.
46. N: What about it presently?
47. P: I am having pains all over now as we speak now.
48. N: Baba, the main thing you must ensure is that you don't allow the drugs to be exhausted before you come here.
49. P: Before coming here?

50. N: Yes. You'll have to keep using them until we say stop. Because if you stop it, we won't know the extent of it's effectiveness. Had it been you are still using it and the hand is still shaking, we would understand. You have stopped for more than a week now. You understand?
51. P: Yes
52. N: It's alright. ((writes)) We have written all the needed drugs for you. Please regards to your people at home. And please call the next patient ((mentions name))

NPI 37

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 10 years; Patient: male; Age: 73 years; Occupation: Retired civil servant; Ailment: Stroke; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

22. N: Good day Sir
23. P: ((Nods and looks on))
24. N: How are you today? ((looks on))
25. R: No changes
26. N: ((looks through the file)) IT IS the memory, it is still the short term.
27. R: As he was coming home from the church last Sunday. He lost control while driving ((Narrates the scenario)).... So, we rushed him to the hospital. Although there was no injury. He only damaged other cars. Now when he talks, he diverts talks a lot ... But since last month, he has been like this.
28. N: Does he feel dizzy often?
29. P: No sir
30. N: ((Examines the patient's B.P)) Does he still have all the drugs?
31. R: No. It's only these ones are remaining.
32. N: I see that he has done a CT, which shows there were some slight issues when the accident occurred (0.2) But (0.4) Don't worry. He would be fine.
33. R: I pray o.
34. N: He will. I am going to increase his dose. ((writes)). Initially, he was taking 5ml but I've increased it to 10ml.
35. R: For how long are we going to continue using this?
36. N: What I've written for you will cover up to the next time you'll visit us.
37. P: ((Nods))
38. R: Okay. Thank you sir.
39. N: Do you have any other complain? (0.8) Daddy, I'm talking to you. Do you have any other complain?
40. P: ((smiles))
41. N: ((smiling)). He would be fine. Just help him with the drugs. Let's see in four weeks' time.
42. R: Thank you sir.

NPI 38

Background information: Neurologist: female; Experience: 4 years; Patient: male; Age: 43 years; Occupation: Trader; Ailment: Hysteria; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: Welcome
2. R: Thank you
3. N: ((Goes through the file)) Who ask you to come here?
4. R: When we can no longer understand the case, we were told to bring him here.
5. N: I mean when you got here this morning, who directed you to our clinic?
6. R: The nurse that is talking to us (sic)
7. N: You know why I am asking is because the last time you came here, Prof has already asked your husband to be attended to by doctors in the other clinic.
8. R: They didn't tell us o.
9. N: Okay. Mr P^{SP}, how are you sir.
10. P: Hmm. Hmmm
11. N: I say how are you?
12. P: Yes.
13. N: Does he talk with you.
14. R: Sometimes
15. N: No problem. I will give you a note. You will go to the other clinic.
16. R: Where ma?
17. N: I will ask someone to take you there. ((writes)) That is it. They will attend to you.

NPI 39

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 5 years; Patient: male; Age: 23 years; Occupation: Student; Ailment: Comprehension deficit; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

1. N: How is it since you left here?
2. R: That is why we have come so you can tell us what to do today.
3. N: Okay. P^{SP} how you?
4. P: I'm fine
5. N: How was school
6. P: Fine
7. N: Have you done your exam?
8. P: Yes
9. N: Which of them?
10. P: Sir?
11. N: Which of them?
12. P: Yes
13. N: Which of the exams did you do? First or Second
14. P: Yes
15. N: ((faces the relation)) Ask him if he has done first or second semester exams
16. R: They said which exam you have done
17. P: E mem
18. N: First semester?

19. P: Yes
20. N: Abi it's second semester?
21. P: Yes
22. N: Which of them?
23. P: Yes
24. N: ((faces the relation)) Has he gone back to school since that time?
25. R: Yes sir. It was his guardian in school that called us last week to come and take him when the thing started again.
26. N: We'll will have to carry out some tests. You will do MRI again. Then (0.8) is the speech therapist still coming.
27. R: We have stopped after he improved.
28. N: Okay. I remember that we felt he should be left alone at some point. We may need to bring him back for the moment. The reason I am asking you to do MRI is because of the fall. I don't think there is cause to worry but let's just be proactive ((writes)). Let's see you next week, then we'll would take it up from there.
29. R: Thank you sir
30. N: Bye bye
31. P: Bye bye

NPI 40

Background information: Neurologist: male; Experience: 13 years; Patient: male; Age: 71 years; Occupation: Retired public servant; Ailment: Parkinson disease; Visitation status: accompanied by a relation

7. P: Good afternoon Ma.
8. N: Morning ma. Morning Sir. You are welcome. Come and have your seat ma.
9. R: Oh. Good morning sir. How are you sir?
10. N: I am very (0.2) very (0.2) very FINE. How are you too?
11. R: Fine thank God
12. N: And baba? How are you today sir?
13. R: He has some complaints sir
14. N: Oh! Hope you are hearing from P^{SP}?
15. P: It's not long that she left the North. She called this morning.
16. N: She talked to me yesterday too. Oh sorry: So (0:2) How are things generally. Dr P^{SP} called too about 20 minutes ago as I was coming from the hostel. What are happened Sir? I heard you have not been feeling too well.
17. R: Yes Sir (smiling) (0.2) he lost appetite. He's not been eating like previously.
18. N: What caused that?
19. R: I don't even know.
20. N: Since when did : : it appear he lost appetite?
21. R: It's like last week.
22. Neu; okay:-
23. R: He was sitting on the couch and I was just (0.2) talking to him. And then (0.2) What he was saying was but eh (0.2) (...) On the second day, we went to Dr P^{SP} place. So he did all the check, his sugar level (0.2) and something (0.2) and everything. So he now requested that we should do some (0.2) tests.
24. N: They did CT scan of the brain?
25. R: Yes Sir
26. N: Where you given the film?

27. R: Yes
28. N: Let me see (...) was low
29. R: That has been the case (0.2)
30. N: For a while?
31. R: Yes Sir.
32. N: Has he done neck surgery before?
33. R: No
34. N: How much did it cost to do this test?
35. R: Can I remember now? Hmm the CT (0.2) I think is 36.
36. N: What about the blood test?
37. R: Malaria is 1000
38. N: Ok
39. R: The blood test (0.8) I can't remember again.
40. N: You can't remember again? ((looks through the results and speaks on)) Hope he did not have fever?
41. P: Ehm It's not a usual thing for him to have temperature but we have used Coartem In the course of the ehm...
42. N: The thing that cause this is (...) (explains other discoveries). They are basically the same thing
43. R: He doesn't have strength to work about like before.
44. N: Two or three things are those we discovered to have caused this. First is the electrolyte problem. Second is due to his low thyroid. That thyroid at zero point something. That could also be a reason (0.2) why he can lose appetite and he can be forgetful.
45. R: Ok
46. N: What we'll try to do is to repeat this ((raises up one of the films)). This was done (0.8)
47. R: In plastic
48. N: So that's recent enough.
49. R: On Thursday
50. N: That's the best cue to slow down- we'll have to let him see (...) Hope he is not constipated? Not too bad:- ((to the patient)) daddy, let me ask you the actual complain you have? Don't let us treat the lab. Let's talk to you as a person. (\$ \$ \$) How did it actually begin?
51. P: I just saw a change of (<>) (0.2)
52. N: Just came up?
53. P: I had a change of hmm:::::
54. N: You felt well within yourself. You are okay. Did you travel recently?
55. P: ((Nods in disagreement))
56. N: Did you have any fever recently?
57. P: No. I don't have a:::::ny fever rather than malaria.
58. N: Yes, the malaria virus is found in the result. Why the (0.4) What happened that made you lose your appetite? Can you remember anything that might have caused that? Or you just felt odd that time.
59. P: No. Just the weight. People will tell me.
60. N: You are big and all that...? Your Weight is 89. That maybe a reason to cut down and all that.
61. R: Yes

62. N: The first record shows you are hypertensive. ((To the relative)) Is he still hypertensive? And he's using his drug? Not missing any?
63. R: Yes
64. N: Fine. It's okay. How has it been since that feeling?
65. R: The Prestor?
66. N: Yes! The Prestor is over-working we'll have to stop it. All your lipids are low. All that can cause it.
67. R: And so the dose
68. N: Yes. Any derailment in the body chemistry can result in this. The Prestors (0.4) there is no need. We must stop all the Prestors. All and, (0.2) lipid agents. You don't need them. I think maybe the effect of drug and maybe the viral thing caused what you saw. Here it is showing everything was low. Too low. Your cholesterol is 107. Normally, it should be like 180. Something below 200 will be fine. Your (...) is normal, that one is great. That's great. But HDL which is the one that is a good one. That is the one that keeps the blood vessel and all that. It's low! We want it to be high. So, usually. How to treat that is do some exercise and drink red wine.
69. R: Red wine? Isn't that alcoholic?
70. N: A glass of red wine. Usually that will make a difference. But LDL is low too 62. It means that both high cholesterol and very low cholesterol are bad. High cholesterol will cause clogging. When it is too low, it means the blood vessel are thin and can break easily. So the Presto has to be stopped. (0.8) And give him a glass of red wine. That would help. And do some exercise around the house. The next is the electrolyte imbalance which seems to have been corrected.
71. R: Has it been corrected?
72. N: Yes. This one, sodium is 144, it was 125 here. He should just eat a little salt in his meals. If there is no salt at all. That's not good for you. All these will affect brain function. Slokay will correct that one.
73. R: Ok- :
74. N: We can't do anything about atrophy because it is normal with age. This one is not because of anything. It's age-related effect.
75. R: I was afraid that it should not be (0.4). What do you call?
76. N: Azymas. NURSE and. If it were to be that. His response will not be the same. So I think what we are seeing are mainly related to this bio-chemical changes.
77. P: How do one (sic) correct this in : : : : a short while.
78. N: We will write them for you. Thereafter, I will check it our endocrinologist are there. We may ask for their opinion on some drugs like Tyrotin. I will just attack if one them is in the clinic and will be back ((steps out and returns after 5.13 minutes)) Fortunately, the endocrinologist are there. They said they have issues with the results from the (...) . They recommend that you repeat these tests at (...). They said, their results are more reliable there... ((To the P)) how do you feel generally sir?
79. P: I feel alright. Feel okay < >
80. N: How is your memory sir?
81. P: I remembered you... It's only that < I know something was not right and: em : : em something.
82. N: ... something was wrongites. I'm going to test you sir. ((pat Nods) in affirmation)) Do you remember the words I told you to pronounce before? I want to test your ability to remember things. Just put the words in mind "shoe, broom, goat" ((P repeats the words)) ((N examines the P and continues asking)). What do you have for breakfast sir?

83. P: Hmm : : (...) and then (...)
84. N: But normally what do you have for breakfast sir? ((continues physical examination)). Please spread forth your hands. No! open your fingers. Sixty six. Hmm. It's alright. It's okay. ((stops examining the P) Now, what are those three things I told you to put in mind?
85. P: Em : : : : : (0.2) em: go: :em. Bro:::om. Then hmm : : : :
86. N: It's an animal. Domestic animal.
87. P: Go : : : at
88. N: Correct.
89. R: Really?
90. N: Yes, he go it correctly. Two out of 3 is not bad.
91. P: Is it goat?
92. N: So, we will just take up from there. Let's keep observing him improve. ((writes, then hands over the notes to R))
93. R: We are grateful sir o. *Ese gan ni*. So, when do we check again
94. N: I've written it there. 8 weeks.
95. P: Thank you si::: sir sir.
96. N: Well done. Please take care